

Multiple Representations of Selfie Numbers - II

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Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as **selfie numbers**. There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. It can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers**, etc. Also we can use **binomial coefficients, quadratic (square), cubic functions**, etc. In the past author worked with these functions separately. For more details see the author's work [7]-[40]. This work is combined study of previous applied functions with different combinations. These are done using single, double, triple functions, etc. In this situation, instead of single representation, we have multiples representations. It covers the numbers between 1000-3000. For the previous work up to 999 refer to [41].

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1 Selfie Numbers

Few years back, the author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some functions and operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. In the past they were named as **wild narcissistic numbers** without use of any extra function. Let's summarize below some of the known result done by the author.

1.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3}/2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

1.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \\
 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 145 := 1! + 4! + 5! & 363239 := 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 733 := 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363269 := 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 5177 := 5! + 17 + 7! & 403199 := 40319 + 9!
 \end{array}$$

1.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! & = 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} & = 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) & = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} & = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 & = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 & = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\
 759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 & = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.
 \end{array}$$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer [7]-[20].

1.4 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**.

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 235 := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 := 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 256 := 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 4427 := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 := F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 46493 := F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & 54128 := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [21]-[32].

1.5 Triangle Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n \times (n + 1)}{2} = C(n + 1, 2).$$

The letter "C" represents as "**binomial coefficient**". The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below:

$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$	$874 := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$
$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$	$0105 := 50 + T(10)$
$2887 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$	$1155 := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$
$4965 := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$	$1224 := T(T(T(4) - T(T(2)))) - 2 + 1$
$4999 := 49 + T(99)$	$2418 := T(81) - T(42)$
$99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$	$99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$
$99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6$	$99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [21]-[32].

1.6 Binomial Coefficients

The examples given in subsection 1.4 and 1.5 are with **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **Binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$6435 := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5)$	$= C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6)$
$15504 := C(15 + 5, 0! + 4)$	$= C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1)$
$42504 := C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4})$	$= C(4!, -05 + 24)$
$54264 := C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4))$	$= C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!)$
$74613 := C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!)$	$= C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!)$

$$12650 := C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!)$$

$$12870 := C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!)$$

$$14950 := C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!)$$

$$18564 := C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!)$$

$$19448 := C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8)$$

$$26334 := C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$43758 := C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8)$$

$$53130 := C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!)$$

$$28 := C(8, 2)$$

$$792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$$

$$924 := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$2024 := C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!)$$

$$4845 := C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4)$$

$$00378 := C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!)$$

$$00792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!)$$

$$00924 := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)).$$

The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Above numbers are in **digit's order**, **reverse order of digits** and in **both ways**. For more details refer [33, 34, 35, 36, 37].

1.7 Square-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic (square) numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, \quad n > 0, n \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** with **square selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$	$49 := Q((-9) + Q(4))$
$81 := Q(8 + 1)$	$89 := Q(9) + 8$
$128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	$224 := ((Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2)))$
$292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	$275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$	$0107 := 7 + Q(010)$
$1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	$0231 := -((Q(13) - Q(20)))$
$1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	$1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
$10025 := ((100^2) + Q(5))$	$08136 := (Q(6) + Q((Q(3) + ((1 + 80))))))$
$99378 := (9 \times ((Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8))$	$37293 := (-3) + (((Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3))$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [38]

1.8 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$C(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** with **cubic selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$135 := 1 \times C(3) \times 5$	$135 := (5 \times C((3 \times 1)))$
$153 := 1 + C(5) + C(3)$	$163 := ((C(3) \times 6) + 1)$
$1625 := ((1 + (6 \times 2)) \times C(5))$	$1499 := ((C(9) + C(9)) + 41)$
$1657 := ((16 \times C(5)) - C(7))$	$1512 := ((C(2) - 1) \times C((5 + 1)))$
$1664 := (C(((1 \times 6) + 6)) - C(4))$	$1533 := (3 \times (C((3 + 5)) - 1))$
$10728 := (((C(10) + C(7)) - 2) \times 8)$	$05529 := -(((C(9) - C(2)) + (C(5) \times (-50))))$
$10744 := ((C(10) + C(7)) \times (4 + 4))$	$05697 := ((-7) \times C(9)) + (C(6) \times 50)$
$24356 := (2 \times (C((-4) + C(3))) + (5 + 6))$	$36274 := (((-4) + C(7)) - 2) + C((6 + C(3)))$
$24357 := ((C(2) \times (-4)) + C((C(3) - ((5 - 7))))))$	$36276 := (((-6) + C(7)) + 2) + C((6 + C(3)))$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [39]

This work brings multiple representations of **selfie numbers**. The is obtained by using together the functions **Fibonacci**, **Triangular**, **Square Cubic numbers**. Along with basic operations **factorial** and **square-root** are also applied. This is the second part of the work. It covers the numbers between 1000 to 3000. The first part is given in [41].

2 Multiple Representations of Selfie Numbers

This section brings **multiple representations of selfie numbers** having functions such as, **Square**, **Cubic**, **Triangular** and **Fibonacci**. Also it includes operations such as, **square-root**, **factorial**, etc. By multiple representations we understand that there are more than one values instead of single representation. This work is only up to three digits numbers. Four digits onwards shall be given in second part of this work. Due to simplifications of brackets, some numbers are not in order according to left side, but after reorganizing, these can be put in same order as of left side.

$$1000 := 10^{F(Q(0!+0!))}$$

$$1000 := 10^{T(0!+0!)}$$

$$1000 := C(10) + 00$$

$$1001 := C(10) + 01$$

$$1001 := T(T(Q(T(1+0!)))) - F(Q(T(0!+1)))$$

$$1002 := -1 + Q(Q(0!+0!)) + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1002 := C(10) + 02$$

$$1002 := T(1 + Q(0! + 0!)) + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1003 := C(10) + 03$$

$$1003 := Q(Q(1+0!)) + F(Q(0!+3))$$

$$1003 := T(Q(1+0!)!) + T(0! + Q(T(3)))$$

$$1004 := C(10) + 04$$

$$1004 := Q(Q(1+0!)) + (0! + F(Q(4)))$$

$$1005 := C(10) + 05$$

$$1005 := F(Q(Q(1+0!))) + \sqrt{-0! + T(Q(5))}$$

$$1005 := T(-1 + T(Q(T(0!+0!)))) + T(5)$$

$$1006 := C(10) + 06$$

$$1007 := C(10) + 07$$

$$1007 := T(T(10-0!)) - T(7)$$

$$1008 := C(10) + 08$$

$$1008 := -Q(Q(1+0!)) \times (0! - Q(8))$$

$$1008 := T(1 + T(T(0! + 0!))) \times T(8)$$

$$1009 := C(10) + 09$$

$$1009 := F(Q(Q(1+0!))) + 0! + T(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1009 := Q(1 + Q(Q(0! + 0!))) + ((\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$1009 := Q(1 + Q(Q(0! + 0!))) + T(\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1010 := C(10) + 10$$

$$1011 := C(10) + 11$$

$$1011 := Q(1+0!)! + F(Q(Q(1+1)))$$

$$1011 := -Q(1 + 0!) + T(T(Q(T(1 + 1))))$$

$$1012 := C(10) + 12$$

$$1012 := Q(1 + 0!) \times T(1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$1012 := Q(1 + Q(1 + 0!)) + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1013 := -1 - T(T(T(1 + 0!))) + T(T(Q(3)))$$

$$1013 := C(10) + 13$$

$$1014 := C(10) + 14$$

$$1014 := F(Q(1 + 0!))! \times Q(F(1 + F(4)!))$$

$$1014 := T(T(10 - 1)) - T(T(F(4)))$$

$$1014 := T(T(10 - 1)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$1014 := -T(T(T(1 + 0!))) + T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$1015 := C(10) + 15$$

$$1015 := T(-1 + T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) + Q(5)$$

$$1016 := C(10) + 16$$

$$1016 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! - 1 + Q(F(F(6)))$$

$$1016 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! - 1 + Q(T(6))$$

$$1017 := C(10) + 17$$

$$1017 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! + Q(F(1 + 7))$$

$$1017 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! + Q(T(-1 + 7))$$

$$1018 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! + 1 + Q(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1018 := C(10) + 18$$

$$1018 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! + (1 + Q(F(8)))$$

$$1019 := C(10) + 19$$

$$1019 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1020 := C(10) + 20$$

$$1020 := Q(1 + 0!) \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!)$$

$$1020 := T(Q(1 + 0!))! + T(T(2))! + 0$$

$$1020 := T(T(1 + 0!))! + T((T(2) + 0!))!$$

$$1021 := C(10) + 21$$

$$1021 := F(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + F(Q(2 + 1))$$

$$1021 := F(Q(T(1 + 0!))) + F(Q(Q(2 \times 1)))$$

$$1021 := T(Q(1 + 0!))! + T(T(2))! + 1$$

$$1022 := (1 + 0!)^{T(Q(2))} - 2$$

$$1022 := -1 - 0! + Q(2 \times Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1022 := C(10) + 22$$

$$1022 := T(Q(1 + 0!))! + T(T(2))! + 2$$

$$1023 := (1 + 0!)^{T(Q(2))} - F(F(3))$$

$$1023 := -1 + Q(-0! + Q(2)! + Q(3))$$

$$1023 := -1 + Q(0! + T(Q(2)) + T(T(3)))$$

$$1023 := C(10) + 23$$

$$1023 := F((1 + 0!)^{Q(2)}) + Q(3!)$$

$$1023 := F(10 + T(T(2))) + T(F(T(3)))$$

$$1023 := T(Q(1 + 0!))! + T(T(2))! + 3$$

$$1024 := (1 + 0!) \times C(2 \times 4)$$

$$1024 := (1 + 0!)^{2+F(F(4)!)}$$

$$1024 := 1 \times 02^{T(4)}$$

$$1024 := C(10) + 24$$

$$1024 := Q((10 - 2) \times 4)$$

$$1024 := T(Q(1 + 0!))! + T(T(2))! + 4$$

$$1025 := 1 + (0! + T(2))^5$$

$$1025 := 1 + Q(02^5)$$

$$1025 := -10 + T(T(2) \times T(5))$$

$$1025 := C(10) + 25$$

$$1025 := T(Q(1 + 0!)) + T(T(2))! + 5$$

$$1026 := 1 + 0! + Q(Q(2) \times F(6))$$

$$1026 := 1 + 0! + Q(-Q(2) + Q(6))$$

$$1026 := T(10 + F(T(T(2)))) \times 6$$

$$1026 := C(10) + 26$$

$$1026 := T(Q(1 + 0!)) + T(T(2))! + 6$$

$$1026 := T(T(1 + 0!)) \times T(T(2) \times 6)$$

$$1027 := (F(10) + Q(2!)) \times F(7)$$

$$1027 := C(10) + 27$$

$$1027 := -F(T(T(1 + 0!))) + T(T(2 + 7))$$

$$1027 := T(1 + 0!) + Q(Q(2) + T(7))$$

$$1027 := T(Q(1 + 0!)) + T(T(2))! + 7$$

$$1028 := 1 + T(T(0! + F(T(T(2)))))) - 8$$

$$1028 := C(10) + 28$$

$$1028 := Q(1 + 0!) + Q(Q(2) \times 8)$$

$$1028 := T(F(10)) - \sqrt{F(T(T(2)))\sqrt{T(8)}}$$

$$1028 := T(Q(1 + 0!)) + T(T(2))! + 8$$

$$1029 := (-1 - 0!) \times T(2) + T(T(9))$$

$$1029 := 1 + (0! + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times Q(F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1029 := C(10) + 29$$

$$1029 := -T(1 + 02) + T(T(9))$$

$$1029 := T(Q(1 + 0!)) + T(T(2))! + 9$$

$$1030 := C(10) + 30$$

$$1030 := -Q(1 + 0!) + T(T(Q(3))) - 0!$$

$$1031 := C(10) + 31$$

$$1031 := -Q(1 + 0!) + T(T(Q(3 \times 1)))$$

$$1032 := (-1 - 0! + T(Q(3))) \times Q(2)!$$

$$1032 := C(10) + 32$$

$$1032 := Q(1 + 0!)! + F(F(3!)) + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1032 := -T(1 + 0!) + T(T(3^2))$$

$$1032 := T(T(1 + F(T(03)))) - T(2)$$

$$1033 := -1 - 0! + T(T(3 \times 3))$$

$$1033 := C(10) + 33$$

$$1033 := Q(-1 - 0! + F(Q(3))) + Q(3)$$

$$1033 := Q(-Q(1 + 0!) + Q(3!)) + Q(3)$$

$$1033 := T(T(1 + F(T(03)))) - F(3)$$

$$1034 := -1 + T(T(\sqrt{03^4}))$$

$$1034 := -1 + T(T(T(03)) + 4!)$$

$$1034 := 10 + F(3)^{T(4)}$$

$$1034 := 10 + Q(Q(3!)) - 4$$

$$1034 := C(10) + 34$$

$$1034 := -F(10) + Q(Q(3) + 4!)$$

$$1034 := -T(10) + Q(Q(3) + 4!)$$

$$1035 := -(Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) - Q(Q(3!)) + 5)$$

$$1035 := -1 + Q(F(Q(03))) - 5!$$

$$1035 := C(10) + 35$$

$$1035 := F(10) \times F(F(3!)) - 5!$$

$$1035 := T(10 + 35)$$

$$1036 := 1 + T(T(03 + 6))$$

$$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$$

$$1036 := 10^3 + T(F(6))$$

$$1036 := C(10) + 36$$

$$1037 := 1 + (0! + Q(T(3))) \times T(7)$$

$$1037 := 1 + 0! + T(T(F(3) + 7))$$

$$1037 := C(10) + 37$$

$$1037 := Q(-1 - 0! + F(Q(3))) + F(7)$$

$$1037 := T(F(10) - F(T(3))) - T(F(7))$$

$$1038 := C(10) + 38$$

$$1038 := Q(Q(1 + 0!)) + F(F(3!)) + Q(F(8))$$

$$1038 := T(1 + 0!) + T(Q(3) + T(8))$$

$$1038 := T(1 + 0!) + T(T(F(F(3)) + 8))$$

$$1038 := T(1 + 0!) + T(T(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}))$$

$$1039 := 1 + 03 + T(T(9))$$

$$1039 := -1 - Q(Q(0! + 3)) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$1039 := C(10) + 39$$

$$1039 := F(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(Q(F(3))) + Q((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1040 := -(Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) - Q(Q(F(4)!))) \times 0!$$

$$1040 := C(10) + 40$$

$$1040 := -Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(Q((4 - 0)!))$$

$$1040 := -Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(Q((\sqrt{4} + 0)!))$$

$$1040 := -Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(Q(T(\sqrt{4} + 0!))$$

$$1040 := Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(T(T(F(4)) + 0!))$$

$$1041 := C(10) + 41$$

$$1041 := F(10) + F(Q(4)) - 1$$

$$1041 := T(10) + F(Q(4)) - 1$$

$$1041 := T(T(1 + 0!)) + T(T(T(4) - 1))$$

$$1041 := T(T(1 + 0!)) + T(T(Q(4 - 1)))$$

$$1042 := (-T(10) + Q(4!)) \times 2$$

$$1042 := 1 + T(T(-0! + T(4))) + T(T(2))$$

$$1042 := C(10) + 42$$

$$1042 := F(10) + F(4^2)$$

$$1042 := T(10) + F(4^2)$$

$$1043 := (1 + 0!) \times 4 + T(T(Q(3)))$$

$$1043 := C(10) + 43$$

$$1043 := F(10) + F(Q(4)) + F(F(3))$$

$$1043 := T(F(10) - T(4)) + F(T(3))$$

$$1044 := C(10) + 44$$

$$1044 := F(10) + \sqrt{4} + F(Q(4))$$

$$1044 := T(10) + \sqrt{4} + F(Q(4))$$

$$1044 := -T(F(10)) + F(F(4) \times T(F(4)))$$

$$1044 := T(F(10)) - T(-4! + F(T(4)))$$

$$1044 := T(T(10)) - T(-4! + T(T(4)))$$

$$1044 := T(T(10)) - T(T(4) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))))$$

$$1045 := 10 + T(45)$$

$$1045 := C(10) + 45$$

$$1045 := F(10) \times (4! - 5)$$

$$1046 := 1 + T(0! + 4!) + 6!$$

$$1046 := C(10) + 46$$

$$1046 := F(Q(1 + 0!))! - Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1047 := -1 + T(T(-0! + T(4))) + F(7)$$

$$1047 := C(10) + 47$$

$$1047 := -Q(Q(1 + 0!)) + Q(Q(F(4)!)) - F(F(7))$$

$$1047 := T(1 + 0!) \times (T(4!) + Q(7))$$

$$1048 := C(10) + 48$$

$$1048 := Q(1 + 0!)! + Q(4 \times 8)$$

$$1048 := Q(1 + 0!) \times (Q(Q(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1048 := T(10) + F(Q(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1049 := 10 + 4 + T(T(9))$$

$$1049 := C(10) + 49$$

$$1049 := F(Q(Q(1 + 0!)))/F(4) + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$1050 := 10 \times T(T(5) - 0!)$$

$$1050 := 50 \times F(F(F(Q(1 + 0!)))!)$$

$$1050 := C(10) + 00$$

$$1051 := C(10) + 51$$

$$1051 := F(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(F(5 + 1))$$

$$1051 := Q(Q(1 + 0!)) + T(T(Q(F(5 - 1))))$$

$$1051 := T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) + Q(5 - 1)$$

$$1052 := -1 + T(0! + Q(5)) \times T(2)$$

$$1052 := C(10) + 52$$

$$1052 := -F(10) + 5! + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1053 := (-1 - 0! + T(5)) \times Q(Q(3))$$

$$1053 := C(10) + 53$$

$$1053 := F(1 + 0! + 5) \times Q(Q(3))$$

$$1053 := T(1 + 0!) \times T(5 + T(T(3)))$$

$$1054 := (F(Q(1 + 0!))! + Q(5)) \times F(Q(F(4)))$$

$$1054 := 1 + T(0! + Q(5)) \times F(4)$$

$$1054 := 1 + T(0! + Q(5)) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1054 := C(10) + 54$$

$$1055 := C(10) + 55$$

$$1055 := Q(F(Q(1 + 0!))) \times 5! - Q(5)$$

$$1055 := Q(T(1 + 0!)) \times 5! - Q(5)$$

$$1056 := (-1 - 0!) \times 5! + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1056 := -10 + Q(Q(5)) + Q(T(6))$$

$$1056 := C(10) + 56$$

$$1056 := F(10) \times T(5) + T(T(6))$$

$$1056 := T(10) \times T(5) + T(T(6))$$

$$1057 := (T(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + T(5)) \times 7$$

$$1057 := C(10) + 57$$

$$1057 := T(T(F(T(T(1 + 0!)))) - T(5) + T(T(7)))$$

$$1058 := (1 + 0!) \times Q(T(5) + 8)$$

$$1058 := -(F(F(Q(1 + 0!)))! - Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(8)))$$

$$1058 := C(10) + 58$$

$$1059 := (-1 + 5)! + T(T(9))$$

$$1059 := -1 + Q(5) + T(T(9))$$

$$1059 := C(10) + 59$$

$$1059 := Q(F(Q(1 + 0!))) \times 5! - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$1060 := C(10) + 60$$

$$1060 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! + Q(F(F(6)) + 0!)$$

$$1060 := Q(Q(1 + 0!))! + Q(T(6) + 0!)$$

$$1061 := C(10) + 61$$

$$1062 := (1 + 0!) \times (T(T(6)) + T(Q(2)!))$$

$$1062 := C(10) + 62$$

$$1062 := -Q(F(10)) + Q(Q(F(6))) - Q(F(Q(2)))$$

$$1062 := -Q(T(10)) + Q(Q(F(6))) - Q(T(2))$$

$$1063 := C(10) + 63$$

$$1063 := -Q(F(10)) + Q(Q(F(6))) - F(3!)$$

$$1063 := T(T(10)) - Q(T(6)) - Q(T(3))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1064 &:= C(10) + 64 \\
 1064 &:= Q(1 + 0!) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(4)) \\
 1065 &:= -(Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) - Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) \\
 1065 &:= -1 + Q(T(6)) + Q(Q(5)) \\
 1065 &:= C(10) + 65 \\
 1065 &:= F(10) \times F(6) + Q(Q(5)) \\
 1065 &:= \sqrt{1 + (0! + 6)!} \times T(5) \\
 1065 &:= T(10) \times F(6) + Q(Q(5)) \\
 1066 &:= C(10) + 66 \\
 1066 &:= Q(-1 + T(6)) + T(Q(6)) \\
 1066 &:= Q(Q(-1 + 6)) + Q(F(F(6))) \\
 1067 &:= C(10) + 67 \\
 1067 &:= Q(1 + 0!) + Q(Q(6)) - F(F(7)) \\
 1067 &:= -Q(1 + 0!) + Q(T(6)) + T(\sqrt{T(Q(7))}) \\
 1068 &:= C(10) + 68 \\
 1068 &:= Q(-1 + F(0! + F(6))) - F(8) \\
 1068 &:= T(1 + 0!) + Q(Q(6)) - T(F(8)) \\
 1068 &:= T(1 + 0!) - T(T(6)) + Q(T(8)) \\
 1069 &:= -1 - 0! + Q(6) + T(T(9)) \\
 1069 &:= C(10) + 69 \\
 1069 &:= F(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) \\
 1069 &:= -Q(F(10)) + Q(Q(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1069 &:= T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) \\
 1070 &:= C(10) + 70 \\
 1070 &:= -Q(T(10)) + T(T(F(7))) - 0! \\
 1070 &:= T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 0 \\
 1071 &:= C(10) + 71 \\
 1071 &:= -Q(F(10)) + Q(Q(7 + 1)) \\
 1071 &:= -Q(T(10)) + Q(Q(7 + 1)) \\
 1071 &:= T(T(F(T(T(1 + 0!)))) + T(T(7)) - 1 \\
 1071 &:= T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 1 \\
 1072 &:= 7 \times Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) - F(Q(2))!! \\
 1072 &:= C(10) + 72 \\
 1072 &:= Q(Q(1 + 0!)) \times (T(F(7)) - Q(2)!) \\
 1072 &:= T(F(10)) - F(7) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) \\
 1072 &:= T(T(1 + 0!) + T(7)) + Q(Q(2)!) \\
 1072 &:= T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 2 \\
 1073 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) + T(T(F(T(3)))) \\
 1073 &:= 10 + T(7) + T(T(Q(3))) \\
 1073 &:= 10 - F(F(7)) + Q(Q(3!)) \\
 1073 &:= C(10) + 73 \\
 1073 &:= -T(10) + T(Q(7) - F(3)) \\
 1073 &:= T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 3 \\
 1074 &:= -10 + Q(T(7)) + T(4!) \\
 1074 &:= C(10) + 74 \\
 1074 &:= Q(10) - F(7) + F(Q(4)) \\
 1074 &:= T(F(10)) - F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) \\
 1074 &:= T(F(10)) - F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1074 &:= T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 4 \\
 1075 &:= -(F(Q(1 + 0!))! - Q(7)) \times Q(5) \\
 1075 &:= -(T(T(1 + 0!)) - Q(7)) \times Q(5) \\
 1075 &:= C(10) + 75 \\
 1075 &:= T(1 + 0! + T(7)) + F(T(5)) \\
 1075 &:= T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1076 := C(10) + 76$$

$$1076 := Q(1 + 0!) \times (F(F(7)) + Q(6))$$

$$1076 := Q(1 + 0!) + T(T(7)) + T(Q(6))$$

$$1076 := T(F(10)) - F(F(7)) - T(T(6))$$

$$1076 := T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 6$$

$$1077 := C(10) + 77$$

$$1077 := T(Q(1 + 0!)) - 7 + Q(T(7))$$

$$1077 := T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 7$$

$$1077 := T(T(T(1 + 0!))) + T(Q(7)) - Q(F(7))$$

$$1078 := -1 + \sqrt{0! + 7! \times T(F(8))}$$

$$1078 := C(10) + 78$$

$$1078 := -Q(F(10)) + 7 + Q(Q(8))$$

$$1078 := -Q(T(10)) + 7 + Q(Q(8))$$

$$1078 := T(T(1 + 0!)) + T(T(7)) + T(T(8))$$

$$1078 := T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 8$$

$$1079 := -1 - 0! + T(Q(7) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1079 := -1 - 0! + T(T(F(7)) - T(9))$$

$$1079 := C(10) + 79$$

$$1079 := F(10) + Q(-Q(7) + Q(9))$$

$$1079 := \sqrt{1 - (0 - 7!) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))}$$

$$1079 := T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + 9$$

$$1080 := C(10) + 80$$

$$1080 := T(10 + T(8)) - 0!$$

$$1081 := C(10) + 81$$

$$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$$

$$1082 := (Q(10) + Q(F(8))) \times 2$$

$$1082 := 1 + T(0! + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(2)))$$

$$1082 := 1 + T(0! + T(T(8)/Q(2)))$$

$$1082 := C(10) + 82$$

$$1082 := T(10 + T(8)) + F(2)$$

$$1083 := 3 \times Q(-1 - 0! + F(8))$$

$$1083 := 3 \times Q(T(10) - T(8))$$

$$1083 := C(10) + 83$$

$$1083 := T(1 + 0!) \times Q(F(8) - F(3))$$

$$1083 := T(10 + T(8)) + F(3)$$

$$1084 := -8 \times Q(F(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(F(Q(F(4))))$$

$$1084 := C(10) + 84$$

$$1084 := T(1 + 0!) + T(T(8) + T(4))$$

$$1084 := T(10 + T(8)) + F(4)$$

$$1084 := T(10 + T(8)) + T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1085 := C(10) + 85$$

$$1085 := -Q(1 + 0!) + Q(8 + Q(5))$$

$$1085 := Q(1 + 0!) + T(F(8) + Q(5))$$

$$1086 := -10 \times F(8) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1086 := -10 \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1086 := C(10) + 86$$

$$1087 := C(10) + 87$$

$$1087 := Q(1 + 0!) + Q(T(8)) - F(F(7))$$

$$1087 := Q(10) + F(Q(Q(F((1/7) \times F(8))))))$$

$$1087 := Q(Q(1 + 0!)) + Q(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(\sqrt{T(Q(7))})$$

$$1088 := -(Q(1 + 0!) - F(8)) \times Q(8)$$

$$1088 := (Q(10) + T(8)) \times 8$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1088 &:= 8 \times T((1 + 0!) \times 8) & 1092 &:= F(10) + T(T(9)) + 2 \\
 1088 &:= C(10) + 88 & 1092 &:= Q(F(9) - 1) + F(Q(2)) \\
 1088 &:= Q(8 \times Q(1 + 0!)) + Q(8) & 1092 &:= T(1 + 0!) + Q(F(9) - F(2)) \\
 1088 &:= -T(F(10)) + T(T(8) + T(8)) & 1092 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 2 \\
 1088 &:= -T(T(10)) + T(T(8) + T(8)) & & \\
 & & 1093 &:= 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 3 \\
 1089 &:= (1 + (-0! + \sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 9 & 1093 &:= C(10) + 93 \\
 1089 &:= (-1 + F(0! + 8))^{F(\sqrt{9})} & 1093 &:= F(10) + T(T(9)) + 3 \\
 1089 &:= (Q(10) + F(8)) \times 9 & 1093 &:= Q(1 + 0!) + Q(-\sqrt{9} + Q(3!)) \\
 1089 &:= C(10) + 89 & 1093 &:= Q(F(9) - 1) + Q(F(3)) \\
 1089 &:= Q(Q(10) - Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) & 1093 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 3 \\
 1089 &:= Q(Q(10 - 8)! + 9) & & \\
 1089 &:= Q(T(8) - \sqrt{9}) & 1094 &:= (F(Q(1 + 0!)) + Q(Q(9)))/F(4)! \\
 1089 &:= T(10 + T(8)) + F(T(\sqrt{9})) & 1094 &:= (T(1 + 0!) + Q(Q(9)))/T(F(4)) \\
 1089 &:= T(T(1 + 0!))! - T(T(8)) + T(T(9)) & 1094 &:= 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 4 \\
 & & 1094 &:= C(10) + 94 \\
 1090 &:= 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 0 & 1094 &:= F(10) + T(T(9)) + 4 \\
 1090 &:= 1 + Q(F(9) - 0!) & 1094 &:= Q(1 + 0!) + T(T(9)) + T(T(4)) \\
 1090 &:= C(10) + 90 & 1094 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 4 \\
 1090 &:= F(10) + T(T(9)) + 0 & & \\
 1090 &:= Q(10) + T(T(9) - 0!) & 1095 &:= 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 5 \\
 1090 &:= Q(Q(1 + 0!)! + 9) + 0! & 1095 &:= -1 + T(0! + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 1090 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 0 & 1095 &:= C(10) + 95 \\
 & & 1095 &:= F(10) + T(T(9)) + 5 \\
 1091 &:= 1 + 0! + Q(F(9) - 1) & 1095 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 5 \\
 1091 &:= 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 1 & 1095 &:= T(T(10))/F(\sqrt{9}) + T(Q(5)) \\
 1091 &:= C(10) + 91 & & \\
 1091 &:= F(10) + T(T(9)) + 1 & 1096 &:= 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 6 \\
 1091 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 1 & 1096 &:= C(10) + 96 \\
 & & 1096 &:= F(10) + T(T(9)) + 6 \\
 1092 &:= 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 2 & 1096 &:= Q(1 + 0!) + Q(F(9)) - Q(F(6)) \\
 1092 &:= 1 + T(0! + T(9)) + T(Q(2)) & 1096 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 6 \\
 1092 &:= C(10) + 92 & 1096 &:= T(T(10)) - \sqrt{9} - Q(T(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1097 := 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 7$$

$$1097 := -10 + Q(F(9)) - Q(7)$$

$$1097 := C(10) + 97$$

$$1097 := F(10) + T(T(9)) + 7$$

$$1097 := Q(Q(Q(1 + 0!))) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!) - 7)$$

$$1097 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 7$$

$$1098 := 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 8$$

$$1098 := -1 + T(T(9)) + Q(8)$$

$$1098 := C(10) + 98$$

$$1098 := F(10) + T(T(9)) + 8$$

$$1098 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 8$$

$$1099 := 1 + Q(-0! + F(9)) + 9$$

$$1099 := 10 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1099 := C(10) + 99$$

$$1099 := -F(10) + Q(F(9)) - F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1099 := F(10) + T(T(9)) + 9$$

$$1099 := T(10) + 9 + T(T(9))$$

$$1099 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 9$$

$$1100 := 11 \times Q(T(Q(0! + 0!)))$$

$$1100 := C(11) - T(F(C(0! + 0!)))$$

$$1100 := C(11) - T(T(T(T(0! + 0!))))$$

$$1101 := Q(F(Q(T(1 + 1)))) - T(T(Q(1 + 0!)))$$

$$1101 := T(11) + T(T(Q(T(1 + 0!))))$$

$$1102 := 1 - F(10) + Q(F(Q(F(Q(2))))))$$

$$1102 := F(C(1 + 1)) + T(0! + T(Q(T(2))))$$

$$1102 := T(T(T(1 + 1))) + T(0! + T(Q(T(2))))$$

$$1104 := Q(1 + 1) \times T(-0! + 4!)$$

$$1104 := -Q(11) + Q(0! + F(Q(F(4))))$$

$$1105 := C(11) - 0! - Q(T(5))$$

$$1105 := Q(F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + 0!) - 5!$$

$$1105 := Q(F(Q(T(1 + 1))) + 0!) - 5!$$

$$1105 := Q(Q(T(T(1 + 1))) - 0!) - 5!$$

$$1106 := T(Q(T(T(1 + 1)))) - 0! + Q(T(6))$$

$$1106 := T(T(C(1 + 1))) - 0! + Q(T(6))$$

$$1107 := C(Q(T(1 + 1))) + T(-0! + T(7))$$

$$1107 := Q(F(-(1 - 10))) - Q(7)$$

$$1107 := T(Q(T(T(1 + 1)))) + Q(T(-0! + 7))$$

$$1107 := T(T(C(1 + 1))) + Q(F(0! + 7))$$

$$1108 := Q(11) + F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{0! + 8}))))$$

$$1108 := Q(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + 0! + T(T(8))$$

$$1108 := T(Q(T(T(1 + 1)))) + (0! + Q(F(8)))$$

$$1108 := T(T(C(1 + 1))) + (0! + Q(F(8)))$$

$$1109 := Q(11) + 0! + F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9}))))$$

$$1109 := -T(T(11)) - 0! + T(Q(9))$$

$$1110 := -T(T(11)) + T(Q(Q(T(1 + 0!))))$$

$$1111 := Q(F(Q(T(1 + 1)))) - T(Q(T(1 + 1)))$$

$$1112 := F(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + C(1 + Q(2))$$

$$1112 := Q(F(Q(T(1 + 1)))) + (1 - T(Q(T(2))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1113 &:= Q(1+1)! + Q(-1 + F(Q(3))) & 1121 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(T(2)))) + 1 \\
 1113 &:= -Q(Q(Q(1+1))) + Q(1 + Q(3!)) & 1121 &:= Q(11) + C(Q(F(Q(2))) + 1) \\
 1113 &:= T(1+11) + T(T(Q(3))) & 1121 &:= Q(F(Q(F(Q(1+1)))) - F(Q(F(Q(2)))) - 1 \\
 & & 1121 &:= Q(F(Q(T(1+1)))) - F(Q(T(2))) - 1 \\
 \\
 1114 &:= -1 + C(11) - C(F(4!)) & & \\
 1114 &:= -1 + C(11) - C(T(F(4))) & 1122 &:= 2 \times T(11 \times T(2)) \\
 1114 &:= -1 + C(11) - C(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) & 1122 &:= C(1+1)! / T(C(2)) + 2 \\
 & & 1122 &:= F(11 + Q(2)) + C(C(2)) \\
 \\
 1115 &:= C(11) - C(1+5) & 1122 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(T(2)))) + 2 \\
 & & 1122 &:= -Q(11) + Q(Q(Q(2))) + F(Q(Q(2))) \\
 \\
 1116 &:= 1 + C(11) - C(6) & & \\
 1116 &:= Q(Q(T(1+1))) + T(T(1 + F(6))) & 1123 &:= C(1+1)! / T(C(2)) + 3 \\
 1116 &:= T(T(Q(T(1+1)))) + Q(Q(T(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}))) & 1123 &:= C(11) + C(C(2)) - 3! \\
 & & 1123 &:= F(Q(Q(1+1))) + Q(2) \times F(Q(3)) \\
 \\
 1117 &:= Q(-1 + F(Q(T(1+1)))) + T(7) & 1123 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(T(2)))) + 3 \\
 & & 1123 &:= Q(11 \times T(2)) + F(Q(3)) \\
 & & 1123 &:= T(Q(T(T(1+1)))) + Q(Q(2)) + Q(T(T(3))) \\
 \\
 1119 &:= -1 + C(1+1)! / Q((\sqrt{9})!) & & \\
 1119 &:= -1 + C(1+1)! / Q(T(\sqrt{9})) & 1124 &:= (1+1)^{T(Q(2))} + Q(T(4)) \\
 1119 &:= -1 + C(1+1)! / T(F(T(\sqrt{9}))) & 1124 &:= C(1+1)! / T(C(2)) + 4 \\
 1119 &:= -1 + F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(\sqrt{9}))) & 1124 &:= F(11) + T(T(T(2) \times F(4))) \\
 1119 &:= -1 - Q(F(Q(1+1)))! + Q(F(9)) & 1124 &:= F(11) + T(T(T(2)^{\sqrt{4}})) \\
 1119 &:= -1 - Q(T(T(1+1))) + Q(F(9)) & 1124 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(T(2)))) + 4 \\
 1119 &:= -1 - T(C(1+1)) + Q(F(9)) & 1124 &:= Q(11) + Q(Q(2)) + F(Q(4)) \\
 & & 1124 &:= Q(Q(1+1) \times C(2)) + Q(T(4)) \\
 & & 1124 &:= T(\sqrt{T(T(11)) - 2}) - 4 \\
 \\
 1120 &:= C(1+1)! / Q((2+0)!) & & \\
 1120 &:= C(1+1)! / T(C(2)) + 0 & & \\
 1120 &:= F(Q(1+1))! + Q(20) & 1125 &:= (11-2) \times C(5) \\
 1120 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0 & 1125 &:= T(11-2) \times Q(5) \\
 1120 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(T(2+0)))) & 1125 &:= (-T(T(1+1)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 \\
 1120 &:= T(T(1+1))! + Q(20) & 1125 &:= (T(T(T(T(1+1)))) - T(T(2))) \times 5 \\
 & & 1125 &:= 5 \times Q(11 + Q(2)) \\
 & & 1125 &:= C(1+1)! / T(C(2)) + 5 \\
 & & 1125 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))! / T(F(T(T(2)))) + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1126 &:= C(1+1)!/T(C(2)) + 6 \\
 1126 &:= -F(11) - Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1126 &:= F(Q(1+1))! + C(2)!/Q(6) \\
 1126 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))/T(F(T(T(2)))) + 6 \\
 1126 &:= T(1+C(1+2)) + 6! \\
 1126 &:= T(Q(T(1+1))) + T(T(Q(2))) + Q(6) \\
 1126 &:= T(T(1+1))! + T(T(F(2)+6)) \\
 1126 &:= T(T(1+T(1+2))) + 6! \\
 \\
 1127 &:= (-1+Q(2)!) \times Q(7) \\
 1127 &:= 1 + T(1+2)! + T(T(7)) \\
 1127 &:= -1 + T(-2+Q(7)) \\
 1127 &:= -1 + T(F(1+F(T(T(2)))) + F(7)) \\
 1127 &:= C(1+1)!/T(C(2)) + 7 \\
 1127 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))/T(F(T(T(2)))) + 7 \\
 \\
 1128 &:= C(1+1)!/T(C(2)) + 8 \\
 1128 &:= F(Q(Q(1+1))) \times Q(2)!/F(8) \\
 1128 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))/T(F(T(T(2)))) + 8 \\
 1128 &:= T(-1-12) + T(8) \\
 \\
 1129 &:= 1 + T(2+T(9)) \\
 1129 &:= -11 - Q(Q(2)) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1129 &:= C(1+1)!/T(C(2)) + 9 \\
 1129 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))/T(F(T(T(2)))) + 9 \\
 1129 &:= Q(F(11-2)) - C(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1129 &:= Q(Q(1+1) + Q(Q(2))) + C(9) \\
 \\
 1130 &:= -C(F(Q(1+1))) + Q(F(Q(3))) + 0! \\
 1130 &:= T(T(11)) - T(T(Q(3))) + 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1131 &:= -Q(1+1)! + Q(F(Q(3))) - 1 \\
 1131 &:= T(1+1) \times (-1 + T(C(3))) \\
 \\
 1132 &:= -Q(1+1)! + Q(F(3^2)) \\
 1132 &:= -Q(1+1)! + Q(Q(3!)) - 2 \\
 1132 &:= Q(1+1) + T(T(Q(3))) + 2 \\
 1132 &:= T(1+1) \times T(C(3)) - 2 \\
 \\
 1133 &:= -1 + 3 \times T(C(3)) \\
 1133 &:= F(11) + Q(3) + T(T(Q(3))) \\
 1133 &:= -Q(1+1)! + Q(F(Q(3))) + F(F(3)) \\
 1133 &:= T(1+1) \times T(C(3)) - F(F(3)) \\
 \\
 1134 &:= (1+1) \times (-Q(3) + Q(4!)) \\
 1134 &:= F(C(1+1)) \times C(3) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1134 &:= T(1+1) \times T(3^{F(4)}) \\
 1134 &:= T(1+1) \times T(3+4!) \\
 1134 &:= T(1+1) \times T(Q(3)) \times F(4) \\
 1134 &:= T(T(1+1)^3) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 1134 &:= -T(T(1+T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 \\
 1135 &:= (11 + C(3!)) \times 5 \\
 1135 &:= (11 + C(T(3))) \times 5 \\
 1135 &:= C(11) - Q(Q(3) + 5) \\
 1135 &:= F(T(T(1+1)))/T(F(T(3))) + T(5) \\
 1135 &:= -Q(Q(1+1)) + Q(F(Q(3))) - 5 \\
 1135 &:= T(Q(1+1)) \times Q(Q(3)) + T(Q(5)) \\
 1135 &:= T(Q(1+1)) + Q(3) \times C(5) \\
 \\
 1136 &:= (-F(11) + T(T(T(3)))) \times F(6) \\
 1136 &:= (Q(11) + F(F(3!))) \times F(6) \\
 1136 &:= (Q(11) + T(T(3))) \times F(6) \\
 1136 &:= C(11) - C(3!) + F(F(6)) \\
 1136 &:= C(11) - C(T(3)) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1136 := -F(11) + Q(C(3) + F(6))$$

$$1137 := 11 + T(3)! + T(T(7))$$

$$1137 := C(C(1 + 1)) + Q(-3 + T(7))$$

$$1137 := Q(11) \times C(F(3)) + Q(F(7))$$

$$1137 := Q(11) \times F(3!) + Q(F(7))$$

$$1138 := 1 + Q(Q(-1 + 3!)) + C(8)$$

$$1138 := Q(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + C(T(3)) + T(T(8))$$

$$1138 := Q(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + F(3) \times Q(F(8))$$

$$1138 := Q(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + Q(T(T(3))) + Q(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1139 := 11 + T(F(3) + T(9))$$

$$1139 := -1 - Q(1 + 3) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1139 := -Q(11) + Q(Q(3!)) - Q((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1139 := -Q(11) + Q(Q(T(3))) - Q(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1140 := F(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + T(Q(4) + 0!)$$

$$1140 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 0$$

$$1140 := T(T(T(Q(1 + 1)))) - Q(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 0!)$$

$$1141 := Q(F(Q(T(1 + 1)))) - T(4 + 1)$$

$$1141 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 1$$

$$1142 := (1 + 1) \times Q(4!) - T(Q(2))$$

$$1142 := C(1 + 1)!/C(4) + C(C(2))$$

$$1142 := Q(11) + F(Q(F(4))) + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1142 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 2$$

$$1142 := T(11 + 4!) + C(C(2))$$

$$1143 := (1 + 1) \times Q(4!) - Q(3)$$

$$1143 := (C(T(1 + 1)) + Q(T(4))) \times Q(3)$$

$$1143 := (Q(11) + F(4)!) \times Q(3)$$

$$1143 := (Q(11) + T(F(4))) \times Q(3)$$

$$1143 := -F(11) + \sqrt{C(C(4))} + 3!!$$

$$1143 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 3$$

$$1143 := T(1 + 1) \times (F(4) + T(C(3)))$$

$$1143 := T(1 + 1) \times (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(C(3)))$$

$$1144 := (1 + 1) \times (Q(4!) - 4)$$

$$1144 := (-Q(1 + 1) + Q(4!)) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1144 := (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$1144 := -1 + T(1 + C(4)) - C(T(4))$$

$$1144 := -C(1 + 1) + Q(4!) + Q(4!)$$

$$1144 := F(1 + 1 + T(4)) + C(T(4))$$

$$1144 := Q(1 + 1 + T(4)) + C(T(4))$$

$$1144 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 4$$

$$1144 := -T(11) \times T(F(4)) + T(F(T(4)))$$

$$1144 := -T(11) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1145 := (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$1145 := (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$1145 := Q(11) + 4^5$$

$$1145 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 5$$

$$1145 := T(T(1 + 1))! + T(4!) + C(5)$$

$$1146 := (1 + 1) \times Q(4!) - 6$$

$$1146 := C(11) + Q(Q(4)) - Q(T(6))$$

$$1146 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 6$$

$$1147 := F(Q(Q(1 + 1))) - Q(F(4)) + Q(F(7))$$

$$1147 := Q(11) \times F(4) + Q(T(7))$$

$$1147 := Q(11) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + Q(T(7))$$

$$1147 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 7$$

$$1147 := T(11 + C(F(4))) + T(T(7))$$

$$1147 := T(T(C(1 + 1)) + \sqrt{4}) + T(T(7))$$

$$1147 := T(T(T(1 + 1))) + T(F(4))! + T(T(7))$$

$$1147 := T(T(T(1 + 1))) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + T(T(7))$$

$$1147 := -T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(4! + T(7))$$

$$1147 := -T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(4 \times F(7))$$

$$1148 := -C(1 + 1) + Q(-\sqrt{4} + T(8))$$

$$1148 := -Q(11) - C(F(4)) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1148 := Q(F(11 - \sqrt{4})) - 8$$

$$1148 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 8$$

$$1148 := Q(T(Q(1 + 1)) + 4!) - 8$$

$$1148 := T(T(Q(1 + 1))) - F(Q(4)) + T(Q(8))$$

$$1149 := (1 + 1) \times Q(4!) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1149 := 114 + T(T(9))$$

$$1149 := C(11) - C(F(4)!) + F(9)$$

$$1149 := F(11) \times F(F(F(4)!)) - ((\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$1149 := F(C(1 + 1)) + T(\sqrt{4} + T(9))$$

$$1149 := -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 9$$

$$1150 := Q(F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))))) - 5 - 0!$$

$$1150 := Q(F(Q(T(1 + 1)))) - 5 - 0!$$

$$1151 := Q(F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))))) - 5$$

$$1151 := Q(F(Q(T(1 + 1)))) - 5$$

$$1152 := (1 + 1) \times Q(Q(5) - F(2))$$

$$1152 := (1 + 1)^5 \times T(C(2))$$

$$1152 := 2 \times Q(-1 + Q(5))$$

$$1152 := 5 \times T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) - T(2)$$

$$1152 := C(1 + 1) \times F(T(5) - T(2))$$

$$1152 := C(1 + 1) \times Q(T(5) - T(2))$$

$$1152 := F(1 + \sqrt{1 + 5!}) \times C(2)$$

$$1152 := F(T(T(1 + 1))) \times F(T(5) - T(2))$$

$$1152 := Q(Q(11) - Q(5))/C(2)$$

$$1153 := -(1 + 1) + 5 \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1153 := 1 + Q(-1 + Q(5)) \times F(3)$$

$$1153 := 5 \times T(F(C(1 + 1))) - F(3)$$

$$1153 := Q(1 + Q(1 + 5)) - C(3!)$$

$$1153 := -T(1 + 1) + Q(Q(5) + Q(3))$$

$$1154 := -(1 + 1) + Q(F(5 + 4))$$

$$1154 := (1 + Q(-1 + Q(5))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1154 := -1 + T(1 + 5) \times F(T(4))$$

$$1154 := -1 + T(1 + 5) \times T(T(4))$$

$$1154 := -Q(11) + T(Q(5) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$1155 := (Q(Q(Q(1 + 1))) - Q(5)) \times 5$$

$$1155 := -1 + Q(F(Q(15 \times (1/5))))$$

$$1155 := 11 \times (5! - T(5))$$

$$1155 := 55 \times F(C(1 + 1))$$

$$1155 := T(F(11)) - T(5 \times T(5))$$

$$1155 := T(T(1 + 1) \times T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$1156 := 1 + 5 \times T(T(6))$$

$$1156 := 1 + F(T(-1 + 5)) \times T(6)$$

$$1156 := Q(F(15 - 6))$$

$$1156 := Q(Q(1 + 1) + 5 \times 6)$$

$$1157 := 1 + Q(-1 + 5 \times 7)$$

$$1157 := -C(1 + 1) + 5 \times F(F(7))$$

$$1157 := C(11) - C(5) - Q(7)$$

$$1157 := -F(11) \times (T(5) - T(7))$$

$$1157 := F(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) \times F(7)$$

$$1157 := -T(T(11)) + C(T(5)) - 7$$

$$1158 := 1 + 1 + Q(F(Q(-5 + 8)))$$

$$1158 := F(C(1 + 1)) + Q(Q(5)) + C(8)$$

$$1158 := T(1 + 1) + 5 \times T(F(8))$$

$$1158 := T(1 + 1) + 5 \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1158 := T(C(1 + 1)) + F(T(5)) + C(8)$$

$$1158 := -T(T(11)) + C(T(5)) - \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1159 := -1 + C(5) + T(T(9))$$

$$1159 := 11 \times C(5) - C((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1159 := F(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(Q(5) + 9)$$

$$1159 := T(1 + 1) + Q(Q(5) + 9)$$

$$1159 := -T(11) + T(T(5) + F(9))$$

$$1160 := Q(1 + 1) + Q(F(0! + F(6)))$$

$$1160 := T(T(1 + 1))! + Q(T(6)) - 0!$$

$$1161 := -C(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(Q(6) - 1)$$

$$1161 := F(Q(1 + 1))! + Q(F(F(6)))$$

$$1161 := T(T(1 + 1))! + Q(T(6))$$

$$1162 := 1 + Q(Q(6) - 1) - Q(C(2))$$

$$1162 := F(Q(1 + 1))! + Q(Q(6) - 2)$$

$$1162 := T(F(11) - 6)/T(2)$$

$$1162 := T(T(1 + 1)) + Q(Q(6) - 2)$$

$$1162 := T(T(-11 + T(6))) - T(C(T(2)))$$

$$1163 := 1 \times 1 + 6 + Q(F(Q(3)))$$

$$1163 := 1 + 1 + Q(T(6)) + T(3)!$$

$$1163 := 1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{16}))) - T(C(3))$$

$$1163 := C(11) - F(6) \times T(T(3))$$

$$1163 := C(11) - F(F(6)) \times C(F(3))$$

$$1164 := (1 + 1) \times (6 + Q(4!))$$

$$1164 := C(1 + 1) + Q(Q(6) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$1164 := C(11) - T(T(6)) + C(4)$$

$$1164 := Q(1 + 1)! \times Q(6) + T(4!)$$

$$1164 := T(F(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(-F(6) + F(T(4)))$$

$$1165 := (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 5$$

$$1165 := -11 + Q(Q(6)) - 5!$$

$$1165 := -11 + T(6!/T(5))$$

$$1165 := 5 \times F(F(1 \times 1 + 6))$$

$$1166 := Q(F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))))) + \sqrt{Q(F(6)) + Q(6)}$$

$$1166 := -T(11) + C(F(6)) + 6!$$

$$1166 := -T(11) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(F(6))$$

$$1166 := -T(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + 6 + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1167 := 11 + Q(6 + T(7))$$

$$1167 := 11 + Q(F(F(6)) + F(7))$$

$$1167 := -T(F(C(1 + 1))) + 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$1167 := -T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$1168 := -C(1 + 1) + T(6 \times 8)$$

$$1168 := C(C(1 + 1)) + 6! - Q(8)$$

$$1168 := Q(Q(F(Q(1 + 1))!)) - Q(F(6)) - Q(8)$$

$$1168 := T(-1 + Q(1 + 6)) - 8$$

$$1168 := T(T(T(1 + 1)) \times F(6)) - 8$$

$$1169 := C(11) - 6 \times C(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1169 := C(11) - 6 \times \sqrt{C(9)}$$

$$1169 := C(11) - \sqrt{Q(6) \times C(9)}$$

$$1169 := F(1 \times 1 + 6) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1169 := -Q(11) + Q(Q(6)) - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1169 := -Q(11) + Q(Q(6)) - T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1170 &:= C(Q(F(Q(1+1)))) + Q(F(0! + 7)) \\
 1170 &:= Q(F(Q(F(Q(1+1)))) + F(7) + 0! \\
 1170 &:= -T(T(1+1)) + T(Q(7) - 0!) \\
 1171 &:= -(T(T(Q(1+1))) - T(Q(7)) - 1) \\
 1172 &:= -1 + T(-1 + Q(7)) - T(2) \\
 1172 &:= Q(1+1)! \times Q(7) - Q(2) \\
 1172 &:= Q(Q(1+1)) + Q(F(7+2)) \\
 1173 &:= 11 + Q(T(7)) + T(C(3)) \\
 1173 &:= -C(C(1+1)) + C(F(7)) - C(C(F(3))) \\
 1173 &:= Q(1+1)! \times Q(7) - 3 \\
 1173 &:= T(-1+1) + Q(7) + T(Q(3)) \\
 1173 &:= T(1+1) \times (F(7) + T(C(3))) \\
 1174 &:= -(1+1) + Q(7) \times 4! \\
 1174 &:= -(1+1) + T(-7 + F(T(4))) \\
 1174 &:= -(1+1) + T(-7 + T(T(4))) \\
 1175 &:= -(1+1) + Q(7) \times Q(5) \\
 1175 &:= (1+1 + F(F(7))) \times 5 \\
 1175 &:= -1 + T((-1+7)!/T(5)) \\
 1175 &:= -T(1+1) - C(F(7)) + C(T(5)) \\
 1176 &:= 6 \times Q(7 \times (1+1)) \\
 1176 &:= 7 \times F(C(1+1)) \times F(6) \\
 1176 &:= T((1 \times 1 + 7) \times 6) \\
 1177 &:= 1 + (-1 + Q(F(7))) \times 7 \\
 1177 &:= 1 + T(-1 + 7 \times 7) \\
 1178 &:= -11 + T(Q(7)) - T(8) \\
 1178 &:= C(C(1+1)) + T(T(7) + 8) \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) \\
 1179 &:= F(-1 + F(7)) + T(T(9)) \\
 1179 &:= Q(1+1)! \times Q(7) + \sqrt{9} \\
 1179 &:= Q(Q(1+1)) + 7 + Q(F(9)) \\
 1179 &:= T(-1 + Q(7)) + \sqrt{9} \\
 1179 &:= T(Q(1+1)) + F(7) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1180 &:= Q(1+1)! + Q(F(0! + 8)) \\
 1180 &:= -T(Q(T(1+1))) + Q(T(8) - 0!) \\
 1181 &:= Q(F(Q(T(1+1)))) + Q(\sqrt{T(8)} - 1) \\
 1182 &:= -1 + Q(F(1+8)) + C(F(Q(2))) \\
 1182 &:= F(F(F(Q(1+1)!)) + (Q(F(8)) + F(Q(2)))!) \\
 1182 &:= Q(1+1) + T(T(8)) + C(C(2)) \\
 1182 &:= T(T(1+1)) + T(8 \times T(T(2))) \\
 1182 &:= T(T(1+1)) + T(Q(8) - Q(Q(2))) \\
 1182 &:= T(T(1+1)) + T(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C(2)) \\
 1183 &:= (-1 + C(1 + F(8)))/Q(3) \\
 1183 &:= C(T(1+1)) + Q(T(8) - F(3)) \\
 1183 &:= F(Q(Q(1+1))) + Q(8 + 3!) \\
 1183 &:= Q(-1+1) + T(8) + C(3) \\
 1183 &:= -Q(11) + Q(T(8)) + F(T(3)) \\
 1183 &:= Q(11 \times 8) - Q(Q(Q(3))) \\
 1184 &:= (T(11) + 8) \times Q(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1184 := 1 + Q(F(1 + 8)) + C(F(4))$$

$$1184 := C(1 + 1)!/T(8) + C(4)$$

$$1184 := F(T(T(1 + 1))) + T(8 \times T(F(4)))$$

$$1184 := Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))! - 8 + Q(F(Q(F(4))))$$

$$1185 := (T(T(1 + 1)) + T(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$1185 := (T(T(1 + 1)) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 5$$

$$1185 := C(11) - F(8) - C(5)$$

$$1185 := Q(T(1 + 1)) + Q(T(8)) - 5!$$

$$1185 := T(T(1 + 1))! + T(5 \times \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1186 := C(1 + 1) + T(T(8)) + C(F(6))$$

$$1186 := -F(11) - F(8) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1186 := T(11) + 8!/Q(6)$$

$$1186 := T(11) + 8!/T(F(6))$$

$$1187 := -(1 + 1) - T(8) + T(Q(7))$$

$$1188 := (-1 + F(1 + 8)) \times T(8)$$

$$1188 := -(T(1 + 1) - T(8)) \times T(8)$$

$$1188 := Q(-1 + C(\sqrt{1 + 8})) + C(8)$$

$$1188 := -Q(Q(1 + 1))! + Q(F(8) + F(8))$$

$$1189 := -1 - (1 - T(8)) \times F(9)$$

$$1189 := -1 + (-1 + T(8)) \times F(9)$$

$$1189 := -1 + F(1 + 8) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1189 := -C(C(1 + 1)) + T(T(8)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1189 := Q(-1 + Q((\sqrt{1 + 8})!)) - Q((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1189 := Q(T(Q(1 + 1))) + Q(T(8) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1190 := (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 0$$

$$1190 := F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) \times (F(9) + 0!)$$

$$1190 := F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 0$$

$$1191 := (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 1$$

$$1191 := F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 1$$

$$1192 := (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 2$$

$$1192 := F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 2$$

$$1192 := Q(F(Q(1 + 1))) + Q(F(9)) + C(F(Q(2)))$$

$$1192 := Q(Q(1 + 1)) + T(T(9)) + T(2)$$

$$1192 := T(C(1 + 1)) + F(9)^2$$

$$1193 := (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 3$$

$$1193 := 1 + Q(F(9)) + Q(3!)$$

$$1193 := 1 + Q(F(9)) + Q(T(3))$$

$$1193 := -C(1 + 1) + Q(F(9)) + T(Q(3))$$

$$1193 := F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 3$$

$$1193 := -Q(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + C(9) + 3!!$$

$$1193 := -Q(Q(Q(1 + 1))) + C(9) + T(3)!$$

$$1193 := -Q(T(Q(1 + 1))) - \sqrt{9} + Q(Q(T(3)))$$

$$1194 := (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 4$$

$$1194 := 1 + 1 + Q(F(9)) + Q(F(4)!)$$

$$1194 := 11 + Q(F(9)) + C(F(4))$$

$$1194 := F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 4$$

$$1194 := T(11) + T(T(9) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1195 := (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 5$$

$$1195 := C(11) - T(Q(9 - 5))$$

$$1195 := C(11) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 5)$$

$$1195 := C(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(F(9)) - Q(5)$$

$$1195 := F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 5$$

$$1195 := Q(1 + 1)! + Q(F(9)) + T(5)$$

$$1195 := Q(Q(1 + 1))! - (\sqrt{9})! + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1195 := Q(Q(1 + 1))! - T(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1196 &:= (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 6 \\
 1196 &:= C(11) + Q(9) - C(6) \\
 1196 &:= F(11) + T(F(9)) + C(F(6)) \\
 1196 &:= F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 6 \\
 1196 &:= Q(1 + 1) + Q(F(9)) + Q(6) \\
 1196 &:= -Q(1 + 9) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1196 &:= T(F(11)) - Q(T(9) + F(6)) \\
 \\
 1197 &:= (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 7 \\
 1197 &:= 7 \times T(9 \times (1 + 1)) \\
 1197 &:= -C(1 + 9) + C(F(7)) \\
 1197 &:= F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 7 \\
 1197 &:= -Q(F(Q(1 + 1))) \times (Q((\sqrt{9})!) - Q(F(7))) \\
 \\
 1198 &:= (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 8 \\
 1198 &:= F(C(1 + 1)) + Q(F(9)) + F(8) \\
 1198 &:= F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 8 \\
 1198 &:= Q(Q(T(T(1 + 1)))) - 98 \\
 1198 &:= Q(T(C(1 + 1))) - 98 \\
 1198 &:= T(T(1 + 1)) + Q(F(9)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 1199 &:= (1 + 1) \times T(F(9)) + 9 \\
 1199 &:= -(1 + 1) + T(9) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1199 &:= 1 + Q(-1 + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) - C(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1199 &:= F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))) + Q(F(9)) + 9 \\
 1199 &:= Q(F(Q(1 + 1))) + F(9) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1199 &:= Q(Q(1 + 1)) + C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1199 &:= -Q(Q(1 + 1)) + T(9) \times C(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1199 &:= -Q(Q(1 + 1)) - Q(9) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 1199 &:= -Q(T(Q(1 + 1))) + Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 \\
 1200 &:= (1 + Q(2))! \times T(Q(0! + 0!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1200 &:= Q(-1 + F(C(2))) \times F(Q(0! + 0!)) \\
 1200 &:= Q(-1 + F(F(F(Q(2)!))) \times F(Q(0! + 0!)) \\
 \\
 1201 &:= 1 + T(Q(2)!) \times Q(1 + 0!) \\
 1201 &:= Q(-1 + T(C(2))) - Q(1 + 0!)! \\
 1201 &:= Q(Q(1 + Q(2))) + Q(Q(1 + 0!)!) \\
 \\
 1202 &:= 1 + Q(Q(2)!) + Q(Q(0! + Q(2))) \\
 1202 &:= 1 + T(Q(T(2))) + Q(F(0! + C(2))) \\
 \\
 1203 &:= (1 + Q(20)) \times 3 \\
 1203 &:= F(1 + T(T(T(2) - 0!)) + C(T(3)) \\
 \\
 1204 &:= (1 + T(2)) \times (0! + T(4!)) \\
 1204 &:= C((1 + 2)!) + 0! + F(Q(4)) \\
 1204 &:= C(T(1 + 2)) + 0! + F(Q(4)) \\
 1204 &:= Q(-1 + Q(2)! - 0!) + F(4)!! \\
 1204 &:= Q(2) \times (0! + T(4!)) \\
 \\
 1205 &:= Q(-1 + Q(2)!) + Q(0! + Q(5)) \\
 1205 &:= T(F(1 + C(2))) - (0 - F(T(5))) \\
 1205 &:= T(F(1 + F(T(T(2)))) + F(T(5)) \\
 1205 &:= T(F(-1 + T(T(2) + 0!))) + F(T(5)) \\
 1205 &:= T(F(Q(1 + 2))) + F(T(5)) \\
 \\
 1206 &:= 1 + Q(F(Q(F(Q(2)))) + Q(6 + 0!) \\
 1206 &:= C(1 + T(Q(2))) - C(-0! + 6) \\
 1206 &:= Q(Q(2)!) + T(-0! + Q(6)) \\
 1206 &:= T(-1 + T(C(2) + 0!)) + C(6) \\
 \\
 1207 &:= (1 + Q(Q(2))) \times \sqrt{0! + 7!} \\
 1207 &:= -T(-1 + T(0! + C(2))) + C(F(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1208 &:= -1 - Q(Q(2)) + Q(T(8) - 0!) \\
 1209 &:= -1 + T(T(Q(2))) \times (0! + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 1209 &:= Q(-1 + T(C(2))) - Q(0! + \sqrt{9}) \\
 1209 &:= -Q(Q(2)) + Q(-0! + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 1209 &:= -Q(Q(2)) + Q(F(9) + 0!) \\
 1210 &:= (1 + F(C(2))) \times F(10) \\
 1210 &:= (1 + F(C(2))) \times T(10) \\
 1210 &:= (1 + F(F(F(Q(2)!))) \times F(10) \\
 1210 &:= (1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times F(10) \\
 1210 &:= (1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(10) \\
 1211 &:= -(1 + Q(2))! + C(11) \\
 1211 &:= -(T(T(2)) - 1)! + C(11) \\
 1211 &:= 1 + T(Q(2)) \times Q(11) \\
 1211 &:= F(1 + Q(F(Q(2)))) + Q(F(Q(F(Q(1 + 1)))))) \\
 1212 &:= (1 + Q(T(Q(2)))) \times 12 \\
 1212 &:= 1 + T(T(Q(2))) + Q(F(Q(1 + 2))) \\
 1212 &:= Q(-1 + Q(Q(2))) + F(Q(Q(2))) \\
 1213 &:= 1 + F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(-1 + T(3))) \\
 1213 &:= -12 + Q(1 + F(Q(3))) \\
 1213 &:= -12 + Q(-1 + Q(3!)) \\
 1213 &:= -12 + Q(-1 + Q(T(3))) \\
 1213 &:= Q(1 + 21) + C(Q(3)) \\
 1214 &:= -1 + C(T(2)) \times T(-1 + T(4)) \\
 1214 &:= 1 + Q(1 + F(C(2))) + C(Q(F(4))) \\
 1214 &:= -1 + Q(Q((2 + 1)!) - Q(Q(F(4))) \\
 1214 &:= -1 + Q(T(2)) \times (-1 + T(Q(4))) \\
 1215 &:= -1 + C(T(T(2))) + C(T(-1 + 5)) \\
 1215 &:= 15 \times Q(Q(1 + 2)) \\
 1215 &:= T(1 + C(2)) \times C(F(-1 + 5)) \\
 1216 &:= 1 + C(C(2)) + T(1 + Q(6)) \\
 1216 &:= -1 - C(2) + Q(Q(6) - 1) \\
 1216 &:= C(1 + C(2) + 1) + C(6) \\
 1216 &:= C(12) - C(F(6)) \\
 1216 &:= C(T(1 + 2 + 1)) + C(6) \\
 1216 &:= -Q(1 + 2) + Q(-1 + Q(6)) \\
 1217 &:= -1 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \\
 1217 &:= 1 - C(C(2)) + C(-1 + F(7)) \\
 1217 &:= 1 - Q(T(2)) + T(Q(7)) \\
 1217 &:= -C(2) + T(Q(7)) \\
 1217 &:= Q(F(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 1) - (1 + 7) \\
 1218 &:= (1 + 2) \times T(T(-1 + 8)) \\
 1218 &:= -1 + Q(F(Q(F(Q(2)))) - 1 + Q(8)) \\
 1218 &:= -T(12) + Q(T(8)) \\
 1219 &:= -(1 + 2)! + Q(1 + F(9)) \\
 1219 &:= -1 + C(Q(2)) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1219 &:= -1 + Q(C(2)) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1219 &:= 1 + T(2) \times T(1 + C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 1219 &:= 1 + T(2) \times T(C(\sqrt{9}) + 1) \\
 1219 &:= 1 + T(2) \times T(T(1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 1219 &:= Q(-1 + Q((2 + 1)!) - (\sqrt{9})! \\
 1219 &:= Q(-1 + Q(T(2 + 1))) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1219 &:= Q(-1 + T(C(2))) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1219 &:= -T(1 + 2) + Q(1 + F(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1220 &:= 2 \times F(Q(Q(2)) - 0!) \\
 1220 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 0 \\
 1220 &:= 2 \times F(T(Q(2) + 0!)) \\
 1220 &:= 2 \times F(T(T(T(2)) - 0!)) \\
 1220 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 0 \\
 1220 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 0 \\
 1220 &:= Q(-1 + Q(T(T(2)))) - Q(2) - 0! \\
 1220 &:= Q(-1 + T(C(2))) - Q(2) - 0! \\
 \\
 1221 &:= 1 + C(Q(2)) + Q(F(Q(2 + 1))) \\
 1221 &:= 1 + Q(C(2)) + Q(F(Q(2 + 1))) \\
 1221 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 1 \\
 1221 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 1 \\
 1221 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 1 \\
 1221 &:= Q(-1 + T(C(2))) - Q(2) \\
 1221 &:= T(T(1 + T(Q(2)))) - T(T(Q(T(2)))) - 1 \\
 \\
 1222 &:= (1 + F(Q(Q(2)) - F(2))) \times 2 \\
 1222 &:= (1 + F(T(2 + T(2)))) \times 2 \\
 1222 &:= 1 + T(Q(T(2))) + T(2 \times Q(2)!) \\
 1222 &:= 1 - F(F(C(2))) + C(2 + F(C(2))) \\
 1222 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 2 \\
 1222 &:= F(1 + C(2)) \times T(C(2)) - 2 \\
 1222 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 2 \\
 1222 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 2 \\
 1222 &:= Q(C(1 + 2) + C(2)) - F(Q(2)) \\
 1222 &:= T((-1 + C(2))^2) - T(2) \\
 1222 &:= T((1 + T(T(2)))^2) - T(2) \\
 1222 &:= T(1 + 2)! - T(Q(2)) + C(C(2)) \\
 \\
 1223 &:= -1 + (T(Q(2)) + Q(2)!) \times Q(T(3)) \\
 1223 &:= -1 + 2 \times (Q(Q(2)!) + Q(3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1223 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) - C(2) + T(3)! \\
 1223 &:= -1 + Q(2 + Q(2)) \times F(Q(3)) \\
 1223 &:= -1 + Q(T(2)) \times T(Q(2))^{F(3)} \\
 1223 &:= -1 - C(2) + C(C(2)) + 3!! \\
 1223 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 3 \\
 1223 &:= -2 + Q(C(2) + C(3)) \\
 1223 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 3 \\
 1223 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 3 \\
 1223 &:= T((1 + T(T(2)))^2) - F(3) \\
 \\
 1224 &:= (1/2) \times Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) + Q(4!) \\
 1224 &:= (1 + C(2)) \times T(2^4) \\
 1224 &:= (1 + Q(Q(2))) \times (C(2) + C(4)) \\
 1224 &:= (1 + T(2)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(4!)) \\
 1224 &:= (Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(2)!)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1224 &:= -1 + Q(C(2) \times Q(2) + F(4)) \\
 1224 &:= -1 + T((F(2) + T(T(2)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 1224 &:= -1 + T((F(2) + T(T(2)))^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 1224 &:= -1 + T(F(2) + 2 \times 4!) \\
 1224 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2)^2) + 4) \\
 1224 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 4 \\
 1224 &:= C(12) - C(C(2)) + \sqrt{C(4)} \\
 1224 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 4 \\
 1224 &:= F(Q(1 + 2)) \times Q(2 + 4) \\
 1224 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 4 \\
 1224 &:= Q(1 + 2) \times T(2^4) \\
 \\
 1225 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 5 \\
 1225 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 5 \\
 1225 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 5 \\
 1225 &:= Q(1 + 2 + 2^5) \\
 1225 &:= T(-1 + 2 \times 25) \\
 \\
 1226 &:= -(1 + 2)! + C(C(2)) + 6!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1226 &:= 1 + Q(-2 \times (1/2) + Q(6)) & 1229 &:= Q(2) + T(Q(2) + T(9)) \\
 1226 &:= 1 + T(F(2) + 6 \times C(2)) \\
 1226 &:= 1 + T(F(T(2 + 2)) - 6) & 1230 &:= (-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times (Q(Q(3)) + 0!) \\
 1226 &:= 1 + T(Q(2 \times (1/2) + 6)) & 1230 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + 3!! - 0! \\
 1226 &:= 1 + T(T(T(2 + 2)) - 6) & 1230 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + T(3!) - 0! \\
 1226 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 6 & 1230 &:= T(1 + Q(2)) \times (Q(Q(3)) + 0!) \\
 1226 &:= C(C(2)) - T(T(2)) + 6! \\
 1226 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 6 & 1231 &:= (1 + 2)! + Q(1 + F(Q(3))) \\
 1226 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 6 & 1231 &:= (1 + 2)! + Q(-1 + Q(3!)) \\
 & & 1231 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + 3!! \\
 1227 &:= (1 + 2)!! + F(Q(2)) \times Q(F(7)) & 1231 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + T(3!) \\
 1227 &:= (1 + 2) \times (T(2) + T(T(7))) & 1231 &:= T(1 + 2) + Q(-1 + Q(T(3))) \\
 1227 &:= 2 \times 1^2 + T(Q(7)) \\
 1227 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 7 & 1232 &:= (-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) \times Q(Q(2)) \\
 1227 &:= 2 + T(F(2) \times Q(7)) & 1232 &:= (-Q(2) + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(Q(2)) \\
 1227 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 7 & 1232 &:= (Q(Q(1 + 2)) - Q(F(3))) \times Q(Q(2)) \\
 1227 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 7 & 1232 &:= -1 + C(2) + Q(C(2) + C(3)) \\
 & & 1232 &:= C(C(2)) + (3 \times 2)! \\
 1228 &:= (1 + 2)!! - Q(2) + C(8) & 1232 &:= T(1 + 2)! + F(T(3))^{T(2)} \\
 1228 &:= -(1 + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(2) + Q(T(8)) & 1232 &:= T(1 + T(T(2))) \times (T(F(T(3))) + F(T(T(2)))) \\
 1228 &:= 1 + T(T(C(2))) + T(-T(2) + T(8)) \\
 1228 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 8 & 1233 &:= 1 + C(C(2)) + (3 + 3)! \\
 1228 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 8 & 1233 &:= 1 + T(T(2))! + F(T(3))^3 \\
 1228 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 8 & 1233 &:= Q(12) + Q(33) \\
 1228 &:= Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - Q(2) - Q(8) & 1233 &:= T((1 + T(T(2)))^{F(3)}) + F(T(3)) \\
 1228 &:= T(1 + 2)! - Q(2) + C(8) & 1233 &:= T(-1 + T(2) \times T(T(3))) - T(3)! \\
 & & & \\
 1229 &:= -1 + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9)) & 1234 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + 3!! + F(4) \\
 1229 &:= -12 + C(C(2)) + C(9) & 1234 &:= 1 + F(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + F(T(4))) \\
 1229 &:= 2 \times F(T(1 + Q(2))) + 9 & 1234 &:= 1 + Q(C(2) + C(3)) + \sqrt{C(4)} \\
 1229 &:= C(1 + Q(2)) \times Q(2) + C(9) & 1234 &:= 1 + Q(Q(2)!) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(4!) \\
 1229 &:= F(-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times 2 + 9 & 1234 &:= 3 \times T(12) + C(T(4)) \\
 1229 &:= F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2 + 9 & 1234 &:= C(C(2)) + 3!! + \sqrt{4} \\
 1229 &:= Q(2) + Q(F(2) + F(9)) & 1234 &:= Q(-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) + Q(F(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1234 := -T((1 + T(2))!) - T(3) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1234 := T(12) + Q(34)$$

$$1235 := -(1 + Q(C(2))) \times (3! - Q(5))$$

$$1235 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - Q(3)) \times 5$$

$$1235 := (T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \times 5$$

$$1235 := -1 + 2 \times (C(F(3)) + F(T(5)))$$

$$1235 := -1 + 2 \times (F(T(3)) + F(T(5)))$$

$$1235 := F(12 + 3) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1235 := Q(-1 + Q(2)!) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1235 := T(C(1 + T(2))) - T(3)! - C(5)$$

$$1235 := T(Q(2)) + Q(35)$$

$$1236 := (-1 + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(Q(3)) + F(F(6))$$

$$1236 := (1 + T(T(2))!) \times T(F(T(3)))/T(6)$$

$$1236 := 1 + T(Q(2)) + Q(C(3)) + F(6)$$

$$1236 := 4 + C(C(2)) + 6!$$

$$1236 := -Q(2)! - Q(3!) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1236 := T(1 + Q(2)) \times Q(Q(3)) + T(6)$$

$$1237 := 1 + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(T(7)))$$

$$1237 := 1 - T(2) \times (-T(3) - T(T(7)))$$

$$1237 := F(Q(1 + 2)) \times Q(3!) + F(7)$$

$$1237 := Q(Q(1 + 2)) + Q(C(3)) + 7$$

$$1237 := Q(Q(1 + 2)) + Q(T(3) + T(7))$$

$$1238 := -1 + Q(2)! - Q(Q(3)) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1238 := C(1 + C(2)) - 3 + C(8)$$

$$1238 := F(-1 + C(2)) + Q(C(3)) + 8$$

$$1238 := -F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + F(T(3)) \times T(F(8))$$

$$1238 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) + 3! - Q(8)$$

$$1239 := (1 + T(2))! + C(3) \times T(9)$$

$$1239 := (12)!/Q(3)! - Q(9)$$

$$1239 := 1 + C(C(2)) - 3 + C(9)$$

$$1239 := -2 + C(C(2)) + C(9)$$

$$1239 := 2 + Q(Q(3)) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1239 := C(C(2)) - F(3) + C(9)$$

$$1239 := Q(2)! + C(3) \times T(9)$$

$$1239 := T(-1 + T(T(2))) + T(F(T(3))) \times F(9)$$

$$1239 := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3) + T(T(9))$$

$$1239 := -T(T(12)) + T(3)! \times T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1240 := -(T((1 + T(2))!) - T(F(T(4)))) \times 0!$$

$$1240 := -(T((1 + T(2))!) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 0!$$

$$1240 := -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 0$$

$$1240 := -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!))$$

$$1240 := -1 + C(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{C(4)} + 0!)$$

$$1240 := -1 + C(C(2)) + C(T(4) - 0!)$$

$$1240 := -1 + Q(Q(2)) + Q(0! + F(Q(F(4))))$$

$$1240 := -T((1 + T(2))!) + T(F(T(4))) + 0$$

$$1240 := -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 0$$

$$1241 := -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 1$$

$$1241 := -1 + Q(Q(2)!) + T(Q(T(4 - 1)))$$

$$1241 := -1 + Q(Q(Q(2))) + (F(Q(4)) - 1)$$

$$1241 := C(C(2)) + C(-1 + T(4))$$

$$1241 := C(C(2)) + C(Q(4 - 1))$$

$$1241 := C(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{C(4)} + 1)$$

$$1241 := -T((1 + T(2))!) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$1241 := -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$1242 := (1 + T(T(2)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times C(T(2))$$

$$1242 := (2 + T(Q(4))) \times Q(T(2))$$

$$1242 := (Q(Q(1 + Q(2))) - 4) \times 2$$

$$1242 := (T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) - F(4)) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1242 := (T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1242 &:= (T(T(T(1+2))) - 4!) \times T(T(2)) \\ 1242 &:= 1 + C(C(2)) + C(F(4)^2) \\ 1242 &:= 1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(4!/C(2))) \\ 1242 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 2 \\ 1242 &:= 1 + C(C(2)) + Q(4! + T(2)) \\ 1242 &:= -1 + Q(Q(Q(2))) + F(4^2) \\ 1242 &:= -T((1+T(2))!) + T(F(T(4))) + 2 \\ 1242 &:= -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1243 &:= 1 + (2 + T(Q(4))) \times Q(3) \\ 1243 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 3 \\ 1243 &:= 1 + C(C(2)) + T(4) + T(3)! \\ 1243 &:= 1 + T(T(2)) \times (-4! + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 1243 &:= 4 \times T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 1243 &:= C(-1 + C(2)) + Q(3 \times T(4)) \\ 1243 &:= C(-1 + C(2)) + Q(4! + 3!) \\ 1243 &:= C(-1 + C(2)) + Q(F(4) + C(3)) \\ 1243 &:= C(1 + C(2)) + \sqrt{4} + C(C(F(3))) \\ 1243 &:= C(12) - \sqrt{C(C(4))} + C(3) \\ 1243 &:= Q(-1 + Q(2)!) - F(4)! + 3! \\ 1243 &:= -T((1+T(2))!) + T(T(T(4))) + 3 \\ 1243 &:= T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(F(T(F(4)))) + T(F(T(3))) \\ 1243 &:= -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1244 &:= ((-1 + C(2))! - C(4)) \times (1/4) \\ 1244 &:= -(1 + T(F(T(T(2)))) \times F(T(F(4))) + T(F(T(4))) \\ 1244 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 4 \\ 1244 &:= 1 + Q(2^4) + F(Q(4)) \\ 1244 &:= 1 + \sqrt{T(2)^{T(4)}} + C(T(4)) \\ 1244 &:= 1 + T(2) + T(F(T(4))) - T(4!) \\ 1244 &:= 1 + T(2) + T(T(T(4))) - T(4!) \\ 1244 &:= C(12) - Q(4! - \sqrt{4}) \\ 1244 &:= -T((1+T(2))!) + T(F(T(4))) + 4 \\ 1244 &:= T(12) \times Q(4) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1244 &:= -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 1245 &:= (1 - C(2) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5 \\ 1245 &:= (Q(-1 + Q(Q(2))) + 4!) \times 5 \\ 1245 &:= (T(1 + T(T(2))) + F(T(4))) \times T(5) \\ 1245 &:= (T(1 + T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times T(5) \\ 1245 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 5 \\ 1245 &:= -1 - Q(2) + \sqrt{4} \times Q(Q(5)) \\ 1245 &:= -1 - Q(2) + T(4) \times C(5) \\ 1245 &:= C(1 + Q(2)) \times Q(F(4)) + 5! \\ 1245 &:= -T((1+T(2))!) + T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 1245 &:= T(1 + C(2)) + T(4) \times 5! \\ 1245 &:= -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 1245 &:= T(Q(1 + 2)) + T(4) \times 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1246 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 6 \\ 1246 &:= C(-1 + C(2)) + T(\sqrt{4} \times T(6)) \\ 1246 &:= -Q(1 + Q(2)) \times \sqrt{4} + Q(Q(6)) \\ 1246 &:= Q(-1 + Q(2 + 4)) + F(F(6)) \\ 1246 &:= Q(2) + Q(4!) + T(Q(6)) \\ 1246 &:= -T((1+T(2))!) + T(F(T(4))) + 6 \\ 1246 &:= T(1 + 2 \times 4!) + T(6) \\ 1246 &:= -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 1246 &:= T(T(1 + 2)) + T(F(T(4))) - 6 \\ 1246 &:= T(T(1 + 2)) + T(T(T(4))) - 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1247 &:= (1/4) \times (-1 + C(2))! - F(7) \\ 1247 &:= (1 + 2)!^4 - Q(7) \\ 1247 &:= -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 7 \\ 1247 &:= -1 - T(2) \times (-T(4) - T(T(7))) \\ 1247 &:= F(1 + C(2))^{\sqrt{4}} + T(F(7)) \\ 1247 &:= Q(Q(2 + 4)) - Q(7) \\ 1247 &:= -T((1+T(2))!) + T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 1247 &:= T(1 + 2)^4 - Q(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$1247 := T(1 - C(2) + C(4)) - T(T(7))$$

$$1247 := -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 7$$

$$1248 := (1 + 2)!! + Q(4) + C(8)$$

$$1248 := (1 + 2)! \times (F(4)!! - C(8))$$

$$1248 := -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 8$$

$$1248 := 8 \times T(12) \times F(F(4))$$

$$1248 := 8 \times T(12) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1248 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - 48$$

$$1248 := -T((1 + T(2))!) + T(F(T(4))) + 8$$

$$1248 := T(12) \times (4! - 8)$$

$$1248 := -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 8$$

$$1248 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))) - 8$$

$$1249 := (1 + Q(2))! - C(F(4)) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1249 := (1 + T(2))! + T(49)$$

$$1249 := -1 + 2 \times Q(Q(4) + 9)$$

$$1249 := -1 + C(C(2)) + C(Q(F(4))) + 9$$

$$1249 := 1 - Q(Q(2)) \times (F(4) - Q(9))$$

$$1249 := C(C(2)) + \sqrt{C(4)} + C(9)$$

$$1249 := Q(2)! + T(49)$$

$$1249 := -T((1 + T(2))!) + T(T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$1249 := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + (4 + T(T(9)))$$

$$1249 := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + 4 + T(T(9))$$

$$1249 := -T(Q(1 \times 2)!) + T(T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$1250 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 0$$

$$1250 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$1251 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 1$$

$$1251 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$1252 := (1 + Q(25)) \times 2$$

$$1252 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 2$$

$$1252 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$1252 := -T(12) + F(T(5)) + T(T(2))!$$

$$1253 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 3$$

$$1253 := -1 + T(2 \times Q(5)) - T(T(3))$$

$$1253 := 1 - C(C(2)) + Q(T(5) + C(3))$$

$$1253 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$1253 := -T(12) + C(5 + T(3))$$

$$1254 := (-1 + T(5 \times Q(2))) \times T(F(4))$$

$$1254 := (2 + Q(Q(5))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1254 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 4$$

$$1254 := 1 + T(2) + C(5) \times T(4)$$

$$1254 := Q(2) + T(4) \times C(5)$$

$$1254 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$1254 := -T(T(1 + 2)) + T(5 \times T(4))$$

$$1255 := (1 + 2 \times C(5)) \times 5$$

$$1255 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 5$$

$$1255 := 1 + Q(2) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1255 := -1 + T(F(T(T(2)))) + F(T(5)) + F(T(5))$$

$$1255 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$1256 := (1 + T(C(2)) + 5!) \times F(6)$$

$$1256 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 6$$

$$1256 := -1 + C(C(2)) + Q(5) + 6!$$

$$1256 := 1 + Q(2^5) + T(T(6))$$

$$1256 := 2 \times F(T(5)) + T(F(6))$$

$$1256 := -C(-1 + F(C(2))) - 5 + C(F(F(6)))$$

$$1256 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$1257 := (1/5) \times C(-1 + F(C(2))) - C(7)$$

$$1257 := (1 + T(2))^5 + F(F(7))$$

$$1257 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 7$$

$$1257 := 2^5 + T(Q(7))$$

$$1257 := C(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(5) + 7)$$

$$1257 := Q(2^5) + F(F(7))$$

$$1257 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$1258 := (1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times F(T(5) - \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1258 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 8$$

$$1258 := C(Q(1+2)) + Q(T(5) + 8)$$

$$1258 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$1259 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(5)) + 9$$

$$1259 := -1 + C(2)! / (5 + \sqrt{C(9)})$$

$$1259 := -1 + F(C(2)) \times 5! / F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1259 := 1 + Q(-2 + Q(5)) + C(9)$$

$$1259 := -1 + T(2 + 5) \times T(9)$$

$$1259 := -1 - Q(Q(2)) + 5! + Q(F(9))$$

$$1259 := T(1 + T(2)) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$1260 := (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 0$$

$$1260 := (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 0$$

$$1260 := 2 \times T(-0! + Q(6))$$

$$1260 := 60 \times F(C(2))$$

$$1260 := 60 \times F(F((1+2)!))$$

$$1260 := 60 \times T(T(1+2))$$

$$1260 := Q((1+2)!) \times (Q(6) - 0!)$$

$$1260 := -Q((1+2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 0$$

$$1260 := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 0$$

$$1261 := (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 1$$

$$1261 := (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 1$$

$$1261 := C(F(C(2))) - C(F(F(6)) - 1)$$

$$1261 := -Q((1+2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 1$$

$$1261 := Q((1+2)!) + Q(Q(6) - 1)$$

$$1261 := Q(T(1+2)) + Q(Q(6) - 1)$$

$$1261 := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 1$$

$$1262 := (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 2$$

$$1262 := (1 + T(-F(2) + T(F(6)))) \times 2$$

$$1262 := (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 2$$

$$1262 := (1 - T(C(2)) + T(Q(6))) \times 2$$

$$1262 := -(F(Q(1+2)) - Q(Q(6))) \times F(2)$$

$$1262 := (Q(Q(1+Q(2))) + 6) \times 2$$

$$1262 := 1 + T(C(2)) + Q(Q(6) - F(2))$$

$$1262 := -1 - Q(2)! + Q(Q(6)) - Q(T(2))$$

$$1262 := 6 \times C(1 + Q(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$1262 := C(1 + C(2)) + F(F(6)) + C(C(2))$$

$$1262 := C(1 + C(2)) + T(6) + C(C(2))$$

$$1262 := C(Q(1+2)) + F(F(6)) + C(C(2))$$

$$1262 := -Q((1+2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 2$$

$$1262 := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 2$$

$$1263 := (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 3$$

$$1263 := (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 3$$

$$1263 := 1 + F(C(2)) + C(F(6)) + C(Q(3))$$

$$1263 := -C(1+2) + Q(Q(6)) - 3!$$

$$1263 := -C(-1 + F(C(2))) + C(F(F(6))) + F(3)$$

$$1263 := C(12) - T(Q(6) - T(3))$$

$$1263 := -Q((1+2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 3$$

$$1263 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(6)) - Q(3)$$

$$1263 := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 3$$

$$1263 := -T(12) + Q(Q(6)) + T(Q(3))$$

$$1263 := T(T(1 + C(2))) + T(T(6)) - 3$$

$$1264 := (-1 + Q(Q(2)) + Q(F(6))) \times Q(4)$$

$$1264 := (1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times Q(4)$$

$$1264 := (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1264 &:= (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 4 \\
 1264 &:= -1 - (-2 - T(6)) \times F(T(4)) \\
 1264 &:= -1 + (2 + T(6)) \times F(T(4)) \\
 1264 &:= -C(-1 + F(C(2))) + C(F(F(6))) + F(4) \\
 1264 &:= C(12) - 6! + Q(Q(4)) \\
 1264 &:= -Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 4 \\
 1264 &:= -Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(4) \\
 1264 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 4 \\
 \\
 1265 &:= -(1 + 2)! + Q(Q(6)) - Q(5) \\
 1265 &:= (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 5 \\
 1265 &:= (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 5 \\
 1265 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2)))) - Q(6) \times 5 \\
 1265 &:= 1 + 2 \times (C(F(6)) + 5!) \\
 1265 &:= 5 \times T(1^2 + T(6)) \\
 1265 &:= 5 \times T(1 + F(2 + 6)) \\
 1265 &:= -Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 5 \\
 1265 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 5 \\
 \\
 1266 &:= (1 + Q(2)) \times (-6) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1266 &:= (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 6 \\
 1266 &:= (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 6 \\
 1266 &:= (1 - F(C(2)) + T(T(6))) \times 6 \\
 1266 &:= (-1 - Q(2) + C(6)) \times 6 \\
 1266 &:= (1 - T(T(2)) + C(6)) \times 6 \\
 1266 &:= F(1 + C(2)) + C(F(6)) + 6! \\
 1266 &:= -Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 6 \\
 1266 &:= -Q(2)! + Q(Q(6)) - 6 \\
 1266 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 6 \\
 \\
 1267 &:= (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 7 \\
 1267 &:= (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 7 \\
 1267 &:= (1 - T(C(2)) + C(6)) \times 7 \\
 1267 &:= -1 - F(C(2)) + Q(Q(6)) - 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1267 &:= 2 \times T(6) + T(Q(7)) \\
 1267 &:= -Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 7 \\
 1267 &:= -Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(6)) - F(7) \\
 1267 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 7 \\
 \\
 1268 &:= (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 8 \\
 1268 &:= (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 8 \\
 1268 &:= (F((1 + T(2))!) - 6!)/T(8) \\
 1268 &:= -1 + Q(T(2)) + Q(Q(6)) - T(8) \\
 1268 &:= -1 - T(T(2)) + Q(Q(6)) - F(8) \\
 1268 &:= C(C(2)) + 6! + T(8) \\
 1268 &:= C(C(2)) + Q(6) \times F(8) \\
 1268 &:= Q((1 + 2)!) + 6! + C(8) \\
 1268 &:= -Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 8 \\
 1268 &:= Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(8) \\
 1268 &:= -T(1 + T(T(2))) + T(F(6)) \times T(8) \\
 1268 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 8 \\
 \\
 1269 &:= ((1 + Q(2))! + F(F(6))) \times 9 \\
 1269 &:= ((1 + Q(2))! + T(6)) \times 9 \\
 1269 &:= (-1 + 6 \times C(2)) \times C(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1269 &:= (-1 + 6 \times C(2)) \times \sqrt{C(9)} \\
 1269 &:= (-1 + T(C(2))) \times T(F(6)) + 9 \\
 1269 &:= (-1 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) \times T(F(6)) + 9 \\
 1269 &:= 6 \times Q(-1 + Q(Q(2))) - Q(9) \\
 1269 &:= -Q((1 + 2)!) + Q(Q(6)) + 9 \\
 1269 &:= -Q(2)! + Q(Q(6)) - \sqrt{9} \\
 1269 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 9 \\
 1269 &:= T(Q(1 + 2)) + Q(6) \times F(9) \\
 \\
 1270 &:= 1 - C(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(7 - 0!)) \\
 1270 &:= T(Q(1 + 2)) + T(Q(7)) + 0 \\
 \\
 1271 &:= -1 - Q(2)! + Q(Q(7 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1271 &:= -1 - Q(2)! + Q(T(7+1)) & 1276 &:= 1 + T(C(2) + 7 \times 6) \\
 1271 &:= -Q(1 + Q(2)) + Q(Q(7-1)) & 1276 &:= 1 + T(F(2) + T(7) + T(6)) \\
 1271 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 1 & 1276 &:= 1 - C(2) - F(7) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 & & 1276 &:= 1 - F(F(2) + 7) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1272 &:= (1+2)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(C(2))) & 1276 &:= -C(1+2) + 7 + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1272 &:= (-F(C(2)) + F(F(7))) \times T(T(2)) & 1276 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 6 \\
 1272 &:= 12 + 7!/Q(2) & & \\
 1272 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 2 & 1277 &:= -1 + 2 \times (F(F(7)) + T(T(7))) \\
 1272 &:= T(T(12) - T(7)) - T(2) & 1277 &:= 1 + 2 + Q(7) + T(Q(7)) \\
 & & 1277 &:= -1 - Q(Q(2)!) - C(7) + C(F(7)) \\
 1273 &:= 1 - (F(C(2)) - F(F(7))) \times 3! & 1277 &:= -6 + Q(Q(F(Q(2)!!)) - F(7) \\
 1273 &:= 1 + 2 + T(Q(7)) + T(Q(3)) & 1277 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 7 \\
 1273 &:= 1 + Q(2)! \times (Q(7) + Q(F(3))) & & \\
 1273 &:= -Q(Q(2)!) + Q(Q(7) - 3!) & 1278 &:= (1 - F(C(2)) + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 1273 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 3 & 1278 &:= (1 - T(T(T(2))) + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 1273 &:= T(T(1+T(2))) + 3 \times T(T(7)) & 1278 &:= -1 + C(T(T(2))) + C(7) + (\sqrt{T(8)})! \\
 1273 &:= T(T(12) - T(7)) - F(3) & 1278 &:= -1 - T(Q(2)) + T(Q(7)) + Q(8) \\
 & & 1278 &:= T(1 + T(F(T(T(2)))) - T(F(7)) + T(T(8)) \\
 1274 &:= -1 + F(Q(2)) \times F(F(7)) + Q(4!) & 1278 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 8 \\
 1274 &:= -1 + T(-(2-7) \times T(4)) & & \\
 1274 &:= -1 + T(F(2) + \sqrt{7^4}) & 1279 &:= -1 + Q(C(2)) \times (-7 + C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 1274 &:= -C(-1 + F(C(2))) + F(7) + C(F(\sqrt{C(4)})) & 1279 &:= -1 + Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(-Q(7) + Q(9)) \\
 1274 &:= F(-1 + C(2)) \times Q(7) \times \sqrt{4} & 1279 &:= 1 + T(Q(2)) + F(F(7)) + T(T(9)) \\
 1274 &:= T(12) \times Q(7)/F(4) & 1279 &:= -1 + T(T(2))! + (1/9) \times 7! \\
 1274 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 4 & 1279 &:= C((1+2)!) + C(7) + ((\sqrt{9})!!) \\
 & & 1279 &:= C(T(1+2)) + T(7) + T(T(9)) \\
 1275 &:= (1 + F(C(2)) + F(F(7))) \times 5 & 1279 &:= F(Q(1+2)) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(9)) \\
 1275 &:= (2 + Q(7)) \times Q(5) & 1279 &:= Q(1+2) + T(Q(7)) + T(9) \\
 1275 &:= T((1+2+7) \times 5) & 1279 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 9 \\
 1275 &:= T(Q(1+2)) + T(Q(7)) + 5 & 1279 &:= T(T(T(1+2))) + (F(7) + T(T(9))) \\
 & & 1279 &:= T(T(T(1+2))) + F(7) + T(T(9)) \\
 1276 &:= 1 + T(2 \times 7 + Q(6)) & & \\
 1276 &:= 1 + T(2 \times T(7) - 6) & 1280 &:= (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 0
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1280 := (-Q(Q(2))) \times (-80)$$

$$1280 := 80 \times Q(Q(2))$$

$$1280 := C(1 + T(2)) \times (F(8) - 0!)$$

$$1280 := C(1 + T(2)) \times (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) - 0!)$$

$$1281 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 1$$

$$1281 := 1 - Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q((\sqrt{8+1}!))$$

$$1281 := 1 - Q(Q(2)) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1281 := C(1 + Q(2)) + Q(F(8 + 1))$$

$$1282 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 2$$

$$1282 := (1 + Q(Q(2)!) + Q(8)) \times 2$$

$$1282 := -(C(-1 + F(C(2))) - C(F(8)) - F(C(2)))$$

$$1282 := 1 + T(C(T(2))) + T(T(8) + T(T(2)))$$

$$1282 := 1 + T(T(2)!) + T(T(8) - T(2))$$

$$1282 := F(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + T(T(8)) + T(T(2))$$

$$1282 := -Q(2)! + Q(T(8)) + T(Q(2))$$

$$1282 := -T(12) + Q(T(8)) + C(Q(2))$$

$$1282 := -T(12) + Q(T(8)) + Q(C(2))$$

$$1282 := T(F(1 + C(2))) + T(T(8)) + F(C(2))$$

$$1283 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 3$$

$$1283 := -1 + (-2 + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(3)$$

$$1283 := -12 + Q(T(8)) - F(F(3))$$

$$1283 := 1 - C(2) + Q(T(8)) - T(3)$$

$$1283 := -1 - F(C(2)) + Q(T(8)) + Q(3)$$

$$1283 := -1 - Q(2) - 8 + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1283 := -1 - T(T(2)) + Q(T(8)) - T(3)$$

$$1283 := -F(-1 + C(2)) + T(8)^{F(3)}$$

$$1283 := -F(1 + T(T(2))) + T(8)^{F(3)}$$

$$1283 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - F((1/3) \times F(8))$$

$$1284 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 4$$

$$1284 := (1 + Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(8)) \times 4$$

$$1284 := -12 + Q(Q(8 - \sqrt{4}))$$

$$1284 := -12 + T(8)^{F(F(4))}$$

$$1284 := -12 + T(8)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1284 := 2 \times (T(T(8)) - 4!)$$

$$1284 := -2^8 + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1284 := -Q(12) + Q(F(8)) + F(Q(4))$$

$$1284 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (8 + 4)$$

$$1285 := (1 + 2^8) \times 5$$

$$1285 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 5$$

$$1286 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 6$$

$$1286 := -(2 + 8) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1286 := -1 + C(T(2)) \times F(8) + 6!$$

$$1286 := -1 - Q(T(2)) + T(8) \times Q(6)$$

$$1286 := C(1 + Q(2)) + Q(F(8)) + 6!$$

$$1286 := -T(1 + T(2)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times C(6)$$

$$1286 := -T(1 + T(2)) + T(F(6)) \times T(8)$$

$$1287 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 7$$

$$1287 := (-1 + Q(2 + 8)) \times F(7)$$

$$1287 := (T(12) + F(8)) \times F(7)$$

$$1287 := -1 - C(2) + Q(8 + T(7))$$

$$1287 := C(-1 + C(2)) - Q(Q(8)) + 7!$$

$$1287 := -Q(1 + 2) + Q(8 + T(7))$$

$$1287 := T(T(1 + C(2))) + 7 \times T(8)$$

$$1287 := T(T(T(1 + T(2)))) - T(-\sqrt{T(8)} + T(7))$$

$$1288 := (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 8$$

$$1288 := (-1 + Q(2)!) \times (Q(8) - 8)$$

$$1288 := (Q(-1 + Q(Q(2))) - Q(8)) \times 8$$

$$1288 := \sqrt{1 + T(T(2))!} \times T(8) \times 8$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1288 &:= -C(2) + T(8) \times T(8) & 1292 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 2 \\
 1288 &:= F(8 \times (1 + 2))/T(8) & 1292 &:= 9 \times Q(12) - Q(2) \\
 1288 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^8} - 8 & 1292 &:= C(C(2)) + T(\sqrt{9} + T(C(2))) \\
 1288 &:= T(T(T(1 + T(2)))) - T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) & 1292 &:= Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 2 \\
 & & 1293 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 3 \\
 \\
 1289 &:= (1 + 2) \times Q(F(8)) - F(9) & & \\
 1289 &:= (-1 + F(C(2))) \times Q(8) + 9 & 1293 &:= (12)!/9! - C(3) \\
 1289 &:= 1 + (T(2) \times T(F(8)) + T(F(9))) & 1293 &:= 9 \times F(12) - 3 \\
 1289 &:= -1 + 2 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(\sqrt{9}))) & 1293 &:= 9 \times Q(12) - 3 \\
 1289 &:= 1 + C(Q(2)) + T(8) \times F(9) & 1293 &:= Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 3 \\
 1289 &:= 1 + Q(Q(2)!) - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!! & & \\
 1289 &:= -1 + T(C(2)) \times T(8) - T(\sqrt{9}) & & \\
 1289 &:= 1 + T(F(2) + F(8)) + T(T(9)) & 1294 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 4 \\
 1289 &:= -1 - T(2) + Q(T(8)) - \sqrt{9} & 1294 &:= -1 - T(C(2)) + C(9 + \sqrt{4}) \\
 1289 &:= C(Q(2)) + Q(8 + C(\sqrt{9})) & 1294 &:= -2 + (\sqrt{9})!^4 \\
 & & 1294 &:= -2 + Q(9 \times 4) \\
 & & 1294 &:= -2 + T(\sqrt{9})^4 \\
 \\
 1290 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (C((\sqrt{9})!) - 0!) & 1294 &:= 9 \times F(12) - F(F(4)) \\
 1290 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 0 & 1294 &:= 9 \times F(12) - \sqrt{4} \\
 1290 &:= 1 + C(Q(2)) + Q(F(9) + 0!) & 1294 &:= C((1 + 2)!) \times (\sqrt{9})! - \sqrt{4} \\
 1290 &:= 1 + Q(C(2)) + Q(F(9) + 0!) & 1294 &:= Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 4 \\
 1290 &:= -1 + T(Q(Q(2))) + Q(F(9)) - 0! & & \\
 1290 &:= C(1 + C(2)) + T(F(9) - 0!) & & \\
 1290 &:= Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 0 & 1295 &:= (-1 + C(T(2))) \times T(9) + C(5) \\
 1290 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + T(T(9)) - 0! & 1295 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 5 \\
 1290 &:= T((1 + T(2))!) + T(T(9) - 0!) & 1295 &:= (12)!/9! - Q(5) \\
 & & 1295 &:= -1 + F(C(2)) + T(T(9) + 5) \\
 & & 1295 &:= -1 + Q(Q(2 + 9 - 5)) \\
 \\
 1291 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 1 & 1295 &:= -1 + T(T(2) + T(9)) + 5! \\
 1291 &:= -1 - Q(2) + Q(T(9 - 1)) & 1295 &:= -1 + T(T(2) + T(9)) + T(T(5)) \\
 1291 &:= Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 1 & 1295 &:= Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 5 \\
 1291 &:= T(-1 + F(C(2))) + T(T(9) + 1) & & \\
 1291 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9) + 1) & & \\
 \\
 1292 &:= (1/2) \times F(2 \times 9) & 1296 &:= -(1 + 2 - 9) \times C(6) \\
 & & 1296 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 6 \\
 & & 1296 &:= (1 + T(2))! \times (9 \times 6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1296 := (12 - 9)! \times C(6)$$

$$1296 := 6 \times (1 + 2)!^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1296 := 6 \times T(1 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1296 := F(12) \times (\sqrt{9} + 6)$$

$$1296 := F(12) \times 9!/F(6)!$$

$$1296 := Q(1 + 29 + 6)$$

$$1296 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 6$$

$$1296 := T(-1 + T(T(2)) + T(9)) + T(6)$$

$$1296 := T(1 - 2 + 9) \times T(F(6))$$

$$1296 := T(12 - 9) \times C(6)$$

$$1297 := (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 7$$

$$1297 := 1 + Q(29 + 7)$$

$$1297 := 1 + T(C(2)) + T(9) \times T(7)$$

$$1297 := 1 + T(T(2))^{\sqrt{9+7}}$$

$$1297 := -1 + T(T(T(2)) + T(9)) - T(7)$$

$$1297 := 1 - T(T(2))! + T(9 \times 7)$$

$$1297 := -F(1 + C(2)) + C(-F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7))$$

$$1297 := -F(12) + T(T(9)) + T(T(7))$$

$$1297 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 7$$

$$1298 := (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 8$$

$$1298 := 1 + Q(2) - \sqrt{9} + Q(T(8))$$

$$1298 := 1 + Q(Q(2)!) + (C(9) - 8)$$

$$1298 := 1 + T(C(2)) + T(F(9)) + T(T(8))$$

$$1298 := 1 + T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(F(9)) + T(T(8))$$

$$1298 := -1 - C(T(2)) + T(T(9) + \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1298 := -1 - Q(2)! + \sqrt{9} \times Q(F(8))$$

$$1298 := 1 \times 2 + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}$$

$$1298 := F(12 - 9) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1298 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 8$$

$$1298 := -T(1 + T(T(2))) + T(T(9) + \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1298 := T(T(F(T(1 + 2)))) - F(9) + T(T(8))$$

$$1299 := (-1 + C(T(T(2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 9$$

$$1299 := (12)!/9! - T(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1299 := 1 + T(T(2) + F(9)) + T(F(9))$$

$$1299 := 9 \times F(12) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1299 := 9 \times Q(12) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1299 := C((1 + 2)!) \times (\sqrt{9})! + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1299 := C(T(1 + 2)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1299 := Q(Q((1 + 2)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + 9$$

$$1300 := 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + F(Q(0! + 0!))$$

$$1300 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(0! + 0!)$$

$$1300 := Q(Q(T(3))) + Q(0! + 0!)$$

$$1301 := 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(0! + 1)$$

$$1301 := -1 + Q(Q(T(3))) + T(T(1 + 0!))$$

$$1302 := (1 + C(3!)) \times (0! + 2)!$$

$$1302 := (1 + C(T(3))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1302 := Q(Q(3!)) + (0! + 2)!$$

$$1302 := Q(Q(T(3))) + T(T(2))$$

$$1303 := 1 + (C(3!) + 0!) \times 3!$$

$$1303 := 1 + (C(T(3)) + 0!) \times T(3)$$

$$1303 := 1 + 3! + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1303 := 1 + T(3) + Q(Q(T(3)))$$

$$1304 := -1 + C(Q(3)) + Q(4!)$$

$$1304 := 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + 0! + F(4)!$$

$$1304 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(-0! + 4)$$

$$1304 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(0! + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1304 := -1 + Q(Q(T(3))) + Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!)$$

$$1304 := -C(3) + C(0! + T(4))$$

$$1304 := C(\sqrt{1 + (3! - 0)!}) - C(F(4))$$

$$1304 := Q(Q(T(3))) - 0! + Q(F(4))$$

$$1305 := 1 - C(3) + C(\sqrt{0! + 5!})$$

$$1305 := 1 - Q(F(3)) \times (-0! - T(Q(5)))$$

$$1305 := Q(3) + Q(Q(0! + 5))$$

$$1306 := 1 + Q(3) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1306 := T(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1307 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) - 0! + F(7)$$

$$1307 := 1 + Q(Q(3)) + T(Q(7))$$

$$1307 := T(F(T(1 + 3))) - F(F(7))$$

$$1308 := (1 + C(T(3)) + 0!) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1308 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + F(-0! + 8)$$

$$1308 := 13 - 0! + Q(T(8))$$

$$1308 := T(F(T(1 + 3))) - 0! - T(F(8))$$

$$1308 := T(T(T(1 + 3))) - 0! - T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1309 := 13 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$1309 := Q(Q(3!)) + F(0! + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1309 := T(F(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1309 := T(Q(1 + 3) + 0!) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1309 := T(T(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1309 := -T(T(T(3))) + T(F(0! + 9))$$

$$1309 := -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(0! + 9))$$

$$1310 := 1 - T(T(T(3))) + T(F(10))$$

$$1310 := 1 - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(10))$$

$$1311 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(Q(1 + 1))$$

$$1311 := -1 + Q(Q(T(3))) + Q(Q(1 + 1))$$

$$1311 := 1 - F(C(F(3))) + C(11)$$

$$1311 := 1 - T(T(3)) + C(11)$$

$$1312 := (1 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(Q(2))$$

$$1312 := T(1 + T(C(F(3)) + 1)) + T(F(C(2)))$$

$$1312 := T(1 + T(F(T(3)) + 1)) + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$1313 := 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(1 + 3)$$

$$1313 := 1 + Q(Q(F(3))) + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1313 := 1 + Q(Q(F(3))) + Q(Q(T(3)))$$

$$1313 := 1 + T(T(T(3))) + T(1 + T(Q(3)))$$

$$1313 := F(T(-1 + T(3))) + T(1 + T(C(F(3))))$$

$$1313 := F(T(-1 + T(3))) + T(1 + T(F(T(3))))$$

$$1314 := 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + (1 + Q(4))$$

$$1314 := -1 + T(3)! + T(F(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$1314 := Q(-1 + F(Q(3))) + Q(-1 + Q(4))$$

$$1314 := Q(1 + Q(T(3))) - T(T(4))$$

$$1315 := -Q(1 + 3) + C(\sqrt{1 + 5!})$$

$$1315 := Q(-1 + F(Q(3))) + 1 + Q(T(5))$$

$$1315 := T(F(C(F(3)) + 1)) + (1 + 5)!$$

$$1315 := T(F(F(T(3)) + 1)) + (1 + 5)!$$

$$1315 := T(T(T(1 + 3))) - Q(15)$$

$$1316 := -1 + F(C(3 - 1)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1316 := -1 + F(Q(3) - 1) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1316 := 1 + T(3)! + T(F(1 + F(6)))$$

$$1316 := -1 + T(T(3)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1317 := -F(Q(1 + 3)) + Q(-1 + Q(7))$$

$$1317 := T(T(3)) + Q(T(1 + 7))$$

$$1318 := 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + F(8)$$

$$1318 := 1 + T(T(3)) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1319 := -1 + Q(F(3))! + Q(T(-1 + 9))$$

$$1319 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + (1 + \sqrt{9})!$$

$$1319 := -1 + Q(Q(T(3))) + (1 + \sqrt{9})!$$

$$1320 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(Q(2) + 0!)$$

$$1320 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 0$$

$$1320 := F(T(1 + 3)) \times (T(2) + 0!)$$

$$1320 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 0$$

$$1320 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times (T(2) + 0!)$$

$$1320 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 0$$

$$1321 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 1$$

$$1321 := Q(-1 + 3!) + Q(Q((2 + 1)!))$$

$$1321 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 1$$

$$1321 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 1$$

$$1322 := (1 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(Q(2)) + T(Q(2))$$

$$1322 := -1 + C(3 + C(2)) - C(2)$$

$$1322 := -1 + C(Q(3) + 2) - C(2)$$

$$1322 := -1 + T(T(3))^2 \times T(2)$$

$$1322 := -1 - C(F(3)) + C(C(2) + T(2))$$

$$1322 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 2$$

$$1322 := -Q(3) + C(C(2) + T(2))$$

$$1322 := Q(Q(3!)) + 2 + Q(2)!$$

$$1322 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 2$$

$$1322 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 2$$

$$1323 := (1 + 3!)^2 \times C(3)$$

$$1323 := (-1 + F(3!)^2) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$1323 := (1 + T(3))^2 \times C(3)$$

$$1323 := 3 \times Q(F(2^3))$$

$$1323 := 3 \times Q(T(2 \times 3))$$

$$1323 := -C(-1 - 3) + C(3 + C(2))$$

$$1323 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 3$$

$$1323 := Q(1 + 3!) \times (Q(2)! + 3)$$

$$1323 := Q(1 + 3 \times 2) \times C(3)$$

$$1323 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 3$$

$$1323 := -\sqrt{C(1 + 3)} + C(3 + C(2))$$

$$1323 := T(3)^{Q(2)} + C(3)$$

$$1323 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 3$$

$$1323 := T(T(3)) \times T(2) \times T(T(3))$$

$$1324 := 1 + C(3) + Q(Q(2 + 4))$$

$$1324 := 1 + C(3) + Q(T(2 \times 4))$$

$$1324 := 1 + C(3 + C(2)) - \sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$1324 := 1 + F(F(3!))^2 \times F(4)$$

$$1324 := 1 + T(T(3))^2 \times F(4)$$

$$1324 := 1 + T(T(3))^2 \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1324 := -1 - 3! + C(C(2) + F(4))$$

$$1324 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 4$$

$$1324 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 4$$

$$1324 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2) + 4!$$

$$1324 := T((1 + 3)!) + 2^{T(4)}$$

$$1324 := T(1 + T(3)) + Q(T(2 \times 4))$$

$$1324 := T(1 + T(3)) + T(T(2))^4$$

$$1324 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 4$$

$$1325 := (-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times Q(5)$$

$$1325 := (1 + Q(3!) + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(5)$$

$$1325 := (Q(3) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 5$$

$$1325 := -1 + C(3 + C(2)) - 5$$

$$1325 := -1 + T(F(3) + Q(2 + 5))$$

$$1325 := -1 + T(Q(3 \times 2) + T(5))$$

$$1325 := -1 + T(T(3))^2 + T(5)$$

$$1325 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 5$$

$$1325 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 5$$

$$1325 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 5$$

$$1326 := -1 + C(3) + Q(2) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1326 := 1 + C(3 + C(2)) - 6$$

$$1326 := 3! + Q(2)! + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1326 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 6$$

$$1326 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 6$$

$$1326 := T(-13 + 2^6)$$

$$1326 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 6$$

$$1327 := -(1 + 3) + C(-2 + F(7))$$

$$1327 := -(1 + 3) + C(Q(2) + 7)$$

$$1327 := 1 + T(T(3) + T(2 + 7))$$

$$1327 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 7$$

$$1327 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 7$$

$$1327 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 7$$

$$1328 := -(1 - 3) \times (-2 + T(T(8)))$$

$$1328 := (Q(13) - F(Q(2))) \times 8$$

$$1328 := (Q(13) - T(2)) \times 8$$

$$1328 := -3!! + Q(2) \times C(8)$$

$$1328 := -3 + C(T(2) + 8)$$

$$1328 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 8$$

$$1328 := F(3) \times (-2 + T(T(8)))$$

$$1328 := Q(Q(3!)) + 8 \times Q(2)$$

$$1328 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 8$$

$$1328 := \sqrt{1 + 3} \times (-2 + T(T(8)))$$

$$1328 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 8$$

$$1329 := -1 + 3!^{Q(2)} + F(9)$$

$$1329 := -1 + T(3)^{Q(2)} + F(9)$$

$$1329 := 1 - 3 + C(2 + 9)$$

$$1329 := 3 + T(T(T(2)) + T(9))$$

$$1329 := F(1 + Q(3)) \times Q(2)! + 9$$

$$1329 := Q(1 + T(3)) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1329 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(2)! + 9$$

$$1329 := T((1 + 3)!) - T(T(2)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1329 := T(T(1 + 3)) \times Q(2)! + 9$$

$$1330 := (-1 + T(Q(T(3)))) \times (3 - 0!)$$

$$1330 := (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times F(3) + 0$$

$$1330 := -1 + C(3! + 3! - 0!)$$

$$1330 := -1 + C(F(3) \times 3! - 0!)$$

$$1330 := -1 + C(F(3) \times T(3) - 0!)$$

$$1330 := -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 0$$

$$1330 := -1 + C(Q(3) + 3 - 0!)$$

$$1330 := -1 + C(T(3) + T(3) - 0!)$$

$$1330 := -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(3!) - 0!$$

$$1330 := F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 0$$

$$1330 := F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 0$$

$$1330 := T(F(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(T(3)) - 0!)$$

$$1330 := T(T(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(T(3)) - 0!)$$

$$1331 := (1 + Q(3!)) \times Q(3!) - 1$$

$$1331 := (1 + Q(T(3))) \times Q(T(3)) - 1$$

$$1331 := (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times F(3) + 1$$

$$1331 := -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 1$$

$$1331 := C(13 - 3 + 1)$$

$$1331 := F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 1$$

$$1331 := F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 1$$

$$1332 := (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times F(3) + 2$$

$$1332 := -(1 - 3) \times T(T(3)^2)$$

$$1332 := 1 + (3 + F(T(3)))^{T(2)}$$

$$1332 := 1 + (Q(3) + F(3))^{T(2)}$$

$$1332 := 1 + C(3 \times 3 + 2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1332 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 2 \\
 1332 &:= F(3) \times T(T(3)^2) \\
 1332 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 2 \\
 1332 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 2 \\
 1332 &:= Q(3!) + 3!^{Q(2)} \\
 1332 &:= \sqrt{1+3} \times T(Q(3 \times 2)) \\
 1332 &:= \sqrt{1+3} \times T(T(3)^2) \\
 \\
 1333 &:= (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))))) \times F(3) + 3 \\
 1333 &:= 1 + (3! + C(3!)) \times 3! \\
 1333 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 3 \\
 1333 &:= 1 + F(3) \times T(T(3)^{F(3)}) \\
 1333 &:= 1 + Q(3!) + Q(Q(3 + 3)) \\
 1333 &:= 1 + Q(T(3)) + Q(Q(3 + 3)) \\
 1333 &:= C(-1 + 3! + 3!) + F(3) \\
 1333 &:= C(-1 + T(3) + T(3)) + F(3) \\
 1333 &:= F(3) + C(Q(3) + F(3)) \\
 1333 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 3 \\
 1333 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 3 \\
 1333 &:= T(C(1 + 3)) - T(3)! - C(3) \\
 \\
 1334 &:= (1 + Q(3!)) \times Q(3!) + \sqrt{4} \\
 1334 &:= (1 + T(Q(3 + 3))) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1334 &:= (1 + T(T(3) \times T(3))) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1334 &:= (1 + T(T(3)^{F(3)})) \times F(F(4)) \\
 1334 &:= (1 + T(T(3)^{F(3)})) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1334 &:= (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))))) \times F(3) + 4 \\
 1334 &:= (Q(-1 + Q(3!)) - Q(Q(Q(3)))) \times (-1/4) \\
 1334 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 4 \\
 1334 &:= -1 + T(T(3 \times 3)) + T(4!) \\
 1334 &:= 3 + C(3 + \sqrt{C(4)}) \\
 1334 &:= 3 + C(C(3) - Q(4)) \\
 1334 &:= C(\sqrt{1+3}) + T(C(3) + 4!) \\
 1334 &:= F(13) \times 3! - C(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1334 &:= F(13) \times T(3) - C(4) \\
 1334 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 4 \\
 1334 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 4 \\
 \\
 1335 &:= (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))))) \times F(3) + 5 \\
 1335 &:= (F(Q(1 + 3)) - 3!) \times 5 \\
 1335 &:= (T(13) - F(3)) \times T(5) \\
 1335 &:= -1 + 3! - Q(3) + Q(Q(5)) \\
 1335 &:= 1 + 3 + C(3! + 5) \\
 1335 &:= 1 + 3 + C(5 + T(3)) \\
 1335 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 5 \\
 1335 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 5 \\
 1335 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 5 \\
 1335 &:= T((1 + 3)!) + T(3 \times T(5)) \\
 1335 &:= T((1 + 3)!) + T(5 \times Q(3)) \\
 \\
 1336 &:= (-1 + F(3!) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(6) \\
 1336 &:= (-1 + F(T(3)) \times T(T(3))) \times F(6) \\
 1336 &:= (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))))) \times F(3) + 6 \\
 1336 &:= (Q(13) - F(3)) \times F(6) \\
 1336 &:= -1 + 3! + C(3 + F(6)) \\
 1336 &:= 1 + 3 + Q(3!) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1336 &:= 1 + 3 + Q(T(3)) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1336 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 6 \\
 1336 &:= -1 + T(3) + C(3 + F(6)) \\
 1336 &:= 13 + C(3) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1336 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 6 \\
 1336 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 6 \\
 1336 &:= T(T(T(1 + 3))) + (C(3) - T(T(6))) \\
 \\
 1337 &:= (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))))) \times F(3) + 7 \\
 1337 &:= (-1 - T(T(T(3)) - F(3))) \times (-7) \\
 1337 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 7 \\
 1337 &:= -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + 7 \times 3!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1337 &:= -1 - 3!! + 3! \times C(7) \\ 1337 &:= -1 - T(3)! + T(3) \times C(7) \\ 1337 &:= F((1 + 3)!)/Q(3!) + Q(7) \\ 1337 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 7 \\ 1337 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 7 \\ 1337 &:= Q(Q(1 + 3)) + T(-3 + Q(7)) \\ 1337 &:= T(T(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(T(3))) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1338 &:= (1 + T(3)) \times T(3) + Q(T(8)) \\ 1338 &:= (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times F(3) + 8 \\ 1338 &:= -(1 - 3) \times (3 + T(T(8))) \\ 1338 &:= 1 + 3! + C(3 + 8) \\ 1338 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 8 \\ 1338 &:= -1 + Q(Q(F(3))) + 3 \times Q(F(8)) \\ 1338 &:= 1 + T(3) + C(3 + 8) \\ 1338 &:= F(3) \times (3 + T(T(8))) \\ 1338 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 8 \\ 1338 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 8 \\ 1338 &:= \sqrt{1 + 3} \times (3 + T(T(8))) \\ 1338 &:= -T(3) \times (F(T(3)) - T(F(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1339 &:= (1 + Q(3!)) \times F(Q(3)) + Q(9) \\ 1339 &:= (-1 + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times F(3) + 9 \\ 1339 &:= -1 + C(F(3) + Q(3)) + 9 \\ 1339 &:= -1 + Q(3) + C(F(3) + 9) \\ 1339 &:= 13 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \\ 1339 &:= C(F(3)) + C(F(3) + 9) \\ 1339 &:= F(Q(1 \times 3)) + Q(Q(3!)) + 9 \\ 1339 &:= F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(3))) + 9 \\ 1339 &:= Q(Q(-1 + 3!)) + 3!! - (\sqrt{9})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1340 &:= 1 + C(F(3)) + C(T(4) + 0!) \\ 1340 &:= 1 + C(Q(3)) + F(Q(4) - 0!) \\ 1340 &:= -1 + Q(Q(T(3))) + T(T(4) - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1340 &:= F(1 + Q(Q(F(3)))) - Q(Q(4)) - 0! \\ 1340 &:= Q(3) + C(T(4) + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1341 &:= -Q(Q(1 + 3)) + F(Q(4) + 1) \\ 1341 &:= T(1 + 3) + C(T(4) + 1) \\ 1341 &:= T(Q(3)) + Q(Q(T(4 - 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1342 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times (C(4) - T(2)) \\ 1342 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times (F(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \\ 1342 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \\ 1342 &:= 1 + T(Q(3)) + Q(T(4 \times 2)) \\ 1342 &:= 1 - 3 + C(4) \times F(C(2)) \\ 1342 &:= F(-1 + Q(3)) \times C(4) - 2 \\ 1342 &:= Q(-1 + F(Q(3))) + Q(Q(4)) - F(Q(2)) \\ 1342 &:= Q(1 + Q(3!)) - C(4!/C(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1343 &:= -1 + F(3)!/(4! + 3!) \\ 1343 &:= -1 + Q(Q(3!)) + 3 \times Q(4) \\ 1343 &:= -1 + T(T(3)) \times 4^3 \\ 1343 &:= C(1 + 3!) + C(4 + 3!) \\ 1343 &:= C(1 + T(3)) + T(4)^3 \\ 1343 &:= F(1 + Q(3)) + F(4!)/Q(3!) \\ 1343 &:= Q(Q(-1 + 3!)) - \sqrt{4} + 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1344 &:= (-1 + 3! + Q(4)) \times C(4) \\ 1344 &:= (1 + F(4 + 3!)) \times 4! \\ 1344 &:= (-1 + Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times Q(4) \\ 1344 &:= (-1 + Q(Q(3)) - 4!) \times 4! \\ 1344 &:= (-1 + T(3) + Q(4)) \times C(4) \\ 1344 &:= (13 + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times C(4) \\ 1344 &:= (-3 + 4!) \times C(4) \\ 1344 &:= (C(3) + 1) \times \sqrt{4} \times 4! \\ 1344 &:= C(1 + 3) \times F(4 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1344 &:= F(Q(3) - 1) \times Q(4 + 4) & 1347 &:= T(T(3)) + T(C(4) - F(7)) \\
 1344 &:= T(1 + T(3)) \times (4! + 4!) & 1347 &:= T(T(3)) + T(\sqrt{4} + Q(7)) \\
 1344 &:= T(T(3)) \times 4^{F(4)} \\
 1344 &:= T(T(3)) \times 4^{T(\sqrt{4})} & 1348 &:= (1 + T(F(T(3))))^{F(F(4))} - F(8) \\
 1344 &:= T(T(3)) \times Q(4 + 4) & 1348 &:= (1 + T(F(T(3))))^{\sqrt{4}} - F(8) \\
 & & 1348 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4) \times F(8) \\
 1345 &:= (-1 + C(3) \times T(4)) \times 5 & 1348 &:= 13 \times 4 + Q(T(8)) \\
 1345 &:= (-1 + T(F(T(3)))) \times T(T(F(4))) + F(T(5)) & 1348 &:= 1 - Q(Q(3)) + F(Q(4)) + Q(F(8)) \\
 1345 &:= (-13 - Q(Q(4))) \times (-5) & 1348 &:= \sqrt{1+3} \times (\sqrt{C(4)} + T(T(8))) \\
 1345 &:= 1 + C(F(3))! / (5 \times F(4)!) & 1348 &:= T(F(T(1+3))) - 8 \times 4! \\
 1345 &:= 1 + F(3)! / (5 \times F(4)!) & 1348 &:= -T(T(3)) + Q(Q(4) + F(8)) \\
 1345 &:= Q(1 + 34) + 5! & 1348 &:= T(T(T(1+3))) - 8 \times 4! \\
 1345 &:= T((1 + T(3))^{\sqrt{4}}) + 5! & & \\
 1345 &:= T((1 + T(3))^{\sqrt{4}}) + T(T(5)) & 1349 &:= (-Q(1 + 3!) + Q(C(4))) / \sqrt{9} \\
 1345 &:= T(1 + F(3) \times 4!) + 5! & 1349 &:= -1 - (-3 \times T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 1345 &:= T(-T(3) + T(T(4))) + 5! & 1349 &:= -1 + 3! \times Q(4! - 9) \\
 1345 &:= T(-T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) & 1349 &:= -1 + C(3) \times (Q(4) + F(9)) \\
 & & 1349 &:= -1 + F(C(F(3))) \times C(4) + (\sqrt{9})! \\
 & & 1349 &:= Q(13) + 4! + Q(F(9)) \\
 1346 &:= 1 + Q(3 + 4) + Q(Q(6)) & & \\
 1346 &:= 1 + T(3)! + Q(4 + T(6)) & 1350 &:= (-C(3)) \times (-50) \\
 1346 &:= 1 - T(T(T(3))) + T(F(T(4))) + T(F(6)) & 1350 &:= 50 \times C(3) \\
 1346 &:= F(3) + C(4) \times F(F(6)) & 1350 &:= C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 0 \\
 1346 &:= F(3) + C(4) \times T(6) & 1350 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 0 \\
 1346 &:= \sqrt{1+3} + C(4) \times T(6) & 1350 &:= Q(-1 + Q(Q(F(3)))) \times (5 + 0!) \\
 & & 1350 &:= T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 0 \\
 & & 1350 &:= T(-1 + T(F(T(3)))) + (0! + 5)! \\
 1347 &:= (-1 + T(3)!) \times F(F(4)) - T(F(7)) & & \\
 1347 &:= (1 + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times F(F(4)) + F(7) & 1351 &:= -1 + F(C(F(3))) + C(\sqrt{1+5}) \\
 1347 &:= (1 + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{4} + F(7) & 1351 &:= C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 1 \\
 1347 &:= -(1 - T(3)!) \times \sqrt{4} - T(F(7)) & 1351 &:= F(1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(5 + 1)) \\
 1347 &:= 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + F(\sqrt{4}) + Q(7) & 1351 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 1 \\
 1347 &:= 3 \times (C(F(4)!) + F(F(7))) & 1351 &:= Q(-1 + T(3)) + T(51) \\
 1347 &:= C(T(1 + 3)) + (4 + C(7)) & 1351 &:= T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 1 \\
 1347 &:= Q(1 + 3) + C(4 + 7) \\
 1347 &:= Q(Q(3!)) + \sqrt{4} + Q(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1351 := T(-1 + C(3)) + C(T(5 - 1))$$

$$1352 := (1/5) \times F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - F(2)$$

$$1352 := (1/5) \times F(-1 + T(T(3))) - F(2)$$

$$1352 := (-1 + C(3)) \times 52$$

$$1352 := (1 - C(3)) \times (-52)$$

$$1352 := 1 + T(T(3)) + F(T(5)) + T(T(2))!$$

$$1352 := 2 \times Q(1^3 + Q(5))$$

$$1352 := C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 2$$

$$1352 := F(3) \times Q(Q(5) + F(2))$$

$$1352 := Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 2$$

$$1352 := Q(13) \times (5 + T(2))$$

$$1352 := T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 2$$

$$1353 := (Q((1 + 3)!) - C(5)) \times 3$$

$$1353 := 1 + C(C(F(3))) + (5! + 3!)$$

$$1353 := -1 + C(Q(3)) + Q(5)^{F(3)}$$

$$1353 := -1 + Q(3) + Q(Q(5)) + 3!!$$

$$1353 := -1 + Q(3) + Q(Q(5)) + T(3)!$$

$$1353 := 1 + T(T(3)) + C(5 + T(3))$$

$$1353 := C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 3$$

$$1353 := F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/(5 \times F(F(3)))$$

$$1353 := F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/\sqrt{5^{F(3)}}$$

$$1353 := F(-1 + T(T(3)))/((1/3) \times T(5))$$

$$1353 := Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 3$$

$$1353 := T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 3$$

$$1354 := (1/5) \times F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$1354 := (1/5) \times F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1354 := (1/5) \times F(-1 + T(T(3))) + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$1354 := (1/5) \times F(-1 + T(T(3))) + F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1354 := -1 + C(3! + 5) + 4!$$

$$1354 := -1 + C(5 + T(3)) + 4!$$

$$1354 := -1 + T(3)! + Q(Q(5)) + T(4)$$

$$1354 := 3!! + Q(Q(5)) + Q(F(4))$$

$$1354 := C(Q(3)) + 5^4$$

$$1354 := Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 4$$

$$1354 := Q(Q(-1 + 3!)) + Q(Q(5) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1354 := T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 4$$

$$1354 := T(3)! + F(T(5)) + 4!$$

$$1354 := T(3)! + Q(Q(5)) + Q(F(4))$$

$$1355 := 1 + C(Q(3)) + 5 \times C(5)$$

$$1355 := 1 + Q(F(3) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1355 := -1 + Q(Q(3)) + T(Q(5) + Q(5))$$

$$1355 := Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 5$$

$$1355 := T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 5$$

$$1356 := (1 + Q(3 \times 5)) \times 6$$

$$1356 := (T(-1 + C(3)) - C(5)) \times 6$$

$$1356 := -1 + 3!! + C(5) + C(F(6))$$

$$1356 := Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 6$$

$$1356 := T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 6$$

$$1356 := T(3) \times (-5 + T(T(6)))$$

$$1357 := -1 + 3!! + Q(Q(5)) + F(7)$$

$$1357 := -1 + T(3)! + F(T(5)) + T(7)$$

$$1357 := -1 - Q(T(3)) + F(T(5)) + Q(T(7))$$

$$1357 := 1 - T(3)! - T(Q(5)) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1357 := C(13) - 7 \times 5!$$

$$1357 := -F(T(3)) + T(5) \times T(F(7))$$

$$1357 := Q(1 + Q(3!)) - (5 + 7)$$

$$1357 := Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 7$$

$$1357 := T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 7$$

$$1358 := 1 + 3!! + C(5) + C(8)$$

$$1358 := 1 + Q(T(3)) + Q(5) + Q(T(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1358 &:= 1 + T(3)! + C(5) + C(8) \\ 1358 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 8 \\ 1358 &:= T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 8 \\ 1358 &:= T(1 + T(3)) + F(T(5)) + (\sqrt{T(8)})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1359 &:= (-1 + C(3) + C(5)) \times 9 \\ 1359 &:= (-1 - 3! \times Q(5)) \times (-9) \\ 1359 &:= (-1 - T(3) \times Q(5)) \times (-9) \\ 1359 &:= -1 + 5 \times F(T(3)) \times F(9) \\ 1359 &:= -1 - F(3!) \times (-5 \times F(9)) \\ 1359 &:= -1 - F(T(3)) \times (-5 \times F(9)) \\ 1359 &:= C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 9 \\ 1359 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + C(5) + 9 \\ 1359 &:= T(1 \times 3) \times Q(T(5)) + 9 \\ 1359 &:= T(13) \times T(5) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\ 1359 &:= T(35) + C(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1360 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 0 \\ 1360 &:= T(C(1 + 3)) - 6! + 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1361 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 1 \\ 1361 &:= T(C(1 + 3)) - 6! + 1 \\ 1361 &:= T(Q(1 + 3)) + Q(Q(6) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1362 &:= (-(1 + 3) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 1362 &:= (F(13) - 6) \times T(T(2)) \\ 1362 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 2 \\ 1362 &:= T(C(1 + 3)) - 6! + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1363 &:= -F(13) + T(F(6)!/T(3)!) \\ 1363 &:= Q(1 + 36) - 3! \\ 1363 &:= Q(1 + 36) - T(3) \\ 1363 &:= Q(-1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1363 &:= T(1 + T(F(T(3)))) + T(T(F(6))) - T(3) \\ 1363 &:= T(C(1 + 3)) - 6! + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1364 &:= (-1 + T(Q(3))) \times (T(6) + T(4)) \\ 1364 &:= (C(-1 + 3!) + C(6)) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1364 &:= -1 + T(T(3)) + C(4) \times T(6) \\ 1364 &:= 1 - Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(6) + \sqrt{4}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1364 &:= C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 4 \\ 1364 &:= -F(13) + F(F(F(6)) - 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$1364 := -F(13) + F(T(6) - 4)$$

$$1364 := Q(-1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 4$$

$$1364 := T(C(1 + 3)) - 6! + 4$$

$$1364 := T(T(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(4))$$

$$1365 := (-13 \times T(6)) \times (-5)$$

$$1365 := 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 5$$

$$1365 := 65 \times F(Q(3) - 1)$$

$$1365 := C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 5$$

$$1365 := Q(-1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 5$$

$$1365 := T(C(1 + 3)) - 6! + 5$$

$$1366 := 1 + (T(3) \times T(T(6)) - T(6))$$

$$1366 := 1 + T(3) \times T(T(6)) - T(6)$$

$$1366 := 3! + Q(F(6)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1366 := C(1 + 3) + 6 + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1366 := C(1 + 3) + Q(Q(6)) + 6$$

$$1366 := C(1 + F(C(F(3)))) - F(F(6)) - C(F(F(6)))$$

$$1366 := F(-1 + 3 \times 6) - T(T(6))$$

$$1366 := Q(-1 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 6$$

$$1366 := T(13) - T(6) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1366 := T(C(1 + 3)) - 6! + 6$$

$$1367 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-6) - F(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1367 &:= 6 \times Q(Q(1+3)) - Q(F(7)) \\
 1367 &:= C(1+3) + Q(Q(6)) + 7 \\
 1367 &:= F(3) \times C(F(6)) + C(7) \\
 1367 &:= F(T(-1+T(3))) + T(T(F(6))) + T(F(7)) \\
 1367 &:= Q(-1+C(3)+6) + C(7) \\
 1367 &:= Q(-1+Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 7 \\
 1367 &:= T(C(1+3)) - 6! + 7 \\
 1367 &:= T(Q(1+3)) + 6 + T(Q(7)) \\
 \\
 1368 &:= (1+3)! \times (Q(6) + F(8)) \\
 1368 &:= (1-3 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (1/8) \\
 1368 &:= (F(3) + Q(6)) \times T(8) \\
 1368 &:= (\sqrt{1+3} + Q(6)) \times T(8) \\
 1368 &:= 8 \times T(3 \times 6) \\
 1368 &:= C(1+3) + Q(Q(6)) + 8 \\
 1368 &:= Q(-1+Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 8 \\
 1368 &:= Q(3) \times (C(6) - Q(8)) \\
 1368 &:= T(C(1+3)) - 6! + 8 \\
 \\
 1369 &:= (1+36)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 1369 &:= (1+T(F(T(3))))^{F(-6+9)} \\
 1369 &:= (-1 - T(F(T(3)))) \times (F(6) - T(9)) \\
 1369 &:= 1 - (3 - T(T(6))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1369 &:= 1 + (-3 + T(T(6))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1369 &:= 1 + 3!! + C(6) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1369 &:= Q(-1+Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + 9 \\
 1369 &:= Q(1+Q(3-6+9)) \\
 1369 &:= T(C(1+3)) - 6! + 9 \\
 \\
 1370 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 0 \\
 \\
 1371 &:= (1+3) \times C(7) - 1 \\
 1371 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 1 \\
 \\
 1372 &:= (1+3!) \times Q(7 \times 2) \\
 1372 &:= (1+3) \times 7^{T(2)} \\
 1372 &:= (1+C(3)) \times 7^2 \\
 1372 &:= (1+T(3)) \times Q(7 \times 2) \\
 1372 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 2 \\
 \\
 1373 &:= 1 + F(3) \times C(7) \times F(3) \\
 1373 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 3 \\
 1373 &:= -C(13) + T(3 \times T(7)) \\
 1373 &:= T(-1+T(3)) \times T(F(7)) + F(T(3)) \\
 \\
 1374 &:= (-1+3) + F(F(7)) \times F(4)! \\
 1374 &:= (1+3) \times C(7) + \sqrt{4} \\
 1374 &:= -(1+3) + T(4 \times F(7)) \\
 1374 &:= -(1+3) + T(T(7) + 4!) \\
 1374 &:= -(1-3) + 4 \times C(7) \\
 1374 &:= -1 + (-3 + T(7)) \times T(T(4)) \\
 1374 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 4 \\
 \\
 1375 &:= (1+3+7) \times C(5) \\
 1375 &:= (3! + Q(7)) \times Q(5) \\
 1375 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 5 \\
 1375 &:= F(3+7) \times Q(5) \\
 1375 &:= T(1+3) + T(F(7)) \times T(5) \\
 1375 &:= T(3+7) \times Q(5) \\
 \\
 1376 &:= -1 + 3! \times F(F(7)) - F(F(6)) \\
 1376 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 6 \\
 1376 &:= -1 + Q(37) + F(6) \\
 1376 &:= -1 + T(3) \times F(F(7)) - T(6) \\
 \\
 1377 &:= 1 + Q(37) + 7 \\
 1377 &:= -1 + T(3+7 \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1378 := 1 + 3! \times F(F(7)) - F(8)$$

$$1378 := 1 + Q(37) + 8$$

$$1378 := T(-1 + 3) + 7 \times 8$$

$$1379 := 1^3 + T(7 + T(9))$$

$$1379 := -1 + (-3 + F(F(7))) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1379 := 1 + Q(37) + 9$$

$$1379 := 1 + T(F(3 + 7) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1379 := 1 + T(T(3 + 7) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1379 := C(-1 + C(3))/F(7) + C(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1380 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 0$$

$$1380 := T(3) \times (T(F(8)) - 0!)$$

$$1381 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 1$$

$$1381 := 1 + T(3) \times (T(F(8)) - 1)$$

$$1381 := F(1 + Q(Q(F(3)))) - C((\sqrt{8+1})!)$$

$$1381 := Q(-1 + Q(Q(F(3)))) + Q(F(8 + 1))$$

$$1382 := (-1) + (T(3) \times T(F(8)) - T(2))$$

$$1382 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 2$$

$$1382 := (Q(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 2$$

$$1382 := -1 + T(3)! + T(T(8)) - T(2)$$

$$1382 := -1 + T(3) \times T(F(8)) - T(2)$$

$$1382 := 13 + Q(F(8) + Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1382 := 13 + Q(T(8) + F(2))$$

$$1382 := 1 - C(3!) + F(F(8) - Q(2))$$

$$1383 := (-1 + F(Q(3))) \times Q(8) - C(Q(3))$$

$$1383 := (-1 + T(T(3)) + Q(F(8))) \times 3$$

$$1383 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 3$$

$$1383 := Q(1 + Q(3!)) + 8 + 3!$$

$$1383 := T(3)! + T(T(8)) - 3$$

$$1383 := T(3) \times T(F(8)) - 3$$

$$1384 := (-1 + C(3) + T(T(8))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1384 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 4$$

$$1384 := -1 + Q(Q(F(3))) + Q(F(8) + Q(4))$$

$$1384 := -1 + T(3)! + T(T(8)) - F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1384 := 1 + T(3) \times T(F(8)) - F(4)$$

$$1384 := C(1 + F(C(F(3)))) - C(F(8)) - F(4)$$

$$1384 := -C(3!) + Q(Q(8) - 4!)$$

$$1384 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(8) + 4!$$

$$1384 := T(3) \times T(F(8)) - F(F(4))$$

$$1384 := T(3) \times T(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$1384 := T(3) + T(T(8)) + Q(4)$$

$$1385 := (1 + T(3))! - T(85)$$

$$1385 := (1 + T(F(3) + F(8))) \times 5$$

$$1385 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 5$$

$$1385 := (Q(Q(1 + 3)) + F(8)) \times 5$$

$$1385 := 1 - C(3!) + Q(8 \times 5)$$

$$1385 := 1 - C(T(3)) + Q(8 \times 5)$$

$$1385 := Q(Q(3!)) + Q(8) + Q(5)$$

$$1386 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 6$$

$$1386 := (-3!!) \times (-1/8) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1386 := (F(3) + Q(8)) \times F(F(6))$$

$$1386 := -1 + C(F(F(3)) + F(8)) - C(F(F(6)))$$

$$1386 := 1 + C(Q(3)) + (6! - Q(8))$$

$$1386 := 1 + Q(Q(3)) + 8 + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1386 := T(3 + 8) \times T(6)$$

$$1387 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 7$$

$$1387 := 1 + F(Q(3)) + 8 \times Q(F(7))$$

$$1387 := 1 + T(3)! + T(8 + T(7))$$

$$1387 := 1 + T(3) \times T(8 + F(7))$$

$$1387 := -C(13) + 7 \times C(8)$$

$$1387 := T(13) + Q(8 + T(7))$$

$$1388 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 8$$

$$1388 := 1 + 3 \times Q(F(8)) + Q(8)$$

$$1388 := 1 + C(F(F(3)) + F(8)) - C(F(8))$$

$$1388 := Q(13) \times 8 + T(8)$$

$$1388 := F(3) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(F(8))$$

$$1388 := \sqrt{1+3} + T(T(8)) + (\sqrt{T(8)})!$$

$$1388 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) + C(8) + T(T(8))$$

$$1389 := (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 9$$

$$1389 := -(Q(1 + 3!) - C(8)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1389 := -1 + T(T(3)) + Q(-8 + T(9))$$

$$1389 := C(1 + 3) \times F(8) + T(9)$$

$$1389 := C(1 + F(C(F(3)))) - C(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1389 := Q(13) + Q(8) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1389 := T(3)! + T(T(8)) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1389 := T(3) \times T(F(8)) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1390 := F(13) + Q(F(9)) + 0!$$

$$1390 := Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 0$$

$$1391 := -(-1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - 1$$

$$1391 := 1 + F(C(F(3))) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!) + 1)$$

$$1391 := 1 + F(F(3!)) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!) + 1)$$

$$1391 := Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 1$$

$$1392 := -(1 + 3)! + ((\sqrt{9})!) \times 2$$

$$1392 := ((1 + 3)! + F(9)) \times Q(2)!$$

$$1392 := (-1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-9 + T(2))$$

$$1392 := (Q(1 + 3!) + 9) \times Q(2)!$$

$$1392 := -2 \times (-1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1392 := C(T(3)) + T(T(9) + T(2))$$

$$1392 := F(13) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(2))$$

$$1392 := Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 2$$

$$1392 := Q(T(13)) - Q(Q(9) + 2)$$

$$1393 := (1 + 3)! + Q(F(9) + 3)$$

$$1393 := 1 + C(T(3)) + T(T(9) + 3)$$

$$1393 := 1 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + T(3)$$

$$1393 := C(1 + F(C(F(3)))) + (\sqrt{9})! - C(F(C(F(3))))$$

$$1393 := Q(1 + 3) + Q(9) + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1393 := Q(-1 + C(3)) - \sqrt{9} + 3!!$$

$$1393 := Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + \sqrt{9} + T(T(3))$$

$$1393 := Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 3$$

$$1393 := T(T(1 + T(3))) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(T(3)))$$

$$1394 := -(1 - 3) \times C(9) - C(4)$$

$$1394 := -1 + 3 \times T(F(9) - 4)$$

$$1394 := -1 + 3 \times T(\sqrt{9} \times T(4))$$

$$1394 := F(13) \times (\sqrt{9})! - 4$$

$$1394 := F(13) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - 4$$

$$1394 := F(3) \times C(9) - C(4)$$

$$1394 := Q(-1 + 3!) + Q(F(9) + F(4))$$

$$1394 := Q(-1 + Q(3!)) + Q(9 + 4)$$

$$1394 := Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 4$$

$$1394 := Q(-1 + T(3)) + Q(F(9) + F(4))$$

$$1394 := Q(13) + Q(T(9) - T(4))$$

$$1394 := \sqrt{1+3} \times C(9) - C(4)$$

$$1395 := (1 + 3)! - 5 \times C(9)$$

$$1395 := (-1 + Q(3)!/Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 5$$

$$1395 := -1 + Q(39) - C(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1395 &:= 1 + Q(F(9) + 3) + Q(5) \\
 1395 &:= 3 \times T(T(9) - T(5)) \\
 1395 &:= Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 5 \\
 \\
 1396 &:= (-1 + C(3))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6! \\
 1396 &:= 1 + 3 \times T(9 + T(6)) \\
 1396 &:= 1 + T(3)! - T(9) + 6! \\
 1396 &:= 3!! + Q(F(9) - F(6)) \\
 1396 &:= C(13) - Q(9) - 6! \\
 1396 &:= Q(1^3 + 9) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1396 &:= Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 6 \\
 1396 &:= T(3)! + Q(F(9) - F(6)) \\
 \\
 1397 &:= -1 - (3 - 9) \times F(F(7)) \\
 1397 &:= 1 + C(3) + Q(9 + T(7)) \\
 1397 &:= -1 + Q(3) + Q(F(9)) + F(F(7)) \\
 1397 &:= 1 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(\sqrt{9} + 7) \\
 1397 &:= C(T(1 + 3)) - 9 + T(T(7)) \\
 1397 &:= Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 7 \\
 1397 &:= T(1 + T(3)) + Q(9 + T(7)) \\
 \\
 1398 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(3))) + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 1398 &:= 3! \times F(F(9) - F(8)) \\
 1398 &:= 3 + C(9) + T(T(8)) \\
 1398 &:= -F(13) \times (F(\sqrt{9}) - 8) \\
 1398 &:= Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 8 \\
 1398 &:= T(3) \times F(F(9) - F(8)) \\
 1398 &:= T(T(3)) + Q(9) + Q(T(8)) \\
 \\
 1399 &:= 3 \times Q(9) + Q(F(9)) \\
 1399 &:= C(1 + T(3)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(9)) \\
 1399 &:= F(13) \times (\sqrt{9})! + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 1399 &:= Q(-1 - 39) - T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1399 &:= Q(-1 + C(3)) - (\sqrt{9})! + C(9) \\
 1399 &:= Q(-1 + C(3)) - T(\sqrt{9}) + C(9) \\
 1399 &:= Q(1 + Q(3!)) - (\sqrt{9})! + Q((\sqrt{9})!) \\
 1399 &:= Q(1 + Q(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \\
 1399 &:= T(1 + T(3) + T(9)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 1399 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9)) + T(F(9)) \\
 \\
 1400 &:= 14 \times Q(T(Q(0! + 0!))) \\
 \\
 1401 &:= T(14) + Q(Q(T(T(1 + 0!)))) \\
 1401 &:= T(14) + Q(T(C(1 + 0!))) \\
 \\
 1402 &:= -1 + F(Q(F(4))) + Q(0! + T(C(2))) \\
 1402 &:= -1 + Q(Q(F(4)! + 0!) + F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \\
 1402 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - 0! - T(Q(Q(2))) \\
 1402 &:= T(14) + 0! + Q(T(C(2))) \\
 \\
 1403 &:= -1 + 4 \times T(C(3) - 0!) \\
 1403 &:= -1 + T(C(4)) - Q(-0! + C(3)) \\
 1403 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(Q(0! + 3)) \\
 1403 &:= F(Q(F(4))) + Q(0! + Q(3!)) \\
 \\
 1404 &:= (1 + F(F(F(4)! + 0!))) \times F(4)! \\
 1404 &:= -(1 - 40) \times Q(F(4)!) \\
 1404 &:= -(1 - 40) \times T(F(T(F(4)))) \\
 1404 &:= -1 + C(Q(F(4))) + Q(-0! + C(F(4))) \\
 1404 &:= 4 \times T(1 + 4! + 0!) \\
 1404 &:= 4 \times T(Q(1 + 4) + 0!) \\
 \\
 1405 &:= 1 + T(C(4)) - Q(0! + Q(5)) \\
 1405 &:= -1 + T(C(4) - 0!) - F(T(5)) \\
 1405 &:= 1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(0! + T(5)) \\
 1405 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(0! + T(5)) \\
 1405 &:= C(Q(-1 + 4)) + Q(0! + Q(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1405 := C(Q(F(4))) + Q(0! + Q(5))$$

$$1405 := Q(1 + Q(F(4)!)) + Q(5 + 0!)$$

$$1405 := T(-1 - 40) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1406 := (-1 + F(4)) \times T(0! + T(F(6)))$$

$$1406 := 1 + Q(F(4)!) + Q(0! + Q(6))$$

$$1406 := C(T(4)) + T(T(6 + 0!))$$

$$1406 := \sqrt{4} \times T(0! + Q(6))$$

$$1406 := \sqrt{4} \times T(0! + T(F(6)))$$

$$1407 := 1 + C(T(4)) + T(T(7))$$

$$1407 := T(-1 + F(T(4))) - T(-0! + F(7))$$

$$1407 := T(T(T(-1 - 4))) + T(Q(7) - 0!)$$

$$1408 := (-1 + 4! - 0!) \times Q(8)$$

$$1408 := C(4) \times (0! + F(8))$$

$$1408 := C(4) \times (0! + T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1409 := 1 + (F(F(F(4)!) + 0!) \times Q(F((\sqrt{9}!)))$$

$$1409 := 1 - C(4) \times (-0! - F(F((\sqrt{9}!)))$$

$$1409 := 1 - C(4) \times (-0! - T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1409 := Q(Q(1 + 4)) + Q(0! + C(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1409 := Q(Q(1 + 4)) + Q(T(0! + T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1409 := T(-1 + 4! - 0!) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1411 := -1 + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + Q(Q(Q(1 + 1)))$$

$$1411 := -1 + Q(Q(F(4))) + C(11)$$

$$1411 := -1 + Q(Q(T(\sqrt{4}))) + C(11)$$

$$1412 := -1 + T(C(4)) - 1 - T(T(C(2)))$$

$$1412 := C(1 + T(4)) + Q(Q(1 + 2))$$

$$1412 := F(14) + T(T(1 + C(2)))$$

$$1412 := F(14) + T(T(1 + F(T(T(2))))))$$

$$1412 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 1) + Q(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1412 := Q(Q(4)) + Q(F(Q(1 + 2)))$$

$$1413 := 1 + C(1 + T(4)) + Q(Q(3))$$

$$1413 := -1 + T(Q(T(\sqrt{4}))) + Q(1 + Q(T(3)))$$

$$1413 := -1 - F(Q(4)) + Q(Q(1 + 3!))$$

$$1413 := -1 - F(Q(4)) + Q(Q(1 + T(3)))$$

$$1413 := T(T(-1 + T(4))) + T(C(3))$$

$$1414 := (1 + Q(T(4))) \times 14$$

$$1414 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - C(1 + 4)$$

$$1414 := Q(Q(1 + (4 - 1)!)) - F(Q(4))$$

$$1415 := -1 + Q(Q((4 - 1)!)) + 5!$$

$$1415 := -1 + Q(Q(T(4 - 1))) + 5!$$

$$1415 := 1 + T(C(4)) - T(Q(1 + 5))$$

$$1415 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) + (1 - C(5))$$

$$1415 := Q(T(-1 + T(4))) - F(15)$$

$$1416 := (1 + 4)! + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1416 := 1 + T(T(T(4))) - C(-1 + 6)$$

$$1416 := T(1 + C(4)) - C(1 + F(6))$$

$$1417 := Q(1 + Q(F(4)!)) - 1 + Q(7)$$

$$1417 := Q(4!) + Q(1 + T(7))$$

$$1418 := 1 + Q(T(4) + 1) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1418 := Q(1 + Q(F(4)!)) + Q(-1 + 8)$$

$$1419 := -1 + T(F(T(4))) - (-1 + T(\sqrt{9}))!$$

$$1419 := -1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(T(-1 + T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1419 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - (-1 + T(\sqrt{9}))!$$

$$1419 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(-1 + T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1419 := -Q(T(4) + 1) + T(T(1 + 9))$$

$$1420 := -1 + Q(Q(F(4)!)) + C(Q(2) + 0!)$$

$$1420 := 1 + T(T(T(4))) - Q(T(Q(2)) + 0!)$$

$$1420 := F(1 + T(4)) + C(T(Q(2)) + 0!)$$

$$1420 := T(F(T(4))) - (T(T(2)) - 0!)$$

$$1420 := T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(2)) - 0!)$$

$$1421 := 1 + T(F(T(4))) - (T(T(2)) - 1!)$$

$$1421 := 1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)) - 1)$$

$$1421 := 1 + T(T(T(4))) - (1 + Q(2))!$$

$$1421 := 1 + T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(2)) - 1!)$$

$$1421 := 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)) - 1)$$

$$1421 := C(1 + 4) + Q(Q((2 + 1)!))$$

$$1421 := C(1 + 4) + Q(Q(T(2 + 1)))$$

$$1421 := Q(14) + Q(F(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 1)$$

$$1422 := (-1 + F(4)!) \times 2 - Q(Q(2))$$

$$1422 := (-1 + F(Q(4)) - C(C(2))) \times F(Q(2))$$

$$1422 := (1 + T(Q(4)) + F(C(2))) \times Q(T(2))$$

$$1422 := (1 + T(Q(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times Q(T(2))$$

$$1422 := (-1 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(2)) - T(C(2))$$

$$1422 := (1 - F(4)!) + C(2)) \times (-2)$$

$$1422 := (1 - T(4) + T(T(2)))! \times 2$$

$$1422 := -1 + T(F(T(4)) - 2) - F(T(T(2)))$$

$$1422 := C(1 + T(4)) + C(T(2)) + Q(C(2))$$

$$1422 := F(1 + T(4)) \times Q(Q(2)) - 2$$

$$1422 := T(1 + T(4)) \times F(C(2)) + T(C(2))$$

$$1422 := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$1423 := 1 + F(4)! \times (F(C(2)) + C(3!))$$

$$1423 := 1 + F(Q(4)) + T(2 + C(3))$$

$$1423 := -1 + Q(4) \times F(2 + Q(3))$$

$$1423 := -1 + Q(4) \times F(C(2) + 3)$$

$$1423 := -1 + \sqrt{4} \times (-C(2) + 3!)$$

$$1423 := 1 + T(T(T(4)) + 2) - T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1423 := -1 - Q(4) + 2 \times 3!)$$

$$1423 := T(-1 + F(T(4)) - F(2)) - F(T(3))$$

$$1423 := T(1 + T(4 \times 2)) + T(3)!$$

$$1424 := ((-1 + 4)!! - C(2)) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1424 := (-1 + Q(T(4)) - T(Q(2))) \times Q(4)$$

$$1424 := (F(14) - F(C(2))) \times 4$$

$$1424 := (Q(1 + 4) + Q(C(2))) \times Q(4)$$

$$1424 := 2 \times (-1 + 4)!! - Q(4)$$

$$1424 := C(-1 + \sqrt{C(4)}) + T(T(C(2)) + T(4))$$

$$1424 := F(-1 + Q(4) - Q(2)) \times Q(4)$$

$$1424 := F(1 + T(4)) \times 2^4$$

$$1424 := Q(4) \times F(C(2) + F(4))$$

$$1424 := Q(4) \times F(F(2) + T(4))$$

$$1424 := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(2)) - T(T(4))$$

$$1425 := (-1 + 4! \times Q(2)) \times T(5)$$

$$1425 := (1 + C(4) - C(2)) \times Q(5)$$

$$1425 := (F(1 + T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times T(5)$$

$$1425 := (Q(1 + Q(4)) - Q(2)) \times 5$$

$$1425 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2)) - 5!$$

$$1425 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2)) - T(T(5))$$

$$1425 := T(1 + C(4)) - (F(2) + 5)!$$

$$1425 := T(1 + C(4)) - T(T(2)) \times 5!$$

$$1426 := 1 + T(F(T(4)) - 2) - 6$$

$$1426 := 1 + T(T(T(4)) - 2) - 6$$

$$1426 := -14 + 2 \times 6!$$

$$1427 := (-1 + F(4)) \times T(T(2))! - F(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1427 &:= -1 + (4! + C(T(2))) \times T(7) & 1430 &:= -1 + T(4 + Q(T(3) + 0!)) \\
 1427 &:= -1 + F(Q(4)) + Q(C(2) + F(7)) & 1430 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 0 \\
 1427 &:= -1 + F(Q(4) + F(2)) - Q(F(7)) & 1430 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3 + 0)) \\
 1427 &:= 1 + Q(T(4)) + T(2 + Q(7)) & 1430 &:= -1 + T(\sqrt{4} \times C(3) - 0!) \\
 1427 &:= 1 + T(4!) + T(T(2))! + T(T(7)) & 1430 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4)) - 3 + 0!) \\
 1427 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(F(7)) \\
 1427 &:= -1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 7) & 1431 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 1 \\
 1427 &:= -C(-1 + Q(4)) + 2 \times Q(Q(7)) & 1431 &:= T((-1 + T(4)) \times T(3) - 1) \\
 1427 &:= C(T(4)) + F(C(2)) + T(T(7)) & 1431 &:= T(-1 - T(4) + C(3 + 1)) \\
 1427 &:= F(4)! \times 2 - F(7) \\
 1427 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(T(2))! - F(7) \\
 1427 &:= T(T(4)) + Q(2) \times C(7) \\
 \\ \\
 1428 &:= (1 + C(4) + T(2)) \times F(8) & 1432 &:= (-4 + 3!) \times 2 \\
 1428 &:= (1 + Q(4)) \times Q(2) \times F(8) & 1432 &:= (-4 + T(3)!) \times 2 \\
 1428 &:= -(1 - 4) \times (C(C(2)) - T(8)) & 1432 &:= 1 + T(4! + C(3) + 2) \\
 1428 &:= (T(1 + T(4)) + 2) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) & 1432 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 2 \\
 1428 &:= 2 \times F(1 + F(F(4)!)) \times F(8) & 1432 &:= 1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3) \times F(2)) \\
 1428 &:= 2 \times F(1 + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times F(8) & 1432 &:= 1 + T(Q(4 + 3) + Q(2)) \\
 1428 &:= 2 \times F(-1 + T(4)) \times F(8) & 1432 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4)) - T(3)/T(2)) \\
 1428 &:= -Q(4) + Q(2 + T(8)) & 1433 &:= (-1) + (\sqrt{4} \times 3! - 3!) \\
 1428 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(8) & 1433 &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! - T(3) \\
 1428 &:= -T(4!) + C(Q(2) + 8) & 1433 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 3 \\
 \\ \\
 1429 &:= 1 + 42 \times F(9) & 1433 &:= 1 + T(Q(4)) + Q(Q(3 + 3)) \\
 1429 &:= -1 + Q(4)!/(C(2)! \times 9!) & 1433 &:= -1 - 4! + C(Q(3)) + C(Q(3)) \\
 1429 &:= 1 + T(4!) + T(2 + T(9)) & 1433 &:= -1 - F(4)! + 3! + 3! \\
 1429 &:= 1 - T(4!) + C(T(2) + 9) & 1433 &:= 1 - \sqrt{C(4)} + 3! + 3! \\
 1429 &:= -1 - T(T(4)) + T(9 \times T(T(2))) & 1433 &:= 1 - \sqrt{C(4)} + T(3)! + T(3)! \\
 1429 &:= Q(-1 + 4!) + Q(Q(2))! + (\sqrt{9})! & 1433 &:= -1 - T(F(4)) + T(3)! + T(3)! \\
 \\ \\
 1430 &:= (1 + C(4)) \times (F(C(F(3))) + 0!) & 1434 &:= (-1 + 4! + C(3!)) \times F(4)! \\
 1430 &:= (-1 + C(F(4))) \times F(Q(3) + 0!) & 1434 &:= (-1 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3)) + T(4!) \\
 1430 &:= (1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (Q(F(3!)) + 0!) & 1434 &:= (1 - 4 + 3!) \times F(F(4)) \\
 & & 1434 &:= (1 - 4 + 3!) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & & 1434 &:= (1 - 4 + T(3)!) \times F(F(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1434 &:= 1 + C(4) + Q(C(3) + T(4)) \\
 1434 &:= -1 + C(T(4)) + T(C(3) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 1434 &:= -1 + C(T(4)) + T(\sqrt{4} + C(3)) \\
 1434 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 4 \\
 1434 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) + T(-3 + T(T(4))) \\
 1434 &:= F(4) + T(-F(3) + F(T(4))) \\
 \\
 1435 &:= (-1 + 4)!! + 3!! - 5 \\
 1435 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times 3!! - 5 \\
 1435 &:= (1 + Q(F(4))) \times Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(5)) \\
 1435 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 5 \\
 1435 &:= C(T(4) + 1) - T(T(3)) + C(5) \\
 1435 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 3!! - 5 \\
 1435 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! - 5 \\
 1435 &:= T(-1 + 4)! + T(3)! - 5 \\
 1435 &:= T(14) + T(3)! + F(T(5)) \\
 1435 &:= -T(14) + T(F(5 \times F(3))) \\
 1435 &:= T(4) \times Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(5)) \\
 1435 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 5 \times T(T(3)) \\
 \\
 1436 &:= (1 - F(4)) \times (F(3) - 6!) \\
 1436 &:= 1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(T(3) + F(6)) \\
 1436 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 6 \\
 1436 &:= 1 + T(Q(4)) + 3 + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1436 &:= -4 + 3!! + 6! \\
 1436 &:= -4 + T(3)! + 6! \\
 \\
 1437 &:= 1 + Q(Q(4)) - T(Q(3)) + T(Q(7)) \\
 1437 &:= 1 + T(F(T(4))) - F(T(3)) \times F(7) \\
 1437 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 7 \\
 1437 &:= 1 - C(T(4)) + T(3) \times T(T(7)) \\
 1437 &:= -C(14) + F(3! + F(7)) \\
 1437 &:= -C(14) + F(T(3) + F(7)) \\
 1437 &:= F(1 + Q(4)) + Q(3) - Q(F(7)) \\
 \\
 1437 &:= Q(1 + C(4) - C(3)) - 7 \\
 1437 &:= Q(\sqrt{4} + Q(3!)) - 7 \\
 \\
 1438 &:= -(-1 + 4)! + Q(38) \\
 1438 &:= (1 - F(4)!!) \times (3! - 8) \\
 1438 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 8 \\
 1438 &:= -F(4)! + Q(38) \\
 1438 &:= Q(1 + T(4)) + T(T(3)) + Q(T(8)) \\
 1438 &:= -\sqrt{4} + T(3)! + (\sqrt{T(8)})! \\
 1438 &:= T(4! + 1) \times T(3) - C(8) \\
 1438 &:= -T(F(4)) + Q(38) \\
 \\
 1439 &:= -1 + F(F(4)) \times (-3 + 9)! \\
 1439 &:= -1 + Q(4) \times (Q(3) + Q(9)) \\
 1439 &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times (-3 + 9)! \\
 1439 &:= 1 + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1439 &:= -1 + T(4) \times F(3 + 9) \\
 1439 &:= -1 + T(4) \times Q(3 + 9) \\
 1439 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4)) - F(3)) + 9 \\
 1439 &:= -1 + T(\sqrt{4} \times C(3)) - T(9) \\
 1439 &:= -1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(T(T(3)))) + 9 \\
 \\
 1440 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 0 \\
 1440 &:= (-1 + 4)!! + (4 - 0)!! \\
 1440 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 0 \\
 1440 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 0 \\
 1440 &:= 40 \times Q((-1 + 4)!) \\
 1440 &:= 40 \times T(F(T(F(4)))) \\
 1440 &:= -Q(4!) + T(C(4) - 0!) \\
 1440 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 0 \\
 1440 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(4 - 0)! \\
 1440 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 0 \\
 1440 &:= T(-1 + 4)! + T(4 - 0)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1441 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 1 \\
 1441 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 1 \\
 1441 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 1 \\
 1441 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\
 1441 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times T(4 - 1)! \\
 1441 &:= 1 + \sqrt{4} \times T(4 - 1)! \\
 1441 &:= 1 - Q(4!) + T(C(4) - 1) \\
 1441 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 1 \\
 1441 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 1 \\
 1441 &:= T(T(-1 + T(4))) + T(T(T(F(4)) + 1)) \\
 1441 &:= T(T(1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + T(T(-1 + T(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1442 &:= (1 + (4!/4!)) \times 2 \\
 1442 &:= (1 + (\sqrt{4} \times F(4))!) \times 2 \\
 1442 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 2 \\
 1442 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 2 \\
 1442 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 2 \\
 1442 &:= (C(1 + \sqrt{C(4)}) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 2 \\
 1442 &:= 1 + C(T(4)) + Q(F(4 \times 2)) \\
 1442 &:= 1 + C(T(4)) + Q(T(4 + 2)) \\
 1442 &:= 1 + T(4) + T(F(T(4)) - 2) \\
 1442 &:= 1 + T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 2) \\
 1442 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 2 \\
 1442 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1443 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 3 \\
 1443 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 3 \\
 1443 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 3 \\
 1443 &:= -(1 - 4) + \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! \\
 1443 &:= (Q(-1 + Q(4)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3 \\
 1443 &:= 1 + C(4) + C(T(4)) + T(C(3)) \\
 1443 &:= -1 + Q((F(4) + Q(4)) \times F(3)) \\
 1443 &:= -1 + Q(C(4)/\sqrt{4} + 3!) \\
 1443 &:= -1 + Q(Q(4) + Q(4) + 3!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1443 &:= -1 + Q(\sqrt{4} \times (Q(4) + 3)) \\
 1443 &:= -1 + Q(T(4) + T(4 + 3)) \\
 1443 &:= C(-1 + T(4)) - T(F(4)) + T(3)! \\
 1443 &:= F(4) + F(F(4)) \times 3!! \\
 1443 &:= F(4) + F(F(4)) \times T(3)! \\
 1443 &:= F(4) + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \\
 1443 &:= F(4) + \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! \\
 1443 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 3 \\
 1443 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 3 \\
 1443 &:= T(1 + F(T(4))) - T(-4 + T(T(3))) \\
 1443 &:= T(1 + T(T(4))) - T(-4 + T(T(3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1444 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 4 \\
 1444 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 4 \\
 1444 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 4 \\
 1444 &:= (14 + 4!)^{F(F(4))} \\
 1444 &:= (14 + 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1444 &:= (F(-1 + T(4)) + 4)^{F(F(4))} \\
 1444 &:= (F(-1 + T(4)) + 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1444 &:= (F(14) - Q(4)) \times 4 \\
 1444 &:= 4 \times Q(-1 - 4) + Q(4) \\
 1444 &:= Q((-1 - 4) + Q(4)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1444 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 4 \\
 1444 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 4 \\
 1444 &:= T(1 + T(4)) + T(T(T(4)) - T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 1444 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 4 \times 4!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1445 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 5 \\
 1445 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 5 \\
 1445 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 5 \\
 1445 &:= (1 + \sqrt{F(4)! \times C(4)!}) \times 5 \\
 1445 &:= (-1 + T(4!)) - T(4) \times 5 \\
 1445 &:= 5 \times Q(1 + 4 \times 4) \\
 1445 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1445 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 5 & 1448 &:= (-1 + C(4)) \times 4! - Q(8) \\
 1445 &:= T(-1 + F(T(4))) - F(T(4)) + T(5) & 1448 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 8 \\
 1445 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) + T(5) & 1448 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 8 \\
 & & 1448 &:= -1 + F(4!)/(4 \times 8) \\
 1446 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 6 & 1448 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - F(T(4)) - T(8) \\
 1446 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4) + 6!) & 1448 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8) \\
 1446 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 6 & 1448 &:= -1 - Q(4!) + Q(4! + F(8)) \\
 1446 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 6 & 1448 &:= 4 + Q(\sqrt{4} + T(8)) \\
 1446 &:= (-1 + Q(4) - Q(Q(4))) \times (-6) & 1448 &:= C(T(4)) - C(4) + C(8) \\
 1446 &:= (1 + Q(Q(4)) - Q(4)) \times 6 & 1448 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 8 \\
 1446 &:= (-1 - 4! \times T(4)) \times (-6) & 1448 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 8 \\
 1446 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (F(4) + 6!) & & \\
 1446 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 6 & 1449 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 9 \\
 1446 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 6 & 1449 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 9 \\
 1446 &:= \sqrt{4} + Q(\sqrt{4} + Q(6)) & 1449 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 9 \\
 1446 &:= T(-1 + 4) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))) & 1449 &:= (-1 + Q(4! - \sqrt{4})) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1446 &:= T(F(4)) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))) & 1449 &:= (1 + T(4) \times Q(4)) \times 9 \\
 & & 1449 &:= (4!/4)! + C(9) \\
 1447 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 7 & 1449 &:= 1 + 4 + Q(4 + F(9)) \\
 1447 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 7 & 1449 &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times (-4 + C(9)) \\
 1447 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(F(4))! + 7 & 1449 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - 9 \times T(4) \\
 1447 &:= -(1 - 4) + Q(T(4) + T(7)) & 1449 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - \sqrt{4} \times T(9) \\
 1447 &:= -1 + C(T(4)) + 7 \times C(4) & 1449 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - 9 \times T(4) \\
 1447 &:= 1 + T(F(T(4))) - F(4) - T(F(7)) & 1449 &:= -1 - \sqrt{4} \times (4 - C(9)) \\
 1447 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - F(\sqrt{4}) - T(F(7)) & 1449 &:= 1 - T(4) + \sqrt{4} \times C(9) \\
 1447 &:= -C(1 + 4) \times F(4)! + C(F(7)) & 1449 &:= -F(4!)/(F(F(4)) - F(9)) \\
 1447 &:= F(4) + Q(T(4) + T(7)) & 1449 &:= F(4!)/(-\sqrt{4} + F(9)) \\
 1447 &:= Q(1 + F(4)!) + F(4)! \times F(F(7)) & 1449 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 9 \\
 1447 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(4)!! + 7 & 1449 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 9 \\
 1447 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(F(4))! + 7 & & \\
 1447 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(7) & 1450 &:= 1 + C(Q(F(4))) + (5 + 0)!! \\
 1447 &:= T(F(T(4))) - F(F(4)) - T(F(7)) & 1450 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - F(\sqrt{5! + 0!}) \\
 & & 1450 &:= C(T(4) + 1) + 5! - 0! \\
 1448 &:= (-1 + 4)!! \times \sqrt{4} + 8 & 1450 &:= Q(1 + Q(F(4)!)) + Q(Q(F(5 - 0!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1450 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 0$$

$$1450 := Q(T(1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + T(Q(5 + 0!))$$

$$1451 := (1 + 4)! + C(\sqrt{1 + 5!})$$

$$1451 := (1 + 4)! + C(\sqrt{5! + 1})$$

$$1451 := C(1 + 4) + T(51)$$

$$1451 := -F(1 + T(4)) + T(F(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$1451 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 1$$

$$1451 := T(F(T(4))) - F(\sqrt{5! + 1})$$

$$1452 := (-1 + F(4)^5) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1452 := (-1 + T(\sqrt{4})^5) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1452 := -(1 - 4) \times Q(Q(5) - T(2))$$

$$1452 := 2 \times (1 + F(4)!! + 5)$$

$$1452 := C(1 + T(4)) + 5! + F(2)$$

$$1452 := F(4) \times Q(Q(5) - T(2))$$

$$1452 := Q(-1 + C(4) - Q(5)) + C(2)$$

$$1452 := Q(1 + Q(4) + 5) \times F(Q(2))$$

$$1452 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 2$$

$$1452 := T(T(4) + 1) \times (-5 + C(T(2)))$$

$$1453 := 1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(53)$$

$$1453 := 5 \times Q(1 + Q(4)) + F(3!)$$

$$1453 := C(T(4) + 1) + C(5) - 3$$

$$1453 := F(1 + Q(4)) - Q(T(5) - 3)$$

$$1453 := -F(14) + 3 \times F(T(5))$$

$$1453 := -F(14) + T(5! / F(3))$$

$$1453 := Q(-1 + 4! + T(5)) + Q(3)$$

$$1453 := Q(-1 + C(4) - Q(5)) + Q(3)$$

$$1453 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 3$$

$$1454 := -1 + T(C(4)) - 5^4$$

$$1454 := -1 + T(F(4))! + T(5) + T(F(4))!$$

$$1454 := -1 + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + T(5) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))!$$

$$1454 := 5 \times Q(1 + Q(4)) + Q(F(4))$$

$$1454 := C(1 + \sqrt{C(4)}) + 5 + F(4)!!$$

$$1454 := F(-1 + T(4)) - T(T(5)) + T(F(T(4)))$$

$$1454 := Q(-1 + 4!) + Q(Q(5)) + T(4!)$$

$$1454 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 4$$

$$1455 := (-1 + C(4)) \times Q(5) - 5!$$

$$1455 := (1 - 4! + 5!) \times T(5)$$

$$1455 := -(1 - Q(F(F(4)!))) \times Q(5) - 5!$$

$$1455 := -1 + C(\sqrt{-4 + C(5)}) + C(5)$$

$$1455 := F(1 + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(T(5))$$

$$1455 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 5$$

$$1455 := T(14) \times T(5) - T(T(5))$$

$$1456 := (1 + F(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6))$$

$$1456 := (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6))$$

$$1456 := C(1 + 4) + C(5 + 6)$$

$$1456 := F(1 + F(4)!) \times (5! - F(6))$$

$$1456 := F(1 + Q(4)) - 5! - F(F(6))$$

$$1456 := -Q(-1 + Q(4)) + Q(5 + Q(6))$$

$$1456 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 6$$

$$1456 := Q(4) \times T(5 + F(6))$$

$$1457 := (-1 + Q(4)) \times 5! - C(7)$$

$$1457 := 1 - (F(F(4)!) - 5!) \times F(7)$$

$$1457 := 1 - (\sqrt{C(4)} - 5!) \times F(7)$$

$$1457 := 1 + (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(5)) \times T(F(7))$$

$$1457 := F(1 + F(4)!) + Q(Q(5) + F(7))$$

$$1457 := Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 7$$

$$1457 := -Q(14) + T(57)$$

$$1457 := T(1 + 4) \times 5! - C(7)$$

$$1457 := T(-1 + F(T(4))) - T(5) - F(7)$$

$$1457 := T(-1 + T(5 \times \sqrt{4})) - T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1457 &:= T(-T(1 + T(4)) + 5!) - T(7) \\
 1457 &:= T(-T(1 + T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(7) \\
 1458 &:= 1 + Q(C(4) - Q(5)) - Q(8) \\
 1458 &:= 1 - Q(F(F(4)!)) + Q(-Q(5) + Q(8)) \\
 1458 &:= C(1 + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times F(-5 + 8) \\
 1458 &:= Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 8 \\
 1458 &:= \sqrt{(-1 + T(4))^5 \times T(8)} \\
 1458 &:= -T(1 + T(T(F(4)))) + T(58) \\
 1459 &:= 1 + (F(4) + T(5)) \times Q(9) \\
 1459 &:= 1 + C(4 + 5) + C(9) \\
 1459 &:= 1 + F(4)^5 \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 1459 &:= 1 + F(4)^5 \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1459 &:= -1 + Q(T(4)) + T(Q(5)) + T(T(9)) \\
 1459 &:= 1 + T(\sqrt{4})^5 \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 1459 &:= Q(-1 + Q(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + Q(T(5)) + 9 \\
 1460 &:= (1 + C(Q(F(4)))) \times F(\sqrt{F(6) + 0!}) \\
 1460 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - Q(F(6) + 0!) \\
 1460 &:= Q(-1 + C(F(4))) + Q(T(6 + 0!)) \\
 1460 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - Q(6 - 0!) \\
 1461 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - Q(F(\sqrt{1 + F(6)}))! \\
 1462 &:= (-1 - T(4) - 6!) \times (-2) \\
 1462 &:= 1 + F(F(F(4)!)) + 2 \times 6! \\
 1462 &:= -1 + F(Q(4)) - Q(6) + C(C(2)) \\
 1462 &:= 1 + \sqrt{4} \times 6! + F(C(2)) \\
 1462 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(T(6))/T(2) \\
 1462 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))/T(2) \\
 1462 &:= F(1 + Q(4)) + Q(F(F(6))) - Q(Q(2)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1463 &:= -1 + 4! + 6! \times F(3) \\
 1463 &:= -1 + 4! + 6! + 3!! \\
 1463 &:= -1 + 4! + 6! + T(3)! \\
 1463 &:= 14 + 6! + C(Q(3)) \\
 1463 &:= -1 - T(4!) + Q(Q(6) + T(3)) \\
 1463 &:= T(F(T(4))) - (1/3) \times T(T(6)) \\
 1463 &:= T(T(T(4))) - (1/3) \times T(T(6)) \\
 1464 &:= (-1 + 4)!! + 6! + 4! \\
 1464 &:= (1 + 6 \times T(4)) \times 4! \\
 1464 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times 6! + 4! \\
 1464 &:= (Q(1 + 4) + Q(6)) \times 4! \\
 1464 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6! + 4! \\
 1464 &:= T(F(T(4))) - T(6) - F(T(4)) \\
 1464 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(6) - T(T(4)) \\
 1465 &:= (1 + Q(Q(4)) + Q(6)) \times 5 \\
 1465 &:= 1 + 4! \times (Q(6) + Q(5)) \\
 1465 &:= 1 + C(4) \times F(F(6)) + 5! \\
 1465 &:= 1 + C(4) \times T(6) + 5! \\
 1465 &:= 5 \times (-1 + T(4!) - 6) \\
 1465 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6! + Q(5) \\
 1466 &:= -1 + C(F(4)) + 6! + 6! \\
 1466 &:= 1 + C(T(4)) + T(Q(6) - 6) \\
 1466 &:= -1 + F(4) \times (6! - T(T(6))) \\
 1466 &:= 1 + Q(\sqrt{4} + Q(6)) + F(F(6)) \\
 1466 &:= -1 + T(4! - 6) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1466 &:= -1 + T(\sqrt{4}) \times (6! - T(T(6))) \\
 1466 &:= Q(Q(1 + 4)) + Q(F(6) + T(6)) \\
 1467 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times (6! + F(7)) \\
 1467 &:= 1 + \sqrt{4} \times (6! + F(7)) \\
 1467 &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times 6! + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1468 &:= -(Q(1 + Q(Q(F(4)))) - Q(Q(F(6))) - Q(Q(8))) & 1472 &:= ((1 + 4)! - T(7)) \times Q(Q(2)) \\
 1468 &:= 1 + F(4) \times (6! - T(F(8))) & 1472 &:= (-1 + 4!) \times C(-T(2) + 7) \\
 1468 &:= 1 + T(4! - 6) + Q(T(8)) & 1472 &:= (-1 + 4!) \times Q(7 + F(2)) \\
 1468 &:= 1 + T(6 \times F(4)) + Q(T(8)) & 1472 &:= (C(1 + \sqrt{C(4)}) + 7) \times 2 \\
 1468 &:= 1 + T(\sqrt{4}) \times (-T(T(6)) + (\sqrt{T(8)}))! & 1472 &:= (Q(1 + 4) + C(7)) \times Q(2) \\
 1468 &:= -1 - C(F(4)!) - C(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) & 1472 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 2 \\
 1468 &:= -C(-1 + T(4)) + C(T(6) - 8) & 1472 &:= T(-1 + F(T(4))) - F(7) \times F(2) \\
 1468 &:= C(Q(4)) - T(Q(6) + T(8)) & 1472 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - T(T(2)) \\
 1468 &:= -C(Q(F(4))) + C(-F(6) + F(8)) & & \\
 1468 &:= T(F(T(4))) - T(F(6)) - T(8) & 1473 &:= (1 + T(4) \times Q(7)) \times 3 \\
 1468 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(F(6)) - C(8) & 1473 &:= -1 + F(Q(4)) - F(F(7)) + 3!! \\
 & & 1473 &:= -1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(F(7) - F(3)) \\
 & & 1473 &:= 1 - \sqrt{4} \times (-7 - C(Q(3))) \\
 & & 1473 &:= -4 + C(F(7)) - 3!! \\
 & & 1473 &:= -4 + C(F(7)) - T(3)! \\
 & & 1473 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 3 \\
 1469 &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times (6 + C(9)) & & \\
 1469 &:= -1 - \sqrt{4} \times (-6 - C(9)) & 1474 &:= -(1 - 4) \times T(T(7)) + Q(Q(4)) \\
 1469 &:= F(14) - Q(F(6)) + Q(F(9)) & 1474 &:= 1 + \sqrt{C(C(4))} + Q(7 + 4!) \\
 1469 &:= -F(T(1 + 4)) + 9 \times T(T(6)) & 1474 &:= -1 - F(4)!! + C(F(7)) - \sqrt{4} \\
 1469 &:= -Q(4) + T(6 \times 9) & 1474 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 4 \\
 1469 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 6!/T(9) & 1474 &:= -C(-1 + T(4)) + C(F(7)) + T(F(4)) \\
 & & 1474 &:= F(4)!! - F(F(7)) + F(Q(4)) \\
 & & 1474 &:= -T(1 + T(4)) + T(7) \times F(T(4)) \\
 & & 1474 &:= -T(1 + T(4)) + T(7) \times T(T(4)) \\
 & & 1474 &:= T(14) + Q(F(7) + 4!) \\
 1470 &:= (-F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-70) & & \\
 1470 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 0 & 1475 &:= (1 + Q(F(4)) + Q(7)) \times Q(5) \\
 1470 &:= 70 \times F(-1 + Q(F(4))) & 1475 &:= (T(4) + Q(7)) \times Q(5) \\
 1470 &:= 70 \times F(C(\sqrt{4})) & 1475 &:= -1 + T(\sqrt{4} \times T(7)) - 5! \\
 1470 &:= 70 \times T(T(-1 + 4)) & 1475 &:= -1 + T(\sqrt{4} \times T(7)) - T(T(5)) \\
 1470 &:= 70 \times T(T(F(4))) & 1475 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 5 \\
 1470 &:= T(14) \times (F(7) + 0!) & 1475 &:= C(1 + T(4)) + F(7 + 5) \\
 & & 1475 &:= -Q(1 + Q(4)) + Q(7!/5!) \\
 & & 1475 &:= T(F(T(4))) - 5 \times F(7) \\
 1471 &:= -1 - Q(Q(4)) + C(F(7) - 1) & & \\
 1471 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 1 & & \\
 1471 &:= Q(14) + T(Q(7) + 1) & & \\
 1471 &:= T(-1 + F(T(4))) - F(7) - 1 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1476 &:= -(1+4)! + T(7 \times F(6)) \\
 1476 &:= (1 - Q(F(4)) + Q(7)) \times Q(6) \\
 1476 &:= (F(1 + F(4)!) + F(F(7))) \times 6 \\
 1476 &:= (F(-1 + T(4)) + 7) \times T(F(6)) \\
 1476 &:= (T(1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 7) \times 6 \\
 1476 &:= -1^4 + C(F(7)) - 6! \\
 1476 &:= -1 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{C(C(4))} - C(7)}) - 6! \\
 1476 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 6 \\
 1476 &:= C(-1 - 4) \times T(7) + 6! \\
 1476 &:= C(4!) - C(7) \times Q(6) \\
 1476 &:= Q((-1 + 4)!) \times \sqrt{Q(Q(7))} - 6! \\
 1476 &:= T(1 + Q(4) + T(7)) + Q(T(6)) \\
 \\
 1477 &:= ((1 + 4)! + T(F(7))) \times 7 \\
 1477 &:= (1 + C(4)) \times T(7) - C(7) \\
 1477 &:= (1 + F(T(4))) \times T(7) - T(F(7)) \\
 1477 &:= (T(T(1 + 4)) + T(F(7))) \times 7 \\
 1477 &:= 1 + F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) + F(7)) \\
 1477 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 7 \\
 1477 &:= F(1 + Q(4)) - Q(F(7)) + Q(7) \\
 1477 &:= -F(14) + C(F(7)) - C(7) \\
 1477 &:= T(14) + Q(7) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 1478 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(8)) \\
 1478 &:= (C(-1 + 4!) - C(7)) \times (1/8) \\
 1478 &:= 1 + F(Q(4)) + Q(7) + Q(F(8)) \\
 1478 &:= 14 \times F(7) + Q(T(8)) \\
 1478 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 8 \\
 1478 &:= C(1 + T(4)) + 7 \times F(8) \\
 1478 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(T(7)) + T(T(8)) \\
 \\
 1479 &:= (1 + 4)! \times F(7) - Q(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1479 &:= -1 + 4 \times (C(7) + C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 1479 &:= -1 + 4 \times (C(7) + \sqrt{C(9)}) \\
 1479 &:= -1 + Q(47) - C(9) \\
 1479 &:= 1 + Q(T(4)) + T(Q(7) + \sqrt{9}) \\
 1479 &:= 1 + T(C(4)) - 7 - T(F(9)) \\
 1479 &:= 1 + T(F(T(4))) - T(7) - F(9) \\
 1479 &:= -1 - 4 \times (-C(7) - \sqrt{C(9)}) \\
 1479 &:= 7 \times T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 9 \\
 1479 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(-7 - 9)) \\
 \\
 1480 &:= -1 + Q(Q(4)) + Q(T(8) - 0!) \\
 1480 &:= T(1 + C(4)) - T(T(8)) + 0! \\
 1480 &:= T(-1 + F(T(4))) - \sqrt{T(8)} + 0! \\
 1480 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - \sqrt{T(8)} + 0! \\
 \\
 1481 &:= -C(14) + Q(Q(8) + 1) \\
 1481 &:= Q(1 + F(Q(F(4)))) + Q(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{8+1})))) \\
 1481 &:= Q(Q(4)) + Q(T(8) - 1) \\
 \\
 1482 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times T(T(8) + 2) \\
 1482 &:= (-1 + Q(Q(4)) - 8) \times F(Q(2))! \\
 1482 &:= (-F(4)!! - F(8)) \times (-2) \\
 1482 &:= -1 + F(Q(4)) + C(8) - Q(Q(2)) \\
 1482 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(T(8) + 2) \\
 1482 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(8 - T(T(2))) \\
 \\
 1483 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times (F(8) + 3!!) \\
 1483 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times T(T(8) + F(3)) \\
 1483 &:= 1 + \sqrt{4} \times (F(8) + 3!!) \\
 1483 &:= 1 + \sqrt{4} \times T(T(8) + F(3)) \\
 1483 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - 8!/T(3)! \\
 1483 &:= C(1 + T(4)) - Q(8) + C(T(3)) \\
 1483 &:= Q(14) + Q(T(8)) - Q(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1483 := T(-1 + C(4)) - C(8) - T(T(3))$$

$$1483 := T(1 + Q(4)) + Q(T(8)) + F(Q(3))$$

$$1483 := T(T(T(4))) - T(8) - T(T(3))$$

$$1484 := (1 + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times F(F(4))$$

$$1484 := (1 + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1484 := (1 + T(\sqrt{4} + T(8))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1484 := -1 + (T(F(4)) + F(8)) \times F(T(4))$$

$$1484 := -1 + C(F(4)) \times F(8 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1484 := -1 + T((T(4) + 8) \times F(4))$$

$$1484 := -1 + T(C(4) - T(8 - 4))$$

$$1484 := -1 + T(T(4 + 8) - 4!)$$

$$1484 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4))$$

$$1484 := -Q(14) + 8!/4!$$

$$1485 := (1 + C(4)) \times F(8) + 5!$$

$$1485 := (1 - Q(4)) \times (F(8) - 5!)$$

$$1485 := (Q(1 + Q(4)) + 8) \times 5$$

$$1485 := T(1 + 48 + 5)$$

$$1486 := 1 + Q(F(4)) \times F(8) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1486 := 1 + T(48 + 6)$$

$$1487 := -(1 - 4) \times C(8) - Q(7)$$

$$1487 := 4! \times Q(8) - Q(7)$$

$$1487 := -F(14) + 8 \times F(F(7))$$

$$1487 := F(4) \times C(8) - Q(7)$$

$$1487 := T(T(4) + T(8)) + T(T(7))$$

$$1488 := -(1 - 4) \times Q(8) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1488 := (1 - Q(Q(4)) + Q(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$1488 := (T(-1 + T(4)) - T(F(8))) \times (-8)$$

$$1488 := T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}})$$

$$1489 := (1 + 4)! + Q(-8 + T(9))$$

$$1489 := 1 - (Q(4) - C(8)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1489 := 1 + (Q(Q(4)) - 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1489 := 1 + F(4!)/F(8) - ((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1489 := 1 + T(T(4) + F(8)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1489 := 4 + T(9 \times \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1489 := F(1 + Q(4)) - T(8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1489 := T(-1 + F(T(4))) + (1/9) \times T(8)$$

$$1489 := T(-1 + T(T(4))) + (1/9) \times T(8)$$

$$1490 := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - Q(T(\sqrt{9}) + 0!)$$

$$1490 := T(-1 + F(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{9}) - 0!$$

$$1490 := T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{9}) - 0!$$

$$1491 := Q(14) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) - 1$$

$$1491 := -Q(Q(1 + 4)) + Q(T(9) + 1)$$

$$1491 := T(-1 + F(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1491 := T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1491 := T(T(1 + T(4))) - T(\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1492 := (1 + Q(4) + C(9)) \times 2$$

$$1492 := 1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(9 \times T(T(2)))$$

$$1492 := -3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)$$

$$1492 := F(1 + \sqrt{C(4)}) + 2 \times C(9)$$

$$1492 := F(-1 + T(4)) + 2 \times C(9)$$

$$1492 := Q(14) + Q(9 \times Q(2))$$

$$1492 := Q(14) + Q(F(9) + 2)$$

$$1492 := -T(14) + F((1/2) \times F(9))$$

$$1492 := -T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + C(C(2))$$

$$1493 := (-1 + F(F(4)!)!)/9/3$$

$$1493 := -1 + Q(4!) + F(9) \times C(3)$$

$$1493 := -1 + Q(F(4)) + T(9 \times T(3))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1493 &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times (\sqrt{C(9)} + 3!!) & 1496 &:= 1 + T(4) + T(9 \times 6) \\
 1493 &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times C(9) + Q(3!) & 1496 &:= -1 - 4! + Q(\sqrt{9} + Q(6)) \\
 1493 &:= -1 - Q(4!) + Q(T(9)) + T(Q(3)) & 1496 &:= -Q(-1 + 4!) + Q(9 + Q(6)) \\
 1493 &:= -2 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9) & 1496 &:= -Q(1 + 4) + Q(\sqrt{9} + Q(6)) \\
 1493 &:= C(\sqrt{4}) + T(9 \times T(3)) & & \\
 1493 &:= Q(Q(4)) + Q(F(9)) + Q(Q(3)) & 1497 &:= -1 + (-\sqrt{4} + C((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 7 \\
 1493 &:= T(-1 + T(4) + T(9)) + F(T(3)) & 1497 &:= 1 + C(T(4)) + T(\sqrt{9} + T(7)) \\
 & & 1497 &:= -1 + F(\sqrt{C(4)}) - (\sqrt{9})!! + C(F(7)) \\
 1494 &:= (-1 + C(F(4)!) + F(9)) \times F(4)! & 1497 &:= 1 + F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(T(7)) \\
 1494 &:= (-1 + Q(Q(4)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times F(4)! & 1497 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(T(7)) \\
 1494 &:= (-1 + T(4!)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - T(4!) & 1497 &:= -4! + Q(Q(9)) - 7! \\
 1494 &:= -(-C(-1 + 4) - ((\sqrt{9})!)) \times \sqrt{4} & 1497 &:= F(1 + Q(4)) - Q(\sqrt{9} + 7) \\
 1494 &:= (Q(1 + T(4)) + T(9)) \times Q(F(4)) & 1497 &:= T(1 + T(4)) + T(Q(9) - T(7)) \\
 1494 &:= -1 + Q(4!) - Q(9) + C(T(4)) & & \\
 1494 &:= -1 + T(4) + T(9 \times T(F(4))) & 1498 &:= 1 + C(F(4) + 9) - T(F(8)) \\
 1494 &:= -1 + T(C(4)) - T(F(9)) + T(4) & 1498 &:= -1 + F(Q(4)) + F((\sqrt{9})!) \times Q(8) \\
 1494 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{4}}) & 1498 &:= 1 + Q(Q(4)) + C(9) + C(8) \\
 1494 &:= C(1 + 4) + Q(F(9)) + F(4) & 1498 &:= -1 + \sqrt{C(C(4))} + F(8 \times F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 1494 &:= Q((-1 + 4)!) + \sqrt{4} \times C(9) & 1498 &:= 1 - 4! + Q(\sqrt{9} + T(8)) \\
 1494 &:= Q(14) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + \sqrt{4} & 1498 &:= F(1 + T(F(4))) + T(9 \times \sqrt{T(8)}) \\
 1494 &:= T(1 + Q(4)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + Q(4!) & 1498 &:= -F(Q(4)) + T(F(9) + T(8)) \\
 1494 &:= T(T(T(4))) + (9 - T(T(4))) & 1498 &:= T(-1 + C(4)) - T(\sqrt{9}) - C(8) \\
 & & 1498 &:= T(1 + F(T(4))) - 98 \\
 & & 1498 &:= T(1 + T(T(4))) - 98 \\
 1495 &:= (1 + T(4!) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 & 1498 &:= T(F(T(4))) - F(9) - 8 \\
 1495 &:= (-1 - Q(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(\sqrt{9}) - Q(5)) & 1498 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(\sqrt{9}) - T(8) \\
 1495 &:= 1 + Q(C(4) - C(\sqrt{9})) + C(5) & & \\
 1495 &:= 1 - C(F(4)) + Q(F(9) + 5) & & \\
 1495 &:= -F(F(F(4)! + 1)) + C(\sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!!/5}) & 1499 &:= -1 + (Q(Q(4)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 1495 &:= -T(14) + Q(T(9) - 5) & 1499 &:= 14 + T(9 + T(9)) \\
 1495 &:= T(F(T(4))) - 9 \times 5 & 1499 &:= C(F(4)! + 1) + F(9) \times F(9) \\
 1495 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 9 \times 5 & 1499 &:= F(14) - F(9) + Q(F(9)) \\
 & & & \\
 1496 &:= (Q(14) - 9) \times F(6) & 1500 &:= 1 \times 5 \times T(Q(0! + 0!)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1501 := 1 + 5 \times T(Q(0! + 1!))$$

$$1502 := C(C(\sqrt{-1 + 5})) + T(-0! + T(Q(T(2))))$$

$$1502 := C(F(1 + 5)) + T(-0! + T(Q(T(2))))$$

$$1503 := F(\sqrt{-1 + T(Q(5))}) - T(0! + T(Q(3)))$$

$$1503 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - 0! - T(F(T(3)))$$

$$1503 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 0! - Q(T(3))$$

$$1503 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 0! - T(C(F(3)))$$

$$1504 := (1 + 5)! + Q(0! + C(F(4)))$$

$$1504 := (-1 + F(T(5) - 0!)) \times 4$$

$$1504 := -1 + 5 \times (0! + T(4!))$$

$$1504 := -Q(Q(5) - 0!) + T(C(4))$$

$$1504 := -T(F(1 + 5)) + T(F(T(4)))$$

$$1505 := (1 + T((5 - 0!)!)) \times 5$$

$$1505 := (-1 - T(Q(5) - 0!)) \times (-5)$$

$$1506 := T(50) + T(T(6))$$

$$1506 := T(T(1 + 5) - 0!) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1507 := -1 + T(50) + F(F(7))$$

$$1507 := T(Q(1 + 5)) + Q(0! + T(7))$$

$$1508 := T(T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) - T(0! + T(8))$$

$$1509 := 1 + F(T(5) - 0!) \times Q(F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1512 := (-1 + Q(F(5 + 1))) \times Q(2)!$$

$$1512 := (-1 - C(5)) \times (-12)$$

$$1512 := T(1 + Q(5) + 1) \times Q(2)$$

$$1512 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - T(1 + T(T(2)))$$

$$1512 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(1 + T(T(2)))$$

$$1513 := (1 + Q(T(T(5 - 1))))/F(3)$$

$$1513 := 1 + (5 - 1) \times T(C(3))$$

$$1513 := 1 + Q(Q(5 + 1)) + C(3!)$$

$$1513 := F(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) \times (1 + Q(Q(F(3))))$$

$$1513 := Q(T(1 + 5 + 1)) + C(Q(3))$$

$$1514 := 1 + T(T(T(5 - 1))) - C(F(4))$$

$$1514 := 1 + T(T(T(5 - 1))) - C(T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$1514 := T(1 + 51) + T(Q(4))$$

$$1515 := (1 + Q(T(5 - 1))) \times T(5)$$

$$1516 := (1 - 5)! + T(T(T(\sqrt{16})))$$

$$1516 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - (\sqrt{16})!$$

$$1517 := Q(1 + Q(5)) + Q(1 + T(7))$$

$$1518 := (1 + 5) \times T(1 + F(8))$$

$$1518 := T(1 + T(5 + 1)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1519 := C(-1 + T(5)) - Q(1 + F(9))$$

$$1519 := -T(1 + 5) + T(F(1 + 9))$$

$$1519 := -T(1 + 5) + T(T(1 + 9))$$

$$1520 := -1 + Q(5!/F(Q(2)) - 0!)$$

$$1520 := -1 + Q(5!/T(2) - 0!)$$

$$1520 := -1 + Q(5 \times C(2) - 0!)$$

$$1520 := -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 0$$

$$1520 := Q(15 + Q(2)!) - 0!$$

$$1520 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - 20$$

$$1520 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 20$$

$$1521 := -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 1$$

$$1521 := Q(Q(1 + 5) + 2 + 1)$$

$$1522 := 1 - (5 - C(C(2))) \times T(2)$$

$$1522 := 1 + (-Q(5) + Q(C(2)))^2$$

$$1522 := 1 + Q(5 \times C(2) - F(2))$$

$$1522 := 1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(2 \times Q(2)))$$

$$1522 := -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 2$$

$$1522 := 1 + Q(T(5) + (2 + 2)!)$$

$$1522 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - T(2) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1522 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(2) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1523 := -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 3$$

$$1523 := C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + 3 \times Q(C(2))$$

$$1523 := Q(-1 + 5 \times C(2)) + F(3)$$

$$1523 := Q(-1 + T(5)) \times C(2) - T(Q(3))$$

$$1523 := Q(15) + 2 + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1523 := Q(Q(1 + 5) + T(2)) + F(3)$$

$$1523 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + Q(F(Q(2)) + Q(3!))$$

$$1523 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + Q(T(2) + Q(T(3)))$$

$$1524 := (1 + 5) \times (-2 + Q(Q(4)))$$

$$1524 := (1 - 5 + C(C(2))) \times F(4)$$

$$1524 := (1 - 5 + C(C(2))) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1524 := -1 + Q(Q(5)) + Q(T(2) \times T(4))$$

$$1524 := -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 4$$

$$1524 := -1 - Q(5) \times (T(2) - C(4))$$

$$1524 := -1 - T(5) + T(F(F(2) \times T(4)))$$

$$1524 := 1 - T(5) - 2 + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1524 := Q(5) + C(C(2)) + F(Q(4))$$

$$1525 := (-1/2) \times F(15) \times (-5)$$

$$1525 := (1/2) \times F(15) \times 5$$

$$1525 := (1 + (1/2) \times 5!) \times Q(5)$$

$$1525 := -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 5$$

$$1525 := -15 + T(T(2 \times 5))$$

$$1525 := Q(15 \times 2) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1526 := -1 + C(T(5)) - C(2) \times T(T(6))$$

$$1526 := 1 + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2)!) + 6$$

$$1526 := -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 6$$

$$1526 := 1 - Q(5) \times (F(Q(2)) - Q(F(6)))$$

$$1526 := -1 - Q(5) + Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1526 := 1 - T(5) + T(F(2 + F(6)))$$

$$1526 := 1 - T(5) + T(T(T(-2 - 6)))$$

$$1526 := 5 + Q(T(2) + Q(6))$$

$$1526 := C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) - F(C(2)) + C(6)$$

$$1526 := F(1 + T(5)) + C(T(2)) + C(F(6))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1527 &:= 1 + 5 + Q(T(2) \times F(7)) \\
 1527 &:= -1 + F(T(5)) + C(C(2)) + T(T(7)) \\
 1527 &:= -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 7 \\
 1527 &:= 15 + 7 \times C(T(T(2))) \\
 1527 &:= C(\sqrt{1+5!}) + Q(2 \times 7) \\
 1527 &:= Q(-1 + T(5)) + C(Q(2) + 7) \\
 1527 &:= Q(Q(1 + 5)) + T(7 \times T(2)) \\
 1527 &:= Q(Q(1 + 5)) - 2 + F(F(7)) \\
 1527 &:= T(F(5 \times 2)) - F(7) \\
 1527 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(T(2)) - 7 \\
 \\
 1528 &:= (1 + 5) \times Q(Q(Q(2))) - 8 \\
 1528 &:= (-1 + Q(5)) \times Q(C(2)) - 8 \\
 1528 &:= (1 + T(T(5) + Q(2))) \times 8 \\
 1528 &:= -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 8 \\
 1528 &:= 1 + T(5 + T(F(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(8)) \\
 1528 &:= C(F(1 + 5)) \times F(Q(2)) - 8 \\
 1528 &:= C(T(-1 + 5)) + T(\sqrt{-1 + T(Q(5))}) \\
 1528 &:= F(-1 + 5) \times C(C(2)) - 8 \\
 1528 &:= -F(1 + 5) + T(2) \times C(8) \\
 1528 &:= Q(F(1 + 5)) \times Q(2)! - 8 \\
 1528 &:= Q(Q(5)) + T(2 \times F(8)) \\
 1528 &:= T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - 2 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 1528 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 2 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 \\
 1529 &:= -(-1 + Q(T(5))) \times C(2) + T(Q(9)) \\
 1529 &:= -1 + (Q(5) + Q(T(2))) \times T(9) \\
 1529 &:= -1 + Q(-Q(5) + Q(C(2))) + 9 \\
 1529 &:= -1 + T(5) \times T(2) \times F(9) \\
 1529 &:= C(-1 + T(5)) - C(T(2)) \times T(9) \\
 1529 &:= F(\sqrt{1+5!}) + 2 \times ((\sqrt{9})!!) \\
 1529 &:= Q(Q(1 + 5)) + F(Q(2) + 9) \\
 1529 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - (2 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1530 &:= Q(F(F(1 + 5))) + Q(F(Q(3)) - 0!) \\
 1530 &:= Q(T(1 + 5)) + Q(F(Q(3)) - 0!) \\
 1530 &:= -T(-1 + 5) + T(T(Q(3) + 0!)) \\
 1530 &:= T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - T(3 + 0!) \\
 1530 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(3 + 0!) \\
 \\
 1531 &:= -Q(F(-1 + 5)) + T(T(T(3 + 1))) \\
 1531 &:= T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - F(T(3)) - 1 \\
 1531 &:= -T(Q(1 + 5)) + C(F(1 + T(3))) \\
 1531 &:= -T(T(F(1 + 5))) + C(F(1 + T(3))) \\
 1531 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - Q(3) \\
 \\
 1532 &:= (5 + T(C(3))) \times Q(2) \\
 1532 &:= (F(-1 + T(5)) + T(3)) \times Q(2) \\
 1532 &:= 1 - 5 + 3 \times C(C(2)) \\
 1532 &:= 3 \times C(F(1 + 5)) - Q(2) \\
 1532 &:= C(-1 + Q(5))/Q(3) - Q(2) \\
 1532 &:= Q(1 + T(5)) \times T(3) - Q(2) \\
 1532 &:= Q(Q(-1 + 5)) \times 3! - Q(2) \\
 1532 &:= \sqrt{1+5!} + Q(F(Q(2)) + Q(3!)) \\
 1532 &:= T(F(T(1^5 + 3))) - F(T(T(2))) \\
 1532 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(3) - 2 \\
 \\
 1533 &:= (1 - C(5 + 3)) \times (-3) \\
 1533 &:= -1 + T(F(5 \times F(3))) - T(3) \\
 1533 &:= F(-1 + T(5)) + Q(F(3 \times 3)) \\
 1533 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (Q(Q(3)) - F(3!)) \\
 1533 &:= Q(1 + T(5)) \times T(3) - 3 \\
 1533 &:= Q(Q(-1 + 5)) \times 3! - 3 \\
 1533 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - (1/3) \times T(T(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1534 &:= -(1 + 5) + T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\
 1534 &:= 1 + F(T(5) + F(3)) - C(4) \\
 1534 &:= 1 - 5! + T(F(3) + F(T(4))) \\
 1534 &:= -1 - Q(Q(5)) + 3!! \times F(4) \\
 1534 &:= 1 - T(T(5)) + T(F(3) + F(T(4))) \\
 1534 &:= 3 \times C(F(1 + 5)) - \sqrt{4} \\
 1534 &:= C(-1 + Q(5))/Q(3) - \sqrt{4} \\
 1534 &:= Q(1 + T(5)) \times T(3) - \sqrt{4} \\
 1534 &:= -\sqrt{-1 + 5} + 3! \times Q(Q(4)) \\
 1534 &:= -\sqrt{-1 + 5} + 3 \times \sqrt{C(C(4))} \\
 \\
 1535 &:= (1 + Q(T(5)) + Q(Q(3))) \times 5 \\
 1535 &:= 3 \times (1 + 5)! - Q(Q(5)) \\
 1535 &:= -5 + T(F(5 \times F(3))) \\
 1535 &:= T(T(T(1^5 + 3))) - 5 \\
 \\
 1536 &:= (1 + 5) \times F(3)^{F(6)} \\
 1536 &:= 6 \times (1 + T(5))^{F(3)} \\
 1536 &:= 6 \times Q(1 + 5 \times 3) \\
 1536 &:= C((-1 + 5)!)/(3 + 6) \\
 1536 &:= C(-1 + 5) \times (3 + T(6)) \\
 1536 &:= \sqrt{C(C(-1 + 5)) \times (3 + 6)} \\
 1536 &:= T(1 + T(5)) \times T(3) + 6! \\
 \\
 1537 &:= (1 - Q(5)) \times Q(3!) + Q(Q(7)) \\
 1537 &:= 1 + T(5) + Q(3 \times F(7)) \\
 1537 &:= 3 \times F(-1 + T(5)) + T(T(7)) \\
 1537 &:= C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) - C(3) + F(F(7)) \\
 1537 &:= Q(-1 + 5) + Q(3 \times F(7)) \\
 1537 &:= Q(-1 + Q(5)) + Q(3 + T(7)) \\
 1537 &:= -T(\sqrt{-1 + 5}) + T(T(3 + 7)) \\
 1537 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - (1/7) \times T(T(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1538 &:= -(-1 - Q(Q(5))) \times Q(3) - Q(Q(8)) \\
 1538 &:= -1 - Q(T(5)) + Q(F(3) \times F(8)) \\
 1538 &:= -1 - Q(T(5)) + Q(T(3) + T(8)) \\
 1538 &:= -F(F(-1 + 5)) + T(F(F(3) + 8)) \\
 1538 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 3 \times C(8) \\
 1538 &:= -\sqrt{-1 + 5} + T(F(F(3) + 8)) \\
 1538 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(3) - 8 \\
 \\
 1539 &:= (1 + C(5 + 3)) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1539 &:= (1 + T(5) + 3) \times Q(9) \\
 1539 &:= (C((-1 + 5)!) + C(3)) \times (1/9) \\
 1539 &:= (Q(-1 + 5) + 3) \times Q(9) \\
 1539 &:= (Q(5) - 3!) \times Q(9) \\
 1539 &:= 9 \times T(3 \times (1 + 5)) \\
 1539 &:= Q(Q(1 + 5)) + 3 \times Q(9) \\
 \\
 1540 &:= T(1 + 54) + 0 \\
 1540 &:= T(15 + 40) \\
 \\
 1541 &:= 1 + T(54 + 1) \\
 1541 &:= T(1 + 54) + 1 \\
 \\
 1542 &:= (1 + 5) \times (Q(Q(4)) + F(2)) \\
 1542 &:= (C(F(1 + 5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times F(Q(2)) \\
 1542 &:= 1 + 5 + 4! \times Q(C(2)) \\
 1542 &:= 1 + 5 + F(4) \times C(C(2)) \\
 1542 &:= T(1 + 54) + 2 \\
 \\
 1543 &:= C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) - 4 + C(3!) \\
 1543 &:= Q(Q(1 + 5)) + Q(Q(4)) - Q(3) \\
 1543 &:= T(1 + 54) + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1544 &:= (1 + 5!) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + Q(4!) \\ 1544 &:= (-1 + 5!) \times C(4) + \sqrt{C(4)} \\ 1544 &:= (-1 - C(5) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 4 \\ 1544 &:= F(1 + 5) + C(4) \times 4! \\ 1544 &:= F(1 + 5) + Q(Q(4)) \times F(4)! \\ 1544 &:= T(1 + 54) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1545 &:= (-1 + 5! - Q(4)) \times T(5) \\ 1545 &:= (Q(Q(1 + 5)) - F(Q(4))) \times 5 \\ 1545 &:= -1 + Q(5) + Q(C(4) - Q(5)) \\ 1545 &:= T(1 + 54) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1546 &:= -(1 + 5) + Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(6)) \\ 1546 &:= -1 + C(\sqrt{C(5) - 4}) + C(6) \\ 1546 &:= C(5) \times \sqrt{4} + Q(Q(6)) \\ 1546 &:= C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) - F(\sqrt{4}) + C(6) \\ 1546 &:= Q(5) + Q(F(4) + Q(6)) \\ 1546 &:= T(1 + 54) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1547 &:= (1 + 5! - \sqrt{4}) \times F(7) \\ 1547 &:= (-1 + 5 \times 4!) \times F(7) \\ 1547 &:= (Q(15) - 4) \times 7 \\ 1547 &:= C(1 + 5) + C(4 + 7) \\ 1547 &:= T(1 + 54) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1548 &:= -1 + T(54) + Q(8) \\ 1548 &:= 5! + F(Q(4)) + Q(F(8)) \\ 1548 &:= F(-1 + 5) \times (4 + C(8)) \\ 1548 &:= Q(1 + 5) \times (C(4) - F(8)) \\ 1548 &:= T(1 + 54) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1549 &:= C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + C(F(4)!) + F(\sqrt{9}) \\ 1549 &:= C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + \sqrt{4} + C((\sqrt{9})!) \\ 1549 &:= Q(Q(1 + 5)) + Q(Q(4)) - \sqrt{9} \\ 1549 &:= T(1 + 54) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1550 &:= T(-1 + 5) + T(F(T(5 - 0!))) \\ 1550 &:= T(-1 + 5) + T(T(T(5 - 0!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1551 &:= Q(15) + T(51) \\ 1551 &:= \sqrt{1 + 5!} + T(F(T(5 - 1))) \\ 1551 &:= \sqrt{1 + 5!} + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\ 1551 &:= \sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} + T(F(T(5 - 1))) \\ 1551 &:= \sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1552 &:= Q(Q(1^5 + 5)) + Q(Q(Q(2))) \\ 1552 &:= Q(Q(-1 + 5)) + Q(Q((5 - 2)!)) \\ 1552 &:= Q(Q(1 + 5)) + Q(T(5) + F(2)) \\ 1552 &:= T(1 - Q(5) + 5!)/T(2) \\ 1552 &:= T(C(1 + 5) - 5!)/T(2) \\ 1552 &:= T(F(T(-1 + 5))) + T(5) - T(2) \\ 1552 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(5) - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1553 &:= -1 + T(5 \times T(5)) - Q(Q(T(3))) \\ 1553 &:= C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + Q(T(5)) - 3 \\ 1553 &:= Q(F(F(1 + 5))) + C(5) + F(Q(Q(F(3)))) \\ 1553 &:= T(C(-1 + 5)) - T(5) - C(C(F(3))) \\ 1553 &:= T(F(T(-1 + 5))) + T(5) - F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$1554 := (-1 + T(5)) \times (-Q(5) + T(Q(4)))$$

$$1554 := -1^5 + T(5) + T(F(T(4)))$$

$$1554 := -1^5 + T(5) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1554 := -1 + T(5) + T(F(5 \times \sqrt{4}))$$

$$1554 := -1 + T(5) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))$$

$$1554 := -C(1 + 5) + T(-5 + C(4))$$

$$1555 := 15 + T(55)$$

$$1556 := 1 + F(T(5)) + Q(T(5)) + 6!$$

$$1556 := 1 + T(5) + T(T(T(Q(5) - T(6))))$$

$$1556 := Q(15) + C(5 + 6)$$

$$1556 := Q(F(Q(F(-1 + 5)))) + Q((1/6) \times 5!)$$

$$1556 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - 5 + T(6)$$

$$1556 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 5 + T(6)$$

$$1557 := 1 + C(5) + T(Q(5) + T(7))$$

$$1557 := 1 + F(T(5)) + T(T(5) + T(7))$$

$$1557 := -15 - Q(Q(5)) + C(F(7))$$

$$1557 := F(-1 + 5) \times (F(T(5)) - T(F(7)))$$

$$1557 := -F(-1 + 5) + 5! \times F(7)$$

$$1557 := -\sqrt{-1 + T(Q(5))} + 7 \times Q(T(5))$$

$$1558 := \sqrt{-1 + T(Q(5))} + T(T(T(Q(5) - F(8))))$$

$$1558 := \sqrt{-1 + T(Q(5))} + T(T(T(Q(5) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}))))$$

$$1559 := -1 + 5! \times F(5 + F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1559 := -1 + T(T(5)) \times (T(5) - F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1559 := -1 - 5! \times (-T(5) + F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1559 := -1 - T(5) \times (-C(5) + T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1559 := -1 - T(Q(5) + 5) + Q(T(9))$$

$$1559 := F(1 + 5) \times F(T(5)) - T(Q(9))$$

$$1559 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - T(5) + F(9)$$

$$1560 := (1 + Q(5)) \times 60$$

$$1560 := (-1 - Q(5)) \times (-60)$$

$$1560 := 5! \times F(F(6) - 0!)$$

$$1560 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(6) - 0!$$

$$1561 := 1 + 5! \times F(6 + 1)$$

$$1561 := 1 + T(T(5)) \times F(6 + 1)$$

$$1561 := C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + T(T(6)) - 1$$

$$1561 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(6)$$

$$1562 := 1 + F(T(5)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(2))!$$

$$1562 := 1 + Q(5) + 6 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1562 := 1 + Q(5) + Q(F(6)) \times Q(2)!$$

$$1562 := 1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{-5 + T(6)}))) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$1562 := Q(1 + T(5)) + Q(Q(6)) + T(Q(2))$$

$$1562 := T(C(-1 + 5)) - 6 - C(C(2))$$

$$1562 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) + T(6) + F(2)$$

$$1562 := T(T(1 + 5)) + C(F(6) + T(2))$$

$$1563 := (-1 + F(Q(5)))/(F(6) \times 3!)$$

$$1563 := 1 + C(5 + 6) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1563 := 6 \times Q(Q(-1 + 4)) + C(3)$$

$$1563 := F(-1 + 5) \times C(F(6)) + C(3)$$

$$1563 := F(F(-1 + 5)) \times T(T(F(6))) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1563 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} \times T(T(F(6))) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1563 := T(T(1 + 5)) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(T(3))$$

$$1564 := (-1 + 5)! + T(F(6 + 4))$$

$$1564 := (-1 + 5)! + T(T(6 + 4))$$

$$1564 := -1 + C(5) + 6! \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1564 := -1 + Q(5) + T(T(6 + 4))$$

$$1564 := -6 \times (1 - 5) + T(F(T(4)))$$

$$1564 := -6 \times (1 - 5) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1564 := -Q(1 + 5) + Q(Q(6) + 4)$$

$$1565 := (1 + 5)! + 6! + C(5)$$

$$1565 := -1 - T(Q(5)) + T(Q(6) + Q(5))$$

$$1565 := T(T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) - T(F(6)) - F(T(5))$$

$$1565 := T(T(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))})) - T(F(6)) - F(T(5))$$

$$1566 := (Q(15) + Q(6)) \times 6$$

$$1566 := 1 + C(5) + 6! + 6!$$

$$1566 := T(T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) + (T(6) - T(T(F(6))))$$

$$1566 := T(T(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))})) + T(6) - T(T(F(6)))$$

$$1567 := -1 + T(56) - T(7)$$

$$1567 := Q(15) \times F(6) - F(F(7))$$

$$1568 := C(-1 + T(5)) - T(6 \times 8)$$

$$1568 := C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + C(6) + F(8)$$

$$1568 := F(1 + 5) \times Q(6 + 8)$$

$$1568 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} \times (6! + Q(8))$$

$$1568 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} \times (6! + Q(8))$$

$$1568 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} \times Q(Q(6) - 8)$$

$$1568 := T(F(T(-1 + 5))) - F(6) + T(8)$$

$$1569 := -(-1 + Q(Q(5))) \times F(6) + Q(Q(9))$$

$$1569 := -1 + Q(Q(5)) + T(6) \times T(9)$$

$$1569 := 5! + 6! + C(9)$$

$$1569 := 6 \times T((-1 + 5)!) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1569 := T(T(F(1 + 5))) + T(F(6) + F(9))$$

$$1570 := -1 - Q(Q(5)) + C(F(7)) - 0!$$

$$1570 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} \times (Q(T(7)) + 0!)$$

$$1571 := -1 - Q(Q(5)) + C(F(7))$$

$$1572 := (1 + 5!) \times F(7) - F(2)$$

$$1572 := -(-1 + 5)! + T(2 \times T(7))$$

$$1572 := -(-1 - T(T(5))) \times F(7) - F(2)$$

$$1572 := 7 \times Q(15) - T(2)$$

$$1572 := -Q(Q(5)) + C(\sqrt{-C(7) + C(C(2))})$$

$$1573 := (-1 - 5!) \times (-7 - 3!)$$

$$1573 := (-1 - 5!) \times (-7 - T(3))$$

$$1573 := (-1 - T(T(5))) \times (-7 - T(3))$$

$$1573 := 7 \times Q(15) - F(3)$$

$$1574 := (1 + 5!) \times F(7) + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$1574 := (1 + 5!) \times F(7) + F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1574 := (1 + C(5)) \times F(7) - C(4)$$

$$1574 := (-1 + T(5)) \times T(F(7)) + T(4!)$$

$$1574 := -(-1 - T(T(5))) \times F(7) + F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1574 := -1 - (-5 \times 7!) \times (1/Q(4))$$

$$1574 := -1 + 5 \times 7 + T(F(T(4)))$$

$$1574 := -1 + 5 \times 7 + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1574 := -1 + T(5) \times T(T(7)/\sqrt{4})$$

$$1574 := T(T(1 + 5)) + C(7) + C(T(4))$$

$$1575 := 15 + F(7) \times 5!$$

$$1575 := 75 \times F(F(1 + 5))$$

$$1575 := 75 \times T(1 + 5)$$

$$1575 := Q(C(-1 + 4)) - Q(Q(7)) - 5!$$

$$1576 := (-1 + C(5)) \times F(7) - Q(6)$$

$$1576 := (-Q(1 + 5) + F(F(7))) \times F(6)$$

$$1576 := (Q(15) - T(7)) \times F(6)$$

$$1576 := 1 + T(5) \times T(-7 + T(6))$$

$$1576 := C(-1 + 5) + 7 \times C(6)$$

$$1576 := F(-1 - 5) + F(7) - F(F(6))$$

$$1576 := F(-1 - 5) + F(7) - T(6)$$

$$1576 := F(T(-1 + 5)) \times T(7) + T(F(6))$$

$$1576 := Q(1 + 5) + T(Q(7) + 6)$$

$$1577 := -1 + 5! + F(F(7)) + T(Q(7))$$

$$1577 := 1 + C(5) \times F(7) - Q(7)$$

$$1577 := -1 + T(Q(5)) + T(Q(7)) + T(7)$$

$$1577 := C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + (F(7) + F(F(7)))$$

$$1578 := (Q(1 + T(5)) + 7) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1578 := -1 - F(T(5)) + C(F(7)) - 8$$

$$1578 := Q(Q(5)) - C(7) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1578 := T(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) \times F(7) + (\sqrt{T(8)})!$$

$$1578 := T(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + 7 \times C(\sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1579 := (1 + 5!) \times F(7) + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1579 := (1 + 5!) \times F(7) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1579 := -(1 - 5) \times T(T(7)) - T(9)$$

$$1579 := -(-1 - T(T(5))) \times F(7) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1579 := -1 + 5 \times (C(7) - C(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1579 := -1 + 5 \times (C(7) - \sqrt{C(9)})$$

$$1579 := -1 + C(5) \times F(7) - T(9)$$

$$1579 := -1 - 5 \times (-C(7) + \sqrt{C(9)})$$

$$1579 := -1 - Q(Q(5)) + Q(7) \times T(9)$$

$$1581 := T(T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) - T(T(8) - 1)$$

$$1581 := T(T(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))})) - T(T(8) - 1)$$

$$1582 := (1 + Q(T(5))) \times (8 - F(2))$$

$$1582 := 1 + (T(5) + C(8)) \times T(2)$$

$$1582 := 1 + T(5 + T(8)) + T(T(2))!$$

$$1582 := -15 + F(F(8) - Q(2))$$

$$1582 := F(1 + T(5)) + T(T(8) - 2)$$

$$1582 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(8) + T(T(2))$$

$$1583 := (1 + Q(5)) \times Q(8) - Q(Q(3))$$

$$1583 := 1 + F(T(5)) + T(8) \times C(3)$$

$$1583 := 1 - T(5) + F(8 + Q(3))$$

$$1583 := C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + T(8) + C(T(3))$$

$$1583 := T(1 + Q(5)) + C(8) + T(3)!$$

$$1584 := (1 + 5)! + T(8) \times 4!$$

$$1584 := (1 + T(5) + C(8)) \times F(4)$$

$$1584 := (5! - F(8)) \times Q(4)$$

$$1584 := F(-1 + 5) \times T(8 \times 4)$$

$$1584 := Q(5 \times 8) - Q(4)$$

$$1584 := \sqrt{1 + 5!} \times F(8 + 4)$$

$$1584 := T(-8 \times (1 - 5)) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1585 &:= -1 + T(58) - C(5) \\ 1585 &:= -15 + Q(8 \times 5) \\ 1585 &:= -\sqrt{1+5!} + T(T(T(8)) - F(T(5))) \\ 1585 &:= -\sqrt{1+T(T(5))} + T(T(T(8)) - F(T(5))) \\ 1585 &:= T(T(T(-1+5))) + T(-\sqrt{T(8)} + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1586 &:= 1 + Q(Q(5) - 8) + Q(Q(6)) \\ 1586 &:= -1 - F(T(5)) + C(F(8) - F(6)) \\ 1586 &:= -C(5) + T(Q(8) - 6) \\ 1586 &:= -T(-1+5) + T(8!/6!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1587 &:= 1 + T(Q(5)) + T(8) + T(Q(7)) \\ 1587 &:= -F((1/8) \times 5!) + C(F(7)) \\ 1587 &:= Q(5 \times 8) - F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1588 &:= -1 + F(Q(5) - 8) - 8 \\ 1588 &:= 1 - F(T(5)) + C(F(8) - 8) \\ 1588 &:= -F(1+5) + T(Q(8) - 8) \\ 1588 &:= Q(1+T(5)) + T(8) + Q(T(8)) \\ 1588 &:= T(C(-1+5) - 8) - 8 \\ 1588 &:= T(-F(15) + T(T(8))) - 8 \\ 1588 &:= T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1589 &:= -1 + T(5! - Q(8)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\ 1589 &:= -1 + T(5 + T(8)) + C(9) \\ 1589 &:= -F(1+5) + F(8+9) \\ 1590 &:= T(-1+T(5)) + T(T(T(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) - 0!) \\ 1591 &:= -(1+5) + F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9}))) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1592 &:= (-5!) \times (-9) + C(C(2)) \\ 1592 &:= (Q(-1+T(5)) + \sqrt{9}) \times C(2) \\ 1592 &:= -5 + F((1/2) \times F(9)) \\ 1592 &:= T(-Q(5) + Q(9)) - Q(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1593 &:= (Q(-1+Q(5)) - T(9)) \times 3 \\ 1593 &:= -1 + Q(5!/ \sqrt{9}) - 3! \\ 1593 &:= -1 + Q(T(5)) + Q(F(9) + 3) \\ 1593 &:= 1 - 5 + F(F(9)/F(3)) \\ 1593 &:= 59 \times C(3) \\ 1593 &:= T(1 + T(T(-(5-9)))) - 3 \\ 1593 &:= T(\sqrt{1+5!} + T(9)) - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1594 &:= -(1+5) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + 4 \\ 1594 &:= (Q(5) + 1) \times Q(9) - \sqrt{C(C(4))} \\ 1594 &:= -1 + (-5 + F(9)) \times F(T(4)) \\ 1594 &:= 9 \times (1+5) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 1594 &:= F(F(1+5) + 9) - F(4) \\ 1594 &:= Q(15) + Q(F(9) + F(4)) \\ 1594 &:= T(1+T(5)) + C(9) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 1594 &:= T(-Q(5) + Q(9)) - \sqrt{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1595 &:= -1 + T(5! - C(9-5)) \\ 1595 &:= F(1+T(5)) - F(\sqrt{9}) + F(T(5)) \\ 1595 &:= F(T(-1+5)) \times (-5 + F(9)) \\ 1595 &:= F(T(-1+5)) + T(F(T(9-5))) \\ 1595 &:= Q(1+5! - Q(9)) - 5 \\ 1595 &:= Q(1+5) \times T(9) - Q(5) \\ 1595 &:= Q(1+5 + F(9)) - 5 \\ 1595 &:= Q(5!/ \sqrt{9}) - 5 \\ 1595 &:= T(T(-1+5)) + T(T(T(9-5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$1596 := (1 + 5! - T(9)) \times T(6)$$

$$1596 := -1^5 + F(9 + F(6))$$

$$1596 := -1 + F(C(5) - \sqrt{9} \times Q(6))$$

$$1596 := -1 + Q(Q(5)) + C(\sqrt{9}) \times Q(6)$$

$$1596 := 1 - 5 + Q(F(9) + 6)$$

$$1596 := T((-1 - 5) + \sqrt{9}) \times F(6)$$

$$1596 := T((1 + T(5) - 9) \times F(6))$$

$$1596 := T(5 + T(9) + 6)$$

$$1597 := 1 + T((5 + \sqrt{9}) \times 7)$$

$$1597 := 1 + T((5 - \sqrt{9}) \times T(7))$$

$$1597 := F(1^5 + 9 + 7)$$

$$1598 := 1^5 + F(9 + 8)$$

$$1598 := 1 + Q(Q(5)) + C(\sqrt{9}) \times T(8)$$

$$1598 := -T(T(-1 + 5)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(8)$$

$$1599 := -1 + F(T(5)) - T(9) + T(T(9))$$

$$1599 := -1 + Q((1/9) \times 5! \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$1599 := -1 + Q(T(5) - 9 + F(9))$$

$$1599 := -1 + \sqrt{5 \times C((\sqrt{9})!!/9)}$$

$$1599 := F(F(1 + 5) + 9) + F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1599 := T(1 + T(T(-5 - 9))) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1599 := T(\sqrt{1 + 5!} + T(9)) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1600 := Q((-1 + T(6)) \times (0! + 0!))$$

$$1600 := Q(-1 - 6) \times C(0! + 0!)$$

$$1600 := Q(Q(6) + Q(0! + 0!))$$

$$1601 := 1 + Q(Q(6) + Q(0! + 1))$$

$$1602 := -(1 - 6) + F(0! + Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1602 := -1 + Q(Q(6) - 0!) + T(C(T(2)))$$

$$1602 := 6 + T(0! + T(T(Q(2))))$$

$$1602 := C(F(1 + 6)) - T(F(0! + C(2)))$$

$$1602 := T(F(T(\sqrt{16})) + 0!) + T(T(2))$$

$$1602 := T(T(T(\sqrt{16})) + 0!) + T(T(2))$$

$$1603 := F(16 + 0!) + 3!$$

$$1603 := F(16 + 0!) + T(3)$$

$$1603 := Q(-1 + Q(6)) + T(C(3))$$

$$1604 := (-1 - Q(T(6) - 0!)) \times (-4)$$

$$1604 := 1 + 6 + F(0! + Q(4))$$

$$1604 := C(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}) + T(0! + T(T(4)))$$

$$1604 := F(6) + T(0! + F(T(4)))$$

$$1605 := -T(-1 - 60) + C(T(5))$$

$$1605 := T(60) - Q(T(5))$$

$$1605 := T(F(T(\sqrt{16})) - 0!) + 5!$$

$$1605 := T(T(T(\sqrt{16})) - 0!) + 5!$$

$$1609 := -1 + F(T(6 - 0!)) + C(T(Q(F(\sqrt{9}))))$$

$$1609 := F(1 + 6) + T(0! + T(T(Q(F(\sqrt{9}))))$$

$$1610 := F(T(-1 - 6)) + C(10)$$

$$1611 := Q((\sqrt{16})!) + T(T(Q(T(1 + 1))))$$

$$1611 := T(T(1 + F(6))) + Q(Q(1 + 1)!)$$

$$1612 := 16 + T(1 + T(T(Q(2))))$$

$$1612 := Q(Q(-1 + 6)) + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1612 := T(-1 - 6) + F(1 + Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1613 := F(16 + 1) + Q(Q(F(3)))$$

$$1614 := T(-1 - 61) - C(T(F(4)))$$

$$1614 := T(-1 - 61) - C(T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$1615 := T(-1 + T(1 + F(6))) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1615 := T(T(Q(T(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}))) - 1) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1616 := -1 + T(T(6)) \times (1 + 6)$$

$$1617 := (-T(T(6))) \times (-7)$$

$$1617 := -1 + F(F(6)) + F(17)$$

$$1617 := -1 + T(6) + F(17)$$

$$1618 := 1 - T(T(6)) \times (1 - 8)$$

$$1618 := F(16 + 1) + F(8)$$

$$1619 := -1 + (F(F(6)) - 1) \times Q(9)$$

$$1619 := -1 + Q(6) \times T(9)$$

$$1619 := -1 + T(F(6)) \times T(9)$$

$$1620 := (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0$$

$$1620 := (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(0! + C(2))$$

$$1620 := (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 0$$

$$1620 := 20 \times Q(1 + F(6))$$

$$1620 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 0$$

$$1620 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0$$

$$1620 := T(C(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}})) \times T(C(2) + 0!)$$

$$1620 := T(F(6)) \times T(0! + C(2))$$

$$1620 := T(F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0!$$

$$1621 := (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 1$$

$$1621 := (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 1$$

$$1621 := (\sqrt{16})! + F(Q(Q(2)) + 1)$$

$$1621 := 1 + Q(6) \times T(Q(2 + 1))$$

$$1621 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 1$$

$$1621 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 1$$

$$1622 := (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 2$$

$$1622 := (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 2$$

$$1622 := -1 + 6! + T(T(C(2)) + T(T(2)))$$

$$1622 := 1 + F(F(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + Q(2)!)$$

$$1622 := 1 + Q(Q(6) + Q(2)) + F(C(2))$$

$$1622 := -1 + T(2 \times T(6)) + T(T(2))!$$

$$1622 := Q(1 + Q(6)) + T(22)$$

$$1622 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 2$$

$$1622 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 2$$

$$1623 := (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 3$$

$$1623 := (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 3$$

$$1623 := (1 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1623 := (1 - Q(6) + Q(Q(2)!)) \times 3$$

$$1623 := -1 + Q(Q(6) + Q(2)) + Q(F(3))!$$

$$1623 := C(1 + 6) - Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(3)!)$$

$$1623 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 3$$

$$1623 := T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 3$$

$$1623 := T(2 \times T(6)) + T(3)!$$

$$1624 := (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 4$$

$$1624 := (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 4$$

$$1624 := (-1 - T(T(6))) \times (T(2) - T(4))$$

$$1624 := -1 + Q(Q(6) + F(2)) + Q(Q(4))$$

$$1624 := C(-1 - 6) + C(C(2)) + F(Q(4))$$

$$1624 := F(1 + F(6) + C(2)) + C(F(4))$$

$$1624 := Q(-1 - 6) \times C(2) + 4!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1624 &:= Q(Q(6) + Q(2)) + 4! \\
 1624 &:= \sqrt{16} \times T(Q(2) + 4!) \\
 1624 &:= T(1 + 6) \times (T(2) + F(T(4))) \\
 1624 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 4 \\
 1624 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 4 \\
 1624 &:= T(T(1 + 6)) \times \sqrt{2^4} \\
 \\
 1625 &:= (1 + 6 \times 2) \times C(5) \\
 1625 &:= (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 5 \\
 1625 &:= (1 + Q(6 + 2)) \times Q(5) \\
 1625 &:= (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 5 \\
 1625 &:= -(1 - 6) \times T(25) \\
 1625 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 5 \\
 1625 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 5 \\
 \\
 1626 &:= (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 6 \\
 1626 &:= (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 6 \\
 1626 &:= -Q(1 + F(6)) + F(Q(Q(2))) + 6! \\
 1626 &:= Q(F(1 + 6)) \times T(Q(2)) - Q(F(6)) \\
 1626 &:= T((1/2) \times T(16)) - 6! \\
 1626 &:= T(-1 - 6) \times C(Q(2)) + T(Q(6)) \\
 1626 &:= T(-1 - 6) \times Q(C(2)) + T(Q(6)) \\
 1626 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 6 \\
 1626 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 6 \\
 1626 &:= T(T(-1 + 6)) \times F(T(T(2))) + T(T(F(6))) \\
 \\
 1627 &:= (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 7 \\
 1627 &:= (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 7 \\
 1627 &:= 2 \times C(1 + F(6)) + Q(F(7)) \\
 1627 &:= F(\sqrt{16}) \times C(C(2)) + T(F(7)) \\
 1627 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 7 \\
 1627 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 7 \\
 1627 &:= T(Q(6)) + Q(T(2) + T(7)) \\
 1627 &:= T(\sqrt{16}) + 7 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \\
 1628 &:= (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 8 \\
 1628 &:= (1 + Q(6)) \times (C(2) + T(8)) \\
 1628 &:= (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 8 \\
 1628 &:= (1 + T(F(6))) \times (C(2) + T(8)) \\
 1628 &:= (1 + T(F(6))) \times (F(T(T(2))) + T(8)) \\
 1628 &:= -C(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(2 \times T(8)) \\
 1628 &:= T(1 + 6) + Q(Q(2) + T(8)) \\
 1628 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 8 \\
 1628 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 8 \\
 \\
 1629 &:= (1 + 6!/Q(2)) \times 9 \\
 1629 &:= (1 + C(6) - T(C(2))) \times 9 \\
 1629 &:= (1 + C(F(F(6))) + C(C(2)))/(\sqrt{9})! \\
 1629 &:= (-1 + F(F(6))) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 9 \\
 1629 &:= (-1 + T(6)) \times Q(Q(T(2))) + 9 \\
 1629 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(C(2)) + 9 \\
 1629 &:= T(1 + F(6)) \times T(F(T(T(2)))) + 9 \\
 1629 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) - F(2) + T(F(9)) \\
 \\
 1630 &:= T(-1 + Q(6)) + C(Q(3) + 0!) \\
 1630 &:= T(-1 + T(F(6))) + C(T(3 + 0!)) \\
 1630 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(F(T(3)) + 0!)) \\
 1630 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 0 \\
 \\
 1631 &:= F(F(1 + 6)) \times (3! + 1) \\
 1631 &:= F(F(1 + 6)) \times (T(3) + 1) \\
 1631 &:= Q(-1 + Q(6)) + T(C(3) + 1) \\
 1631 &:= Q(-1 + Q(6)) + T(T(T(3) + 1)) \\
 1631 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 1 \\
 \\
 1632 &:= -1 + Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(Q(2))) \\
 1632 &:= -1 - C(6) + Q(C(3) + Q(Q(2))) \\
 1632 &:= 2 \times T(16) \times T(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1632 &:= F(1 + F(6)) \times 3! \times C(2) \\
 1632 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \times F(Q(3)) \times Q(2)! \\
 1632 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 2 \\
 \\
 1633 &:= 1 + (T(T(6)) - C(3)) \times C(F(3)) \\
 1633 &:= 1 + T(Q(6) + T(3)) + C(Q(3)) \\
 1633 &:= 1 - T(6) + T(Q(T(3)) + T(T(3))) \\
 1633 &:= F(-1 + 6 \times 3) + Q(3!) \\
 1633 &:= F(-1 + 6 \times 3) + Q(T(3)) \\
 1633 &:= F(-1 + 6 \times 3) + T(F(T(3))) \\
 1633 &:= Q(16) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(3!)) \\
 1633 &:= Q(16 + C(3)) - C(3!) \\
 1633 &:= T(\sqrt{C(16)}) - T(T(T(3))) - C(T(3)) \\
 1633 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 3 \\
 \\
 1634 &:= 1 + Q(6) + F(C(3) - T(4)) \\
 1634 &:= 1 + Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)) \\
 1634 &:= 1 + T(F(6)) + F(C(3) - T(4)) \\
 1634 &:= 1 + T(F(6)) + F(T(T(3)) - 4) \\
 1634 &:= 1 - C(6) + Q(C(3) + Q(4)) \\
 1634 &:= 1 - T(T(6)) - C(T(3)) + T(C(4)) \\
 1634 &:= F(T(-1 + 6)) + F(3)^{T(4)} \\
 1634 &:= T(Q(1 + 6) + 3) + Q(Q(4)) \\
 1634 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 4 \\
 \\
 1635 &:= (1 + 3 \times Q(6)) \times T(5) \\
 1635 &:= (1 + 3 \times T(F(6))) \times T(5) \\
 1635 &:= (1 + Q(F(6))) \times C(3) - 5! \\
 1635 &:= (T(16) - C(3)) \times T(5) \\
 1635 &:= -1 + Q(6) + Q(5 \times F(3!)) \\
 1635 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 5 \\
 \\
 1636 &:= C(1 + 6) - 3 + Q(Q(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1636 &:= C(F(1 + 6)) - T(C(3) + 6) \\
 1636 &:= Q(1 + Q(6)) + Q(T(3)) + T(T(6)) \\
 1636 &:= Q(1 + Q(6) + 3) + Q(6) \\
 1636 &:= Q(Q(1 + 6) - Q(3)) + Q(6) \\
 1636 &:= T(\sqrt{16}) \times F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1636 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 6 \\
 \\
 1637 &:= -1 - (T(T(6)) + 3) \times (-7) \\
 1637 &:= -1 + (T(T(6)) + 3) \times 7 \\
 1637 &:= -1 + F(F(6)) \times 3! \times F(7) \\
 1637 &:= 1 + Q(6) + Q(C(3) + F(7)) \\
 1637 &:= 1 + Q(6) + Q(-Q(3) + Q(7)) \\
 1637 &:= -1 + T(6) \times T(3) \times F(7) \\
 1637 &:= -2 + Q(Q(6)) + C(7) \\
 1637 &:= C(-1 + 6) + 7 \times C(3!) \\
 1637 &:= T(T(1 + 6)) + T(3) + T(Q(7)) \\
 1637 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 7 \\
 \\
 1638 &:= (C((\sqrt{16})!) - 3!) \times (1/8) \\
 1638 &:= F(1 + 6) \times 3! \times F(8) \\
 1638 &:= F(1 + 6) \times T(3) \times F(8) \\
 1638 &:= -T(-1 + 6) + T(T(T(3)) + T(8)) \\
 1638 &:= T(6) \times T(T(3) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \\
 1638 &:= -T(Q(6)) + Q(8 \times T(3)) \\
 1638 &:= T(Q(6)) + T(8) \times C(3) \\
 1638 &:= T(T(1 + 6)) + T(3)! + C(8) \\
 1638 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 8 \\
 \\
 1639 &:= (1 + 6)^3 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 1639 &:= 1 + 6! + C(3) \times F(9) \\
 1639 &:= 1 + F(F(6)) \times (-3 + Q(9)) \\
 1639 &:= 1 + T(6) \times T(3 + 9) \\
 1639 &:= C(1 + 6) + C(3!) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 1639 &:= C(1 + 6) + Q(C(3) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1639 := T(T(1 + F(6))) + T(F(Q(3))) + 9$$

$$1640 := (F(F(6)) - 1) \times (Q(Q(F(4))) + 0!)$$

$$1640 := 1 + Q(Q(6)) + C(F(4)! + 0!)$$

$$1640 := 1 + Q(Q(6)) + C(\sqrt{C(4)} - 0!)$$

$$1640 := 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 0$$

$$1640 := Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 0$$

$$1640 := Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 0$$

$$1640 := \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \times T(40)$$

$$1641 := 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 1$$

$$1641 := Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 1$$

$$1641 := Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$1641 := T(1 + F(6)) + T(F(T(4))) + 1$$

$$1642 := (1 + T(Q(6) + 4)) \times 2$$

$$1642 := (1 + T(T(F(6)) + 4)) \times 2$$

$$1642 := (1 - 6! + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2$$

$$1642 := -1 - Q(F(6)) + F(4)!! + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1642 := 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 2$$

$$1642 := C(F(1 + 6)) - Q(4!) + F(C(2))$$

$$1642 := Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 2$$

$$1642 := Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 2$$

$$1642 := T(1 + F(6)) + F(Q(4)) + F(2)$$

$$1642 := -T(T(1 + 6)) + 4 \times C(C(2))$$

$$1643 := -1 + 4 \times T(T(6)) + T(3)!$$

$$1643 := 1 + T(Q(6)) + Q(Q(4)) + T(3)!$$

$$1643 := 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 3$$

$$1643 := -1 - T(T(F(6))) + T(4) \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1643 := C(1 + 6) + 4 + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1643 := F(16) - C(4) + 3!!$$

$$1643 := F(16) - C(4) + T(3)!$$

$$1643 := Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 3$$

$$1643 := -Q(F(6)) + F(Q(4)) + 3!!$$

$$1643 := Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 3$$

$$1643 := -T(\sqrt{16}) + T(F(T(4))) + F(3)$$

$$1644 := (-T(1 + 6) + Q(4!)) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1644 := (T(-1 + T(6)) + C(4)) \times T(F(4))$$

$$1644 := (T(1 + T(6)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times T(T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$1644 := (-T(T(6))) \times (-4) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))!$$

$$1644 := 1 + 6! - C(4) + F(Q(4))$$

$$1644 := -1 - F(6) + T(F(F(4))) + F(T(4))$$

$$1644 := -1 - F(6) + T(\sqrt{4} + F(T(4)))$$

$$1644 := 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 4$$

$$1644 := Q(1 + F(6)) + F(Q(4)) + Q(4!)$$

$$1644 := Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 4$$

$$1644 := -Q(6) + (\sqrt{C(4)})!/4!$$

$$1644 := Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 4$$

$$1644 := T(6) \times C(4) + T(4!)$$

$$1645 := (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 5$$

$$1645 := 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 5$$

$$1645 := 5 \times F(16)/F(4)$$

$$1645 := Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 5$$

$$1645 := -Q(6) + Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)$$

$$1645 := Q(T(1 + 6)) + T(Q(4)) + Q(5)$$

$$1645 := Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 5$$

$$1645 := T(1 - 6 + C(4)) - C(5)$$

$$1646 := (-1 + C(T(6)))/T(4) + 6!$$

$$1646 := (-1 + Q(6)) \times T(4) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1646 := 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 6$$

$$1646 := C(-1 - 6) + Q(F(4)) + Q(6)$$

$$1646 := Q(1 + 6) + F(-4 + T(6))$$

$$1646 := Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 6$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1646 &:= Q(1 + Q(6)) + Q(Q(4)) + F(F(6)) \\ 1646 &:= Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 1646 &:= T(T(1 + F(6))) - F(T(4)) + T(T(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1647 &:= -1 + Q(Q(6)) + Q(F(4)) + C(7) \\ 1647 &:= 16 + T(F(T(4))) + T(F(7)) \\ 1647 &:= -1 - C(6) + \sqrt{C(4)} \times F(F(7)) \\ 1647 &:= -1 - F(6) + F(4!)/T(7) \\ 1647 &:= 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 7 \\ 1647 &:= -6 + T(C(4)) - 7 \\ 1647 &:= C(6) + T(4 + Q(7)) \\ 1647 &:= Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 7 \\ 1647 &:= Q(Q(1 + 6)) - F(Q(4)) + F(F(7)) \\ 1647 &:= Q(Q(6)) + \sqrt{C(4)} + C(7) \\ 1647 &:= Q(Q(6)) + T(\sqrt{4} \times F(7)) \\ 1647 &:= Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 1647 &:= T(T(1 + 6)) + Q(4) + T(Q(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1648 &:= (C(6) - T(4)) \times 8 \\ 1648 &:= (T(-1 + T(6)) - 4) \times 8 \\ 1648 &:= 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 8 \\ 1648 &:= 6! \times F(4) - C(8) \\ 1648 &:= Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 8 \\ 1648 &:= Q(1 + Q(6)) + F(4)!! - Q(F(8)) \\ 1648 &:= Q(T(1 + 6)) + 4! \times T(8) \\ 1648 &:= Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1649 &:= (1 - T(T(6))) \times (-4) + C(9) \\ 1649 &:= 1 - C(F(6)) + F(4) \times (\sqrt{9})!! \\ 1649 &:= 1 - Q(T(6)) + T(C(4)) + 9 \\ 1649 &:= Q(1 + 6) + Q(F(4)!) + F(9) \\ 1649 &:= Q(1 + 6) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + 4 \\ 1649 &:= Q(1 + F(F(6))) + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + 9 \\ 1649 &:= Q(1 + Q(6)) + C(4) + C((\sqrt{9})!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1649 &:= Q(1 + T(6)) + Q(F(4)) + Q(F(9)) \\ 1649 &:= Q(T(\sqrt{16})) + T(T(T(4))) + 9 \\ 1649 &:= T(-1 + Q(6)) - Q(4) + T(T(9)) \\ 1649 &:= -T(16) + F(4) \times T(F(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1650 &:= Q(-1 + 6) \times T(\sqrt{5! + 0!}) \\ 1651 &:= T(Q(-1 + 6)) + T(51) \\ 1652 &:= -1 + T((6 - 5!) \times (-1/2)) \\ 1652 &:= -1 + T(F(6) + Q(5 + 2)) \\ 1652 &:= -1 + T(-T(6) + T(T(5) - T(2))) \\ 1652 &:= -1 + T(T(F(6)) + T(T(5 - 2))) \\ 1652 &:= F(1 + 6) \times C(5) + C(F(Q(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1653 &:= (Q((\sqrt{16})!) - Q(5)) \times 3 \\ 1653 &:= -1 + Q(Q(6) + 5) - C(3) \\ 1653 &:= C(F(1 + 6)) - Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(3)) \\ 1653 &:= T(\sqrt{16} + 53) \\ 1653 &:= T(T(6) + T(5 + 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1654 &:= (1 + F(6)! - Q(Q(5)))/4! \\ 1654 &:= 1 + T((-6 + 5!)/\sqrt{4}) \\ 1654 &:= 1 + T((-6 + Q(5)) \times F(4)) \\ 1654 &:= 1 + T((-6 + T(T(5)))/(\sqrt{4})) \\ 1654 &:= 1 + T(Q(6) + 5 + Q(4)) \\ 1654 &:= 1 + T(-T(6) + T(5!/T(4))) \\ 1654 &:= 1 + T(T(F(6)) + F(5 + F(4))) \\ 1654 &:= -6 + T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1655 &:= (6 + T(Q(5))) \times 5 \\ 1655 &:= -1 + Q(Q(6) + 5) - Q(5) \\ 1655 &:= T(F(T(\sqrt{16}))) + 5! - 5 \\ 1655 &:= T(F(T(\sqrt{16}))) + T(T(5)) - 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$1655 := T(T(T(\sqrt{16}))) + (T(T(5)) - 5)$$

$$1655 := T(T(T(\sqrt{16}))) + 5! - 5$$

$$1656 := (T(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(6)$$

$$1656 := -1 + Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(5)) - 6$$

$$1656 := 6 \times T(T(1 + 6)) - 5$$

$$1656 := 6 \times T(T(5) + F(6))$$

$$1657 := 1 + 6 \times T(-5 + T(7))$$

$$1657 := 1 - 6! - Q(5) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1657 := 16 \times C(5) - C(7)$$

$$1657 := -Q(1 + Q(6)) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1657 := \sqrt{16} + T(57)$$

$$1658 := -1 + T(6) \times (T(5) + Q(8))$$

$$1658 := F(16) + 5 + T(T(8))$$

$$1658 := Q(1 + Q(6)) + Q(Q(5)) - 8$$

$$1659 := (1 + 6)! - C(T(5)) - T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1659 := (1 + Q(F(6))) \times Q(5) + F(9)$$

$$1659 := (1 + T(\sqrt{6!/5})) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1659 := -(1 - 6) \times T(Q(5)) + F(9)$$

$$1659 := -1^6 + Q(Q(5)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1659 := -C(6) + Q(Q(5)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1659 := F(1 + 6) \times C(5) + F(9)$$

$$1659 := T(F(T(\sqrt{16}))) + T(T(5)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1660 := T(F(T(\sqrt{16}))) + (6 - 0)!$$

$$1660 := T(T(1 + F(6))) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))$$

$$1660 := T(T(T(\sqrt{16}))) + (6 - 0)!$$

$$1661 := 1 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1662 := (Q(16) + T(6)) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1662 := 1 + F(6) + T(T(F(6)) + F(C(2)))$$

$$1662 := 1 + Q(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)) - Q(2))$$

$$1662 := 1 + Q(F(6)) + F(T(6) - Q(2))$$

$$1662 := 1 + T(T(F(6)) + T(6)) + F(T(T(2)))$$

$$1663 := -1 + (C(6) - F(6)) \times C(F(3))$$

$$1663 := -1 + F(T(6)) - C(T(6)) - T(T(3))$$

$$1663 := -1 + Q(F(6)) \times (-F(6) + F(Q(3)))$$

$$1663 := 1 + T(Q(6) + T(6)) + Q(3)$$

$$1663 := -1 - Q(F(6)) + C((1/3) \times Q(6))$$

$$1663 := T(1 + Q(6)) + T(T(6)) + C(Q(3))$$

$$1663 := T(\sqrt{16}) + T(T(F(6)) + T(T(3)))$$

$$1664 := (-1 - 6) + T(6) \times C(4)$$

$$1664 := 1 + T(T(F(6)) + T(6)) + T(4)$$

$$1664 := 16 + F(6)!/4!$$

$$1664 := C(6 + 6) - C(4)$$

$$1664 := F(1 + 6) \times F(6) \times Q(4)$$

$$1664 := T(1 + Q(6)) + Q(T(6) + T(4))$$

$$1664 := -T(16) + 6 \times T(4!)$$

$$1665 := -((-1 + 6)! - T(T(6))) \times T(5)$$

$$1665 := (1 + Q(6)) \times T(-6 + T(5))$$

$$1665 := (1 + T(F(6))) \times T(-6 + T(5))$$

$$1665 := 1 + Q(F(6)) + Q(5 \times F(6))$$

$$1665 := -16 + Q(Q(6) + 5)$$

$$1665 := T(-1 + 6) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))$$

$$1665 := T(T(16 - 6)) + C(5)$$

$$1666 := F(1 + 6) + T(Q(6) + T(6))$$

$$1666 := F(1 + 6) + T(T(F(6)) + T(6))$$

$$1666 := Q(-1 + Q(6)) + F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))$$

$$1666 := Q(-1 + Q(6)) + T(6) \times T(6)$$

$$1666 := T(1 + T(6) + T(6)) + 6!$$

$$1666 := T(T(T(\sqrt{16}))) + 6 \times T(6)$$

$$1667 := (1 + F(6))!/C(6) - F(7)$$

$$1667 := 1 + 6! + T(-6 + Q(7))$$

$$1667 := 1 + F(Q(F(Q(F(6) - 6)))) \times Q(7)$$

$$1667 := -C(-1 + T(6)) + C(T(6)) + T(T(7))$$

$$1667 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times F(6) - F(7)$$

$$1668 := Q(F(1 + F(6))) + F(6) \times Q(8)$$

$$1668 := Q(-\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} + Q(6)) + C(8)$$

$$1668 := T(-1 - 6) + T(Q(6) + F(8))$$

$$1668 := T(-1 + 6) + T(T(6) + T(8))$$

$$1669 := 1 + \sqrt{F(6)^6} + Q(F(9))$$

$$1669 := -16 + F(F(F(6))) - C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)))$$

$$1669 := 16 + T(T(F(6)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1669 := C(1 + 6) + T(6 + T(9))$$

$$1669 := Q(1 + 6) + Q(6) \times T(9)$$

$$1671 := -(C(Q(T(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}))) - Q(Q(7)) + 1)$$

$$1671 := -C(1 + F(6)) + Q(Q(7)) - 1$$

$$1672 := -(-1 + 6)! + 7 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1672 := (-1 + T(-F(6) + T(7))) \times F(T(T(2)))$$

$$1672 := (C(6) - 7) \times C(2)$$

$$1672 := -1 - (T(6) - 7!)/T(2)$$

$$1672 := -1 + Q(Q(6)) + F(7 \times 2)$$

$$1672 := T(T(\sqrt{16})) + 7 \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$1673 := (1 + 6) \times (F(F(7)) + T(3))$$

$$1673 := -(1 + 6) + (1/3) \times 7!$$

$$1673 := (T(6) - 7!) \times (-1/3)$$

$$1673 := F(16) + F(3) \times C(7)$$

$$1674 := 1 - (T(6) - 7!)/F(4)$$

$$1674 := 1 - (T(6) - 7!)/T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1674 := -1 + T(T(6)) + Q(T(4) + T(7))$$

$$1674 := -6 + 7!/F(4)$$

$$1674 := C(1 + 6) + C(7 + 4)$$

$$1674 := Q(1 + Q(6)) + Q(7) + Q(Q(4))$$

$$1674 := T(1 + 7 \times F(6)) + T(T(F(4)))$$

$$1675 := (C(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}) - C(7)) \times (-5)$$

$$1675 := (-F(6) + C(7)) \times 5$$

$$1675 := 1 + T(T(F(6))) + (1/5) \times 7!$$

$$1675 := 67 \times Q(5)$$

$$1675 := T(\sqrt{16}) + 7! - C(T(5))$$

$$1676 := 1 - 6 + Q(Q(7)) - 6!$$

$$1676 := 1 - 6 + Q(Q(7) - F(6))$$

$$1676 := -1 - C(F(6)) + C(F(7)) - F(6)$$

$$1676 := Q(1 + Q(6)) + C(7) - Q(6)$$

$$1676 := T(16) + T(Q(7) + 6)$$

$$1676 := T(16) + T(T(F(7)) - T(F(6)))$$

$$1677 := (T(16) - 7) \times F(7)$$

$$1677 := -1 - C(F(6)) + C(F(7)) - 7$$

$$1677 := Q(1 + Q(6)) - \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + C(7)$$

$$1677 := Q(Q(-1 + 6) + F(7)) + F(F(7))$$

$$1677 := Q(Q(T(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}))) + T(Q(7) + 7)$$

$$1678 := C(F(1 + 6)) - 7 - C(8)$$

$$1678 := -F(F(1+6)) + T(F(7)) \times F(8)$$

$$1678 := -F(\sqrt{16}) + Q(Q(7) - 8)$$

$$1678 := Q(-1+6) + T(Q(7) + 8)$$

$$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$$

$$1679 := -1 + F(6)!/(F(7) - 9)!$$

$$1679 := -1 + T(-F(6) + T(7)) \times F(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1680 := (1+6)!/\sqrt{8+0!}$$

$$1680 := T(6) \times 80$$

$$1680 := 80 \times F(F(6))$$

$$1680 := 80 \times T(6)$$

$$1680 := Q(Q(1+6) - 8) - 0!$$

$$1680 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 0$$

$$1681 := 1 + F(6) \times T(F(8) - 1)$$

$$1681 := Q(-8 \times (1 - 6) + 1)$$

$$1681 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 1$$

$$1682 := ((1+6)! + \sqrt{T(8)})/T(2)$$

$$1682 := (F(T(-1+6)) + T(F(8))) \times 2$$

$$1682 := (-Q(-6 + Q(8))) \times (-1/2)$$

$$1682 := 1 + Q(6 + T(8) - F(2))$$

$$1682 := 1 + Q(Q(6) + 8 - T(2))$$

$$1682 := 2 \times Q(F(6) + F(8))$$

$$1682 := -3 + F(F(F(6))) - C(F(8))$$

$$1682 := C(F(1+6)) - C(8) - T(2)$$

$$1682 := \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \times Q(F(8) + C(2))$$

$$1682 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 2$$

$$1683 := (Q(1+6) + C(8)) \times 3$$

$$1683 := (Q(Q(-1+6)) - Q(8)) \times 3$$

$$1683 := C(F(1+6)) - C(8) - F(3)$$

$$1683 := F(\sqrt{16}) \times T(T(8) - 3)$$

$$1683 := Q(Q(1+6) - 8) + F(3)$$

$$1683 := -T(1+6) + T(Q(8) - T(3))$$

$$1683 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 3$$

$$1684 := -1 + F(F(F(6))) - F(8)^{F(4)}$$

$$1684 := -1 + F(T(6)) - F(8)^{F(4)}$$

$$1684 := \sqrt{16} + 8!/4!$$

$$1684 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 4$$

$$1685 := (C(1+6) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 5$$

$$1685 := -C(C(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}})) + C(8+5)$$

$$1685 := -C(F(6)) + C(8+5)$$

$$1685 := F(T(6)) - C(T(8) - T(5))$$

$$1685 := \sqrt{16} + Q(T(8) + 5)$$

$$1685 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 5$$

$$1686 := (1 + C(6) + Q(8)) \times 6$$

$$1686 := (-T(T(6)) + C(8)) \times 6$$

$$1686 := F(16) - F(8) + 6!$$

$$1686 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 6$$

$$1687 := (1 + C(6)) \times 8 - Q(7)$$

$$1687 := (F(F(1+6)) + 8) \times 7$$

$$1687 := 6 + Q(-8 + Q(7))$$

$$1687 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 7$$

$$1687 := T(6) \times Q(8) + C(7)$$

$$1687 := T(F(1+6)) + T(8 \times 7)$$

$$1688 := (1 - T(6) + T(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$1688 := -1 + Q(6) + T(T(8) + F(8))$$

$$1688 := -1 + T(F(6)) + T(T(8) + F(8))$$

$$1688 := -1 - T(T(6)) + 8!/F(8)$$

$$1688 := F(\sqrt{16}) + F(F(8)) - C(F(8))$$

$$1688 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 8$$

$$1688 := T(6 \times 8) + C(8)$$

$$1689 := 1 + (-6! + Q(Q(8)))/F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1689 := 8 \times (-1 + 6)! + C(9)$$

$$1689 := F(F(6)) + C(8) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1689 := -Q(Q(1 + 6)) + Q(Q(8)) - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1689 := T(-1 - 6) \times Q(8) + C(9)$$

$$1689 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 9$$

$$1689 := T(1 - 6 + Q(8)) - Q(9)$$

$$1689 := T(6) + C(8) + Q(F(9))$$

$$1690 := F(16) + T(T(F(T(\sqrt{9})))) + 0!$$

$$1690 := Q(F(1 + 6)) \times (9 + 0!)$$

$$1691 := F(T(-1 + 6)) + T(T(9) + 1)$$

$$1692 := (-1 + 9 \times F(F(6))) \times Q(F(Q(2)))$$

$$1692 := (\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} + T(9)) \times T(C(2))$$

$$1692 := -1 + F(F(F(6))) + F((\sqrt{9})!) - C(F(C(2)))$$

$$1692 := -1 + T(6) \times Q(9) - C(2)$$

$$1692 := Q(6) \times (T(9) + 2)$$

$$1692 := -Q(6) + C(\sqrt{9} \times Q(2))$$

$$1692 := -Q(6) + \sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2)!)$$

$$1692 := T(F(6)) \times (T(9) + 2)$$

$$1693 := 1 + T(6) \times Q(9) - Q(3)$$

$$1693 := 1 + T(F(6)) \times (T(9) + F(3))$$

$$1693 := 1 - Q(6) + C(9 + 3)$$

$$1693 := 1 - T(F(6)) + C(9 + 3)$$

$$1693 := F(1 + 6) + 9!/C(3!)$$

$$1693 := Q(1 + Q(6)) + Q(9 + Q(3))$$

$$1693 := Q(1 + Q(6)) + Q(\sqrt{9} \times 3!)$$

$$1693 := T(1 + T(6)) + T(\sqrt{9})! + T(3)!$$

$$1693 := T(\sqrt{C(16)}) - 9 - T(C(3))$$

$$1694 := (1 + F(F(6))) \times (Q(9) - 4)$$

$$1694 := (1 + T(6)) \times (Q(9) - 4)$$

$$1694 := (1 - C(6) - Q(Q(9))) \times (-1/4)$$

$$1694 := -1 - 6! + T(T(9) + 4!)$$

$$1694 := -F(1 + F(6)) + C(4 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$1694 := -T(16) + T(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(4))$$

$$1694 := -T(F(1 + 6)) + T(F(9)) \times F(4)$$

$$1695 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{9} + T(5)$$

$$1695 := (-1 + T(F(6))) \times T(9) + 5!$$

$$1695 := (-1 + T(F(6))) \times T(9) + T(T(5))$$

$$1695 := -6! + T(T(T(9)))/T(5)$$

$$1695 := Q(Q(1 + 6)) - Q(9) - Q(Q(5))$$

$$1696 := (-1 + C(6) - \sqrt{9}) \times F(6)$$

$$1696 := (F(F(1 + 6)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times F(6)$$

$$1696 := (F(F(6)) - 1)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1696 := (T(-1 + T(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(6)$$

$$1696 := 1 + T(69) - 6!$$

$$1696 := 1 + T(T(F(6))) + (T(T(9)) - 6)$$

$$1696 := 16 + 9!/C(6)$$

$$1696 := Q((-1 + 6)!/(\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1697 := 16 - ((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1697 := 16 + Q(F(9) + 7)$$

$$1697 := 1 - F(6) \times (F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$1697 := 1 - F(6) \times (T(T(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7)))$$

$$1697 := C(T(\sqrt{16})) / (-F(\sqrt{9})) + C(F(7))$$

$$1697 := Q(-1 + 6) - C(9) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1697 := T(1 + T(6)) + Q(T(9) - 7)$$

$$1698 := (1 + Q(F(6))) \times F(9) - C(8)$$

$$1698 := -(T(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}) - T(T(9)) - T(T(8)))$$

$$1698 := -1 + T(T(6) + T(9)) - C(8)$$

$$1698 := -1 - C(F(6)) + T(T(9) + F(8))$$

$$1698 := F(1 + 6) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - C(F(8)))$$

$$1698 := F(16) + T(9) + T(T(8))$$

$$1698 := -F(6) \times Q(F(9)) + F(F(8))$$

$$1698 := -Q(Q(1 + 6)) + \sqrt{9} + Q(Q(8))$$

$$1698 := Q(Q(1 + 6)) - T(-8 + T(9))$$

$$1699 := (1 + Q(6)) \times T(9) + F(9)$$

$$1699 := (1 + T(F(6))) \times T(9) + F(9)$$

$$1699 := -(-1 - T(F(6))) \times T(9) + F(9)$$

$$1699 := 1 + T(6) \times Q(9) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1699 := F(16) - F((\sqrt{9}!)) + ((\sqrt{9}!!))$$

$$1699 := F(F(6)) \times Q(9) - F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1699 := Q(Q(1 + 6)) - C(9) + C(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1699 := T(\sqrt{C(16)}) - T(C(\sqrt{9})) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1700 := (1 + Q(F(7))) \times T(Q(0! + 0!))$$

$$1700 := (Q(7) + 1) \times F(Q(F(Q(0! + 0!))))$$

$$1700 := 17 \times Q(T(Q(0! + 0!)))$$

$$1701 := C(-1 + F(7)) - C(F(Q(0! + 1)))$$

$$1701 := C(-1 + F(7)) - C(T(0! + 1))$$

$$1701 := F(1 + 7) \times Q(Q(F(Q(0! + 1))))$$

$$1701 := F(1 + 7) \times Q(Q(T(0! + 1)))$$

$$1701 := T(-1 + 7) \times Q(Q(T(0! + 1)))$$

$$1702 := 1 + C(F(7) - 0!) - C(F(Q(2)))$$

$$1702 := 1 + C(F(7) - 0!) - C(T(2))$$

$$1702 := 1 + F(7 + 0!) \times Q(Q(F(Q(2))))$$

$$1702 := 1 + T(7 - 0!) \times Q(Q(T(2)))$$

$$1702 := T(1 + F(7)) + F(0! + Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1702 := -T(-1 + T(7)) + T(C(0! + T(2)))$$

$$1702 := T(Q(1 + 7)) - T(C(T(2)))$$

$$1703 := -1 + \sqrt{7! + 0!} \times Q(F(3))!$$

$$1703 := 1 + T(T(7)) + Q(Q(T(3)))$$

$$1703 := C(-1 + F(7)) - Q(-0! + 3!)$$

$$1703 := -F(1 + F(7)) + T(C(3 + 0!))$$

$$1703 := -F(F(7)) + Q(-0! + T(Q(3)))$$

$$1703 := T(Q(1 + 7)) + 0! - T(C(3))$$

$$1704 := (1 + 70) \times 4!$$

$$1705 := (-1 + C(7) - 0!) \times 5$$

$$1706 := -1 + C(F(7) - 0!) - F(F(6))$$

$$1706 := C(-1 + F(7)) - 0! - T(6)$$

$$1707 := C(-1 + F(7)) - F(0! + 7)$$

$$1708 := -1 + T(Q(7)) + Q(0! + F(8))$$

$$1708 := -1 + T(Q(7)) + Q(0! + T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1708 := C(-1 + F(7)) + 0! - F(8)$$

$$1709 := -1 - T(T(7)) + Q(0! + T(9))$$

$$1709 := C(1 + F(7)) - T(T(9))$$

$$1710 := 1 + Q(F(7)) + T(T(10))$$

$$1710 := -1 + T(Q(7) + Q(T(0! + 1)))$$

$$1711 := T((1 + T(7)) \times (1 + 1))$$

$$1711 := T(-(-1 - T(7)) \times (1 + 1))$$

$$1712 := 1 + T((1 + T(7)) \times 2)$$

$$1712 := 1 + T(Q(7) + Q(1 + 2))$$

$$1712 := C(-1 + F(7)) - Q(Q(2))$$

$$1713 := 1 + C(7) + Q(1 + Q(3!))$$

$$1713 := 1 + C(7) + Q(1 + Q(T(3)))$$

$$1713 := C(-1 + F(7)) - T(-1 + T(3))$$

$$1714 := -1 + C(7) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$1714 := -1 + Q(7) \times (1 + F(Q(F(4))))$$

$$1714 := -1 + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} \times Q(1 + T(F(4)))$$

$$1714 := -1 + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} \times Q(1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$1715 := (-C(7)) \times (-5)$$

$$1715 := -1 + F(7)!/T(-1 + 5)!$$

$$1716 := 1 + Q(7) \times (-1 + Q(6))$$

$$1716 := 1 - C(7) \times (1 - 6)$$

$$1716 := T(-1 + F(7)) \times (1 + T(6))$$

$$1717 := 1 - Q(T(7)) + Q(Q(7) + 1)$$

$$1718 := -1 + 7! - T(Q(1 + 8))$$

$$1719 := C(-1 + F(7)) - 9$$

$$1719 := T(Q(1 + 7)) - Q(19)$$

$$1720 := (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 0$$

$$1720 := (1 + C(7)) \times (Q(2) + 0!)$$

$$1720 := (1 + C(7)) \times (T(T(2)) - 0!)$$

$$1720 := 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 0$$

$$1720 := C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 0$$

$$1720 := Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 0$$

$$1721 := (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 1$$

$$1721 := 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 1$$

$$1721 := 1 + Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(2 + 1)))$$

$$1721 := C(-1 + F(7)) + (1 - C(2))$$

$$1721 := C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 1$$

$$1721 := Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 1$$

$$1722 := (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 2$$

$$1722 := (-1 + F(7))^{T(2)} - T(T(2))$$

$$1722 := (1 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(2)) - T(T(2))!$$

$$1722 := (Q(17) - 2) \times F(Q(2))!$$

$$1722 := (Q(17) - 2) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1722 := 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 2$$

$$1722 := 1 - 7 + C(C(2) + Q(2))$$

$$1722 := 2 \times T(-1 + 7 \times T(T(2)))$$

$$1722 := C(-1 + F(7)) + (2 - C(2))$$

$$1722 := C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 2$$

$$1722 := C(-2 \times (1 - 7)) - T(T(2))$$

$$1722 := F(17) + C(C(2) - T(2))$$

$$1722 := F(17) + C(F(2) + Q(2))$$

$$1722 := Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 2$$

$$1723 := (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 3$$

$$1723 := (-1 + 7)! + F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(3)))$$

$$1723 := (1 + T(Q(7))) \times 2 - C(Q(3))$$

$$1723 := 1 + (-C(7) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-3)$$

$$1723 := 1 + (T(F(7)) - Q(T(2))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1723 &:= 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 3 \\
 1723 &:= 1 - Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(C(2))) + C(3) \\
 1723 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - (2 + 3) \\
 1723 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 3 \\
 1723 &:= F(17) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \\
 1723 &:= Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 3 \\
 1723 &:= T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2))) + Q(Q(T(3))) \\
 \\
 1724 &:= (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 4 \\
 1724 &:= (-1 + F(7))^{T(2)} - 4 \\
 1724 &:= 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 4 \\
 1724 &:= -1 + Q(Q(7)) - Q(2 + 4!) \\
 1724 &:= -1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4!)))) \\
 1724 &:= -1 - 7! + F(Q(2) + Q(4)) \\
 1724 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 4 \\
 1724 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - \sqrt{2^4} \\
 1724 &:= C(-2 \times (1 - 7)) - 4 \\
 1724 &:= Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 4 \\
 1724 &:= \sqrt{1 + 7!} + T(2 + T(T(4))) \\
 \\
 1725 &:= (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 5 \\
 1725 &:= (-1 + C(7) + T(2)) \times 5 \\
 1725 &:= (-C(7) - 2) \times (-5) \\
 1725 &:= (\sqrt{1 + 7!} - 2) \times Q(5) \\
 1725 &:= 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 5 \\
 1725 &:= -7! + F(5 \times Q(2)) \\
 1725 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 5 \\
 1725 &:= F(17) + C(2) + 5! \\
 1725 &:= Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 5 \\
 1725 &:= -T(1 + F(7)) + T(2) \times F(T(5)) \\
 \\
 1726 &:= (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 6 \\
 1726 &:= 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 6 \\
 1726 &:= 1 + Q(Q(7)) - Q(26)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1726 &:= 1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) \\
 1726 &:= 1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + T(6)) \\
 1726 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 6 \\
 1726 &:= Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 6 \\
 \\
 1727 &:= (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 7 \\
 1727 &:= 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 7 \\
 1727 &:= -1 + C(7 - 2 + 7) \\
 1727 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 7 \\
 1727 &:= Q(17) \times F(Q(2))! - 7 \\
 1727 &:= Q(17) \times T(T(2)) - 7 \\
 1727 &:= Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 7 \\
 \\
 1728 &:= (1 + 2 \times F(7)) \times Q(8) \\
 1728 &:= (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 8 \\
 1728 &:= (-1 + 7 \times Q(2)) \times Q(8) \\
 1728 &:= (-1 + F(7))^{F(\sqrt{2 \times 8})} \\
 1728 &:= (-1 + T(7)) \times F(2) \times Q(8) \\
 1728 &:= (1 + T(7) - 2) \times Q(8) \\
 1728 &:= -(1 - 7^2) \times T(8) \\
 1728 &:= 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 8 \\
 1728 &:= C((1/2) \times (1 + 7) + 8) \\
 1728 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 8 \\
 1728 &:= Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 8 \\
 \\
 1729 &:= (-1 + 7)! + C(T(Q(2))) + 9 \\
 1729 &:= 1 + (F(7) - F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1729 &:= 1 + 7! - T(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 9 \\
 1729 &:= 1 + Q(72)/\sqrt{9} \\
 1729 &:= 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9) \\
 1729 &:= C(1 + 7 + 2) + C(9) \\
 1729 &:= C(-1 + F(7)) - C(2) + 9 \\
 1729 &:= Q(T(F(7))) - Q(Q(Q(T(2)))) + 9 \\
 1729 &:= T(-1 + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(F(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1730 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 0$$

$$1730 := T(1 + T(7)) + Q(Q(T(3))) - 0!$$

$$1731 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 1$$

$$1731 := T(1 + T(7)) + Q(Q(T(3)))$$

$$1732 := (-1 + F(7))^3 + Q(2)$$

$$1732 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 2$$

$$1732 := C(F(7)) - T(C(3) + T(2))$$

$$1732 := Q(1 + 7) \times C(3) + Q(2)$$

$$1732 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - 3 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1732 := Q(17) \times 3! - 2$$

$$1732 := Q(17) \times T(3) - 2$$

$$1732 := T((1 + T(7)) \times F(3)) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$1733 := 1 + C(F(7)) - T(3 + C(3))$$

$$1733 := 1 + T(Q(7) + Q(3)) + T(T(3))$$

$$1733 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 3$$

$$1733 := F(17) + T(F(3) \times F(T(3)))$$

$$1733 := Q(17) \times 3! - F(F(3))$$

$$1734 := -(1 - 7) + C(3 \times 4)$$

$$1734 := -1 + (1/3) \times 7! + T(T(4))$$

$$1734 := 17^{F(3)} \times F(4)!$$

$$1734 := 17^{F(3)} \times T(F(4))$$

$$1734 := 3 \times Q(17) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1734 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 4$$

$$1734 := Q(-1 + Q(7)) + 3! - Q(4!)$$

$$1734 := Q(17) \times F(3) \times F(4)$$

$$1735 := -1 + T(T(7)) + T(3)! + F(T(5))$$

$$1735 := -5 \times (-1 - C(7) - 3)$$

$$1735 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 5$$

$$1735 := Q(Q(7)) - T(T(3 + 5))$$

$$1736 := (-1 + F(7))^3 + F(6)$$

$$1736 := 1 + 7 + C(3! + 6)$$

$$1736 := 1 + 7 + C(T(3) + 6)$$

$$1736 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 6$$

$$1736 := -Q(17) + Q(Q(3) + Q(6))$$

$$1736 := -Q(17) + Q(T(3 + 6))$$

$$1737 := C(1 + 7 + 3) + T(T(7))$$

$$1737 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 7$$

$$1737 := F(17) + T(T(T(3))) - T(F(7))$$

$$1737 := Q(1 + F(7)) \times F(3!) + Q(F(7))$$

$$1737 := Q(-1 + Q(7)) - 7 \times Q(Q(3))$$

$$1737 := Q(T(1 + 7)) + Q(3 \times 7)$$

$$1738 := 1 + T(T(7)) + C(3 + 8)$$

$$1738 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 8$$

$$1738 := Q(Q(-1 + 7)) + F(F(3)) + Q(F(8))$$

$$1738 := -T(17) + T(-3 + Q(8))$$

$$1738 := T(T(7)) + F(3) \times T(T(8))$$

$$1739 := 1 + T(T(7)) + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1739 := 1 + T(T(7) + Q(3)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1739 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(3) + 9$$

$$1739 := Q(F(1 + 7)) + Q(Q(3!)) + F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1740 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 0$$

$$1741 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(F(4)! + 1)$$

$$1741 := Q(-1 + F(7)) + F(1 + Q(4))$$

$$1741 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 1$$

$$1742 := 1 + F(7) + C(4 + C(2))$$

$$1742 := 1 + F(7) + C(F(4) \times Q(2))$$

$$1742 := 1 + F(7) + Q(4!) \times F(Q(2))$$

$$1742 := 1 + T(Q(7)) + 4 + C(C(2))$$

$$1742 := -1 - C(7) + T(C(4)) + T(T(2))$$

$$1742 := F(17) + T(Q(4)) + Q(T(2))$$

$$1742 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 2$$

$$1743 := (-1 + T(7) \times F(4)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$1743 := (T(7) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$1743 := -1 + Q(Q(7)) - Q(4!) - Q(Q(3))$$

$$1743 := C(-1 + F(7)) + 4! - Q(3)$$

$$1743 := C(-1 + F(7)) + T(\sqrt{4} + 3)$$

$$1743 := C(-1 + F(7)) - F(4)! + F(C(F(3)))$$

$$1743 := Q(-1 + 7) + F(Q(4)) + 3!!$$

$$1743 := Q(-1 + Q(7)) - T(4! + Q(3))$$

$$1743 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 3$$

$$1744 := (1 + 7)!/4! + C(4)$$

$$1744 := (-1 + 7)! + Q(Q(4) + Q(4))$$

$$1744 := (-1 + 7)! + \sqrt{4}^{T(4)}$$

$$1744 := (-1 + F(7))^{F(4)} + Q(4)$$

$$1744 := (C(-1 + 7) + \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$1744 := (T(1 + T(7)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4$$

$$1744 := 7!/F(4) + C(4)$$

$$1744 := C(1 + 7 + 4) + Q(4)$$

$$1744 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 4$$

$$1745 := (-1 + T(T(7))) \times 4 + C(5)$$

$$1745 := (C(7) + F(4!)) \times 5$$

$$1745 := 1 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!)) - 5!$$

$$1745 := 1 + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!)) - 5!$$

$$1745 := 17 + C(\sqrt{4! + 5!})$$

$$1745 := C(-1 + F(7)) + \sqrt{4} + T(5)$$

$$1745 := Q(1 + 7) + Q(Q(4) + Q(5))$$

$$1745 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 5$$

$$1746 := (-1 + C(7)) \times F(4) + 6!$$

$$1746 := (Q(17) + \sqrt{4}) \times 6$$

$$1746 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 6$$

$$1746 := T(17) \times T(4) + C(6)$$

$$1747 := (1 + F(F(7))) \times F(4)! + C(7)$$

$$1747 := (1 + F(F(7))) \times T(F(4)) + C(7)$$

$$1747 := Q(17) \times F(4)! + F(7)$$

$$1747 := T(1 + 7) \times F(T(4)) - F(F(7))$$

$$1747 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 7$$

$$1747 := T(-1 + T(7)) + Q(4! + F(7))$$

$$1747 := T(Q(1 + 7)) + T(4) - C(7)$$

$$1748 := (1 + T(F(7))) \times (F(T(4)) - T(8))$$

$$1748 := -(1 + T(F(7))) \times (\sqrt{4} - F(8))$$

$$1748 := -1 + C(F(7)) + C(4) - C(8)$$

$$1748 := 1 + T(Q(7)) + T(4) + C(8)$$

$$1748 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 8$$

$$1749 := (-1 + 7)! - T(F(4)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1749 := (-1 + F(7))^{F(4)} + F(F((\sqrt{9}!))$$

$$1749 := (7 + Q(4!)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1749 := (\sqrt{1 + 7!} + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1749 := F(1 + 7) + C(F(4) + 9)$$

$$1749 := \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times 4! + T(9)$$

$$1749 := T(-(1 - 7)) + C(4 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$1749 := -T(1 + 7) + F(4) \times T(F(9))$$

$$1749 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 9$$

$$1750 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$1750 := \sqrt{T(Q(7))} \times Q(50)$$

$$1751 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$1751 := T(-1 + \sqrt{T(Q(7))}) + Q(F(Q(F(5 - 1))))$$

$$1752 := (1 + C(7) - C(5)) \times C(2)$$

$$1752 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$1752 := (-1 + Q(7) + Q(5)) \times Q(2)!$$

$$1752 := -T(-1 + F(7)) + F(T(5)) \times T(2)$$

$$1752 := -T(-1 + F(7)) + T((1/2) \times 5!)$$

$$1752 := T(-1 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(5) - F(2))$$

$$1753 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$1753 := F(17) + 5! + Q(3!)$$

$$1753 := F(17) + 5! + T(F(T(3)))$$

$$1753 := F(17) + T(T(5)) + T(F(T(3)))$$

$$1753 := Q(7 + Q(5)) + C(Q(3))$$

$$1753 := T(17) + Q((1/3) \times 5!)$$

$$1754 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$1754 := -1 + C(7 + 5) + C(T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$1754 := -1 + Q(7!/5!) - Q(F(4))$$

$$1754 := T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(5) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$1755 := (-(1 + 7) + C(5)) \times T(5)$$

$$1755 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$1755 := 5 \times T(F(1 + 7) + 5)$$

$$1755 := 5 \times T(T(-1 + 7) + 5)$$

$$1755 := F(7) \times (5! + T(5))$$

$$1755 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - 5! - Q(Q(5))$$

$$1755 := T(Q(1 + 7)) - T(5 \times 5)$$

$$1756 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$1756 := (1 + T(F(7))) \times 5 + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1756 := (-1 - C(7)) \times (-5) + Q(6)$$

$$1756 := 1 + Q(T(7)) - T(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1756 := Q(17 + Q(5)) - F(6)$$

$$1756 := T(T(T(-1^7 + 5))) + C(6)$$

$$1757 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$1757 := 1 + T(7) + C(5 + 7)$$

$$1757 := -1 - T(F(7)) + Q(T(5) + T(7))$$

$$1757 := Q(17 + Q(5)) - 7$$

$$1758 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$1758 := -1 + C(7) + 5! + Q(T(8))$$

$$1758 := 1 - F(7) + T(-5 + Q(8))$$

$$1758 := F(17) + C(5) + T(8)$$

$$1758 := Q(17 + Q(5)) - \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1758 := T(1 + T(F(7))) - 5! \times F(8)$$

$$1758 := T(1 + T(F(7))) - T(T(5)) \times F(8)$$

$$1759 := (-1) + (5 \times C(7) + T(9))$$

$$1759 := (1 + F(7)) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$1759 := -1 + 5 \times F(F(7)) + T(F(9))$$

$$1759 := 1 + Q(7!/5!) - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1759 := -\sqrt{1 + 7!} + T(T(5) + T(9))$$

$$1759 := T(Q(7) + 1) + Q(Q(5) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1762 := -1 + Q(7 \times 6) - F(2)$$

$$1762 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(F(6) + F(2))$$

$$1762 := C(F(7)) - T(T(6) + C(2))$$

$$1762 := Q(7 \times 6) - 2$$

$$1762 := -T(1 + T(7)) + C(T(6) - C(2))$$

$$1763 := -1 + (7 \times 6)^{F(3)}$$

$$1763 := -1 + 6 \times Q(7) \times 3!$$

$$1763 := -1 + 63 \times T(7)$$

$$1763 := 1 + Q(7 \times 6) - F(3)$$

$$1764 := (7 \times 6)^{F(F(4))}$$

$$1764 := 4 \times F(1 + 7) \times T(6)$$

$$1764 := 4 \times T(-1 + 7) \times T(6)$$

$$1764 := Q(7) \times \sqrt{6^4}$$

$$1764 := Q(Q(1 + 7) - 6 - Q(4))$$

$$1764 := \sqrt{(7 \times 6)^4}$$

$$1764 := T(7) \times T(6) \times F(4)$$

$$1765 := 1 + Q(7) \times (T(6) + T(5))$$

$$1765 := 1 + Q(7 \times 6! / 5!)$$

$$1765 := 1 + \sqrt{7! \times C(T(6)) / T(5)}$$

$$1765 := T(1 + T(7)) + 6! + F(T(5))$$

$$1766 := 1 + C(F(7)) - (C(6) + C(6))$$

$$1766 := 1 + T(7) + Q(T(6)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1766 := 1 + T(T(F(7)) - T(6)) - 6!$$

$$1766 := -1 - Q(F(7)) + Q(F(6) + Q(6))$$

$$1766 := F(17) + Q(T(6) - F(6))$$

$$1766 := T(1 + T(7)) + C(T(T(6)) / T(6))$$

$$1767 := -F(-1 + F(7)) + T(6) \times T(F(7))$$

$$1767 := Q(Q(7) + 1) - 6! - F(7)$$

$$1768 := 1 - Q(F(7)) + Q(Q(6) + 8)$$

$$1768 := F(7) \times T(F(6) + 8)$$

$$1769 := -1 + Q(7 \times 6) + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1769 := 1 + Q(Q(7) - 6) - Q(9)$$

$$1769 := -1 + T(-7 + T(6) + T(9))$$

$$1769 := F(F(7)) + C(F(6)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1769 := Q(F(7)) + Q(F(9) + 6)$$

$$1770 := T((-T(T(7))) \times (-1/7) + 0!)$$

$$1770 := T(1 + T(T(7)) / 7) + 0$$

$$1770 := T(\sqrt{1 + 7!} - F(7) + 0!)$$

$$1771 := -1 - Q(T(7)) + T(71)$$

$$1771 := T(1 + T(T(7)) / 7) + 1$$

$$1772 := -1 + F(F(7)) + T(F(F(7) - T(2)))$$

$$1772 := -1 + Q(Q(7) - 7) + Q(F(Q(2)))$$

$$1772 := -1 + Q(Q(7) - 7) + Q(T(2))$$

$$1772 := 1 + T(F(7)) + 7! / T(2)$$

$$1772 := C(1 + 7) + 7! / Q(2)$$

$$1772 := T(1 + 7) \times Q(7) + C(2)$$

$$1772 := T(1 + T(T(7)) / 7) + 2$$

$$1772 := T(\sqrt{1 + 7!}) - T(7)^2$$

$$1773 := (1 + Q(7 + 7)) \times Q(3)$$

$$1773 := (-C(17) - T(T(7))) \times (-1/3)$$

$$1773 := C(-1 + F(7)) + T(7 + F(3))$$

$$1773 := F(F(7)) + T(F(7 + 3))$$

$$1773 := T(1 + T(T(7)) / 7) + 3$$

$$1774 := 1 + F(F(7)) + T(7) \times F(T(4))$$

$$1774 := 1 + Q(Q(7) - 7) + Q(F(4))$$

$$1774 := -1 + T((1/7) \times T(T(7))) + C(4)$$

$$1774 := 1 - C(7) + Q(Q(7) - F(4))$$

$$1774 := T(1 + 7) \times Q(7) + T(4)$$

$$1774 := T(1 + T(T(7)) / 7) + 4$$

$$1775 := (-1 + F(7) + C(7)) \times 5$$

$$1775 := (Q(1 + 7) + 7) \times Q(5)$$

$$1775 := T(1 + T(T(7)))/7 + 5$$

$$1776 := (Q(17) + 7) \times 6$$

$$1776 := -1 + F(7) + Q(7 \times 6)$$

$$1776 := T(-1 + T(7)) + 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$1776 := T(1 + T(T(7)))/7 + 6$$

$$1776 := T(F(7)) + C(F(7)) - C(F(6))$$

$$1777 := -1 - T(Q(7)) + T(77)$$

$$1777 := C(-1 + F(7)) + 7 \times 7$$

$$1777 := C(17) - (1/7) \times C(T(7))$$

$$1777 := C(17) - Q(Q(7) + 7)$$

$$1777 := F(17) + 7!/T(7)$$

$$1777 := F(7) + Q(Q(7) - 7)$$

$$1777 := T(1 + 7) \times Q(7) + F(7)$$

$$1777 := T(1 + T(T(7)))/7 + 7$$

$$1778 := 1 + F(7) + Q(7) \times T(8)$$

$$1778 := 17 \times T(F(7)) + T(F(8))$$

$$1778 := 7 \times (F(F(7)) + F(8))$$

$$1778 := -F(17) + C(7 + 8)$$

$$1778 := -\sqrt{1 + 7!} + Q(7 + T(8))$$

$$1778 := T(1 + T(T(7)))/7 + 8$$

$$1779 := 1 + 7 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1779 := 1 + F(7) \times T(F(7)) + T(F(9))$$

$$1779 := -1 - Q(Q(7)) + F(F(7) + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1779 := -1 - Q(Q(7)) + F(T(7) - 9)$$

$$1779 := C(-1 + F(7)) + Q(7) + F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1779 := T(1 + T(T(7)))/7 + 9$$

$$1780 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{8 + 0})!!$$

$$1780 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 0$$

$$1780 := Q(Q(-1 + 7)) + Q(F(8) + 0!)$$

$$1780 := Q(T(1 + 7)) + Q(0! + F(8))$$

$$1781 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 1$$

$$1782 := (-1 + T(7)) \times (Q(8) + 2)$$

$$1782 := (-1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2))$$

$$1782 := (-1 + T(F(7) + F(8))) \times T(2)$$

$$1782 := (Q(17) + 8) \times F(Q(2))!$$

$$1782 := -1 - F(F(7)) + T(F(8) \times T(2))$$

$$1782 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 2$$

$$1783 := (-F(F(7))) \times (-8) - Q(Q(3))$$

$$1783 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(F(3) + 8)$$

$$1783 := C(-1 + F(7)) + Q(8) - Q(3)$$

$$1783 := C(-1 + F(7)) + T(8 + F(3))$$

$$1783 := C(7) + (\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(3)!$$

$$1783 := -F(F(7)) + T(3 \times F(8))$$

$$1783 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 3$$

$$1783 := -Q(-1 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(8)) - Q(3)$$

$$1783 := Q(-1 + Q(7)) - C(8) - Q(3)$$

$$1783 := T(7) \times Q(8) - Q(3)$$

$$1784 := (-1 + 8 \times T(7)) \times \sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$1784 := -(Q(17) - C(8)) \times \sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$1784 := (Q(7) + 1) \times T(8) - Q(4)$$

$$1784 := -1 + T(F(7) + F(8)) \times F(4)$$

$$1784 := -1 + T(T(7) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1784 := 1 - F(F(7)) + T(F(8) \times F(4))$$

$$1784 := C(-1 + F(7)) - 8 + C(4)$$

$$1784 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 4$$

$$1784 := -Q(-1 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(8)) - F(F(4)!)$$

$$1785 := (-1 + T(7 + 8)) \times T(5)$$

$$1785 := 1 + Q(Q(7)) + 8 - Q(Q(5))$$

$$1785 := 85 \times F(1 + 7)$$

$$1785 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 5$$

$$1786 := 1 + (T(F(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(6)$$

$$1786 := C(-1 + F(7)) + Q(8) - 6$$

$$1786 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 6$$

$$1786 := -Q(-1 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(8)) - 6$$

$$1786 := Q(-1 + Q(7)) - C(8) - 6$$

$$1786 := Q(7) + Q(F(8)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1786 := T(7) \times Q(8) - 6$$

$$1786 := T(T(1 + 7)) + 8!/T(F(6))$$

$$1787 := (1 + Q(7)) \times T(8) - F(7)$$

$$1787 := 1 + T(Q(7)) + C(8) + Q(7)$$

$$1787 := F(17) + F(8) + Q(F(7))$$

$$1787 := F(17) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + F(7)$$

$$1787 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 7$$

$$1787 := Q(1 + T(7)) + T(7 + T(8))$$

$$1787 := Q(17 + F(8)) + C(7)$$

$$1788 := (1 + F(F(7)) + Q(8)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1788 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 8$$

$$1789 := F(17) + Q(8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1789 := Q(1 + Q(7)) - (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 9$$

$$1789 := -Q(-1 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(8)) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1789 := Q(-1 + Q(7)) - C(8) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1789 := T(7) \times Q(8) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1790 := -1 + C(F(7)) - T(C(\sqrt{9}) + 0!)$$

$$1790 := -1 + Q(Q(7)) - F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) - 0!$$

$$1790 := -1 - F(F(7)) + Q(T(9)) - 0!$$

$$1791 := -1 + 7 \times Q(Q(\sqrt{9} + 1))$$

$$1791 := -1 + T(7) \times C(\sqrt{9} + 1)$$

$$1791 := -1 + T(7) \times Q(9 - 1)$$

$$1792 := -(-1 + 7) - C((\sqrt{9})!) \times C(2)$$

$$1792 := 1 + 7! - Q(Q(9) - Q(2)!)$$

$$1792 := 2 \times (1 + 7)!/T(9)$$

$$1792 := 7 + T(F(9)) \times T(2)$$

$$1792 := C(-1 + F(7)) + C(F(2) + \sqrt{9})$$

$$1792 := -F(F(7)) + T(9)^2$$

$$1792 := Q(1 + 7) \times T(9 - 2)$$

$$1792 := Q(1 + 7) + C(\sqrt{9} \times Q(2))$$

$$1792 := Q(Q(1 + 7)) - 9 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1792 := Q(Q(1 + 7)) - Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1792 := \sqrt{Q(7) \times F(\sqrt{9})^{Q(Q(2))}}$$

$$1792 := T(T(7)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$1793 := 1 + (F(F(7)) - 9) \times F(3!)$$

$$1793 := 1 + 7 \times Q(Q(Q((1/3) \times (\sqrt{9})!)))$$

$$1793 := 1 + 7 + 3 \times T(F(9))$$

$$1793 := 1 + C(7) + C(9) + 3!$$

$$1793 := 1 + C(7) + C(9) + T(3)!$$

$$1793 := 1 + T(7) + Q(T(9) - 3)$$

$$1793 := 1 + T(T(7)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1793 := 1 - F(F(7)) + T(9)^{F(3)}$$

$$1793 := Q(1 + F(7)) + F(F(9))/F(3)$$

$$1794 := (Q(7) + 1) \times Q((\sqrt{9})!) - F(4)!$$

$$1794 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) + C(4)$$

$$1794 := T(1 + F(7) + T(9)) + 4!$$

$$1794 := -T(F(1 + 7)) + T(9)^{F(F(4))}$$

$$1794 := T(T(1 + 7)) + T(T(9) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1795 := (1 + 7)!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - C(5)$$

$$1795 := (1 + 7)!/T(T(\sqrt{9})) - C(5)$$

$$1795 := (1 + 7)!/T(T(\sqrt{9})) - C(5)$$

$$1795 := (1 + Q(7)) \times Q((\sqrt{9})!) - 5$$

$$1795 := 1 + F(7) + Q(F(9)) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1795 := T(-1 + Q(7)) - T(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1796 := 1 - \sqrt{T(Q(7))} + T(Q(9) - T(6))$$

$$1796 := Q(1 + F(7)) + Q(F(9) + 6)$$

$$1797 := (-Q(Q(7)) + 1)/(\sqrt{9})! + C(F(7))$$

$$1797 := C(F(7)) + T(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(7))$$

$$1797 := F(-1 + F(7)) + T(-F(9) + T(F(7)))$$

$$1797 := Q(-1 + Q(7)) - \sqrt{9} \times Q(F(7))$$

$$1797 := Q(Q(7) + 1) - T(9 + T(7))$$

$$1798 := C(-1 + F(7)) + F(9) + T(8)$$

$$1798 := F(17) + \sqrt{Q(9) + 8!}$$

$$1798 := Q(17) \times (\sqrt{9})! + Q(8)$$

$$1798 := Q(17) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + Q(8)$$

$$1799 := -1 + (Q(7) - 9) \times T(9)$$

$$1799 := -1 + 7!/F(\sqrt{9}) - ((\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$1799 := 1 + F(7) + T(F(9)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1799 := -1 + Q(7 \times (\sqrt{9})!) + Q((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1799 := -1 + T((\sqrt{7+9})!) \times T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1799 := -1 - Q(7) + Q(F(9) + 9)$$

$$1799 := \sqrt{1 + 7!} + C(\sqrt{9} + 9)$$

$$1800 := T(\sqrt{1 + 8}) \times T(Q(0! + 0)!)$$

$$1801 := Q(T(8) - 1) + Q(Q(0! + 1)!)$$

$$1802 := 1 + Q(T(8) - 0!) + Q(Q(2)!)$$

$$1802 := T(1 + Q(8)) - C(-0! + C(2))$$

$$1803 := -1 + T(Q(8)) - T(-0! + Q(F(3))!)$$

$$1804 := (1 + F(8)) \times (Q(Q(F(4)))) + 0!$$

$$1804 := -T(1 + F(8) + 0!) + T(C(4))$$

$$1804 := -T(1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 0!) + T(C(4))$$

$$1804 := T(Q(8)) - T(-0! + 4!)$$

$$1805 := 5 \times Q(18 + 0!)$$

$$1805 := -T(T(-1 + 8)) + T(T(\sqrt{0! + 5!}))$$

$$1806 := -1 + C(8) - 0! + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1806 := -T(-1 + F(8)) + T(-0! + Q(F(6)))$$

$$1806 := T(-1 + Q(8)) - T(T(6) - 0!)$$

$$1807 := -1 + C(8) + Q(Q(-0! + 7))$$

$$1807 := -1 + Q(T(8)) + C(0! + 7)$$

$$1807 := -T(F(1 + 8)) + 0! + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1808 := (1 + Q(T(\sqrt{T(8)} - 0!))) \times 8$$

$$1808 := C(8) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1808 := Q(Q(-1 - 8) - 0!) + C(8)$$

$$1809 := (\sqrt{1 + 8})!! + Q(-0! + F(9))$$

$$1809 := 1 + C(8) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$1809 := -1 + Q(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + Q(0! + Q(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$1809 := -C(-1 - 8) - 0! + Q(T(9))$$

$$1809 := T(\sqrt{1+8})! + Q(-0! + F(9))$$

$$1820 := 20 \times T(F(-1+8))$$

$$1810 := 1 - C(\sqrt{T(8)}) + Q(T(Q(T(0!+1))))$$

$$1821 := -1 + T(T(8)) + Q(F(Q(2+1)))$$

$$1810 := Q(1+T(8)) + Q(F(C(0!+1)))$$

$$1821 := -Q(18) + T(Q(C(2))) + 1$$

$$1810 := Q(1+T(8)) + Q(T(T(T(0!+1))))$$

$$1821 := Q(T(-1+\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(1+T(T(Q(2))))$$

$$1811 := -Q(-1+F(8)) + T(T(11))$$

$$1822 := 1 + T(Q(8) - Q(2)) - Q(T(2))$$

$$1811 := -Q(-1+T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(11))$$

$$1822 := -C(\sqrt{1+8}) + Q(Q(C(2)) - F(C(2)))$$

$$1812 := -1 + C(\sqrt{T(8)}) + F(1+Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1822 := Q(Q(-1+8)) - Q(Q(2)!) - F(Q(2))$$

$$1812 := C(T(\sqrt{1+8})) + T(1+T(T(Q(2))))$$

$$1822 := T((-1+F(8)) \times T(2)) - C(2)$$

$$1822 := T((-1+F(8)) \times T(2)) - F(T(T(2)))$$

$$1822 := T((-1+T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(2)) - C(2)$$

$$1822 := T(-1+Q(8) - T(2)) - C(2)$$

$$1813 := (1+T(8)) \times Q(T(3)) + 1$$

$$1822 := T(Q(8) - Q(2)) - C(2)$$

$$1813 := F(18-1) + C(3!)$$

$$1813 := F(18-1) + C(T(3))$$

$$1823 := (F(F(8)) - C(2))/3!$$

$$1823 := (F(F(8)) - C(2))/T(3)$$

$$1823 := -1 - (F(F(8)) - 2)/(-T(3))$$

$$1813 := Q(-1+8) \times (1+Q(3!))$$

$$1823 := -1 + (F(F(8)) - 2)/3!$$

$$1823 := -1 + (F(F(8)) - 2)/T(3)$$

$$1814 := 1 + C(\sqrt{T(8)}) + F(1+Q(4))$$

$$1814 := -1 - T(-1+F(8)) + Q(T(Q(F(4))))$$

$$1814 := -1 - T(-1+T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + Q(T(Q(T(\sqrt{4}))))$$

$$1823 := -1 + (T(F(8)) - T(2)) \times F(T(3))$$

$$1823 := -1 + 8 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(3))))$$

$$1823 := -1 + C(8) + Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1823 := 1 + Q(T(8) + 2) + T(C(3))$$

$$1823 := -1 + T(Q(8)) - Q(Q(2))^{F(3)}$$

$$1815 := Q(1+F(8)) + C(\sqrt{1+5!})$$

$$1815 := T(-1+\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (1+5!)$$

$$1815 := T(-1+\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (1+T(T(5)))$$

$$1823 := -1 + T(Q(8) - Q(2)) - T(3)$$

$$1823 := -1 - 8 \times (T(2) - T(T(T(3))))$$

$$1819 := -(-1+8)! + C(19)$$

$$1823 := -Q(-1+8) + Q(Q(2)!) + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1819 := Q(-1+Q(8) - 1) - Q(T(9))$$

$$1824 := (1 - (1/2) \times F(F(8)))/(-F(4))$$

$$1824 := -(1/2) \times C(8) + T(C(4))$$

$$1824 := (-1 + F(F(8)) - F(2))/F(4)!$$

$$1820 := (1+Q(8)) \times (C(F(Q(2))) + 0!)$$

$$1820 := (1+Q(8)) \times T(-0! + C(2))$$

$$1820 := (1+Q(8)) \times T(T(T(2)) + 0!)$$

$$1824 := (-1 + F(F(8)) - F(2))/T(F(4))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1824 &:= (-1 + Q(F(8)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 4 \\
 1824 &:= (-1 + T(F(8)) - 2) \times \sqrt{C(4)} \\
 1824 &:= (Q(-1 + F(8)) + C(C(2))) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1824 &:= Q(Q((\sqrt{1+8}!)) + C(C(2)) + Q(4)) \\
 1824 &:= Q(T(8)) + T(2 \times Q(4)) \\
 1824 &:= T(18) + T(2 + T(T(4))) \\
 \\
 1825 &:= (1 + 2 \times T(8)) \times Q(5) \\
 1825 &:= (1 + Q(8) + C(2)) \times Q(5) \\
 1825 &:= (Q(-1 + 8) + Q(2)!) \times Q(5) \\
 1825 &:= T((-1 + F(8)) \times T(2)) - 5 \\
 1825 &:= T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(2)) - 5 \\
 1825 &:= T(-1 - T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(2) - 5 \\
 1825 &:= T(1 + T(8)) + C(C(2)) + F(T(5)) \\
 1825 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - 5 \\
 \\
 1826 &:= -1 + 8 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(6) \\
 1826 &:= 1 + Q(F(8) + 2) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1826 &:= 1 + Q(T(8)) + Q(2 + T(6)) \\
 1826 &:= -1 + T(8!/T(T(2))!) + T(T(6)) \\
 1826 &:= -1 + T(F(8)) \times C(2) - T(6) \\
 1826 &:= -1 + T(F(8)) \times F(T(T(2))) - T(6) \\
 1826 &:= -1 + T(Q(8)) - T(F(2) + T(6)) \\
 1826 &:= 18 + C(C(2)) + Q(Q(6)) \\
 1826 &:= -1 - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + C(2) \times T(T(6)) \\
 \\
 1827 &:= (1 + 8) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(7)) \\
 1827 &:= (-1 + Q(8)) \times (F(2) + T(7)) \\
 1827 &:= (T(1 + 8) + C(T(T(2)))) \times 7 \\
 1827 &:= Q(1 + Q(8)) + F(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7)) \\
 1827 &:= Q(1 + Q(8)) + T(2) - Q(Q(7)) \\
 1827 &:= T(F(8)) + T(2 \times T(7)) \\
 1827 &:= T(F(8)) + T(7 \times C(2)) \\
 1827 &:= T(T(8)) - Q(C(2)) + T(Q(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1827 &:= T(T(T(\sqrt{1+8}))) + T(2 \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 1828 &:= 1 + 8 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \\
 1828 &:= 1 + T(8!/T(T(2))!) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \\
 1828 &:= 1 + T(Q(8)) - T(F(2) + F(8)) \\
 1828 &:= 1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(C(2)!/(\sqrt{T(8)}!)) \\
 1828 &:= F(1 + 8 \times 2) + T(F(8)) \\
 1828 &:= Q(18 + Q(2)!) + Q(8) \\
 1828 &:= Q(8) + Q(2 \times F(8)) \\
 1828 &:= Q(T(1 + 8) - T(2)) + Q(8) \\
 \\
 1829 &:= 1 + Q(8) + Q(C(2) + F(9)) \\
 1829 &:= -1 + T((8 + 2) \times T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 1829 &:= -1 + T((F(8) - F(2)) \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 1829 &:= -1 + T(-8 + 2 \times F(9)) \\
 1829 &:= -1 + T(T(8) + C(2) \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 1829 &:= -1 + T(T(8 - T(2)) + T(9)) \\
 1829 &:= -Q(-1 + 8) \times Q(2) + Q(T(9)) \\
 1829 &:= Q(Q(-1 + 8)) - Q(Q(2)!) + Q(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \\
 1830 &:= \sqrt{1+8} \times F(Q(Q(F(3)))) - 0! \\
 1830 &:= T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 0 \\
 1830 &:= T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times (3 + 0)) \\
 1830 &:= T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 0 \\
 1830 &:= T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 0 \\
 1830 &:= T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!}) + 0 \\
 1830 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 0 \\
 1830 &:= T(T(8) + (3 + 0)!) \\
 1830 &:= T(T(\sqrt{1+8}) \times T(3 + 0!)) \\
 \\
 1831 &:= 1 + T(Q(8) - (3 + 1)) \\
 1831 &:= 1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(3 + 1)) \\
 1831 &:= 1 + T(T(8) + (3 + 1)!) \\
 1831 &:= T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1831 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 1$$

$$1831 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 1$$

$$1831 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!}) + 1$$

$$1831 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1$$

$$1832 := (F(-1 - 8) + C(T(3))) \times C(2)$$

$$1832 := (F(-1 + 8) + C(3!)) \times C(2)$$

$$1832 := -1 + T(T(8 + 3)) - T(C(T(2)))$$

$$1832 := -1 - Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(2))$$

$$1832 := 8 \times (T(T(T(3))) - 2)$$

$$1832 := Q(F(1 + 8)) + Q(C(3) - F(2))$$

$$1832 := Q(F(1 + 8)) + Q(F(3) + Q(2)!)$$

$$1832 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 2$$

$$1832 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 2$$

$$1832 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 2$$

$$1832 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!}) + 2$$

$$1832 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 2$$

$$1833 := (1 + F(F(8) - 3!)) \times 3$$

$$1833 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 3$$

$$1833 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 3$$

$$1833 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 3$$

$$1833 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!}) + 3$$

$$1833 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 3$$

$$1833 := T(T(8 + 3)) - T(C(3))$$

$$1834 := -(1 - 8) \times (3! + Q(Q(4)))$$

$$1834 := -1 + C(T(8 - 3)) - T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1834 := 1 - Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(Q(3)) - 4)$$

$$1834 := Q(1 + T(8)) + T(3 \times T(4))$$

$$1834 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 4$$

$$1834 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 4$$

$$1834 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 4$$

$$1834 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!}) + 4$$

$$1834 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 4$$

$$1835 := (-1 + T(8))^{F(3)} + F(T(5))$$

$$1835 := -1 + (C(F(8)) - Q(Q(3))) \times (1/5)$$

$$1835 := -1 + \sqrt{T(8)} + T(\sqrt{5 \times T(3)!})$$

$$1835 := -1 + T(Q(8) - T(3)) + C(5)$$

$$1835 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + F(3 \times 5)$$

$$1835 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 5$$

$$1835 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 5$$

$$1835 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 5$$

$$1835 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!}) + 5$$

$$1835 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 5$$

$$1835 := -T(T(T(1^8 + 3))) + C(T(5))$$

$$1836 := (1 + 8) \times (-C(3) + T(T(6)))$$

$$1836 := (T(1 + 8) + T(3)) \times Q(6)$$

$$1836 := (T(1 + 8) + T(3)) \times T(F(6))$$

$$1836 := 6 \times F(1 + 8) \times Q(3)$$

$$1836 := -Q(18) + 3 \times 6!$$

$$1836 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 6$$

$$1836 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 6$$

$$1836 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 6$$

$$1836 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!}) + 6$$

$$1836 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 6$$

$$1837 := 1 + Q(Q(8) - F(F(3!))) - F(7)$$

$$1837 := 1 + T(8) \times (F(3) + Q(7))$$

$$1837 := 1 - Q(F(8) - F(3)) + C(F(7))$$

$$1837 := -C(\sqrt{1 + 8}) + C(F(3)) \times F(F(7))$$

$$1837 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 7$$

$$1837 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 7$$

$$1837 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 7$$

$$1837 := T(-1 - T(T(8)) + T(3)!) + T(T(7))$$

$$1837 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!} + 7$$

$$1837 := T(T(1 + 8)) \times F(3) - F(F(7))$$

$$1837 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 7$$

$$1838 := (-1 - Q(F(8))) \times (-3) + C(8)$$

$$1838 := 1 - Q(F(8)) + T(3 + Q(8))$$

$$1838 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 8$$

$$1838 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 8$$

$$1838 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 8$$

$$1838 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!} + 8$$

$$1838 := T(T(1 + 8) + T(3)) + C(8)$$

$$1838 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 8$$

$$1839 := -1 + 8!/Q(3!) + ((\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$1839 := 1 + C(8) + T(T(3) + T(9))$$

$$1839 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times 3) + 9$$

$$1839 := T((-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 3) + 9$$

$$1839 := T(1 + Q(8)) - Q(3) \times F(9)$$

$$1839 := T(-1 + Q(8) - 3) + 9$$

$$1839 := T(\sqrt{(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(3)!} + 9$$

$$1839 := T(T(1 + 8)) - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9))$$

$$1839 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 9$$

$$1840 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times (Q(F(4)) - 0!)$$

$$1840 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 0$$

$$1840 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 0$$

$$1840 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 0$$

$$1840 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 0$$

$$1840 := 8 \times (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 0!)$$

$$1840 := -Q(T(8)) + Q(T(T(4))) + 0!$$

$$1841 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 1$$

$$1841 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 1$$

$$1841 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 1$$

$$1841 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 1$$

$$1841 := 1 + 8 \times (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 1)$$

$$1841 := 1 - Q(T(8)) + Q(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$1842 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 2$$

$$1842 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 2$$

$$1842 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 2$$

$$1842 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 2$$

$$1842 := -1 + C(8) + C(C(2) + F(4))$$

$$1842 := 1 - 8 + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) + Q(F(Q(2)))$$

$$1842 := 8 \times T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - T(T(2))$$

$$1842 := T(T(8)) + T(2 \times 4!)$$

$$1842 := T(T(8)) + T(Q(4) \times T(2))$$

$$1843 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 3$$

$$1843 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 3$$

$$1843 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 3$$

$$1843 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 3$$

$$1843 := -(\sqrt{1+8})! + Q(43)$$

$$1843 := 1 + 8 \times T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - T(3)$$

$$1843 := 1 + T(T(8)) + T(3 \times Q(4))$$

$$1843 := C(8) + C(F(4)) + C(F(3))$$

$$1843 := C(8) + C(\sqrt{4} + Q(3))$$

$$1843 := C(8) + C(\sqrt{C(4)} + 3)$$

$$1843 := F(-1 + 8) + T(T(4) \times T(3))$$

$$1843 := F(18) - F(4)!! - F(F(3!))$$

$$1843 := Q(1 + F(8) \times \sqrt{4}) - 3!$$

$$1844 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 4$$

$$1844 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 4$$

$$1844 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 4$$

$$1844 := (-1 + T(F(8)) \times F(F(4))) \times 4$$

$$1844 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 4$$

$$1844 := (-1 - Q(8) + F(Q(4))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1844 := (C(18) - T(4!))/T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1844 := (T(T(-1 + 8)) + T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$1844 := 1 + C(8) + C(F(4) + \sqrt{C(4)})$$

$$1844 := Q(1 + 8) \times 4! - Q(T(4))$$

$$1845 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 5$$

$$1845 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 5$$

$$1845 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 5$$

$$1845 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 5$$

$$1845 := F(-1 + F(8)) \times T(5)/F(T(4))$$

$$1845 := F(F(-1 + 8)) + F(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1845 := Q(18) + Q(C(4) - Q(5))$$

$$1845 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times F(4)) + T(5)$$

$$1845 := T(1 + 8) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))$$

$$1845 := T(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(5)))$$

$$1845 := T(F(1 + 8)) + T(4) \times C(5)$$

$$1845 := T(T(8) + 4!) + T(5)$$

$$1846 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 6$$

$$1846 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 6$$

$$1846 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 6$$

$$1846 := (1 + T(T(8))) \times \sqrt{4} + C(F(6))$$

$$1846 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 6$$

$$1846 := -1 + T(Q(8)) - \sqrt{4} - T(T(6))$$

$$1846 := F(\sqrt{1 + 8}) \times (-Q(F(6)) + F(Q(4)))$$

$$1846 := Q(F(1 + 8)) + 4! + T(Q(6))$$

$$1846 := -\sqrt{1 + 8} + Q(C(4) - T(6))$$

$$1846 := -T(1 + 8) + T(T(T(4))) + 6$$

$$1846 := T(-1 + T(8)) + C(T(4)) + C(6)$$

$$1846 := T(T(-1 + 8)) + F(F(4)) \times 6!$$

$$1846 := T(T(-1 + 8)) + \sqrt{4} \times 6!$$

$$1847 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 7$$

$$1847 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 7$$

$$1847 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 7$$

$$1847 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 7$$

$$1847 := -1 - (8 + Q(Q(4))) \times (-7)$$

$$1847 := -1 - (-T(8) + T(4!)) \times (-7)$$

$$1847 := -1 + (Q(8) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(7)$$

$$1847 := -1 + 8 \times (-\sqrt{4} + F(F(7)))$$

$$1847 := -1 + 8 \times T(7 \times F(4))$$

$$1847 := -1 + 8 \times T(T(T(-4 - 7)))$$

$$1847 := 1 + F(8) - Q(4!) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1847 := -1 - 8 \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$1847 := -1 - 8 \times (\sqrt{4} - F(F(7)))$$

$$1847 := T(1 + F(8) \times F(4)) - F(F(7))$$

$$1847 := T(\sqrt{8^4}) - F(F(7))$$

$$1847 := T(T(1 + 8)) + \sqrt{4} \times T(T(7))$$

$$1848 := ((1 + F(8)) \times 4) \times F(8)$$

$$1848 := ((-1 - F(8)) \times (-4)) \times F(8)$$

$$1848 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 8$$

$$1848 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 8$$

$$1848 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 8$$

$$1848 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 8$$

$$1848 := -(1 - 8) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 8)$$

$$1848 := 18 + T(4! + T(8))$$

$$1848 := 18 + T(T(4) \times \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1848 := T(T(T(1 + 8/4))) \times 8$$

$$1849 := (1 + F(8) \times \sqrt{4})^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$1849 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times C(\sqrt{4}) + 9$$

$$1849 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times F(T(F(4))) + 9$$

$$1849 := (-1 + T(F(8))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 9$$

$$1849 := (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times \sqrt{C(4)} + 9$$

$$1849 := (-F(8) + C(4))^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$1849 := 1 + 8 \times T(-4! + T(9))$$

$$1849 := 1 + 8 \times T(4! - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1849 := 1 + 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4 \times 9}))$$

$$1849 := F(18) + T(4!) - T(T(9))$$

$$1849 := -F(8) + F(T(4)) \times F(9)$$

$$1849 := Q(-1 - 8) + 4 \times 9$$

$$1849 := -T(F(8)) + T(4^{\sqrt{9}})$$

$$1850 := (1 + T(8)) \times 50$$

$$1850 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 0$$

$$1850 := Q(18 + Q(5)) + 0!$$

$$1851 := (-1 + C(F(8))) \times (1/5) - 1$$

$$1851 := (-1 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times (1/5) - 1$$

$$1851 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 1$$

$$1852 := (-1 + C(F(8)))/\sqrt{5^2}$$

$$1852 := (C(-1 + 8) + 5!) \times Q(2)$$

$$1852 := -1 + (C(T(8)) + C(T(5)))/C(T(2))$$

$$1852 := 1 + F(8) + F(T(5)) \times T(2)$$

$$1852 := 1 + F(8) + T((1/2) \times 5!)$$

$$1852 := 1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T((1/2) \times 5!)$$

$$1852 := 1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T((1/2) \times T(T(5)))$$

$$1852 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 2$$

$$1852 := Q(18 + Q(5)) + F(Q(2))$$

$$1852 := Q(18 + Q(5)) + T(2)$$

$$1853 := (-1 + C(F(8))) \times (1/5) + F(F(3))$$

$$1853 := (C(T(8)) + C(T(5)))/C(3)$$

$$1853 := -1 - (-8 - F(T(5))) \times 3$$

$$1853 := -1 + (8 + F(T(5))) \times 3$$

$$1853 := -1 - T(T(8)) + 5! \times T(T(3))$$

$$1853 := -1 - T(T(8)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$1853 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 3$$

$$1853 := Q(1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5) - 3)$$

$$1853 := Q(18 + Q(5)) + Q(F(3))$$

$$1853 := T(1 + F(8)) + Q((1/3) \times 5!)$$

$$1854 := (-1 + C(F(8))) \times (1/5) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$1854 := (8 + F(T(5))) \times F(4)$$

$$1854 := (Q(1 + 8) + C(5)) \times Q(F(4))$$

$$1854 := 1 + F(Q(5) - 8) + Q(Q(4))$$

$$1854 := -1 + T(Q(8)) - T(5)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1854 := -1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(5) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1854 := -1 - T(8) + T(C(5) - C(4))$$

$$1854 := -C(-1 + 8) + C(5 + \sqrt{C(4)})$$

$$1854 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 4$$

$$1854 := T(T(1 + 8) + T(5)) + 4!$$

$$1855 := 1 - F(8) + T(5) \times C(5)$$

$$1855 := 1 - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(5) \times C(5)$$

$$1855 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 5$$

$$1855 := T(T(1 + 8)) + T(Q(5) + T(5))$$

$$1856 := (-1 + F(8 + 5)) \times F(6)$$

$$1856 := (1 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times C(\sqrt{\sqrt{-5 + T(6)}})$$

$$1856 := -1 - Q(8) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1856 := 1 - T(8) + T(Q(6) + Q(5))$$

$$1856 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 6$$

$$1857 := (1 - Q(F(8))) \times (-5) - C(7)$$

$$1857 := 1 + T(F(8)) + C(5) \times F(7)$$

$$1857 := -1 + T(\sqrt{5 \times (\sqrt{T(8)})!}) + T(7)$$

$$1857 := 8 + Q(T(5) + T(7))$$

$$1857 := Q(1 + 8) - Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1857 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 7$$

$$1858 := (-1 + C(F(8))) \times (1/5) + \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1858 := (-1 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)})))/5 + \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1858 := 1 + Q(T(8)) + T(Q(5) + 8)$$

$$1858 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 8$$

$$1858 := T(1 + T(8)) + 5 \times T(F(8))$$

$$1858 := T(1 + T(8)) + 5 \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1859 := (C(-1 - 8) + C(T(5)))/F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1859 := F(18) - 5 - ((\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$1859 := F(18) - 5 - T(\sqrt{9})!$$

$$1859 := Q(-1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5)) + 9$$

$$1859 := Q(F(-1 + 8)) \times (5 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1859 := T(1 + T(8)) + Q(Q(5) + 9)$$

$$1862 := -(-1 - T(F(8))) \times F(6) + T(T(2))$$

$$1862 := F(18) - 6! - 2$$

$$1862 := F(F(-1 + 8)) \times F(6) - 2$$

$$1862 := Q(-1 + 8) \times (Q(6) + 2)$$

$$1862 := T(-1 + T(8)) + 6! + C(C(2))$$

$$1862 := -T(F(-1 + 8)) + T(62)$$

$$1862 := T(Q(8)) - C(6) - 2$$

$$1863 := (1 + F(F(8)) + T(T(6)))/T(3)$$

$$1863 := (-1 + Q(8 - 6)!) \times Q(Q(3))$$

$$1863 := (1 + T(F(8)) + F(T(6)))/T(3)$$

$$1863 := (T(18) + Q(6)) \times Q(3)$$

$$1863 := 6 \times Q(18) - Q(Q(3))$$

$$1863 := C(18) - Q(63)$$

$$1863 := F(18) - 6! - F(F(3))$$

$$1863 := F(F(-1 + 8)) \times F(6) - F(F(3))$$

$$1863 := -Q(F(8)) + Q(F(6) \times 3!)$$

$$1863 := T(6 \times (1 + 8)) + T(C(3))$$

$$1864 := (1 + T(T(8) - 6)) \times 4$$

$$1864 := -8 + Q(Q(6)) + Q(4!)$$

$$1864 := F(1 + 8) + T(6 \times T(4))$$

$$1864 := F(18) - (6 - F(4))!!$$

$$1864 := F(18) - (F(6) - \sqrt{4})!$$

$$1864 := F(F(-1 + 8)) \times (6 + F(F(4)))$$

$$1864 := F(F(-1 + 8)) \times \sqrt{64}$$

$$1864 := Q(18) + T(T(6 + 4))$$

$$1864 := T(Q(8)) - \sqrt{C(6)^{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$1865 := (C(F(8)) + Q(F(6))) \times (1/5)$$

$$1865 := 1 + 8 \times F(F(6) + 5)$$

$$1865 := -1 + T(8) + T(\sqrt{5 \times 6!})$$

$$1865 := 1 + T(Q(8)) - C(6!/5!)$$

$$1865 := Q(1 + T(8)) + T(Q(6) - 5)$$

$$1866 := 18 + T(T(6)) \times F(6)$$

$$1866 := 1 - Q(86) + C(F(F(6)))$$

$$1866 := 1 - Q(86) + C(T(6))$$

$$1866 := Q(Q(F(\sqrt{1+8})))! - 6 + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1866 := T(1 + Q(8)) - 6! + Q(T(6))$$

$$1867 := -1 + T(T(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})))/T(6)) - C(7)$$

$$1867 := 18 + Q(-6 + Q(7))$$

$$1867 := \sqrt{1+8} + F(6) \times F(F(7))$$

$$1868 := -1 + T(F(8)) \times F(6) + F(8)$$

$$1868 := -1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 8 \times T(T(6))$$

$$1868 := Q(-1 + Q(8)) - T(6) - T(Q(8))$$

$$1868 := Q(F(1 + 8)) + 6! - 8$$

$$1869 := -1 + T(Q(8)) - C(6) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1869 := 8 \times T(T(6)) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1869 := F(8) \times (F(6) + Q(9))$$

$$1869 := F(8) \times F(F(6) + \sqrt{9})$$

$$1869 := -T(-1 + F(8)) + 9 \times T(T(6))$$

$$1869 := T(1 + Q(8)) - T(T(6)) - T(9)$$

$$1869 := T(T(8) + T(6)) + C(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1870 := T(F(1 + 8)) + T(Q(7) + 0!)$$

$$1870 := -T(T(8) - 1) + Q(Q(7) + 0!)$$

$$1871 := -1 + 8 \times (F(F(7)) + 1)$$

$$1872 := (T(1 + 8) + 7) \times T(C(2))$$

$$1872 := 18 \times F(7) \times C(2)$$

$$1872 := -C(1 + 8) + Q(Q(7) + 2)$$

$$1872 := F(-1 + 8) \times F(F(7) - F(2))$$

$$1872 := F(-1 + 8) \times Q(F(7) - F(2))$$

$$1872 := Q(Q(-1 + 8)) - Q(7 + Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1872 := T(8) \times (Q(7) + T(2))$$

$$1872 := T(8) \times F(7) \times Q(2)$$

$$1873 := 1 + 8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(3)))$$

$$1873 := 1 + 8 \times F(F(7)) + C(F(3))$$

$$1873 := 1 + 8 \times F(F(7)) + F(3!)$$

$$1873 := 1 + 8 \times F(F(7)) + F(T(3))$$

$$1873 := 1 + T(8) \times (Q(7) + 3)$$

$$1873 := -Q(18) + C(7 + 3!)$$

$$1873 := -Q(18) + F(7)^3$$

$$1874 := -(1 + 8) + C(7) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1874 := 1 + T(Q(8)) - C(7) + T(Q(4))$$

$$1874 := 1 - C(8) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(4)$$

$$1874 := 1 \times 8 \times F(F(7)) + T(4)$$

$$1874 := Q(-1 + 8) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(4!)$$

$$1874 := -Q(18) + C(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$1874 := T(T(1 + 8)) + Q(T(7)) + T(T(4))$$

$$1875 := F(1 \times 8)/7 \times Q(Q(5))$$

$$1875 := (1 \times 8 + 7) \times C(5)$$

$$1875 := (F(1 + 8) + T(F(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$1875 := Q(1^8 + Q(7)) - Q(Q(5))$$

$$1875 := \sqrt{(-1 + Q(8))/7} \times Q(Q(5))$$

$$1875 := T(T(1 + 8)) + 7 \times 5!$$

$$1875 := T(T(1 + 8)) + 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$1876 := 1 + F(8) \times T(F(7)) - T(F(6))$$

$$1876 := C(\sqrt{1 + 8}) + Q(Q(7) - 6)$$

$$1876 := Q(F(8) + F(7)) + 6!$$

$$1876 := T(T(1 + 8)) + Q(-7 + Q(6))$$

$$1877 := -1 + T(T(8)) - F(7) + T(Q(7))$$

$$1877 := 8 \times F(F(7)) + F(7)$$

$$1877 := Q(T(8) + 7) + T(7)$$

$$1877 := -\sqrt{C(Q(8) + 1) - Q(7)} + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1878 := (-1 + (\sqrt{T(8)})! - T(T(7))) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$1878 := -F(8) - C(F(7)) + Q(Q(8))$$

$$1878 := Q(T(1 + 8)) - 7 \times F(8)$$

$$1878 := -T(T(1 + 8)) + Q(Q(7)) + C(8)$$

$$1879 := -1 + 8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1879 := 1 + Q(T(8)) - F(7) + T(F(9))$$

$$1879 := 1 - 7 \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + Q(T(9))$$

$$1879 := -1 - C(8) + Q(Q(7)) - 9$$

$$1879 := -Q(F(8)) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(9)$$

$$1880 := Q(1 + T(8)) + C(8) - 0!$$

$$1880 := -T(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{1+8})))) + T(Q(8) - 0!)$$

$$1881 := C(8) + Q(1 + T(8))$$

$$1881 := F(18) - T(1 + T(8))$$

$$1882 := -(1 + 8) + T(Q(8) - T(2))$$

$$1882 := 1 + C(8) + Q(F(8) + Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1882 := 1 + C(8) + Q(T(8) + F(2))$$

$$1882 := -1 + Q(Q(8) - F(8)) + F(Q(F(Q(2))))$$

$$1882 := F(1 + 8) + T(F(8)) \times F(T(T(2)))$$

$$1882 := F(18) - T(T(8)) - T(C(2))$$

$$1883 := (1 + T(F(8))) \times 8 + C(3)$$

$$1883 := -1 + T(8) + 8 \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1883 := -1 + T(8) + T(F(8)) \times F(T(3))$$

$$1883 := -1 + T(Q(8)) - Q(8 + T(3))$$

$$1883 := -1 - T(8) + 8!/T(T(3))$$

$$1883 := Q(1 + F(8) + F(8)) + F(Q(3))$$

$$1883 := Q(Q(-1 + 8)) - C(8) - 3!$$

$$1884 := -1 + Q(Q(8)) - T(Q(8) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1884 := -1 + T(8) - T(F(8)) + T(C(4))$$

$$1884 := 1 - 8 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + F(T(4)))$$

$$1884 := 1 - 8 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4)))$$

$$1884 := -1 - T(F(8)) + Q(T(8) + T(4))$$

$$1884 := Q(F(1 + 8)) + 8 + F(4)!!$$

$$1884 := T(8) + T(F(8)) \times F(T(F(4)))$$

$$1885 := (-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 5$$

$$1885 := (-C(-1 + 8) + (\sqrt{T(8)})!) \times 5$$

$$1885 := 5 \times F(1 + F(8)) - 8$$

$$1885 := Q(F(1 + 8)) + C(Q(8 - 5))$$

$$1885 := -\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(8) + Q(5))$$

$$1885 := -T(F(8)) + Q(F(8) + Q(5))$$

$$1886 := 1 + Q(Q(8) - F(8)) + Q(6)$$

$$1886 := 1 + T(8) + Q(Q(8) - T(6))$$

$$1886 := -F(1 + 8) + 8!/F(F(6))$$

$$1886 := -F(1 + 8) + 8!/T(6)$$

$$1886 := F(F(-1 + 8)) + T(T(8) + T(6))$$

$$1887 := (1 + T(8)) \times (Q(8) - F(7))$$

$$1887 := 1 + T(T(8) + F(8)) + F(F(7))$$

$$1887 := Q(1 + Q(8) - F(8)) - Q(7)$$

$$1887 := Q(8 + T(8)) - Q(7)$$

$$1887 := Q(Q((\sqrt{1+8})!)) + 8 - Q(7)$$

$$1887 := -T(18) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times C(7)$$

$$1888 := (-1 + \sqrt{T(8)} + T(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$1888 := (-1 + \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 8$$

$$1888 := (-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 8$$

$$1888 := F(Q(F(\sqrt{1+8})!)) / (-F(8)) + Q(Q(8))$$

$$1888 := T(-1 + Q(8)) - (Q(8) + Q(8))$$

$$1889 := -1 + (F(8) + F(8)) \times T(9)$$

$$1889 := -1 + (T(8) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(9)$$

$$1889 := -1 + 8! \times \sqrt{9}/Q(8)$$

$$1889 := Q(Q(-1 + 8)) - 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1890 := (-F(8)) \times (-90)$$

$$1890 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 0$$

$$1890 := 1 - C(8) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})! + 0!))$$

$$1890 := 90 \times F(8)$$

$$1890 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 0$$

$$1890 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 0$$

$$1891 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 1$$

$$1891 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 1)$$

$$1891 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 1$$

$$1891 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 1$$

$$1891 := T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1892 := (\sqrt{1+8})!! + Q(F(9)) + Q(Q(2))$$

$$1892 := 1 + T(8 + T(9) + C(2))$$

$$1892 := 1 + T(Q(8) - 9/T(2))$$

$$1892 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 2$$

$$1892 := 1 + T(T(T((1/9) \times T(8))) + T(T(2)))$$

$$1892 := Q(Q(-1 + 8)) + (\sqrt{9} - C(C(2)))$$

$$1892 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 2$$

$$1892 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 2$$

$$1893 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 3$$

$$1893 := 8!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - C(3)$$

$$1893 := 8 + Q(F(9)) + C(Q(3))$$

$$1893 := F(8) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(F(3)))!$$

$$1893 := F(\sqrt{1+8}) + T(F(9) + C(3))$$

$$1893 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 3$$

$$1893 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 3$$

$$1894 := 1 + 8!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - C(F(4))$$

$$1894 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 4$$

$$1894 := 18 + Q(F(9)) + F(4)!!$$

$$1894 := Q(F(1+8)) + C(9) + Q(F(4))$$

$$1894 := \sqrt{1+8} + T(T(9) + Q(4))$$

$$1894 := T((-1 + F(8)) \times \sqrt{9}) + C(4)$$

$$1894 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 4$$

$$1894 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 4$$

$$1895 := (-1 + 8)!/F(\sqrt{9}) - Q(Q(5))$$

$$1895 := (1 + T(T(8) - 9)) \times 5$$

$$1895 := (-1 - T(T(8) - 9)) \times (-5)$$

$$1895 := (C(-1 + 8) + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 5$$

$$1895 := 1 + Q(8) + T(T(9) + T(5))$$

$$1895 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 5$$

$$1895 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 5$$

$$1895 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 5$$

$$1896 := (C(-1 + 8) - C(\sqrt{9})) \times 6$$

$$1896 := (C(-1 + 8) - \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 6$$

$$1896 := (T(-1 + F(8)) + C(\sqrt{9})) \times F(6)$$

$$1896 := (T(F(8)) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times F(6)$$

$$1896 := -1 + F(8) + Q(F(9)) + 6!$$

$$1896 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 6$$

$$1896 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 6$$

$$1896 := T(-1 + Q(8)) - T(9 + 6)$$

$$1896 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 6$$

$$1897 := -(1 + 8)!/(\sqrt{9})!! + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1897 := (-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 7$$

$$1897 := (1 - 8 \times F(9)) \times (-7)$$

$$1897 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 7$$

$$1897 := -1 - C(8) + 9 + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1897 := Q(1 + T(8)) + T(Q(9) - Q(7))$$

$$1897 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 7$$

$$1897 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 7$$

$$1898 := -(1 - 8) + T(F(9)) + Q(T(8))$$

$$1898 := -1 + (Q(F(8)) - F((\sqrt{9})!))/(-F(8))$$

$$1898 := -1 + 8!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(8)$$

$$1898 := -1 + Q(Q(8)) - C(F(9) - F(8))$$

$$1898 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 8$$

$$1898 := Q(Q(-1 + 8)) + (9 - C(8))$$

$$1898 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 8$$

$$1898 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 8$$

$$1898 := T(F(8)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + C(8)$$

$$1899 := (1 + T(T(8)) - F(9)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1899 := (T(-1 + T(8)) + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1899 := -1 + (Q(F(8)) + F(9)) \times Q(F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1899 := -1 + Q(8 + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) - Q((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1899 := -1 + T(Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) + 9$$

$$1899 := 8! / F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$1899 := -C(F(-1 + 8)) + C(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$1899 := Q(F(8)) + C(9) + C(9)$$

$$1899 := Q(Q((\sqrt{1+8})!)) + \sqrt{9! + C(9)}$$

$$1899 := Q(T(1 + 8)) - T(9) - Q(9)$$

$$1899 := T(-1 + F(8)) \times 9 + 9$$

$$1899 := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 9$$

$$1899 := T(8 \times 9) - C(9)$$

$$1900 := T(19) \times T(Q(0! + 0!))$$

$$1901 := Q(19) + T(T(T(Q(0! + 1))))$$

$$1902 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - F(0! + C(2))$$

$$1902 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - F(Q(T(2)))$$

$$1902 := Q(19) + 0! + T(T(T(Q(2))))$$

$$1903 := 1 + Q(T(9) - 0!) - F(Q(3))$$

$$1904 := (-1 + ((\sqrt{9})! - 0!)) \times Q(4)$$

$$1904 := (F(1 + 9) + 0!) \times F(Q(F(4)))$$

$$1904 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - (0! + 4)!$$

$$1904 := F(9) \times (0! + F(T(4)))$$

$$1905 := -1 + Q(T(9)) + 0! - 5!$$

$$1905 := 1 - Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times (0! - 5!)$$

$$1906 := F(-1 + Q(\sqrt{9} + 0!)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1906 := Q(1 + T(9)) - T(-0! + T(6))$$

$$1907 := -1 - Q(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9}))) + 0!) + C(F(7))$$

$$1907 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - 0! - T(7)$$

$$1908 := -Q(1 + Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) + C(F(-0! + 8))$$

$$1908 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(-0! + 8)$$

$$1909 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - C(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1909 := Q(1 + T(9) + 0!) - T(Q(F(\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$1911 := -T((1 + \sqrt{9})!) + T(T(11))$$

$$1911 := T(F(1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(T(T(1 + 1)))$$

$$1912 := 1 + 91 \times F(C(2))$$

$$1912 := 1 + 91 \times F(F(F(Q(2)!))$$

$$1912 := 1 + 91 \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$1912 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - Q(2)!$$

$$1913 := Q(-1 + T(9) - 1) + C(Q(F(3)))$$

$$1913 := Q(-1 + T(9) - 1) + Q(F(T(3)))$$

$$1914 := -1 + Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(T(F(4)))$$

$$1914 := -1 + Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$1914 := -T(F(-1 + 9)) + T(1 + C(4))$$

$$1914 := -T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(1 + C(4))$$

$$1915 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(1 + 5)$$

$$1916 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + (1 - T(6))$$

$$1917 := -Q(1 + F(9 - 1)) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1917 := -Q(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 1) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$1917 := \sqrt{C(9) \times (1 + 7!)}$$

$$1917 := T(F(1 + 9)) + F(1 + F(7))$$

$$1918 := F(19 - 1) - T(T(8))$$

$$1918 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - 18$$

$$1918 := T(T(1 + 9)) + T(C(\sqrt{1 + 8}))$$

$$1919 := -1 + (9 - 1)!/T(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1919 := -1 + F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(-1 + 9)$$

$$1919 := -1 + Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times (-1 + (\sqrt{9})!)!$$

$$1919 := 1 + T(C(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(1 + 9))$$

$$1920 := (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 0$$

$$1920 := (-1 + 9)!/F(F((2 + 0)!))$$

$$1920 := (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 0$$

$$1920 := (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 0$$

$$1920 := Q(1 + \sqrt{9}) \times (Q(2) + 0)!!$$

$$1921 := (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 1$$

$$1921 := (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 1$$

$$1921 := (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 1$$

$$1921 := 1 + (1/21) \times F((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1921 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(Q(2) + 1)$$

$$1922 := (1/2) \times Q(Q((-1) + 9) - 2)$$

$$1922 := (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 2$$

$$1922 := (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 2$$

$$1922 := (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 2$$

$$1922 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - Q(2)! + T(Q(2))$$

$$1922 := -T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(2)$$

$$1923 := (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 3$$

$$1923 := (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 3$$

$$1923 := (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 3$$

$$1923 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - Q(2) - Q(3)$$

$$1923 := \sqrt{9} + C(2)!/T(T(3))$$

$$1924 := (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 4$$

$$1924 := (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 4$$

$$1924 := (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 4$$

$$1924 := (1 - C(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(2)) + T(C(4))$$

$$1924 := -1 + (F(9) + F(2)) \times F(T(4))$$

$$1924 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - 2 - T(4)$$

$$1924 := Q(1 + T(9)) - C(2) \times 4!$$

$$1924 := Q(1 + T(9)) - T(2) \times C(4)$$

$$1924 := Q(F(9)) + C(C(2)) + Q(Q(4))$$

$$1925 := (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 5$$

$$1925 := (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 5$$

$$1925 := (1 + F(9)) \times F(2 \times 5)$$

$$1925 := (1 + F(9)) \times T(2 \times 5)$$

$$1925 := (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 5$$

$$1925 := (-1 + Q(9) - T(2)) \times Q(5)$$

$$1925 := (Q(9) - Q(2)) \times Q(5)$$

$$1925 := (T(T(1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 5$$

$$1925 := T((\sqrt{9} + 1)!) \times T(T(2)) + C(5)$$

$$1926 := (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1926 &:= (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 6 \\
 1926 &:= (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 6 \\
 1926 &:= -(1 - T(\sqrt{9})!) \times T(2) - T(T(6)) \\
 1926 &:= 9 \times (-2 + C(6)) \\
 1926 &:= Q(1 + T(9)) - T(-2 + T(6)) \\
 1926 &:= T(1 + F(9)) \times T(2) + T(F(6)) \\
 \\
 1927 &:= (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 7 \\
 1927 &:= (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 7 \\
 1927 &:= (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 7 \\
 1927 &:= (-1 + T(9)) \times T(C(2)) + C(7) \\
 1927 &:= -1 + F(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (F(T(T(2)))) + F(F(7)) \\
 1927 &:= 1 + T(F(9)) + C(-2 + F(7)) \\
 1927 &:= 1 + T(F(9)) + C(Q(2) + 7) \\
 1927 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - (2 + 7) \\
 \\
 1928 &:= (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 8 \\
 1928 &:= (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 8 \\
 1928 &:= (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 8 \\
 1928 &:= (-1 + T(9))^2 - 8 \\
 \\
 1929 &:= (-1 + 9)!/F(C(2)) + 9 \\
 1929 &:= (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2))) + 9 \\
 1929 &:= (-1 + Q(9)) \times Q(2)! + 9 \\
 1929 &:= (1 + T(T(F(T(\sqrt{9})))) \times 2 + T(F(9)) \\
 1929 &:= -1 + Q(9) + Q(-2 + T(9)) \\
 \\
 1930 &:= -1 + F(Q(F(\sqrt{9})!)/Q(F(3))! - 0! \\
 1930 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 0 \\
 \\
 1931 &:= F((1 + \sqrt{9})!)/Q(F(3))! - 1 \\
 1931 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1932 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(3)} - Q(2) \\
 1932 &:= (1 + T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(C(3) - Q(2)) \\
 1932 &:= -(1 - 93) \times F(C(2)) \\
 1932 &:= 1 + (1/3) \times Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(Q(2))) \\
 1932 &:= -1 - \sqrt{9} + Q(Q(3!)) + C(2) \\
 1932 &:= 2 \times (1 + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \\
 1932 &:= F((1 + \sqrt{9})!)/(F(3) + 2)! \\
 1932 &:= Q(-1 - 9) + Q(3!) - Q(2) \\
 1932 &:= Q(1 + F(9) + Q(3)) - Q(2) \\
 1932 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 2 \\
 \\
 1933 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(3)} - 3 \\
 1933 &:= F(1 + (\sqrt{9})!) + C(F(3))!/F(C(F(3))) \\
 1933 &:= F(1 + (\sqrt{9})!) + F(3)!/F(F(3!)) \\
 1933 &:= Q(-1 - 9) + Q(3!) - 3 \\
 1933 &:= Q(1 + F(9) + Q(3)) - 3 \\
 1933 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - \sqrt{3 \times 3} \\
 1933 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 3 \\
 1933 &:= T(C(\sqrt{9} + 1)) - T(C(3)) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 \\
 1934 &:= -(1 + 9) + Q(Q(3)) \times 4! \\
 1934 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(3)} - F(F(4)) \\
 1934 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(3)} - \sqrt{4} \\
 1934 &:= (-1 - C(9)) \times (-3) - Q(Q(4)) \\
 1934 &:= -1 + 9 \times (C(3!) - F(\sqrt{4})) \\
 1934 &:= -1 + T(9) \times (C(3) + Q(4)) \\
 1934 &:= -1 + T(T(9)) + 3 \times T(4!) \\
 1934 &:= -1 + T(T(9)) + Q(3 \times T(4)) \\
 1934 &:= 9 \times C(T(3)) - T(4) \\
 1934 &:= F(1 + 9) \times F(Q(3)) + C(4) \\
 1934 &:= Q(1 + F(9) + Q(3)) - \sqrt{4} \\
 1934 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 4 \\
 \\
 1935 &:= (-1 + 9)!/T(T(3)) + T(5) \\
 1935 &:= (C(-1 + (\sqrt{9})!) - C(C(F(3)))) \times (-5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1935 &:= -1 + Q(9 + 35) & 1939 &:= Q(-1 - 9) + Q(3!) + \sqrt{9} \\
 1935 &:= -1 + T(T(9) + T(3)) + F(T(5)) & 1939 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 9 \\
 1935 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 5 & & \\
 & & 1940 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 0 \\
 1936 &:= (-1 + 3 \times Q(9)) \times F(6) & 1940 &:= Q(F(9)) + Q(C(F(4)) + 0!) \\
 1936 &:= (-1 + 9 \times C(3)) \times F(6) & & \\
 1936 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(-3+6)} & 1941 &:= 1 + Q(F(9)) + Q(C(F(4)) + 1) \\
 1936 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(\sqrt{3+6})} & 1941 &:= F(T(-1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) + C(T(4) + 1) \\
 1936 &:= 1 + T(9) \times C(3) + 6! & 1941 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 1 \\
 1936 &:= 1 - 9 + Q(3) \times C(6) & & \\
 1936 &:= C(1 + 9) + 3!! + C(6) & 1942 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(F(4))} + T(T(2)) \\
 1936 &:= Q(-1 + 9 + 36) & 1942 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{\sqrt{4}} + T(T(2)) \\
 1936 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 6 & 1942 &:= (T(T(9)) - C(4)) \times 2 \\
 & & 1942 &:= 9 \times C(F(4)!) - 2 \\
 1937 &:= 1 + Q(F(9) + 3 + 7) & 1942 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 2 \\
 1937 &:= 1 + Q(Q(9) - 37) & 1942 &:= Q(9) \times 4! - 2 \\
 1937 &:= -1 + T(T(9)) + T(7 \times T(3)) & & \\
 1937 &:= 9 \times C(3!) - 7 & 1943 &:= -1 - (-9 \times 4!) \times Q(3) \\
 1937 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 7 & 1943 &:= -1 + 4 \times Q(9) \times T(3) \\
 & & 1943 &:= -1 + 9 \times C((-4! + C(3))!) \\
 1938 &:= 1 + F(C(\sqrt{9})) - F(C(F(3))) \times C(F(8)) & 1943 &:= -1 + 9 \times C(3 \times \sqrt{4}) \\
 1938 &:= -1 + \sqrt{9} + Q(Q(3!) + 8) & 1943 &:= -1 + 9 \times F(4)!^3 \\
 1938 &:= 19 \times (Q(Q(3)) + F(8)) & 1943 &:= -1 + 9 \times T(F(4))^3 \\
 1938 &:= Q(1 + F(9)) \times F(3) - C(8) & 1943 &:= 1 + Q(9) \times 4! - F(3) \\
 1938 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) - T(3) + 8 & 1943 &:= -1 + \sqrt{9} \times 4! \times C(3) \\
 1938 &:= T(T(9)) + T(F(3) \times F(8)) & 1943 &:= -1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{T(4)}} \times F(T(3)) \\
 1938 &:= T(T(9)) + T(T(3) + T(8)) & 1943 &:= 1 + T(\sqrt{9} + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 & & 1943 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 3 \\
 1939 &:= (-1 + T(9))^{F(3)} + \sqrt{9} & 1943 &:= -Q(19) + Q(3 \times Q(4)) \\
 1939 &:= 1 + 9 \times C(3!) - (\sqrt{9})! & & \\
 1939 &:= -1 + Q(F(9) - 3!) + Q(F(9)) & 1944 &:= -(1 - 9) \times \sqrt{F(4)^{T(4)}} \\
 1939 &:= 1 + T(T(9)) + T(-3 + T(9)) & 1944 &:= -(1 - 9) + Q(44) \\
 1939 &:= 19 + F(3)!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1944 &:= 9 \times C(\sqrt{4} + 4) & 1947 &:= T(T(1 + 9)) + C(4) + C(7) \\
 1944 &:= 9 \times T(F(4))^{F(4)} \\
 1944 &:= 9^{F(F(4))} \times 4! \\
 1944 &:= C(9 \times 4)/4! & 1948 &:= 1 + C(\sqrt{9}) - (\sqrt{C(4)})!/(-F(8)) \\
 1944 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 4 & 1948 &:= 1 + C(\sqrt{9}) + (\sqrt{C(4)})!/T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \\
 1944 &:= \sqrt{9^4} \times 4! & 1948 &:= -Q(1 + 9) + 4 \times C(8) \\
 1944 &:= -T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)) & 1948 &:= -Q(1 + 9) + 8 \times Q(Q(4)) \\
 1944 &:= -T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(4))^{\sqrt{4}} & 1948 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 8 \\
 & & 1948 &:= T(-1 + C(\sqrt{9})) + F(-4 + F(8)) \\
 & & 1948 &:= T(1 + T(\sqrt{9})) + F(T(F(4)))!/F(8) \\
 1945 &:= 1 + 9 \times (T(T(T(F(4)))) - T(5)) \\
 1945 &:= 1 + 9 \times (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - T(5)) \\
 1945 &:= 1 + C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(\sqrt{4! + 5!}) \\
 1945 &:= 1 + F((\sqrt{9})!) \times F(4)^5 \\
 1945 &:= 1 + F(T(\sqrt{9})) \times F(4)^5 \\
 1945 &:= 1 - Q(9) + Q(45) \\
 1945 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 5 \\
 1945 &:= T(T(9)) \times \sqrt{4} - C(5) \\
 1945 &:= T(T(9)) + T(4!) + F(T(5)) \\
 & & 1949 &:= -1 - (\sqrt{C(9)!})/(-9 \times 4!!) \\
 & & 1949 &:= -1 + (\sqrt{9})! + 4! \times Q(9) \\
 & & 1949 &:= -1 + (T(F(9)) + F(T(4))) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 & & 1949 &:= -1 + T(\sqrt{9}) + Q(9) \times 4! \\
 & & 1949 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 9 \\
 & & 1949 &:= T(1 + C(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(4))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 & & 1949 &:= T(T(1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 1946 &:= (1 + F(9)) \times F(T(4)) + T(6) \\
 1946 &:= 1 + 9 + Q(\sqrt{C(4)}) + Q(6) \\
 1946 &:= 1 + T(T(9) + 4) + 6! \\
 1946 &:= C(19) - C(-4 + F(F(6))) \\
 1946 &:= C(19) - C(-4 + T(6)) \\
 1946 &:= Q(1 + F(9)) + F(\sqrt{4}) + 6! \\
 1946 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 6 \\
 1946 &:= T(1 + 9) + T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\
 1946 &:= T(T(1 + 9)) + T(C(4) - Q(6)) \\
 & & 1950 &:= C(-1 + C(\sqrt{9})) - C(Q(5)) - 0! \\
 & & 1950 &:= T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 0 \\
 & & 1951 &:= C(-1 + C(\sqrt{9})) - C(Q(5)) \\
 & & 1951 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 & & 1951 &:= T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 1 \\
 1947 &:= -(1/4) \times C(1 + 9) + C(F(7)) \\
 1947 &:= (-1 + F(9)) \times (T(4) + Q(7)) \\
 1947 &:= -1 + F(\sqrt{9}) \times (F(Q(4)) - F(7)) \\
 1947 &:= 1 + T(T(9) + T(4)) + T(T(7)) \\
 1947 &:= Q(-1 + T(9)) + 4 + 7 \\
 & & 1952 &:= (1 + \sqrt{9^5}) \times C(2) \\
 & & 1952 &:= -1 + T(F(9) + T(5 + 2)) \\
 & & 1952 &:= -1 + T(T(9) + T(5) + 2) \\
 & & 1952 &:= Q(-1 + 9 \times 5) + Q(Q(2)) \\
 & & 1952 &:= Q(1 + \sqrt{9}) \times (5! + 2) \\
 & & 1952 &:= T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 2 \\
 & & 1953 &:= (-1 + C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(5))) \times 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1953 := F(-1 + 9) \times (5! - C(3))$$

$$1953 := Q(1 + Q(9) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(3!))$$

$$1953 := T(9 + 53)$$

$$1953 := T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 3$$

$$1954 := (1 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(Q(5))) / \sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$1954 := 1 - (C(\sqrt{9}) - 5!) \times F(\sqrt{C(4)})$$

$$1954 := 1 + T(T(9) + T(5) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1954 := -1 - T(9) + C(5) \times Q(4)$$

$$1954 := F(9) + 5! \times Q(4)$$

$$1954 := Q(-1 + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(5) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1954 := -T(1 + F(9)) + F(T(5) + F(4))$$

$$1954 := T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 4$$

$$1955 := (-1 + C(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 5!) \times 5$$

$$1955 := (1 + Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) \times (5! - 5)$$

$$1955 := (T(T(1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) - T(5)) \times 5$$

$$1955 := -1 + C((\sqrt{9})! + 5) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$1955 := -1 + Q(9) + T(5) \times C(5)$$

$$1955 := Q(1 + F(9)) + 5! + F(T(5))$$

$$1955 := T((\sqrt{9} + 1) \times T(5)) + C(5)$$

$$1955 := T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 5$$

$$1956 := 1 + F(9) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1956 := Q(1 + \sqrt{9}) \times 5! + Q(6)$$

$$1956 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + (1/6) \times 5!$$

$$1956 := T(1 + F(9)) + T(T(5) + Q(6))$$

$$1956 := T(1 + F(9)) + T(T(5) + T(F(6)))$$

$$1956 := T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 6$$

$$1957 := (1 - \sqrt{9}) \times 5! + C(F(7))$$

$$1957 := (C((1 + \sqrt{9})!) - C(5)) \times (1/7)$$

$$1957 := (C((\sqrt{9} + 1)!) - C(5)) \times (1/7)$$

$$1957 := F(-(1 - 9)) + Q(-5 + Q(7))$$

$$1957 := T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 7$$

$$1958 := (1 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times (C(5) - T(8))$$

$$1958 := (1 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times F(5 + \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$1958 := Q(19) + F(Q(5) - 8)$$

$$1958 := -T(1 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(5 + \sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$1958 := T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 8$$

$$1959 := (-1 + 9)! / T(5) - C(9)$$

$$1959 := (1 + C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(5))) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1959 := (1 + Q(9)) \times T(5) + C(9)$$

$$1959 := (1 + Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) \times 5! - Q(9)$$

$$1959 := (1 + T(\sqrt{9})!) - T(T(T(5) - \sqrt{9}))$$

$$1959 := Q(1 + F(9)) + 5 + C(9)$$

$$1959 := Q(T(9)) + T(5) - Q(9)$$

$$1959 := -T(-1 + F(9)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1959 := T(\sqrt{1 \times 9}) \times T(Q(5)) + 9$$

$$1960 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 0$$

$$1960 := -Q(F(-(1 - 9))) + Q(Q(F(6) - 0!))$$

$$1960 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 0$$

$$1960 := T(C(\sqrt{9} + 1)) - (6 - 0)!$$

$$1960 := T(Q(-(1 - 9))) - (6 - 0)!$$

$$1961 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 1$$

$$1961 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + Q(6 - 1)$$

$$1961 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 1$$

$$1962 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 2$$

$$1962 := 9 \times (C(6) + 2)$$

$$1962 := 9 + T(62)$$

$$1962 := Q(F(-(1 - 9))) + Q(Q(6) + F(Q(2)))$$

$$1962 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 2$$

$$1963 := 1 + 9 \times (C(6) + F(3))$$

$$1963 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 3$$

$$1963 := 1 + \sqrt{9} \times T(T(F(6))) - T(F(T(3)))$$

$$1963 := 19 + Q(3) \times C(6)$$

$$1963 := -1 - F(9) + 3 \times T(T(F(6)))$$

$$1963 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + Q(6) - Q(3)$$

$$1963 := Q(1 + T(9)) - T(F(6) + Q(3))$$

$$1963 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 3$$

$$1964 := (-1 + Q(Q(9)) + Q(Q(6)))/4$$

$$1964 := (C(-1 + 9) - F(F(6))) \times 4$$

$$1964 := (C(-1 + 9) - T(6)) \times 4$$

$$1964 := (T(-1 + T(9)) - F(6)) \times F(F(4))$$

$$1964 := (T(-1 + T(9)) - F(6)) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1964 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 4$$

$$1964 := F(1 + 9) \times Q(6) - Q(4)$$

$$1964 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 4$$

$$1964 := T(1 + 9) \times Q(6) - Q(4)$$

$$1965 := (-1 + Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) \times (6 + C(5))$$

$$1965 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 5$$

$$1965 := F(1 + 9) \times T(F(6)) - T(5)$$

$$1965 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 5$$

$$1965 := T(1 + 9) \times Q(6) - T(5)$$

$$1965 := T(1 + 9) \times T(F(6)) - T(5)$$

$$1965 := T(-1 + T(\sqrt{9})) \times (6 + C(5))$$

$$1966 := 1 + (9 \times C(6) + T(6))$$

$$1966 := 1 + 9 \times C(6) + F(F(6))$$

$$1966 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 6$$

$$1966 := 1 + T(9) + F(6)!/T(6)$$

$$1966 := Q(-1 + C(\sqrt{9})) - 6 + Q(Q(6))$$

$$1966 := Q(1 + F(9)) + 6! + T(6)$$

$$1966 := Q(1 + F(9)) + F(F(6)) + 6!$$

$$1966 := Q(-1 + T(9)) - 6 + Q(6)$$

$$1966 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 6$$

$$1967 := (-1) - (\sqrt{9})! \times C(F(6)) + 7!$$

$$1967 := (1 + 9!/Q(Q(6))) \times 7$$

$$1967 := (-1 + C(9)) \times 6 - Q(Q(7))$$

$$1967 := (C(-1 + 9) - T(T(6))) \times 7$$

$$1967 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 7$$

$$1967 := F(1 + 9) \times Q(6) - F(7)$$

$$1967 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 7$$

$$1967 := T(1 + 9) \times Q(6) - F(7)$$

$$1967 := T(1 + 9) \times T(F(6)) - F(7)$$

$$1967 := T(F(1 + 9)) + T(6) + T(T(7))$$

$$1967 := T(T(1 + 9)) + T(6) + T(T(7))$$

$$1968 := (1 + (\sqrt{9})!)! - 6 \times C(8)$$

$$1968 := (1 + Q(9)) \times Q(-6 + 8)!$$

$$1968 := (-1 + T(\sqrt{9}))! + 8 \times T(T(6))$$

$$1968 := (T(-1 + T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(6))) \times 8$$

$$1968 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 8$$

$$1968 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 8$$

$$1968 := \sqrt{9} \times (6! - Q(8))$$

$$1968 := -T(C(\sqrt{9})) + T(68)$$

$$1969 := 1 + ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(F(6))) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1969 := -1 + C(9) + C(F(6)) + C(9)$$

$$1969 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q(F(6)) + 9$$

$$1969 := 1 - T(T(9)) + T(T(T(6)))/\sqrt{9}$$

$$1969 := Q(-1 + (\sqrt{9})!) + 9 \times C(6)$$

$$1969 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + Q(6) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1969 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(F(F(6))) + 9$$

$$1969 := Q(Q(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(Q(6))/\sqrt{9}$$

$$1970 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))} - 0!$$

$$1971 := -Q(-1 + Q(F(\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(7) + 1)$$

$$1971 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + \sqrt{T(Q(7))}$$

$$1972 := (1 - F(9 + 7)) \times (-2)$$

$$1972 := 1 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times C(T(2))$$

$$1972 := 1 + C(\sqrt{9}) \times (Q(7) + Q(2)!)$$

$$1972 := T(1 + Q(9)) - T(Q(7) + Q(2))$$

$$1973 := -1 + F(9 + 7) \times F(3)$$

$$1973 := 1 - C(9) + T(73)$$

$$1973 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + T(7) + Q(3)$$

$$1974 := (F(19) - F(F(7)))/F(F(4))$$

$$1974 := 1 + T(F(9)) + T(4 \times F(7))$$

$$1974 := 1 + T(F(9)) + T(T(7) + 4!)$$

$$1974 := -1 - C(9) + Q(T(7) + 4!)$$

$$1974 := -C(-1 + 9) + T(T(7)) + T(C(4))$$

$$1974 := F(9 + 7) \times F(F(4))$$

$$1974 := F(9 + 7) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1974 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + T(7) + T(4)$$

$$1974 := T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$1975 := (1 + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(7)) \times Q(5)$$

$$1975 := 1 + Q(-(\sqrt{9})! + Q(7)) + C(5)$$

$$1975 := -1 + T(Q(9)) - T(Q(7)) - 5!$$

$$1975 := -1 - C((\sqrt{9})!) + (C(F(7)) - 5)$$

$$1975 := -1 - T(T(9)) + Q(Q(7)) + F(T(5))$$

$$1975 := -F(1 + 9) + 5 \times T(T(7))$$

$$1975 := -T(1 + 9) + 5 \times T(T(7))$$

$$1976 := (-1 + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 76$$

$$1976 := (-1 + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 76$$

$$1976 := 19 \times F(7) \times F(6)$$

$$1976 := -1 - Q(9) + 6 \times C(7)$$

$$1976 := Q(1 + T(9)) - 7!/Q(6)$$

$$1977 := (\sqrt{9} + 1)! + T(F(7) + Q(7))$$

$$1977 := 1 + Q(F(9) + F(7)) - F(F(7))$$

$$1977 := 1 + Q(T(9)) - 7 \times 7$$

$$1977 := -1 + T(T(-F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7))) - F(F(7))$$

$$1977 := F(19) - C(F(7)) - 7$$

$$1977 := -Q(9) + Q(Q(7)) - C(7)$$

$$1978 := (1 + T(9)) \times (7 + T(8))$$

$$1978 := 1 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(F(7)) + C(8)$$

$$1979 := -1 + C((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(7 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1979 := -1 + C(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7) + F(9))$$

$$1979 := -1 + Q((\sqrt{9})!) \times (Q(7) + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1979 := -1 + T(\sqrt{9})! + T(7) \times T(9)$$

$$1979 := -C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$1979 := -Q(F(1 + 9)) + 7! - Q((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1979 := Q(T(9)) - Q(7) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1979 := T(T(9)) - T(F(7)) + T(T(9))$$

$$1980 := -1 - C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(F(8 - 0!))$$

$$1980 := F(1 + 9) \times Q((\sqrt{8 + 0!})!)$$

$$1980 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 0$$

$$1980 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 0$$

$$1981 := -C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(F(8 - 1))$$

$$1981 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 1$$

$$1981 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 1$$

$$1982 := 1 - C((\sqrt{9}!)) + C(F(8) - C(2))$$

$$1982 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 2$$

$$1982 := F(Q(1 + \sqrt{9})) + 8 + F(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$1982 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 2$$

$$1983 := -1 + Q(F((\sqrt{9}!)) + 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$1983 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 3$$

$$1983 := -Q(-1 + F(9)) + C(8) \times 3!$$

$$1983 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 3$$

$$1984 := (1 + 9 + F(8)) \times C(4)$$

$$1984 := (1 + \sqrt{9}) \times C(8) - C(4)$$

$$1984 := -(1 - 9) \times (-8 + Q(Q(4)))$$

$$1984 := (F(1 + 9) + Q(F(8))) \times 4$$

$$1984 := (\sqrt{9} + 1) \times C(8) - C(4)$$

$$1984 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 4$$

$$1984 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 4$$

$$1985 := (Q(19) + T(8)) \times 5$$

$$1985 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 5$$

$$1985 := Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!)) + Q(8) + Q(Q(5)))$$

$$1985 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 5$$

$$1986 := -1 + F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) + C(\sqrt{Q(8) + Q(6)})$$

$$1986 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 6$$

$$1986 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 6$$

$$1987 := -(1 + 9) \times F(8) + C(F(7))$$

$$1987 := -1 + Q(F(9)) + Q(8) \times F(7)$$

$$1987 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 7$$

$$1987 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 7$$

$$1988 := (1 + C(\sqrt{9})) \times (C(8) - Q(F(8)))$$

$$1988 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 8$$

$$1988 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 8$$

$$1989 := (1 + F(9)) \times T(8) + C(9)$$

$$1989 := C(F(1 + (\sqrt{9}!)) + (C(8) - (\sqrt{9}!))$$

$$1989 := F(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 9$$

$$1989 := Q(-1 + F(9)) + Q(Q(8) - F(9))$$

$$1989 := Q(-19 + Q(8)) - Q((\sqrt{9}!))$$

$$1989 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 9$$

$$1990 := Q(T(1 + 9)) - T(T(9)) + 0$$

$$1990 := T(-1 + T(9)) + C(9 + 0!)$$

$$1991 := Q(T(1 + 9)) - T(T(9)) + 1$$

$$1991 := T(1 + 9) + Q(-1 + T(9))$$

$$1992 := (1 + \sqrt{9})! \times (Q(9) + 2)$$

$$1992 := (T(-1 + T(9)) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 2$$

$$1992 := 1 - F(9) + T(9)^2$$

$$1992 := C(1 + 9) \times F(\sqrt{9}) - C(2)$$

$$1992 := Q(T(1 + 9)) - T(T(9)) + 2$$

$$1992 := T(T(-1 + 9)) + T(T(9) + T(T(2)))$$

$$1993 := 1 + (F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(9)) \times Q(F(3))!$$

$$1993 := 1 + \sqrt{9} + Q(T(9)) - Q(T(3))$$

$$1993 := 1 + T(T(\sqrt{9}) + T(9)) + T(T(F(T(3))))$$

$$1993 := 2 + Q(T(9)) - F(9)$$

$$1993 := C(F(1 + (\sqrt{9}!)) - F(9) \times 3!$$

$$1993 := C(F(1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) - F(9) \times T(3)$$

$$1993 := Q(1 + (\sqrt{9}!)) + 9 \times C(3!)$$

$$1993 := Q(Q(9) - F(9)) - C(3!)$$

$$1993 := Q(T(1+9)) - T(T(9)) + 3$$

$$1994 := (C(1+9) - \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1994 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{9} \times T(4)$$

$$1994 := F(19) - Q(Q(9))/F(4)$$

$$1994 := Q(1 + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(9 - 4))$$

$$1994 := Q(-1 + T(9)) + F(9) + 4!$$

$$1994 := Q(T(1+9)) - T(T(9)) + 4$$

$$1994 := T(T(-1+9)) \times \sqrt{9} - 4$$

$$1995 := (-1 + (\sqrt{9})!) + \sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(5))$$

$$1995 := 19 \times T(9 + 5)$$

$$1995 := 95 \times F(-1 + 9)$$

$$1995 := F(1+9) \times F(9) + C(5)$$

$$1995 := Q(T(1+9)) - T(T(9)) + 5$$

$$1996 := (-1 + (\sqrt{9})!) + Q(F(9)) + 6!$$

$$1996 := 1 + \sqrt{9} \times (C(9) - Q(F(6)))$$

$$1996 := -1 + T(9 + T(9)) + C(F(6))$$

$$1996 := 1 + T(T(9)) + C(9) + T(T(6))$$

$$1996 := 1 - T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(\sqrt{9} \times T(6))$$

$$1996 := Q(1 + T(9)) - T(9 + 6)$$

$$1996 := Q(T(1+9)) - T(T(9)) + 6$$

$$1997 := -1 + C(\sqrt{9}) \times (Q(9) - 7)$$

$$1997 := -19 + T(9 \times 7)$$

$$1997 := Q(-1 - 9) + F(9) + F(F(7))$$

$$1997 := Q(T(1+9)) - T(T(9)) + 7$$

$$1998 := -(C((\sqrt{9} + 1)!) - Q(Q(9)) - C(F(8)))$$

$$1998 := 1 + Q(F(9)) + Q(F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(8))$$

$$1998 := 7 + Q(T(9)) - F(9)$$

$$1998 := 9 \times (-9 + T(F(8)))$$

$$1998 := -C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(9 + T(8))$$

$$1998 := -Q(1 + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) - C(9) + Q(Q(8))$$

$$1998 := Q(T(1+9)) - T(T(9)) + 8$$

$$1998 := Q(T(9)) + (9 - T(8))$$

$$1998 := T(1 + 9 \times (1/9)) \times T(T(8))$$

$$1999 := 1 + ((\sqrt{9})! + C((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 9$$

$$1999 := -1 + Q(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$1999 := -1 + Q(T(9)) - Q((1/9) \times T(9))$$

$$1999 := 1 + \sqrt{9} \times T(T(9) - 9)$$

$$1999 := 1 - C(\sqrt{9}) + T(9) \times T(9)$$

$$1999 := C(1+9) \times F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$1999 := Q(T(1+9)) - T(T(9)) + 9$$

$$1999 := T(1 + F(9)) + Q(F(9) + \sqrt{9})$$

$$2000 := C(20)/Q(0! + 0!)$$

$$2000 := C(T(0! + T(2))) \times (0! + 0!)$$

$$2000 := Q(T(Q(T(2)))) - Q(0! + Q(0! + 0!))$$

$$2001 := (T(T(C(2))) + 0!) \times T(0! + 1)$$

$$2001 := (T(T(F(T(T(2)))))) + 0!) \times T(0! + 1)$$

$$2001 := -Q(2)! + Q(T(Q(0! + 0! + 1)))$$

$$2001 := Q(T(0! + C(2))) - Q(0! + 1)!$$

$$2002 := (C(Q(F(Q(2))) + 0!) + 0!) \times 2$$

$$2002 := (C(T(0! + T(2))) + 0!) \times 2$$

$$2002 := (T(T(T(2))) + 0!) \times T(F(0! + T(T(2))))$$

$$2002 := Q(T(Q(T(2)))) + (0! - Q(2)!)$$

$$2002 := T(C(Q(2))) - T((0! + 0!) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$2002 := T(F(-0! + C(2))) \times (0! + F(C(2)))$$

$$2002 := T(Q(C(2))) - T((0! + 0!) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$2003 := C(C(2)) \times Q(0! + 0!) - T(Q(3))$$

$$2003 := F(0! + Q(Q(2))) + T(T(0! + T(3)))$$

$$2003 := F(Q(Q(2))) + C(0! + 0!) - C(F(Q(3)))$$

$$2003 := -Q(2)! + 0! + 0! + Q(T(Q(3)))$$

$$2004 := (T(T(F(T(T(2)))))) + 0! + 0! \times F(4)$$

$$2004 := 2 \times (0! + 0! + C(T(4)))$$

$$2004 := -F(C(2)) + Q(Q(0! + 0!)! + F(\sqrt{C(4)}))$$

$$2004 := Q(Q(2)!) + F(Q(Q(0! + 0!))) + Q(F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$2004 := Q(Q(Q(2)) \times T(0! + 0!)) - T(4!)$$

$$2005 := (Q(20) + 0!) \times 5$$

$$2006 := C(2) + T(0! + 0!) \times T(Q(6))$$

$$2006 := C(Q(Q(2)) - 0!) - Q(0! + Q(6))$$

$$2006 := F(T(T(2))) + T(0! + 0!) \times T(Q(6))$$

$$2006 := F(T(T(2))) + T(0! + 0!) \times T(T(F(6)))$$

$$2006 := -T(Q(2)) + T(T(0! + 0!)) \times T(6)$$

$$2006 := T(T(C(2))) \times T(0! + 0!) + F(6)$$

$$2007 := F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times C(Q(0! + 0!)) - Q(F(7))$$

$$2007 := Q(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times F(Q(F(Q(0! + 0!)))) - Q(F(7))$$

$$2007 := Q(Q(2)!) + T(Q(0! + 0!)) + Q(7)$$

$$2007 := -T(20 - 0!) + C(F(7))$$

$$2008 := C(2)!/Q(Q(0! + 0!)) - C(8)$$

$$2008 := -C(2) + T(0 - 0! + Q(8))$$

$$2008 := -C(2) + T(T(0! + 0!)) \times F(8)$$

$$2008 := -F(T(T(2))) + T(T(0! + 0!)) \times F(8)$$

$$2008 := Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(0! + 0!)! + Q(8)$$

$$2008 := T(C(0! + T(2)) - 0!) - 8$$

$$2008 := T(Q(2)) + T(0! + 0!) \times T(T(8))$$

$$2008 := T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(0! + 0!) - 8$$

$$2009 := Q(C(F(Q(2))) + 0!) + Q(0! + F(9))$$

$$2009 := -Q(Q(2)) \times 0! + Q(T(9))$$

$$2009 := -Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(F(Q(0! + 0!))) + Q((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$2010 := Q(T(Q(T(2)))) - T(0! + Q(0! + 1))$$

$$2010 := T(C(Q(2)) - 0!) - T(T(1 + 0!))$$

$$2010 := T(Q(C(2)) - 0!) - T(T(1 + 0!))$$

$$2012 := -(Q(F(Q(2))) - C(C(1 + 0!))) \times Q(2)$$

$$2012 := C(C(2)) \times Q(1 + 0!) - T(C(2))$$

$$2012 := F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(Q(Q(0! + 1))) - Q(F(Q(2)!))$$

$$2012 := -F(T(T(2)) + 0!) + Q(T(Q(1 + 2)))$$

$$2012 := Q(Q(T(T(2)))) - Q(0! + 1) + T(T(2))!$$

$$2013 := F(Q(2)!)/Q(0! + 1)! + Q(Q(3))$$

$$2013 := Q(T(C(2))) - T(1 + 0!) + T(3)!$$

$$2013 := -T(2) + T(-0! + C(1 + 3))$$

$$2013 := -T(2) + T(-0! + Q(-1 + Q(3)))$$

$$2013 := -T(2) + T(T(0! + 1)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$2014 := -2 + T(0 - 1 + C(4))$$

$$2014 := -2 + T(T(0! + 1)) \times T(T(F(4)))$$

$$2014 := C(C(2)) \times Q(1 + 0!) - F(Q(F(4)))$$

$$2014 := F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(Q(Q(0! + 1))) - F(Q(F(4)))$$

$$2014 := Q(-0! + Q(2)!) + T(-1 + T(T(4)))$$

$$2014 := T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(0! + 1) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$2015 := -C(C(2) + 0!) + C(-1 + T(5))$$

$$2015 := F(Q(2))! - 0! + Q(Q(1 + 5))$$

$$2015 := T(T(2))! - 0! + Q(Q(1 + 5))$$

$$2016 := (2 + 1)!! + Q(Q(6))$$

$$2016 := (Q(C(2)) - C(0! + 1)) \times Q(6)$$

$$2016 := C(2)!/(-0! + F(F(6)))$$

$$2016 := F((2 + 0!)!)/(-1 + F(F(6)))$$

$$2016 := Q(2)! \times Q(0! + 1) \times F(F(6))$$

$$2016 := T(T(2) \times T(0 + 6))$$

$$2017 := -C(Q(2)) + 0! + T(Q(1 + 7))$$

$$2017 := -C(T(T(2))) + T(C(1 + 0!)) + C(F(7))$$

$$2017 := F(2) + T(-0! + Q(1 + 7))$$

$$2017 := -Q(C(2)) + 0! + T(Q(1 + 7))$$

$$2017 := -Q(Q(2)) \times Q(0! + 1)! + Q(Q(7))$$

$$2017 := Q(Q(Q(2)) + 0!) + C(-1 + F(7))$$

$$2017 := T(T(2))! + (0! + Q(T(1 + 7)))$$

$$2018 := 2 + T(0 - 1 + Q(8))$$

$$2018 := 2 + T(T(0! + 1) \times F(8))$$

$$2018 := 2 + T(T(0! + 1) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$2019 := F(Q(2))!! + F(Q(0! + 1)) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$2019 := T(2) + T(-0! + C(1 + \sqrt{9}))$$

$$2019 := T(2) + T(-0! + C(\sqrt{9} + 1))$$

$$2019 := T(2) + T(T(0! + 1) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$2019 := -T(T(2)) \times 0! + Q(T(9))$$

$$2020 := (Q(T(Q(2))) + 0!) \times 20$$

$$2020 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 0$$

$$2020 := Q(Q(2)!) + Q(0! + Q(F(Q(2))!)) + 0!$$

$$2021 := -Q(2) + Q(T(Q(2 + 1)))$$

$$2021 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 1$$

$$2022 := (C(C(2) - 0!) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$2022 := F(Q(2))! \times (0! + Q(Q(2)) \times F(C(2)))$$

$$2022 := -F(Q(2)) + Q((-0! + Q(Q(2))) \times F(Q(2)))$$

$$2022 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 2$$

$$2022 := T(T(2)) + T(-0! + 2^{T(T(2))})$$

$$2022 := T(T(2)) + T(-0! + Q(2)^{T(2)})$$

$$2022 := T(T(2)) + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2))))$$

$$2023 := -2 + Q((0! + Q(2)) \times Q(3))$$

$$2023 := C(2) - 0! + T(T(2) \times T(T(3)))$$

$$2023 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 3$$

$$2023 := T(C(2) + 0!)^2 - F(3)$$

$$2023 := T(T(2)) + 0! + T(T(2) \times T(T(3)))$$

$$2024 := (C(C(2)) - (2 + 0!)!) \times 4$$

$$2024 := (Q(T(2)) - 0!) \times T(-2 + 4!)$$

$$2024 := (T(T(T(2))) + 0!)^2 + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$2024 := 2 \times (Q(Q(2) + 0!) + F(Q(4)))$$

$$2024 := C(2) \times T(0! + F(2 \times 4))$$

$$2024 := C(2) + T(0! - 2 + C(4))$$

$$2024 := C(20)/Q(2) + 4!$$

$$2024 := F(T(T(2))) \times T(0! + F(2 \times 4))$$

$$2024 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 4$$

$$2024 := T(20 + 2) \times F(T(F(4)))$$

$$2025 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 5$$

$$2025 := Q(20 + 25)$$

$$2025 := T(C(2) + 0!)^{-T(2)+5}$$

$$2025 := T(C(2) + 0!)^{F(-2+5)}$$

$$2025 := T(F(T(T(2))) + 0!)^{F(-2+5)}$$

$$2026 := F(2) + Q(0! + C(2)) + Q(6)$$

$$2026 := F(2) + Q(Q(0! + 2)) + Q(6)$$

$$2026 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 6$$

$$2026 := T(Q(2)) + T(T(2) \times T(6))$$

$$2026 := T(T(2) + 0!) + T(T(2) \times T(6))$$

$$2027 := 2 + Q(0 - Q(2) + Q(7))$$

$$2027 := 2 + Q(T(2 + 7))$$

$$2027 := F(F(C(2))) - 0! - C(F(C(2))) + C(7)$$

$$2027 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 7$$

$$2027 := -T(2) - (0! - T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))$$

$$2028 := -20 + 8 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))$$

$$2028 := -20 + Q(2) \times C(8)$$

$$2028 := F(F(C(2))) + C(-0! + C(2)) - C(F(8))$$

$$2028 := F(Q(2)) \times Q(0! + Q(2) + F(8))$$

$$2028 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 8$$

$$2028 := T(2) \times (T(Q(2)) + T(T(8)))$$

$$2028 := T(2) \times (T(T(2) + 0!) + T(T(8)))$$

$$2028 := T(2) \times Q(0! + Q(2) + F(8))$$

$$2029 := C(F(-0! + C(2))) - F(C(2)) \times F((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$2029 := F(0! + T(T(2))) + T(T(2) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$2029 := F(C(2) - 0!) + T(T(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$2029 := Q(2) + Q((0! + Q(2)) \times 9)$$

$$2029 := Q(2) + Q(T(0 \times 2 + 9))$$

$$2029 := Q(2) + T(-0! + C(Q(2))) + 9$$

$$2029 := T(C(0! + T(2))) - T(T(2)) - T(9)$$

$$2029 := T(T(2))! + T(T(T(T(2) + 0!))) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$2029 := T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0!) + T(T(T(2)) + T(9))$$

$$2030 := (0! + Q(2)) \times T(C(3) + 0!)$$

$$2030 := (T(T(2)) - 0!) \times T(C(3) + 0!)$$

$$2030 := (T(T(2)) - 0!) \times T(T(T(3) + 0!))$$

$$2030 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 0$$

$$2031 := F(Q(2)) \times (0! + Q(C(3) - 1))$$

$$2031 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 1$$

$$2031 := T(2) \times (0! + Q(C(3) - 1))$$

$$2031 := T(T(2)) + Q(T(Q(3)))$$

$$2032 := (2 + 0!)!! + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(Q(2))$$

$$2032 := (C(C(2) - 0!) - C(3!)) \times Q(Q(2))$$

$$2032 := (F(2) + T(0! + T(T(3)))) \times F(T(T(2)))$$

$$2032 := (F(C(2)) + F(F(0! + 3!))) \times C(2)$$

$$2032 := C(2) - 0! + Q(T(3^2))$$

$$2032 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 2$$

$$2032 := Q(Q(2)) \times (-0! + F(3!) \times Q(Q(2)))$$

$$2032 := T(C(0! + T(2))) - T(3) \times C(2)$$

$$2032 := T(T(2)) + 0! + Q(T(3^2))$$

$$2033 := (-F(20) + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times (-1/3)$$

$$2033 := C(2) + Q(T(3 \times 3))$$

$$2033 := C(C(2)) + Q(3 + Q(3!))$$

$$2033 := F(T(T(2))) + T(0! + F(T(3)))^{F(3)}$$

$$2033 := Q((0! + Q(2)) \times Q(3)) + C(F(3))$$

$$2033 := Q((Q(2) + 0!) \times Q(3)) + F(3!)$$

$$2033 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 3$$

$$2033 := Q(Q(2)) + 0! + 3!! + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$2033 := Q(T(2)) - 0! + Q(T(3 \times 3))$$

$$2033 := T(C(2) + 0!)^{F(3)} + C(F(3))$$

$$2034 := (-Q(2) + C(0! + 3!)) \times F(4)!$$

$$2034 := (T(Q(2)) + C(T(3))) \times Q(F(4))$$

$$2034 := 2 \times C(Q(3)) + Q(4!)$$

$$2034 := C(C(2) - 0!) \times 3! - 4!$$

$$2034 := F(T(T(2))) \times T(0! + T(T(3))) + T(4)$$

$$2034 := Q((Q(2) + 0!) \times Q(3)) + Q(F(4))$$

$$2034 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 4$$

$$2034 := Q(2 + 0!) + Q(3!/Q(4))$$

$$2034 := Q(T(2)) + T(Q(3))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2034 := T(2) \times T(T(F(T(3)))) + T(F(T(F(4))))$$

$$2034 := T(T(2)) \times C(0! + T(3)) - 4!$$

$$2035 := (2 + 0!) \times 3!! - C(5)$$

$$2035 := (F(2) + T(T(T(3) + 0!))) \times 5$$

$$2035 := (Q(C(2)) + C(0! + 3!)) \times 5$$

$$2035 := (T(C(2)) + 0!) \times T(5 \times F(3))$$

$$2035 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 5$$

$$2035 := Q(F(Q(2))) + 0! + Q(5 \times Q(3))$$

$$2035 := T(2) \times T(3)! - C(5)$$

$$2035 := T(Q(2)) + Q(3 \times T(5))$$

$$2036 := 20 + 3!! + Q(Q(6))$$

$$2036 := 20 + T(3 \times T(6))$$

$$2036 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 6$$

$$2036 := T(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(3 + 6))$$

$$2037 := (T(20) + Q(Q(3))) \times 7$$

$$2037 := -F(C(2)) \times (0! - F(3) \times Q(7))$$

$$2037 := -F(C(2)) \times 0! + 3! \times C(7)$$

$$2037 := -F(C(2)) \times 0! + T(3) \times C(7)$$

$$2037 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 7$$

$$2037 := -Q(20) + Q(3!) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$2037 := -T((1/3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 7!$$

$$2037 := T(T(T(2))) \times (T(3) + T(F(7)))$$

$$2037 := T(T(T(2))) + T(-0! + C(-3 + 7))$$

$$2038 := -C(C(2) - 0!) \times 3! + Q(Q(8))$$

$$2038 := F(20 - 3) + Q(F(8))$$

$$2038 := F(C(2)) + 0! + T(C(3) + T(8))$$

$$2038 := F(C(2) - 0!) + Q(Q(3) + T(8))$$

$$2038 := Q(2) \times C(0! + T(3)) + T(T(8))$$

$$2038 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 8$$

$$2038 := T(2) - T(Q(3)) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2038 := T(T(T(2))) + (0! + T(3 \times F(8)))$$

$$2038 := T(T(T(2))) + 0! + T(3 \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$2038 := T(T(T(2))) + 0! + T(C(3) + T(8))$$

$$2039 := C(2) + T(3) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2039 := C(C(2)) \times (0! + 3) - 9$$

$$2039 := Q(2)! - 0! + Q(Q(3!)) + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$2039 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(3) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2039 := Q(2) + 0! + Q(T(Q(3))) + 9$$

$$2039 := -Q(Q(Q(2))) \times (0! - Q(3)) - 9$$

$$2040 := (0! + T(2))! + T(C(4) - 0!)$$

$$2040 := (Q(Q(2)) + 0!) \times (4 + 0!)!$$

$$2040 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4!)) + 0$$

$$2040 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 0$$

$$2040 := Q(2)! + T(C(4) - 0!)$$

$$2040 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 0$$

$$2041 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4!)) + 1$$

$$2041 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 1$$

$$2041 := Q(0! + Q(2)) + T(C(4) - 1)$$

$$2041 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 1$$

$$2041 := T(T(F(C(2) - 0!))) - T(C(4) + 1)$$

$$2042 := (C(C(2)) - 0!) \times 4 - 2$$

$$2042 := (F(C(2) + 0!) + F(Q(4))) \times 2$$

$$2042 := (F(Q(Q(2))) + F(Q(F(4)))) \times 2$$

$$2042 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4!)) + 2$$

$$2042 := 2^{0!+T(4)} - T(T(2))$$

$$2042 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 2$$

$$2042 := C(T(2)) - 0! + T(C(4) - F(2))$$

$$2042 := -T(C(2)) \times 0! + T(C(4)) - 2$$

$$2042 := T(Q(2)) \times T(0! + Q(4)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2042 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 2$$

$$2043 := (2 + Q(-0! + Q(4))) \times Q(3)$$

$$2043 := (C(C(2)) + 0!) \times 4 - Q(3)$$

$$2043 := (F(T(T(2))) + 0!) \times (-4 + T(T(T(3))))$$

$$2043 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4)!) + 3$$

$$2043 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 3$$

$$2043 := -C(2) + C(0! + T(4)) + T(3)!$$

$$2043 := C(T(2)) + T(0! + C(4) - F(3))$$

$$2043 := -F(C(2)) \times (0! - C(4)) + 3!!$$

$$2043 := F(Q(2)) + (-0! + Q(Q(4))) \times F(3)!$$

$$2043 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 3$$

$$2044 := (C(C(2)) - 0!) \times \sqrt{4 \times 4}$$

$$2044 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4)!) + 4$$

$$2044 := 2^{0!+T(4)} - 4$$

$$2044 := 4 \times C(C(2)) - 4$$

$$2044 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 4$$

$$2044 := Q(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(4)))$$

$$2044 := -Q(2) \times (0! - C(4 + 4))$$

$$2044 := T(2^{T(F(4))}) - T(F(T(F(4))))$$

$$2044 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 4$$

$$2045 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4)!) + 5$$

$$2045 := (T(2) + T(T(0! + T(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$2045 := (T(C(2)) - 0!) \times T(T(4)) + 5!$$

$$2045 := (T(T(0! + T(T(2)))) + T(\sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$2045 := 20 + Q(45)$$

$$2045 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 5$$

$$2045 := C(F(-0! + C(2))) - C(F(4)) - C(5)$$

$$2045 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 5$$

$$2046 := (C(C(2)) + 0!) \times 4 - 6$$

$$2046 := (C(C(2)) - 0!) - \sqrt{4} \times 6$$

$$2046 := (Q(Q(2)) + T(0! + 4!)) \times 6$$

$$2046 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4)!) + 6$$

$$2046 := 2 \times (-0! + Q(4 \times F(6)))$$

$$2046 := 2 \times (-0! + Q(-4 + Q(6)))$$

$$2046 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 6$$

$$2046 := F(C(2)) + Q(4! + T(6))$$

$$2046 := T(20 \times F(4)) + C(6)$$

$$2046 := T(C(2) + 0!)^{\sqrt{4}} + T(6)$$

$$2046 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 6$$

$$2046 := T(T(2))! + T(0! + (1/6) \times T(4!))$$

$$2046 := T(T(2))! + T(T(4 + 0!)) + T(F(6))$$

$$2047 := (-0! + Q(2)!) \times F(4 + 7)$$

$$2047 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4)!) + 7$$

$$2047 := -20 + T(C(4)) - F(7)$$

$$2047 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 7$$

$$2047 := Q(2)! + 7 \times Q(0! + Q(4))$$

$$2047 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 7$$

$$2047 := -T(T(2)) + 0! + T(C(4)) - T(7)$$

$$2047 := -T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 0! + T(-4! + T(F(7)))$$

$$2047 := -T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(0! + T(4 + 7))$$

$$2048 := (2 \times 0 + 4) \times C(8)$$

$$2048 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4)!) + 8$$

$$2048 := 2 \times Q(4 \times 8)$$

$$2048 := 2^{-0!+4+8}$$

$$2048 := 2^{0!+\sqrt{4}+8}$$

$$2048 := 2^{F(4)+8}$$

$$2048 := 2^{T(\sqrt{4})+8}$$

$$2048 := 8 \times (T(2) + 0!)^4$$

$$2048 := C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 8$$

$$2048 := C(2) \times \sqrt{4^8}$$

$$2048 := T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 8$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2049 &:= (C(C(2)) + 0!) \times 4 - \sqrt{9} \\ 2049 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 0!) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 \\ 2049 &:= C(2) \times (-0! + Q(Q(4))) + 9 \\ 2049 &:= C(C(2)) + 0! + (1/9) \times C(4!) \\ 2049 &:= Q(2)! + (0! + 4!) \times Q(9) \\ 2049 &:= T(Q(2) + 0!) \times T(Q(4)) + 9 \\ 2049 &:= -T(T(T(2))) \times 0! + F(F(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\ 2049 &:= -T(T(T(2))) \times 0! + \sqrt{4} \times T(T(9)) \\ 2049 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + F(F(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\ 2049 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + \sqrt{4} \times T(T(9)) \\ 2049 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(-0! + T(4))) + T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2050 &:= (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 0 \\ 2050 &:= (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 0 \\ 2050 &:= F(Q(2))! - 0! + C(\sqrt{5! + 0!}) \\ 2050 &:= F(Q(T(2))) + T(-0! + C(5 - 0!)) \\ 2050 &:= T(T(2))! - 0! + C(\sqrt{5! + 0!}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2051 &:= (2 + 0!)!! + C(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) \\ 2051 &:= (2 + 0!)!! + C(\sqrt{5! + 1}) \\ 2051 &:= (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 1 \\ 2051 &:= (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 1 \\ 2051 &:= T(T(2))! + C(0! + T(5 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2052 &:= (C(C(2)) + (0 \times 5)!) \times Q(2) \\ 2052 &:= (C(C(2)) + 0!) \times (5 - F(2)) \\ 2052 &:= (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 2 \\ 2052 &:= (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 2 \\ 2052 &:= (T(T(2))! - T(F(0! + 5))) \times T(2) \\ 2052 &:= 2^{\sqrt{0!+5!}} + Q(2) \\ 2052 &:= C(C(2)) + T(T(5 \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2053 &:= (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 3 \\ 2053 &:= (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 3 \\ 2053 &:= 2 + C(\sqrt{0! + 5!}) + 3!! \\ 2053 &:= C(F(Q(2))) + 0! + Q(5 \times Q(3)) \\ 2053 &:= Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + Q(0! + Q(5)) + Q(Q(3!)) \\ 2053 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) + T(0! + Q(5) + Q(T(3))) \\ 2053 &:= T(C(2) - 0!) + Q(5 \times Q(3)) \\ 2053 &:= T(C(20 \times (1/5))) - C(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2054 &:= (C(T(2)) - 0!) \times (T(5) + C(4)) \\ 2054 &:= (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 4 \\ 2054 &:= (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 4 \\ 2054 &:= 2^{\sqrt{0!+5!}} + F(4)! \\ 2054 &:= 2^{\sqrt{0!+5!}} + T(F(4)) \\ 2054 &:= 2^{\sqrt{0!+5!}} + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\ 2054 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(T(2) + 0!)) + 4! \\ 2054 &:= -C(C(2)) \times (0! - 5) + F(4)! \\ 2054 &:= Q(-0! + Q(2)!) - T(5) + T(T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2055 &:= (F(2) + T(0! + T(5))) \times T(5) \\ 2055 &:= (F(Q(Q(2))) - Q(-0! + Q(5))) \times 5 \\ 2055 &:= (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 5 \\ 2055 &:= (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 5 \\ 2055 &:= T(2^{0!+5}) - Q(5) \\ 2055 &:= T(C(0! + T(2))) - 5 \times 5 \\ 2055 &:= -T(T(2))! + T(-0! + 5 \times T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2056 &:= (F(2) + Q(0! + T(5))) \times F(6) \\ 2056 &:= (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 6 \\ 2056 &:= (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 6 \\ 2056 &:= 2^{\sqrt{0!+5!}} + F(6) \\ 2056 &:= C(2) \times (0! + Q(-5 + T(6))) \\ 2056 &:= -C(C(2)) \times (0! - 5) + F(6) \\ 2056 &:= C(C(2)) \times \sqrt{0! + T(5)} + F(6) \\ 2056 &:= T(C(T(2) + 0!)) - (\sqrt{-5 + T(6)})! \end{aligned}$$

$$2056 := T(Q(Q(2))) - 0! + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$2057 := (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 7$$

$$2057 := (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 7$$

$$2057 := 20 \times 5! - C(7)$$

$$2057 := Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times (0! + Q(5)) - Q(7)$$

$$2057 := T(T(2)) \times T(0! + Q(5)) - Q(7)$$

$$2058 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + F(\sqrt{0! + 5!})) \times F(8)$$

$$2058 := (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 8$$

$$2058 := (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 8$$

$$2058 := C(C(2) - 0!) \times (-5 + 8)!$$

$$2058 := -F(C(2)) \times (0! - 5! + F(8))$$

$$2058 := T(2) \times (-0! + F(T(5))) + T(F(8))$$

$$2058 := T(2) - Q(5) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2058 := T(T(2)) \times C(T(5) - 8)$$

$$2058 := T(T(T(2))) \times (-0! + 5! - T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$2059 := (Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 9$$

$$2059 := (Q(Q(T(2))) + 0!) \times Q(5) + 9$$

$$2059 := (T(2) + 0!)^5 + T(T(9))$$

$$2059 := C(2) + 0! + Q(5) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2059 := C(2) + C(\sqrt{0! + 5!}) + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$2059 := C(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{0! + 5!}) + C((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$2059 := -F(2) + C(\sqrt{0! + 5!}) + C(9)$$

$$2059 := F(C(2) + 0!) + Q(5 \times 9)$$

$$2059 := F(Q(2) + 5) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2059 := Q(20 + Q(5)) + F(9)$$

$$2059 := Q(T(2)) + Q(5) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2060 := C(Q(F(Q(2)))) + C(\sqrt{0! + (6 - 0)!})$$

$$2060 := F(Q(T(2))) + 0! + Q(T(F(6) + 0!))$$

$$2060 := T(C(0! + T(2))) - T(6) + 0!$$

$$2060 := T(C(Q(2))) - T(6) + 0!$$

$$2060 := T(F(C(2))) - 0! + T(60)$$

$$2060 := T(Q(C(2))) - T(6) + 0!$$

$$2060 := T(T(T(T(2)))) - 0! + T(60)$$

$$2061 := Q(T(2)) \times (-0! + T(T(6)) - 1)$$

$$2061 := T(F(C(2))) + T(-0! + 61)$$

$$2061 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(-0! + 61)$$

$$2062 := 2 \times T(T(0! + F(6))) - F(T(T(2)))$$

$$2062 := 6 \times C(C(2) - 0!) + Q(2)$$

$$2062 := F(Q(Q(2)) + 0!) + Q(F(F(6))) + Q(2)!$$

$$2062 := -Q(Q(2)) - 0! + T(T(6)) \times Q(T(2))$$

$$2062 := T(2) \times T(Q(6)) + C(Q(2))$$

$$2062 := T(2) \times T(Q(6)) + Q(C(2))$$

$$2062 := T(C(0! + T(2))) - T(6) + T(2)$$

$$2063 := (Q(Q(2)!) + F(-0! + F(F(6))))/3$$

$$2063 := F(F(C(2))) - C(T(6)) + T(C(3))$$

$$2063 := -Q(Q(2)! - 0!) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(3!))$$

$$2063 := -Q(Q(2)) \times 0! + T(T(6)) \times Q(3)$$

$$2063 := Q(Q(2)) - 0! + C(F(6)) \times Q(F(3))$$

$$2063 := T(0! + Q(2)) + C(F(6)) \times Q(F(3))$$

$$2064 := (C(T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times \sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$2064 := (T(T(T(2))) + 0! + T(T(F(6)))) \times F(4)$$

$$2064 := 6 \times C(-0! + C(2)) + F(4)!$$

$$2064 := C(C(2)) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(4))$$

$$2064 := Q(Q(2)) \times (0! + F(6) \times Q(4))$$

$$2064 := T(2^{06}) - Q(4)$$

$$2065 := 2 \times 6! + Q(Q(5))$$

$$2065 := T(2^6) - T(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2066 &:= 6 \times C(-0! + C(2)) + F(6) \\ 2066 &:= C(2) + 6 \times C(0! + 6) \\ 2066 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(0! + Q(6)) + Q(F(F(6))) \\ 2066 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(0! + Q(6)) + Q(T(6)) \\ 2066 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(0! + 6) + F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2067 &:= C(2) + 0! + 6 \times C(7) \\ 2067 &:= Q(Q(Q(2) + 0!) + F(F(6))) - Q(7) \\ 2067 &:= Q(Q(T(2)) + 0! + Q(6)) - Q(7) \\ 2067 &:= T(2^6) - F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2068 &:= 2 \times (0 - 6) + T(Q(8)) \\ 2068 &:= F(Q(2))! + Q(0! + Q(6)) - F(8) \\ 2068 &:= -Q(2) \times (0! - 6 - C(8)) \\ 2068 &:= -Q(Q((2 + 0!)!)) + Q(-6 + Q(8)) \\ 2068 &:= T(C(0! + T(2))) - 6 - \sqrt{T(8)} \\ 2068 &:= T(C(T(2) + 0!)) - 6 - \sqrt{T(8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2069 &:= 2 \times (0! + T(6)) + Q(T(9)) \\ 2069 &:= C(2) \times T(0! + T(6)) + T(9) \\ 2069 &:= C(Q(2) + 0!) + 9 \times C(6) \\ 2069 &:= -F(2) + (0! - T(T(6))) \times (-9) \\ 2069 &:= Q(Q(Q(2) + 0!)) + Q(Q(6) + F(\sqrt{9})) \\ 2069 &:= -T(T(2) + 0!) + 9 \times T(T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2070 &:= (Q(2)! - 0!) \times (T(F(7)) - 0!) \\ 2070 &:= 2 \times T(T(0! + 7 + 0!)) \\ 2070 &:= F(Q(2))! \times (0! + C(7) + 0!) \\ 2070 &:= T(T(2)) \times (0! + C(7) + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$2071 := C(-0! + C(2)) + C(F(7) - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2071 &:= -C(2) - 0! + T(Q(7 + 1)) \\ 2071 &:= -F(F(F(Q(2))! + 0!)) + Q(Q(7) - 1) \\ 2071 &:= -Q(T(2)) \times 0! + T(Q(7 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2072 &:= (0! + Q(2))! \times F(7) + C(C(2)) \\ 2072 &:= (C(C(2)) - 0! + 7) \times Q(2) \\ 2072 &:= (F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(7)) \times 2 \\ 2072 &:= (T(20) + Q(7)) \times C(2) \\ 2072 &:= 2 \times (0! + T(T(7 + 2))) \\ 2072 &:= -C(2) + T((0! + 7) \times C(2)) \\ 2072 &:= C(F(-0! + C(2))) - C(7 - 2) \\ 2072 &:= Q(2)! + Q(-0! + Q(7)) - Q(Q(Q(2))) \\ 2072 &:= -T(T(T(2))) - (1/2) \times (0 - T(T(F(7)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2073 &:= -20 + T(T(F(7)))/F(3) \\ 2073 &:= -C(2) + 0! + T(C(7 - 3)) \\ 2073 &:= F(C(2)) - (0! - C(7)) \times 3! \\ 2073 &:= F(C(2)) - (0! - C(7)) \times T(3) \\ 2073 &:= -Q(2)! \times 0! + F(F(7)) \times Q(3) \\ 2073 &:= Q(Q(2)) - 0! + C(7) \times 3! \\ 2073 &:= Q(T(2)) + (0! + C(7)) \times T(3) \\ 2073 &:= T(2) \times (-0! - T(7) + T(3)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2074 &:= 2 \times (0! + Q(7) + F(Q(4))) \\ 2074 &:= Q(C(2) - 0!) + Q(Q(7) - 4) \\ 2074 &:= T(20) + F(F(7)) \times F(T(F(4))) \\ 2074 &:= T(Q(2)) \times F(F(7)) - Q(Q(4)) \\ 2074 &:= T(T(2)) \times (0! + C(7)) + T(4) \\ 2074 &:= -T(T(2)) + T((0! + 7)^{F(F(4))}) \\ 2074 &:= -T(T(2)) + T((0! + 7)^{\sqrt{4}}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2075 &:= (C(2) + 0! + T(T(7))) \times 5 \\ 2075 &:= (F(C(2) + 0!) + Q(7)) \times Q(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2075 &:= (F(Q(0! + 2)) + Q(7)) \times Q(5) & 2079 &:= Q(C(2)) - 0! + T(7 \times 9) \\
 2075 &:= -2 + C(F(7)) - 5! & 2079 &:= -Q(Q(Q(2) + 0!)) + Q(Q(7) + \sqrt{9}) \\
 2075 &:= 5 \times (F(T(T(2))) + (0! + T(T(7)))) & 2079 &:= Q(T(2)) \times T(7 \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 2075 &:= -Q(2) - 0! + T(Q(7) + T(5)) & & \\
 2075 &:= T(2^{-0!+7}) - 5 & & \\
 2075 &:= T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(07)) - 5 & & \\
 & & & \\
 2076 &:= (-2 - 0! - C(7)) \times (-6) & & \\
 2076 &:= -(Q(Q(Q(2)) + 0!) - Q(Q(7)) + Q(6)) & & \\
 2076 &:= Q(0! + 2) \times F(F(7)) - F(F(6)) & & \\
 2076 &:= T(2) \times (0 - T(7) + 6!) & & \\
 & & & \\
 2077 &:= -(-2 + 7)! + C(F(7)) & & \\
 2077 &:= Q(C(2) - 0!) + C(F(7)) - Q(F(7)) & & \\
 2077 &:= -Q(Q(2)! + 0! - 7) + Q(Q(7)) & & \\
 2077 &:= -Q(Q(2) + 0! + F(7)) + Q(Q(7)) & & \\
 2077 &:= -Q(T(2)) \times T(0! + 7) + Q(Q(7)) & & \\
 2077 &:= -T(2) + T(C(-(1/7) \times (0 - T(7)))) & & \\
 2077 &:= -T(2) + T(T(0! + 7) + T(7)) & & \\
 2077 &:= T(T(2)) \times (0! + C(7)) + F(7) & & \\
 & & & \\
 2078 &:= -2 + T((0! + 7) \times 8) & & \\
 2078 &:= -2 + T(Q(0 \times 7 + 8)) & & \\
 2078 &:= -2 + T(T(7) + T(8)) & & \\
 2078 &:= Q(F(C(2))) \times (0! + F(7)) - Q(Q(8)) & & \\
 2078 &:= Q(F(F(F(Q(2)!))) \times (0! + F(7)) - Q(Q(8)) & & \\
 & & & \\
 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(7))) \times 9 & & \\
 2079 &:= (C(2) + 0!) \times T(7 \times \sqrt{9}) & & \\
 2079 &:= (Q(C(2)) + F(7)) \times C(\sqrt{9}) & & \\
 2079 &:= 9 \times T(7 \times T(2)) & & \\
 2079 &:= C(Q(2)) - 0! + T(7 \times 9) & & \\
 2079 &:= -F(2) + T(0! + 7 \times 9) & & \\
 & & & \\
 2080 &:= (C(F(Q(2))) - 0!) \times 80 & & \\
 2080 &:= T(2^{-0!+8-0!}) & & \\
 2080 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 0 & & \\
 2080 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(08+0)}) & & \\
 2080 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 0 & & \\
 2080 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 0 & & \\
 2080 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 0 & & \\
 2080 &:= T(T(2) \times F(8) + 0!) & & \\
 2080 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 0 & & \\
 & & & \\
 2081 &:= (2 \times 0)! + T(Q(8)) & & \\
 2081 &:= F(2) + T(Q(8)) & & \\
 2081 &:= F(Q(Q(2)) + 0!) + Q(1 + F(8)) & & \\
 2081 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 1 & & \\
 2081 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 1 & & \\
 2081 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 1 & & \\
 2081 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 1 & & \\
 2081 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 1 & & \\
 & & & \\
 2082 &:= (Q((Q(2)) - 0!)! + C(8)) \times 2 & & \\
 2082 &:= 2 + T(8^2) & & \\
 2082 &:= F(C(2) + 0!) + C(8) \times Q(2) & & \\
 2082 &:= F(Q(0! + 2)) + (1/2) \times Q(Q(8)) & & \\
 2082 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 2 & & \\
 2082 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 2 & & \\
 2082 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 2 & & \\
 2082 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 2 & & \\
 2082 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 2 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2083 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2))) + 0!) \times 8 + C(3) & 2086 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 6 \\
 2083 &:= F(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 0! + Q(Q(8))/F(3) & 2086 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 6 \\
 2083 &:= T(2) + T(0! + T(8)) + C(3) & 2086 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 6 \\
 2083 &:= T(2) + T(8^{F(3)}) & 2086 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 6 \\
 2083 &:= -T(2) + T(Q(8)) + T(3) & 2086 &:= T(T(2)) + T(8 \times F(6)) \\
 2083 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 3 & 2086 &:= T(T(2)) + T(C(8)/F(6)) \\
 2083 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 3 & 2086 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 6 \\
 2083 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 3 & & \\
 2083 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 3 & & \\
 2083 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 3 & & \\
 & & 2087 &:= C(2) - 0! + T(T(8) + T(7)) \\
 & & 2087 &:= F(Q(Q(2)) + 0!) + Q(F(8)) + Q(7) \\
 & & 2087 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 7 \\
 2084 &:= (C(2) + 0! + C(8)) \times 4 & 2087 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 7 \\
 2084 &:= Q((2 + 0!)!) + 8 \times Q(Q(4)) & 2087 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 7 \\
 2084 &:= Q((2 + 0!)!) + Q(Q(8))/\sqrt{4} & 2087 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 7 \\
 2084 &:= Q(2) + T(\sqrt{8^4}) & 2087 &:= T(T(2)) + 0! + T(T(7) + T(8)) \\
 2084 &:= T(2) + 0! + T(8^{F(F(4))}) & 2087 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 7 \\
 2084 &:= T(2) + 0! + T(\sqrt{8^4}) & & \\
 2084 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 4 & 2088 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + 0! + T(8)) \times T(8) \\
 2084 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 4 & 2088 &:= C(2) + T(8 \times 8) \\
 2084 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 4 & 2088 &:= F(T(T(2))) + T(8 \times 8) \\
 2084 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 4 & 2088 &:= -Q(2)! \times (0! - 88) \\
 2084 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 4 & 2088 &:= Q(T(2)) - 0! + T(8 \times 8) \\
 & & 2088 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 8 \\
 & & 2088 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 8 \\
 & & 2088 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 8 \\
 & & 2088 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 8 \\
 & & 2088 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 8 \\
 2085 &:= (Q(2) + 0!) \times Q(F(8)) - 5! & & \\
 2085 &:= 2 \times T(T(0! + 8)) + T(5) & 2089 &:= (2 + 0!)!! + Q(Q(8) - C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 2085 &:= C(F(-0! + C(2))) + (8 - 5!) & 2089 &:= -C(2) + 9 \times F(F(8 - 0!)) \\
 2085 &:= -F(2) + F(0! + F(8)) - C(Q(5)) & 2089 &:= F(2) + (-0! - T(F(8))) \times (-9) \\
 2085 &:= T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 & 2089 &:= -Q(2) \times (0! - C(8)) + T(9) \\
 2085 &:= T(C(2) \times 08) + 5 & 2089 &:= Q(2 \times 0 + 8) + Q(T(9)) \\
 2085 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) \times 08) + 5 & 2089 &:= Q(F(Q(2)) + F(8 + 0!)) + (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 2085 &:= T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 5 & & \\
 2085 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 5 & & \\
 2086 &:= -(F(Q(Q(2))) - 0! - 6 \times C(8)) & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2089 := Q(Q(2) + Q(-0! + 8)) - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$2089 := Q(T(2)) + T(0! + F(8) \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$2089 := T(2\sqrt{T(8)}) + 9$$

$$2089 := T(C(2) \times 08) + 9$$

$$2089 := T(F(T(T(2)))) \times 08 + 9$$

$$2089 := T(Q(2 \times 0 + 8)) + 9$$

$$2089 := T(T(T(T(2)) + 0!) + T(8)) + 9$$

$$2090 := C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 0$$

$$2090 := F(Q(2))!! + 0! + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!) + 0!)$$

$$2090 := Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 0$$

$$2090 := T(0! + T(2)) + T(C(\sqrt{9} + 0!))$$

$$2090 := T(Q(2)) + T(\sqrt{0! + T(90)})$$

$$2090 := T(T(2) + 0!) + T(C(\sqrt{9} + 0!))$$

$$2091 := C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 1$$

$$2091 := Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 1$$

$$2091 := T(Q(2)) + 0! + T(Q(9 - 1))$$

$$2092 := (0! + T(2)) \times (T(T(9)) - C(C(2)))$$

$$2092 := (-C(C(2)) \times 0! + T(T(9))) \times Q(2)$$

$$2092 := (Q(Q(2)! - 0!) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times Q(2)$$

$$2092 := C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 2$$

$$2092 := F(C(2)) \times Q(0! + 9) - C(2)$$

$$2092 := Q((2 \times 0)! + T(9)) - Q(2)!$$

$$2092 := -Q(2)! \times 0! + Q(T(9) + F(2))$$

$$2092 := Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 2$$

$$2092 := T(T(T(2))) + 0! + 2 \times T(T(9))$$

$$2093 := 2 \times (0! + T(T(9))) + T(T(3))$$

$$2093 := -2 + Q(0! + T(9)) - T(T(3))$$

$$2093 := C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 3$$

$$2093 := F(C(2)) + (0! + T(T(9))) \times F(3)$$

$$2093 := F(C(2) + 0!) + Q(T(9)) + F(Q(3))$$

$$2093 := Q(2) + Q(0! + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + 3!!$$

$$2093 := Q(2 + F(0! + 9)) - Q(F(Q(3)))$$

$$2093 := -Q(C(2)) + (-0! + (\sqrt{9})!!) \times 3$$

$$2093 := Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 3$$

$$2093 := Q(Q(C(2)) - 0!) - Q(F(9)) - 3!!$$

$$2093 := T(T(F(-2 + 9)))/F(3)$$

$$2094 := (C(-0! + C(2)) + (\sqrt{9})!) \times F(4)!$$

$$2094 := (Q(2) + 0!)! + F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(Q(4))$$

$$2094 := 2 \times T(T(9)) + 4!$$

$$2094 := -20 + F(9) + T(C(4))$$

$$2094 := C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 4$$

$$2094 := Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 4$$

$$2094 := -T(20) + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(4))$$

$$2094 := T(T(2)) - 0! + 9 + T(C(4))$$

$$2095 := 2 \times T(T(9)) + Q(5)$$

$$2095 := C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 5$$

$$2095 := F(C(2)) \times Q(0! + 9) - 5$$

$$2095 := F(Q(2))!! + F(0! + 9) \times Q(5)$$

$$2095 := Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 5$$

$$2095 := T((T(2) + 0!)^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(5)$$

$$2095 := T(0! + Q(2)) + T(C(9 - 5))$$

$$2095 := T(2^{T(\sqrt{9})}) + T(5)$$

$$2095 := T(20 + F(9)) + F(T(5))$$

$$2095 := T(T(T(T(2) + 0!)) + 9) + T(5)$$

$$2096 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 0!) \times 9 + F(6)$$

$$2096 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 0!) + 9 \times F(6)$$

$$2096 := C(2) \times (0! + T(9) + C(6))$$

$$2096 := C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 6$$

$$2096 := Q(20) \times F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$2096 := -Q(C(2)) \times 0! + \sqrt{9} \times 6!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2096 &:= Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 6 \\
 2096 &:= Q(Q(2)!) - 0! + Q(\sqrt{9} + Q(6)) \\
 2096 &:= Q(Q(2)) + T(0! + \sqrt{9} \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 2097 &:= (2 \times 0 + 9) \times F(F(7)) \\
 2097 &:= C(C(2)) \times (0! + \sqrt{9}) + Q(7) \\
 2097 &:= C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 7 \\
 2097 &:= Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 7 \\
 2097 &:= Q(C(2) + 0!) + T(9 \times 7) \\
 2097 &:= Q(Q(2)!) - (0 - Q(Q(9))) - 7! \\
 2097 &:= Q(T(2)) \times F(F(0 \times 9 + 7)) \\
 2097 &:= Q(T(2)) + Q(0! + T(9)) - T(7) \\
 2097 &:= T(T(2))! - 0! + T(T(9) + 7) \\
 2097 &:= T(T(C(2))) + T(0! + T(9) + 7) \\
 \\
 2098 &:= 2 \times 9 + T(Q(8)) \\
 2098 &:= -2 + Q(0! + 9) \times F(8) \\
 2098 &:= C(C(2) + 0!) + Q(Q(8) - C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 2098 &:= C(C(2) + 0!) + Q(T(9) - 8) \\
 2098 &:= C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 8 \\
 2098 &:= Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 8 \\
 2098 &:= T(T(2))! + T(-0! + T(9) + 8) \\
 2098 &:= T(T(C(2))) + 0! + T(8 + T(9)) \\
 \\
 2099 &:= -(T(F(T(T(2)))) - T(F(0! + 9)) - T(F(9))) \\
 2099 &:= 2 \times (0! + T(T(9))) + C(\sqrt{9}) \\
 2099 &:= 2 + 9 \times F(F(0! + (\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 2099 &:= 20 + 9 \times T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 2099 &:= 9 \times F(F(-0! + C(2))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 2099 &:= -C(2) + 0! + Q(9) + Q(T(9)) \\
 2099 &:= -C(2) - C(-0! + C(\sqrt{9})) + C(C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 2099 &:= -C(2) - C(-0! + \sqrt{C(9)}) + C(\sqrt{C(9)}) \\
 2099 &:= C(Q(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 9 \\
 2099 &:= C(T(2)) + (0! + T(T(9))) \times F(\sqrt{9})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2099 &:= Q(C(2)) + 0! + Q(T(9)) + 9 \\
 2099 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) \times F(F(0! + (\sqrt{9})!)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 2099 &:= T(2) - Q(0! + F(9)) + T(Q(9)) \\
 2099 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 0!))) - T(F(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(F(9)) \\
 2099 &:= -T(T(2)) - 0! + Q(T(9)) + Q(9) \\
 \\
 2100 &:= 100 \times F(C(2)) \\
 2100 &:= 100 \times F(F(F(Q(2))!)) \\
 2100 &:= 100 \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 2100 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 0 \\
 2100 &:= F(F(F(Q(2))!)) \times Q(10) + 0 \\
 2100 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 0 \\
 \\
 2101 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 1 \\
 2101 &:= F(F(F(Q(2))!)) \times Q(10) + 1 \\
 2101 &:= T(C(T(2) + 1)) + F(C(1 + 0!)) \\
 2101 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 1 \\
 2101 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(C(1 + T(0! + 1))) \\
 2101 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(C(Q(1 + 1))) \\
 \\
 2102 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 2 \\
 2102 &:= F(F(F(Q(2))!)) \times Q(10) + 2 \\
 2102 &:= Q(F(F(Q(2))!)) + Q(F(10)) - F(Q(Q(2))) \\
 2102 &:= T(C(T(2) + 1)) + 0! + F(C(2)) \\
 2102 &:= T(Q(C(2))) - 1 - 0! + Q(2)! \\
 2102 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 2 \\
 2102 &:= T(T(T(2))) + 1 + T(C(0! + T(2))) \\
 \\
 2103 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 3 \\
 2103 &:= F(F(F(Q(2))!)) \times Q(10) + 3 \\
 2103 &:= F(Q(2)) + Q(10) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 2103 &:= T(2) + Q(10) \times T(T(3)) \\
 2103 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2104 &:= (T(2) + 1)! + T(C(4)) & 2107 &:= T(F(T(T(2)))) + F(10) + T(F(7)) \\
 2104 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 4 & 2107 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 7 \\
 2104 &:= F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(10) + 4 \\
 2104 &:= F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(10) - Q(Q(F(4)!)) & 2108 &:= C(2) + Q(10) \times F(8) \\
 2104 &:= Q(2)! + T(C(4)) & 2108 &:= -C(2) + Q(10 + T(8)) \\
 2104 &:= Q(2)! + T(Q((0! + 1) \times 4)) & 2108 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 8 \\
 2104 &:= Q(2)! + T(Q(F(10 - 4))) & 2108 &:= F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(10) + 8 \\
 2104 &:= T(2^{T(T(1+0!))}) + 4! & 2108 &:= F(F(Q(2)!)) + Q(10) \times F(8) \\
 2104 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 4 & 2108 &:= T(C(T(2) + 1)) + T(-0! + 8) \\
 & & 2108 &:= T(F(2) + T(10)) + C(8) \\
 2105 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 5 & 2108 &:= T(T(2 + 1) + 0!) + T(Q(8)) \\
 2105 &:= F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(10) + 5 & 2108 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 8 \\
 2105 &:= T(C(2)) \times T(10) + C(5) \\
 2105 &:= T(C(2)^{1+0!}) + Q(5) & 2109 &:= -C(2) + 1 + Q(0! + T(9)) \\
 2105 &:= T(Q(-2 + 10)) + Q(5) & 2109 &:= C(C(2)) + F(C(1 + 0!)) + 9 \\
 2105 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 5 & 2109 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 9 \\
 & & 2109 &:= F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(10) + 9 \\
 2106 &:= C(T(2)) \times T((0! + 1) \times 6) & 2109 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(10) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 2106 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 6 & 2109 &:= T(2) \times T(1 + T(-0! + 9)) \\
 2106 &:= F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(10) + 6 & 2109 &:= T(2) \times T(1 + T(F(T(\sqrt{9})))) \\
 2106 &:= F(Q(2)! + Q(10) \times F(F(6))) & 2109 &:= T(2) \times T(10 + C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 2106 &:= T(T(2))! + T(T(1 + 0!)) \times T(T(6)) & 2109 &:= T(2) \times T(T(1 + 0!)) + F(9) \\
 2106 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(-10 + T(F(6))) & 2109 &:= -T(T(2)) - 1 + Q(0! + T(9)) \\
 2106 &:= T(T(2)) + Q(10) \times T(6) & 2109 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 9 \\
 2106 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times Q(10) + 6 \\
 & & 2110 &:= -(Q(T(Q(2))) - T(T(11)) + 0!) \\
 2107 &:= (F(Q(F(Q(2)))) + Q(F(Q(0! + 1)))) \times Q(7) & 2111 &:= -Q(T(Q(2))) + T(T(11)) \\
 2107 &:= (T((T(2) + 1)!) + 0!) \times 7 & 2111 &:= T(C(Q(2)) + 1) - F(Q(T(1 + 1))) \\
 2107 &:= (T(Q(2)!) + 1) \times 7 \\
 2107 &:= C(C(T(2))) - C(-1 - 0! + T(7)) & 2112 &:= (Q(Q(2)! - 1) - 1) \times Q(2) \\
 2107 &:= C(T(2)) + T(Q(1 + 7)) & 2112 &:= (T(C(T(2)) - 1) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \\
 2107 &:= F(C(2)) \times Q(10) + 7 & 2112 &:= (T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + 1) + 1) \times T(2) \\
 2107 &:= F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times Q(10) + 7 & 2112 &:= 11 \times Q(2)! \times C(2) \\
 2107 &:= T(C(2) + T(10)) + T(F(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2112 := 2 \times Q(Q(2)) \times T(11)$$

$$2112 := C(2) \times T(11) \times Q(2)$$

$$2112 := Q(2)! \times (F(11) - F(2))$$

$$2113 := (Q(Q(C(2)) + 1) + 1)/F(3)$$

$$2113 := (Q(Q(F(F(Q(2))!)) + 1) + 1)/F(3)$$

$$2113 := -C(Q(2)) + T(T(11)) - F(Q(3))$$

$$2113 := -T(2) + Q(1 + T(Q(3)))$$

$$2113 := T(Q(C(2))) + 11 \times 3$$

$$2114 := C(Q(F(Q(2)))) + F(11) + Q(Q(F(4)!))$$

$$2114 := F(C(2) + 1) + T(C(4))$$

$$2114 := F(Q(2 + 1)) + T(C(4))$$

$$2114 := T(2) + T(T(11)) - Q(T(4))$$

$$2114 := T(C(2)) - (1 + 1) + T(C(4))$$

$$2114 := T(Q(2)) + Q(1 + 1)! + T(C(4))$$

$$2115 := (C(C(2)) - F(11)) \times 5$$

$$2115 := -F(2) + Q(F(F(F(Q(1 + 1))!)) + Q(5))$$

$$2115 := Q(2)! + T(T(11)) - 5!$$

$$2115 := T(2) \times (T(T(1 + 1))! - T(5))$$

$$2115 := T(C(2)) - 1 + T(C(-1 + 5))$$

$$2116 := Q(-2 + 1) + Q(1 + 6))$$

$$2116 := T(-2 + T(11)) + T(F(6))$$

$$2116 := T(C(2)) + T((1 + 1)^6)$$

$$2117 := F(2) + Q(-F(Q(1 + 1)) + Q(7))$$

$$2117 := -Q(C(2)) - Q(Q(1 + 1)) + C(F(7))$$

$$2117 := Q(T(T(2))) + 1 + T(Q(1 + 7))$$

$$2117 := -T(2) + T(T(11)) - T(F(7))$$

$$2117 := T(C(2)) + 1 + T(Q(1 + 7))$$

$$2117 := T(-C(2) + T(11)) + T(T(7))$$

$$2118 := 2 + Q(1 + T(1 + 8))$$

$$2119 := F(Q(Q(2))) - Q(1 + 1)! + Q(F(9))$$

$$2119 := T(2) + Q(1 + T(9))$$

$$2120 := Q(2) \times (1 + Q(Q(2)! - 0!))$$

$$2120 := Q(2) + Q(1 + T(C(2) + 0!))$$

$$2120 := Q(2) + Q(T(Q(1 + 2)) + 0!)$$

$$2121 := (Q(T(Q(2))) + 1) \times 21$$

$$2121 := F(C(2)) \times (1 + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 1)$$

$$2121 := F(F(F(Q(2))!)) \times (1 + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + 1)$$

$$2121 := -Q(2)! + T(C(Q(2)) + 1)$$

$$2122 := F(Q(2))! + Q((-1 + Q(2)!) \times 2)$$

$$2122 := T(C(T(2) + 1)) + T(C(2)) + T(T(2))$$

$$2122 := T(F(C(2))) + T(F(C(2) + 1) + C(T(2)))$$

$$2122 := T(T(2)) \times C(C(2) - 1) + C(Q(2))$$

$$2122 := T(T(2)) \times C(C(2) - 1) + Q(C(2))$$

$$2122 := T(T(2)) + Q(1 + T(T(2)^2))$$

$$2122 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(F(T(T(2) + 1)) + T(T(2)))$$

$$2122 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(T(2) + 1)) + T(T(2)))$$

$$2123 := -(T(F(T(T(2)))) + (1 - T(2) \times T(3)!))$$

$$2123 := -C(Q(2)) + T(2) \times C(Q(3))$$

$$2123 := -Q(C(2)) + (1 + 2) \times C(Q(3))$$

$$2123 := -Q(C(2)) + F(Q(2)) \times C(Q(3))$$

$$2123 := -Q(C(2)) + T(2) \times C(Q(3))$$

$$2123 := Q(Q(Q(2 + 1)))/F(Q(2)) - Q(F(3!))$$

$$2123 := -T(C(2)) - 1 + T(2) \times T(3)!$$

$$2123 := T(T(2)) + 1 + Q(F(2) + T(Q(3)))$$

$$2123 := T(T(2)) + 1 + Q(T(Q(2)) + Q(T(3)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2124 &:= (2 + Q(Q(2)! - 1)) \times 4 \\
 2124 &:= (C(C(2) + 1) - F(C(2))) \times F(4) \\
 2124 &:= (C(Q(2 + 1)) - F(C(2))) \times F(4) \\
 2124 &:= (F(Q(Q(2)) - 1) - Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times F(4)! \\
 2124 &:= (T(T(2))! - 12) \times F(4) \\
 2124 &:= (T(T(2))! - 12) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 2124 &:= -21 + T(F(2) + C(4)) \\
 2124 &:= C(2) + Q((-1 + Q(2)!) \times \sqrt{4}) \\
 2124 &:= Q(2)! + (T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(4!) \\
 2124 &:= T(C(2)) \times (-1 - Q(2) + C(4)) \\
 2124 &:= T(C(2)) + C(2) + T(C(4)) \\
 2124 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(-1 + T(F(2) + T(4))) \\
 2124 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(4))) \\
 \\
 2125 &:= (C(2) + 1 + C(2)) \times C(5) \\
 2125 &:= (C(2) + Q(1 + 2)) \times C(5) \\
 2125 &:= (Q(2) + Q(Q(1 + 2))) \times Q(5) \\
 2125 &:= Q(T(2)) + Q(1 + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 2126 &:= 2 \times (C(-1 + C(2)) + 6!) \\
 2126 &:= -F(F(T(T(2))) + 1) + T(2) \times 6! \\
 2126 &:= -F(Q(2 + 1)) + F(Q(2)) \times 6! \\
 2126 &:= -F(Q(2 + 1)) + T(2) \times 6! \\
 2126 &:= T(Q(2)) + Q(1 + T(T(2) + 6)) \\
 \\
 2127 &:= (-1 + C(2))! - C(C(2)) - Q(Q(7)) \\
 2127 &:= -(Q(Q(2)!) + (1 - Q(Q(2) \times F(7)))) \\
 2127 &:= C(2) - T(12) + C(F(7)) \\
 2127 &:= C(Q(2)) \times F(Q(1 + 2)) - Q(7) \\
 2127 &:= C(T(2)) + 7 \times T((T(2) + 1)!) \\
 2127 &:= F(Q(T(2))) - (1 - Q(2)!) \times T(F(7)) \\
 2127 &:= T(Q(2)) + 1 + Q(-T(2) + Q(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2128 &:= (Q(F(Q(2))) + 1 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 8 \\
 2128 &:= (T(F(T(T(2)))) - 1 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 8 \\
 2128 &:= 12 \times Q(2) + T(Q(8)) \\
 2128 &:= C(2) \times (-1 + T(C(2)) + T(F(8))) \\
 2128 &:= C(2) \times T(1 + 2) + T(Q(8)) \\
 2128 &:= Q(2) \times (-1 + C(C(2)) + F(8)) \\
 2128 &:= -Q(Q(2)!) + Q(-12 + Q(8)) \\
 2128 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (C(1 + Q(2)) + 8) \\
 2128 &:= T(C(T(2) + 1)) + 8 \times T(T(2)) \\
 \\
 2129 &:= (Q(2) + 1)! - Q(Q(2)) + Q(T(9)) \\
 2129 &:= (T(T(2))! + 1) \times T(2) - F(9) \\
 2129 &:= C(C(2)) \times Q(2) + Q(9) \\
 2129 &:= C(C(2)) + (-1 + C(2)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 2129 &:= C(F(C(2) - 1)) - 2 \times F(9) \\
 2129 &:= F(C(2) - 1) + Q(T(9) + F(2)) \\
 2129 &:= Q(C(2) - 1) + T(Q(2)^{\sqrt{9}}) \\
 2129 &:= Q(Q(2)! - 1) + Q(Q(2) + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 2129 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) \times F((1 + 2)!) + Q(9) \\
 2129 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) - T(T(2)) + T(F(9)) \\
 \\
 2130 &:= -Q(Q(T(2))) + T(T(T(1 + 3) + 0!)) \\
 2130 &:= T(C(Q(2))) + 1 + Q(0! + T(3)) \\
 2130 &:= T(Q(C(2))) + 1 + Q(0! + T(3)) \\
 \\
 2131 &:= T(Q(2) + 1) + Q(1 + T(Q(3))) \\
 \\
 2132 &:= (C(C(2)) + F(-1 + Q(3))) \times Q(2) \\
 2132 &:= (T(2) + 1) \times (T(T(3)) + C(C(2))) \\
 2132 &:= -Q(C(2)) - 1 + C(Q(3) + Q(2)) \\
 2132 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(1 + 3!/Q(Q(2))) \\
 2132 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(1 + T(3^2)) \\
 2132 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(1 + 3!) - F(Q(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2132 := -T(T(T(2)) + 1) + T(2) \times T(3)!$$

$$2133 := ((2 + 1)!! - Q(3)) \times 3$$

$$2133 := (2 + 1) \times 3!! - C(3)$$

$$2133 := (21 + C(3!)) \times Q(3)$$

$$2133 := (F(T(T(2))) + 1) \times (T(3) + T(T(T(3))))$$

$$2133 := (Q(2) + F(13)) \times Q(3)$$

$$2133 := (T(21) + T(3)) \times Q(3)$$

$$2133 := 3 \times (-C(2) - 1 + T(3)!)$$

$$2133 := T(2) \times (-1 + T(3)! - F(T(3)))$$

$$2134 := (F(T(T(2))) + 1) \times T(T(T(3))) + F(T(4))$$

$$2134 := 2 \times (-1 + Q(Q(3)) + F(Q(4)))$$

$$2134 := 2 \times C(3) + T(C(4))$$

$$2134 := F(2) + C(13) - C(4)$$

$$2134 := -Q(C(2)) + 1 + C(Q(3) + 4)$$

$$2134 := T(21) \times Q(3) + T(T(4))$$

$$2135 := (1/3) \times F(F(C(2)) - 1) - 5!$$

$$2135 := (2 + 1) \times 3!! - Q(5)$$

$$2135 := (F(C(2)) + T(1 + C(3))) \times 5$$

$$2135 := (Q(C(2)) - 1) + T(C(3)) \times 5$$

$$2135 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(1 + C(3))) \times 5$$

$$2135 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1 + T(3)))) \times 5$$

$$2135 := F(Q(2)) \times 3!! - Q(5)$$

$$2135 := T(2) \times T(3)! - Q(5)$$

$$2136 := (2 + 1) \times (3!! - F(6))$$

$$2136 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(1 + Q(3))) \times 6$$

$$2136 := (T(2) + 1)! \times F(3 + F(6))$$

$$2136 := (T(F(T(2 + 1))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times F(6)$$

$$2136 := C(2)!/T(T(3)) + C(6)$$

$$2136 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 - Q(3) + 6!)$$

$$2136 := -Q(2)! + 3 \times 6!$$

$$2136 := T(2) \times (-1 + T(3)!) - T(6)$$

$$2136 := T(2) \times (1 - Q(3) + 6!)$$

$$2136 := T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) + T(3 \times T(6))$$

$$2137 := (F(C(2)) - 1) \times (-3) + C(F(7))$$

$$2137 := 21 + Q(-3 + Q(7))$$

$$2137 := -C(2) + T((-1 + T(3)) \times F(7))$$

$$2137 := -C(2) + T(1 + C(-3 + 7))$$

$$2137 := -C(2) + T(Q(1 + 3) + Q(7))$$

$$2137 := F(C(2)) + Q(-3 + Q(7))$$

$$2137 := -F(T(T(2))) + T((-1 + T(3)) \times F(7))$$

$$2138 := C(Q(2)) - T(3) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2138 := -F(C(2)) - 1 + 3 \times (\sqrt{T(8)})!$$

$$2138 := Q(C(2)) - T(3) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2138 := Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1) + Q(C(Q(F(3)))) - F(8)$$

$$2138 := Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1) + Q(Q(F(3)!)) - F(8)$$

$$2138 := T(2) + T(T(1 + 3)) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2138 := -T(T(T(2))) - 1 + 3 \times (\sqrt{T(8)})!$$

$$2139 := (1 - C(2) + 3!!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2139 := (1 - C(2) + T(3)!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2139 := (Q(2) + 1)! - T(3) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2139 := (-Q(Q(2)) + C(Q(3))) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2139 := -(T(T(2)) + 1 - T(3)!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2139 := -21 + 3!! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2139 := -F(Q(2)) \times (Q(1 + 3) - C(9))$$

$$2139 := -Q(2) + F(Q(1 + 3)) + Q(F(9))$$

$$2139 := T(2) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) \times F(9))$$

$$2139 := -T(2) \times (Q(1 + 3) - C(9))$$

$$2139 := T(F(2) + C(1 + 3)) - T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$2139 := T(F(2) + T(13))/F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$2139 := -T(T(2)) + T(-1 + T(T(3)) + T(9))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2140 &:= -1 - Q(2) + T(0! + C(4)) \\
 2140 &:= Q(2)! + Q(1 + T(T(4) - 0!)) \\
 2140 &:= -T(T(2)) + 1 + T(C(4) + 0!) \\
 2141 &:= (Q(C(2)) - 1) \times F(Q(F(4))) - 1 \\
 2141 &:= F(Q(Q(2))) - 1 + Q(F(Q(F(4)))) - 1 \\
 2141 &:= -Q(2) + T(-1 + T(T(4) + 1)) \\
 2141 &:= -Q(2) + T(C(4) + 1) \\
 2141 &:= -T(2) - 1 + T(1 + C(4)) \\
 2142 &:= ((2 + 1)!! - F(4)!) \times F(Q(2)) \\
 2142 &:= F(C(2)) \times (T(14) - T(2)) \\
 2142 &:= F(C(2) + 1) \times (C(4) - F(2)) \\
 2142 &:= F(Q(2 + 1)) \times (C(4) - F(2)) \\
 2142 &:= -T(2) + T(1 + 4^{T(2)}) \\
 2142 &:= -T(2) + T(-1 + C(4) + 2) \\
 2142 &:= -T(2) + T(1 + Q(4 \times 2)) \\
 2143 &:= -2 + T(1 + 4^3) \\
 2143 &:= C(F(C(2) - 1)) - \sqrt{4} \times C(3) \\
 2143 &:= Q(2 \times (-1 + 4!)) + C(3) \\
 2143 &:= -Q(21) + F(\sqrt{4} \times Q(3)) \\
 2144 &:= (2 + 1)!! \times F(4) - Q(4) \\
 2144 &:= (-2 + T(Q(4))) \times Q(4) \\
 2144 &:= -(2 - 1) + T(T(4) + T(T(4))) \\
 2144 &:= (C(C(2)) + 4!) \times 4 \\
 2144 &:= C(4 \times (2 - 1)) + T(C(4)) \\
 2144 &:= C(Q(2)) + T(C(4 \times 1^4)) \\
 2144 &:= -F(2) + T(1^4 + C(4)) \\
 2144 &:= -F(2) + T(1 + 4^{F(4)}) \\
 2144 &:= -F(2) + T(1 + Q(4 + 4)) \\
 2144 &:= Q(C(2)) + T(C(4 \times 1^4)) \\
 2145 &:= (2 + 1) \times (F(4)!! - 5) \\
 2145 &:= (Q(2) + 1)! + Q(45) \\
 2145 &:= -Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 5)) \\
 2145 &:= T((C(2) + 1 + 4) \times 5) \\
 2145 &:= T((T(2) + T(4)) \times 5) \\
 2145 &:= T(5 \times F(2 + 1 + 4)) \\
 2146 &:= (T(C(2)) + 1) \times (C(4) - 6) \\
 2146 &:= F(2) + T(1 + \sqrt{4^6}) \\
 2146 &:= F(2) + T(-1 + T(F(4) + F(6))) \\
 2146 &:= F(Q(Q(2)) - 1) + 6 \times Q(Q(4)) \\
 2146 &:= T(Q(T(2))) + 1 + Q(T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 2147 &:= (2 + 1)!! \times F(4) - F(7) \\
 2147 &:= 2 + T(-1 + T(4 + 7)) \\
 2147 &:= 2 - Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2148 &:= (2 + 1)!! + F(Q(4)) + Q(F(8)) \\
 2148 &:= Q(2) \times (Q(-1 + 4!) + 8) \\
 2148 &:= Q(2) \times (Q(1 + 4) + C(8)) \\
 2148 &:= T(2) + T(1^4 + Q(8)) \\
 2148 &:= -T(2) + T(1 + C(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 2148 &:= T(2) + T(1 + \sqrt{4}^{\sqrt{T(8)}}) \\
 2148 &:= T(2) + T(-1 + T(F(4) + 8)) \\
 2148 &:= -T(2) + T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \\
 2148 &:= -T(2) + T(C(4) + 1) + \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 2149 &:= (2 + 1)! + F(Q(4)) + Q(F(9)) \\
 2149 &:= -2 + T(1 + C(4)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 2149 &:= -C(2 + 1) + C(4) \times F(9) \\
 2149 &:= Q(2) + T(-Q(4) + Q(9)) \\
 2149 &:= -T(21) + 4 \times T(F(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2150 &:= (C(T(T(2))) - 1) \times T(5 - 0!) \\ 2150 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) \times 0! \\ 2150 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 0 \\ 2150 &:= T(Q(2)) \times (C(1 + 5) - 0!) \\ 2150 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2151 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 1 \\ 2151 &:= T(T(2)) + T(1 + C(5 - 1)) \\ 2151 &:= T(T(2)) + T(1 + Q(F(5 + 1))) \\ 2151 &:= T(T(2)) + T(-1 + T(\sqrt{5! + 1})) \\ 2151 &:= T(T(2)) + T(-1 + T(\sqrt{T(T(5)) + 1})) \\ 2151 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2152 &:= (C(C(2)) + 1 + Q(5)) \times Q(2) \\ 2152 &:= (F(Q(Q(2))) + F(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 2 \\ 2152 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times T(1 + T(5)) - Q(2)! \\ 2152 &:= T(2) \times (1 + 5)! - C(2) \\ 2152 &:= T(2) \times (1 + 5)! - F(T(T(2))) \\ 2152 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 2 \\ 2152 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2153 &:= C(2) + T(1 + Q(5 + 3)) \\ 2153 &:= C(2) + T(-1 + T(5 + T(3))) \\ 2153 &:= C(F(C(2) - 1)) - C(5) + Q(Q(3)) \\ 2153 &:= -F(Q(Q(2)) + 1) + Q(Q(5)) \times 3! \\ 2153 &:= F(T(T(2))) + T(1 + Q(5 + 3)) \\ 2153 &:= F(T(T(2))) + T(-1 + T(5 + T(3))) \\ 2153 &:= Q(T(T(2))) + 1 + Q(Q(5) + T(T(3))) \\ 2153 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 3 \\ 2153 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$2154 := (-2 + (1 + 5)!) \times F(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2154 &:= T(2) \times ((1 + 5)! - \sqrt{4}) \\ 2154 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 4 \\ 2154 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-1 + T(5) \times 4!) \\ 2154 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-1 + T(T(5)) \times F(4)) \\ 2154 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-1 + T(T(5)) \times T(\sqrt{4})) \\ 2154 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2155 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (1 + 5)! - 5 \\ 2155 &:= T(2) \times (1 + 5)! - 5 \\ 2155 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 5 \\ 2155 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2156 &:= (F(C(2)) + 1) \times (F(T(5)) - C(F(6))) \\ 2156 &:= -F(T(T(2) + 1)) + T(T(5 + 6)) \\ 2156 &:= Q(2) \times (-1 + T(5) \times Q(6)) \\ 2156 &:= -Q(2) + F(-1 + 5) \times 6! \\ 2156 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 6 \\ 2156 &:= -T(T(T(2) + 1)) + T(T(5 + 6)) \\ 2156 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2157 &:= (F(C(2)) - 1) \times C(5) - C(7) \\ 2157 &:= (F(Q(2))! - 1) \times F(Q(-5 - 7)) \\ 2157 &:= (T(T(2))! - 1) \times T(-5 + 7) \\ 2157 &:= Q(2 \times Q(5)) - C(7) \\ 2157 &:= Q(Q(2 + 1)) - T(Q(5)) + Q(Q(7)) \\ 2157 &:= T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 7 \\ 2157 &:= T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2158 &:= -2 + T(-1 + 5) \times C(\sqrt{T(8)}) \\ 2158 &:= -2 + T(\sqrt{-1 + 5}) \times (\sqrt{T(8)})! \\ 2158 &:= F(C(2)) \times (-1 + Q(Q(5))) - F(F(8)) \\ 2158 &:= F(Q(Q(2)) + 1) + Q(Q(5)) - Q(8) \\ 2158 &:= T(2 \times (1 + 5)) + T(Q(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$2158 := T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 8$$

$$2158 := T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 8$$

$$2159 := -2 + T(1 + T(5)) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2159 := -C(T(T(2) + 1)) + C(T(5)) - C(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$2159 := -F(2) + (1 + 5)! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2159 := Q(2 + 1) + C(5) + Q(T(9))$$

$$2159 := Q(Q(C(2))) - 1 - Q(C(5) - Q(9))$$

$$2159 := T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + F(T(5)) + 9$$

$$2159 := T(T(T(Q(2)))) + F(15) + 9$$

$$2160 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 0$$

$$2160 := 60 \times T(F(T(2 + 1)))$$

$$2160 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 0$$

$$2161 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 1$$

$$2161 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 1$$

$$2162 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 2$$

$$2162 := 2 \times T(1 + T(F(6) + F(2)))$$

$$2162 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 2$$

$$2163 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 3$$

$$2163 := (F(T(T(2) + 1)) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 3$$

$$2163 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 3$$

$$2164 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 4$$

$$2164 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 4$$

$$2164 := T(2) \times T(1 + T(F(6))) + F(T(4))$$

$$2165 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 5$$

$$2165 := (Q(21) - F(6)) \times 5$$

$$2165 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 5$$

$$2166 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 6$$

$$2166 := 6 \times Q(Q(Q(2) + 1) - 6)$$

$$2166 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 6$$

$$2167 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 7$$

$$2167 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 7$$

$$2168 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 8$$

$$2168 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 8$$

$$2169 := (2 + 1) \times (-6 + C(9))$$

$$2169 := (2 + 1) \times 6! + 9$$

$$2169 := T(2) \times 1 \times 6! + 9$$

$$2170 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 0$$

$$2170 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 0$$

$$2171 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 1$$

$$2171 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 1$$

$$2172 := (Q(2) + (-1 + 7)!) \times F(Q(2))$$

$$2172 := (Q(2) + (-1 + 7)!) \times T(2)$$

$$2172 := -(Q(Q(Q(2)) - 1) - Q(Q(7)) + Q(2))$$

$$2172 := (T(F(F(T(T(2)))) + 1) - F(F(7))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$2172 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 2$$

$$2172 := C(T(2)) + T(1 + C(7 - T(2)))$$

$$2172 := C(T(2)) + T(Q(1 + 7) + F(2))$$

$$2172 := Q(Q(C(2))) - Q(1 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(2)!)$$

$$2172 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 2$$

$$2173 := -(Q(Q(Q(2)) - 1) - Q(Q(7)) + 3)$$

$$2173 := -(T(2) + 1)! + C(7 + T(3))$$

$$2173 := -(T(2) + 1)! + F(7)^3$$

$$2173 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 3$$

$$2173 := -Q(2)! + C(7 + 3!)$$

$$2173 := -Q(2)! + C(7 + T(3))$$

$$2173 := -Q(2)! + F(7)^3$$

$$2173 := Q(-2 + Q(7)) - Q(3!)$$

$$2173 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 3$$

$$2173 := -T(C(2)) + Q(Q(7) - F(3))$$

$$2174 := -(Q(Q(Q(2)) - 1) - Q(Q(7)) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$2174 := (T(2) + 1)! \times T(F(7)) - T(4)$$

$$2174 := -(T(F(T(T(2)))) + (1 - T(T(7 + 4))))$$

$$2174 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 4$$

$$2174 := F(2) + F(17) + Q(4!)$$

$$2174 := T(2) + T(F(7)) + T(C(4))$$

$$2174 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 4$$

$$2174 := -T(C(2)) - 1 + T(T(7 + 4))$$

$$2174 := T(Q(2 + 1)) + Q(7) + T(C(4))$$

$$2175 := -(C(2) - T(17)) \times T(5)$$

$$2175 := (F(2) + F(-1 + F(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$2175 := (Q(Q(2)) + \sqrt{1 + 7!}) \times Q(5)$$

$$2175 := 5 \times T(2 - 1 + T(7))$$

$$2175 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 5$$

$$2175 := T(2) \times (1 + T(7)) \times Q(5)$$

$$2175 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 5$$

$$2176 := (T(2) + 1)! \times T(F(7)) - F(6)$$

$$2176 := 17 \times Q(Q(2)) \times F(6)$$

$$2176 := -21 + C(7 + 6)$$

$$2176 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 6$$

$$2176 := F(T(T(2))) \times (-1 + F(7) \times T(6))$$

$$2176 := -Q(Q(Q(2)) - 1) + Q(Q(7!/6!))$$

$$2176 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 6$$

$$2176 := T(21) + T(Q(7)) + 6!$$

$$2177 := 7 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1 + T(T(7))$$

$$2177 := -C(2) - C(-1 + 7) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$2177 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 7$$

$$2177 := Q(2 + 1) + Q(Q(7)) - F(F(7))$$

$$2177 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 7$$

$$2177 := -T(C(2)) + T(\sqrt{1 + 7!}) - C(7)$$

$$2177 := T(T(2)) \times T(-1 + T(7)) - T(F(7))$$

$$2178 := (T(2) + 1)! \times T(F(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$2178 := (T(T(T(2)))) + 1 \times (T(F(7)) + 8)$$

$$2178 := 2 \times Q(-1 + F(7) + F(8))$$

$$2178 := 2 \times Q(7) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2178 := 7 \times C(T(2 + 1)) + T(T(8))$$

$$2178 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 8$$

$$2178 := Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(7)) - C(8)$$

$$2178 := T(2) \times ((-1 + 7)! + \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$2178 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 8$$

$$2178 := T(T(2)) \times (-1 + C(7) + F(8))$$

$$2178 := T(T(T(T(2) + 1))) - T(7) + T(T(8))$$

$$2179 := (2 + 1)^7 - F((\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$2179 := (2 + 1)^7 - F(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$2179 := -(Q(Q(Q(2)) - 1) - Q(Q(7)) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$2179 := -C(2) + (1/9) \times C(-1 + T(7))$$

$$2179 := -C(2) + (-1 + T(7)) \times Q(9)$$

$$2179 := -C(2 + 1) + C(F(7)) + 9$$

$$2179 := C(C(2)) + (1 + Q(7) \times F(9))$$

$$2179 := F(Q(2)) + Q(1 + 7) \times F(9)$$

$$2179 := Q(C(2)) - 1 + Q(Q(7) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$2179 := T((T(T(2)) - 1) \times F(7)) + F(9)$$

$$2179 := T(2) + Q(1 + 7) \times F(9)$$

$$2179 := -T(21) + Q(Q(7)) + 9$$

$$2180 := C(Q(2)) + Q(T(1 + 8) + 0!)$$

$$2180 := F(Q(T(2))) + 1 + T(Q(8) + 0!)$$

$$2180 := Q(C(2)) + Q(T(1 + 8) + 0!)$$

$$2180 := -Q(Q(2)) - 1 + C(F(8 - 0!))$$

$$2180 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 0$$

$$2180 := Q(T(T(2))) - 1 + T(Q(8) + 0!)$$

$$2181 := -Q(Q(2)) + C(F(8 - 1))$$

$$2181 := Q(T(2 + 1)) + T(1 + Q(8))$$

$$2181 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 1$$

$$2181 := T(C(2)) + T(1 + Q(8))$$

$$2182 := (T(T(2)) - 1) \times C(8) - T(C(T(2)))$$

$$2182 := C(F(C(2) - 1)) - T(8 - T(2))$$

$$2182 := F(Q(2 + 1)) \times Q(8) + F(Q(2))!$$

$$2182 := F(Q(2 + 1)) \times Q(8) + T(T(2))$$

$$2182 := -Q(Q(2)) + 1 + C(F(8) - C(2))$$

$$2182 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 2$$

$$2182 := T(C(2)) + 1 + T(Q(8) + F(2))$$

$$2182 := T(Q(2)) + T(1 + Q(8)) + C(T(2))$$

$$2182 := T(T(T(2))) + 1 + (\sqrt{T(8)})! \times T(2)$$

$$2182 := T(T(T(2))) + T(1 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(2))$$

$$2183 := 2 + T(1 + Q(8)) + Q(T(3))$$

$$2183 := C(F(C(2) - 1)) - 8 - 3!$$

$$2183 := F(Q(2))^{-1+8} - Q(F(3))$$

$$2183 := -Q(2) + (1/3) \times Q(Q(1 + 8))$$

$$2183 := -Q(2) + Q(1 + 8) \times C(3)$$

$$2183 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 3$$

$$2183 := -T(-1 + C(2)) + T(T(8 + 3))$$

$$2183 := -T(T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(8 + 3))$$

$$2184 := ((2 + 1)!! + 8) \times F(4)$$

$$2184 := (C(2 + 1) + Q(8)) \times 4!$$

$$2184 := -(Q(2) + 1)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(4))$$

$$2184 := C(2) + F(1 + 8) \times C(4)$$

$$2184 := F(Q(2))^{-1+8} - F(4)$$

$$2184 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 4$$

$$2184 := T(2)^{-1+8} - F(4)$$

$$2184 := T(2)^{-1+8} - T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$2184 := T(21 - 8) \times 4!$$

$$2184 := T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(8 + 4)$$

$$2185 := (F(21) - F(8)) \times (1/5)$$

$$2185 := Q(2)! \times (1 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(5))$$

$$2185 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 5$$

$$2185 := T(C(T(2) + 1)) + 5 \times T(\sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$2186 := C(F(C(2) - 1)) - T(F(8))/T(6)$$

$$2186 := C(Q(2)! - 1) - C(F(8)) - 6!$$

$$2186 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 6$$

$$2186 := T(C(2 + 1)) + C(8) + Q(Q(6))$$

$$2186 := T(Q(2)) + F(1 + 8) \times Q(F(6))$$

$$2187 := (2 + 1^8)^7$$

$$2187 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 7$$

$$2188 := -C(2) - 1 + C(-8 + F(8))$$

$$2188 := Q(2) \times (-1 + T(8) + C(8))$$

$$2188 := -Q(2 + 1) + C(F(8) - 8)$$

$$2188 := Q(-2 + Q(-1 + 8)) - F(8)$$

$$2188 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 8$$

$$2188 := T(2) \times T(8) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2188 := T(T(C(2)) + 1) + T((\sqrt{T(8)})! - T(T(8)))$$

$$2188 := T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + 1) + T(-T(T(8)) + (\sqrt{T(8)})!)$$

$$2189 := (T(T(2)) + Q(Q(1 + 8)))/\sqrt{9}$$

$$2189 := -(T(T(T(2))) + (1 - T(F(8) + T(9))))$$

$$2189 := 2 + Q(Q(1 + 8))/\sqrt{9}$$

$$2189 := 2 + \sqrt{1 + 8} \times C(9)$$

$$2189 := -2 + T(T(1 + 8)) + Q(F(9))$$

$$2189 := F(Q(2))^{-1+8} + F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$2189 := Q(T(Q(2))) + T(Q(1 \times 8)) + 9$$

$$2189 := T(2)^{-1+8} + F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$2189 := -T(T(T(2))) - 1 + T(T(8 + \sqrt{9}))$$

$$2190 := (2 + 1) \times (C(9) + 0!)$$

$$2190 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 0$$

$$2190 := T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 0$$

$$2190 := T(Q(T(2))) + T(1 + Q(9 - 0!))$$

$$2190 := -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1 + 9 + 0!))$$

$$2191 := C(F(C(2) - 1)) - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$2191 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 1$$

$$2191 := Q(Q(Q(2))) - 1 + Q(-1 + T(9))$$

$$2191 := T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 1$$

$$2192 := (T(Q(2) + 1) + Q(Q(9)))/T(2)$$

$$2192 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(1 + T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \times F(T(T(2)))$$

$$2192 := -1 - Q(2) + C(9 + Q(2))$$

$$2192 := C(2)!/(1 + \sqrt{9})! + C(C(2))$$

$$2192 := C(2) + (-1 + C(9)) \times T(2)$$

$$2192 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 2$$

$$2192 := Q(Q(2)) \times (1 + F(9) \times Q(2))$$

$$2192 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(-1 + (\sqrt{9})!/Q(Q(2)))$$

$$2192 := T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 2$$

$$2192 := T(F(F(T(T(2)))) + 1) + F((1/2) \times F(9))$$

$$2193 := (2 + 1)! + (1/3) \times Q(Q(9))$$

$$2193 := (2 + 1) \times C(9) + 3!$$

$$2193 := (2 + C(9)) \times 3$$

$$2193 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 3$$

$$2193 := -Q(2) + Q(1 + T(9)) + Q(Q(3))$$

$$2193 := -Q(Q(2)) + Q(T(9) + F(3))$$

$$2193 := T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 3$$

$$2193 := T(2) \times C(9) + T(3)$$

$$2193 := T(2)^{1+T(\sqrt{9})} + T(3)$$

$$2194 := -(2 + 1) + C(9 + 4)$$

$$2194 := (Q(Q(2)) + T(1 + T(9))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$2194 := 2 \times Q(-1 + F(9)) + Q(4)$$

$$2194 := 2 \times Q(-1 + Q((\sqrt{9})!)) - Q(Q(4))$$

$$2194 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 4$$

$$2194 := F(T(T(2)) + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(4)$$

$$2194 := T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 4$$

$$2195 := (Q(21) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5$$

$$2195 := -2 + C(-1 - 9) + 5$$

$$2195 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 5$$

$$2195 := -Q(Q(2)) + T(Q(9) - T(5))$$

$$2195 := T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 5$$

$$2195 := T(F(T(T(2) + 1))) + T(9) + F(T(5))$$

$$2196 := (C(2 + 1) + F(9)) \times Q(6)$$

$$2196 := (T(2) + 1) \times C(9) - 6!$$

$$2196 := (T(T(2)) + F(1 + 9)) \times T(F(6))$$

$$2196 := -F(2) + C(19 - 6)$$

$$2196 := F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 6$$

$$2196 := Q((2 + 1)!) + \sqrt{9} \times 6!$$

$$2196 := Q(2) \times C(9) - 6!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2196 &:= Q(21 + 9) + Q(Q(6)) \\ 2196 &:= Q(9 \times (2 + 1)!) - 6! \\ 2196 &:= Q(T(2 + 1)) + \sqrt{9} \times 6! \\ 2196 &:= T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 6 \\ 2196 &:= -T(T(T(2)) - 1) + T(T(9) + T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2197 &:= (Q(2) + 9) \times Q(F(7)) \\ 2197 &:= C(2 \times (1 + 9) - 7) \\ 2197 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 7 \\ 2197 &:= F(T(T(2)) + 1)^{T(9-7)} \\ 2197 &:= Q(Q(2 + 1)) + Q(-\sqrt{9} + Q(7)) \\ 2197 &:= Q(T(2)) + 1 + \sqrt{9}^7 \\ 2197 &:= T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 7 \\ 2197 &:= T(T(2) + 1) + \sqrt{9}^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2198 &:= (C(2) + C(-1 + C(\sqrt{9})))1/8 \\ 2198 &:= (C(2) + C(-1 + \sqrt{C(9)})) \times (1/8) \\ 2198 &:= (-C(2) - C(-1 + \sqrt{C(9)})) \times (-1/8) \\ 2198 &:= (Q(2) + 1)! - F(\sqrt{9}) + T(Q(8)) \\ 2198 &:= 2 \times T(1 + T(9)) + T(8) \\ 2198 &:= F(2) + C(F(9) - F(8)) \\ 2198 &:= F(F(F(Q(2))!)) + 1 + F(9) \times Q(8) \\ 2198 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 8 \\ 2198 &:= T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2199 &:= (Q((2 + 1)!) + Q(Q(9)))/\sqrt{9} \\ 2199 &:= (Q(2) + C(9)) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 2199 &:= (T(2) + 1 + C(9)) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 2199 &:= (T(T(2))! + F(1 + T(\sqrt{9}))) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 2199 &:= (T(T(2)) - 1)! + 9 \times T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\ 2199 &:= 2 + C(1 + \sqrt{9} + 9) \\ 2199 &:= 2 + F(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 2199 &:= 2 + Q(1 + T(9)) + Q(9) \\ 2199 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (1 + C(9)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2199 &:= F(T(T(2)) + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(\sqrt{9}) \\ 2199 &:= T(2) \times (1 + C(9)) + 9 \\ 2199 &:= -T(Q(2)) + Q(Q(9) - F(9)) \\ 2199 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) + 9 \times T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2200 &:= 2 + C(F(-0! + C(2))) + 0! \\ 2200 &:= F(Q(2)) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) \\ 2200 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + Q(Q(Q(0! + 0!))) \\ 2200 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 0!) + 0 \\ 2200 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) \\ 2200 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 0 \\ 2200 &:= T(2) + C(Q(T(2)) + Q(0! + 0!)) \\ 2200 &:= T(2) + C(T(T(T(2))) - C(0! + 0!)) \\ 2200 &:= T(T(Q(2))) \times T(Q(2)) \times Q(0! + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2201 &:= Q(2) + C(F(C(2) - 1)) \\ 2201 &:= Q(2) + C(Q(T(2)) + Q(1 + 0!)) \\ 2201 &:= Q(Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) - F(Q(F(Q(2)))) - F(F(Q(0! + 1)))! \\ 2201 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 0!) + 1 \\ 2201 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2202 &:= (Q(2)! + C(C(2) - 0!)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2202 &:= F(Q(2))! \times (Q(2)! + C(C(2) - 0!)) \\ 2202 &:= F(Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) + Q(Q((0! + 2)!)) \\ 2202 &:= -Q(T(2)) + T((T(Q(2)) + 0!) \times T(T(2))) \\ 2202 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 0!) + 2 \\ 2202 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 2 \\ 2202 &:= -T(T(2)) + F((T(2) + 0!)!)/T(T(T(2))) \\ 2202 &:= T(T(C(2))) - C(C(2)) \times (0 - T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2203 &:= C(2) - 2 + C(F(0! + 3!)) \\ 2203 &:= C(C(2) + Q(2) + 0!) + 3! \\ 2203 &:= C(\sqrt{C(C(2)) - C(C(2) - 0!)}) + 3! \\ 2203 &:= -F(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2) + F(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2203 &:= Q(2 \times (Q(2))! - 0!) - 3! \\
 2203 &:= Q(Q(2)) + F(Q(2))^{0!+3!} \\
 2203 &:= Q(Q(2)) + T(2)^{0!+T(3)} \\
 2203 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 0! + 3 \\
 2203 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 3 \\
 2203 &:= T(T(2)) + C(C(2) - 0! + T(3)) \\
 2203 &:= T(T(2)) + C(Q(2) + Q(3)) \\
 2203 &:= T(T(T(2+2) + 0!)) - F(T(3)) \\
 \\
 2204 &:= C(C(2) - T(2)) - 0! + T(C(4)) \\
 2204 &:= C(F(C(2) - F(2))) + 0! + F(4)! \\
 2204 &:= C(Q(2)) \times T(C(2)) - Q(T(4)) \\
 2204 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2) + 0!) - Q(4!)) \\
 2204 &:= Q(C(2)) \times T(C(2)) - Q(T(4)) \\
 2204 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 0! + 4 \\
 2204 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 4 \\
 2204 &:= T(T(2))! - F(2) + T(-0! + F(T(4))) \\
 2204 &:= T(T(F(T(T(2)))))) - 2 + T(F(T(4))) \\
 2204 &:= T(T(T(2)))/(-T(2)) + T(T(0! + T(4))) \\
 \\
 2205 &:= 5 \times Q(22 - 0!) \\
 2205 &:= 5 \times Q(F(2) + 20) \\
 2205 &:= C(2) + C(C(2) + 5) \\
 2205 &:= C(2) + C(F(2 + 5)) \\
 2205 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 0! + 5 \\
 2205 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 5 \\
 2205 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(20)/T(5)) \\
 \\
 2206 &:= C(2) + F(2) + C(F(0! + 6)) \\
 2206 &:= F(2) + (0! + Q(2)) \times Q(T(6)) \\
 2206 &:= -F(Q(2)) + Q(-2 + Q(0! + 6)) \\
 2206 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + C(Q(2) + 0! + F(6)) \\
 2206 &:= Q(T(2)) + C(C(2) - 0! + 6) \\
 2206 &:= Q(T(2)) + C(Q(2) + 0! + F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2206 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 0!) + 6 \\
 2206 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 6 \\
 2206 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + T(T(F(6))) \\
 2206 &:= T(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) \times (-0! + T(T(6))) \\
 2206 &:= -T(T(2))! + T(T(T(T(2) + 0!)) + T(6)) \\
 2206 &:= T(T(C(2))) + T(T(2 + F(6))) \\
 2206 &:= T(T(C(2))) + T(T(T(2) + 0! + 6)) \\
 \\
 2207 &:= -2 + Q(-2 + Q(7)) \\
 2207 &:= C(2) + 2 + C(F(7)) \\
 2207 &:= -C(T(T(2))) + T(C(0! + T(2))) + C(7) \\
 2207 &:= F(T(2) \times T(T(2))) - F(0! + F(7)) \\
 2207 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 0! + 7 \\
 2207 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 7 \\
 2207 &:= T(2 + 2) + C(F(7)) \\
 2207 &:= T(Q(2)) + C(20 - 7) \\
 \\
 2208 &:= (C(Q(2))! - Q(Q(2)!))/(\sqrt{0! + 8})! \\
 2208 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2))) + 20) \times 8 \\
 2208 &:= 8 \times T(T(2) + 20) \\
 2208 &:= F((2 + 2)!)/F(8) \\
 2208 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 0! + 8 \\
 2208 &:= T(2)^{C(2)-0!} + F(8) \\
 2208 &:= T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 8 \\
 2208 &:= -T(2) + T(2 + Q(8)) \\
 2208 &:= -T(2) + T(T(2) \times (0! + F(8))) \\
 \\
 2209 &:= 2 \times F(F(C(2))) - C(C(\sqrt{9})) \\
 2209 &:= -2 + T(T(2 + 9)) \\
 2209 &:= Q(2 + (Q(2) + 0!) \times 9) \\
 2209 &:= Q(-2 + Q(-2 + 9)) \\
 2209 &:= Q(2 + T(2 \times 0 + 9)) \\
 2209 &:= Q(C(2) + Q(2) + 0! + F(9)) \\
 2209 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 0! + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2209 := T(2) + C(F(C(2) - 0!)) + 9$$

$$2210 := F(2) + Q(-C(2) + F(10))$$

$$2210 := F(2) + Q(-C(2) + T(10))$$

$$2210 := -F(2) + T(T(F(2) + 10))$$

$$2210 := F(Q(T(2))) \times (T(Q(2)) + T(10))$$

$$2210 := Q(2 \times Q(2)! - 1) + 0!$$

$$2210 := Q(-2 + Q(-1 + C(2))) + 0!$$

$$2210 := Q(2 + T(Q(2 + 1))) + 0!$$

$$2210 := T(T(C(2))) + (Q(2) + T(T(10)))$$

$$2210 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 0$$

$$2210 := T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0$$

$$2211 := F(Q(2)!)/F(C(2)) + F(Q(1 + 1))$$

$$2211 := F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(F(Q(2))!) + F(Q(Q(1 + 1)))$$

$$2211 := T(T(2 - 2 + 11))$$

$$2211 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 1$$

$$2211 := T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1$$

$$2212 := (Q(2)! + Q(Q(2)! - 1)) \times Q(2)$$

$$2212 := F(2) + T(T(2 + Q(1 + 2)))$$

$$2212 := F(2) + T(T(C(2) + 1 + 2))$$

$$2212 := F(Q(2)) + Q(-1 + Q(2)! + Q(2)!)$$

$$2212 := Q(22) + C(12)$$

$$2212 := T(2) + Q(2 + T(Q(1 + 2)))$$

$$2212 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) + 1^2$$

$$2212 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 2$$

$$2212 := T(T(T(2 + 2) + 1)) + F(2)$$

$$2212 := T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2$$

$$2213 := 2 + T(T(-(2 - 13)))$$

$$2213 := C(2) + C(2) + C(13)$$

$$2213 := Q(2) + Q(-2 + Q(1 + 3!))$$

$$2213 := Q(2 + 2) + C(13)$$

$$2213 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 3$$

$$2213 := T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3$$

$$2214 := (F(2) + Q(Q(2 + 1))) \times C(F(4))$$

$$2214 := (F(22) + 1)/F(F(4)!)$$

$$2214 := (F(22) + 1)/\sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$2214 := 2 \times ((Q(2) + 1)! + F(Q(4)))$$

$$2214 := Q(T(2)) \times (-T(Q(2)) + Q(Q(4)))$$

$$2214 := T(2) + T(2 + C(4))$$

$$2214 := T(2) + T(T(F(2) + T(4)))$$

$$2214 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 4$$

$$2214 := T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4$$

$$2215 := (2 + Q(21)) \times 5$$

$$2215 := (-2 - Q(21)) \times (-5)$$

$$2215 := T(2) \times T(T(2))! + F(T(-1 + 4))$$

$$2215 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 5$$

$$2215 := T(T(T(2) + F(T(T(2)))) - (1 - 5)$$

$$2215 := T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5$$

$$2216 := F(C(2)) - 2 + C(F(1 + 6))$$

$$2216 := F(Q(2)) + Q(Q(2)) + C(F(1 + 6))$$

$$2216 := F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2) + Q(-1 + Q(6))$$

$$2216 := Q(Q(2)) \times C(1 + Q(2)) + C(6)$$

$$2216 := T(2) + Q(Q(2)) + C(F(1 + 6))$$

$$2216 := T(2^{T(T(2))}) + T(16)$$

$$2216 := T(C(2 + 2)) + T(16)$$

$$2216 := T(Q(2)^{T(2)}) + T(16)$$

$$2216 := T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 6$$

$$2216 := T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6$$

$$2217 := C(2) + Q(-2 + Q(7))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2217 &:= C(C(2)) \times (T(T(2)) - 1) - C(7) \\ 2217 &:= -F(2) + F(C(2)) + C(F(7)) \\ 2217 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) \times F((2+1)!) + Q(F(7)) \\ 2217 &:= T(T(2)) + T(2 + Q(1 + 7)) \\ 2217 &:= T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 7 \\ 2217 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2218 &:= F(C(2)) + C(21 - 8) \\ 2218 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(-2 + Q(-1 + 8)) \\ 2218 &:= Q(T(2)) + Q(2 + T(1 + 8)) \\ 2218 &:= T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 8 \\ 2218 &:= T(T(T(2))) + C(21 - 8) \\ 2218 &:= T(T(T(2) + F(T(T(2)))))) - (1 - 8) \\ 2218 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2219 &:= C(2) + T(T(2 + 9)) \\ 2219 &:= C(Q(2 + 2) - 1) - Q(F(9)) \\ 2219 &:= F(C(2)) + C(F(C(2) - 1)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\ 2219 &:= F(T(T(2))) + T(T(2 + 9)) \\ 2219 &:= Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)!) - 1) - Q(9) \\ 2219 &:= T(Q(2)) + Q(2 + T(9)) \\ 2219 &:= T(T(C(2) + T(2))) - 1 + 9 \\ 2219 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2220 &:= -(F(Q(F(Q(2)))) - Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times (Q(F(Q(2)))) \\ 2220 &:= 2 + F(C(2)) + C(F(-0! + C(2))) \\ 2220 &:= 20 \times T(T(F(T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 2220 &:= Q(T(2)) + T(T(T(2 + 2) + 0!)) \\ 2220 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(2)!) + 20) \\ 2220 &:= T(T(2)) \times (C(T(2)) + C(C(2) - 0!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2221 &:= (2 + 2)! + C(F(C(2) - 1)) \\ 2221 &:= F(Q(2)!)/Q(2)! + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2221 &:= Q(2)! + C(Q(2) + Q(2 + 1)) \\ 2221 &:= T(Q(2)) + T(T(2 + Q(2 + 1))) \\ 2221 &:= T(T(C(2) + T(2))) + T(T(2) + 1) \\ 2221 &:= T(T(T(2) + F(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(2) + 1) \\ 2221 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2222 &:= (T(C(2))^{T(2)} + T(T(2)))/F(C(2)) \\ 2222 &:= (T(T(2))! + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(2) - F(2) \\ 2222 &:= (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 2222 &:= C(2) + T(2) + T(T(C(2) + T(2))) \\ 2222 &:= Q(F(2) + Q(2)) + C(F(C(2) - F(2))) \\ 2222 &:= Q(Q(F(2) + Q(2))) + F(F(2) + Q(Q(2))) \\ 2222 &:= T(Q(Q(2))) + T(T(2)) + T(Q(2)^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2223 &:= (F(C(2)) + (C(2) - 2)!) \times 3 \\ 2223 &:= 2 + Q(2)! + C(Q(3) + Q(2)) \\ 2223 &:= C(C(2)) + T(C(2 + 2) - T(3)) \\ 2223 &:= Q((Q(Q(2)) - Q(2)) \times Q(2)) - Q(Q(3)) \\ 2223 &:= Q(2 \times (2 + 2)!) - Q(Q(3)) \\ 2223 &:= T(2) \times T(2 + T(2^3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2224 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) \times T(2) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 2224 &:= -C(2) - C(C(2)) + C(-2 + Q(4)) \\ 2224 &:= C(F(2 + 2)) + C(F(C(2)) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \\ 2224 &:= C(T(2)) + C(F(2 + 2) + T(4)) \\ 2224 &:= C(T(2)) + C(T(2)^2 + 4) \\ 2224 &:= F(F(2) + T(T(2))) + T(T(F(2) + T(4))) \\ 2224 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times (-22 + T(4!)) \\ 2224 &:= Q(2) \times (Q(2) - Q(2)! + Q(4!)) \\ 2224 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (T(2) + T(2^4)) \\ 2224 &:= T(2^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(2)) \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$2225 := F(22 \times (1/2)) \times Q(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2225 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(-2 + Q(2 + 5)) & 2229 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(2 + 9)) \\
 2225 &:= T(C(2)) - C(2) + C(C(2) + 5) & 2229 &:= T(C(2)) + T(2) \times (2 + C(9)) \\
 2225 &:= T(C(2) - F(2)) + C(F(2 + 5)) & & \\
 2225 &:= T(T(2)) + F(T(T(2))) + T(T(\sqrt{F(2) + 5!})) & 2230 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - F(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 0!) \\
 2225 &:= T(T(2)) + F(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(2)) + 5)) & 2230 &:= F(C(2)) + Q(C(2) \times 3! - 0!) \\
 & & 2230 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + F(Q(Q(2))) + F(Q(3 + 0!)) \\
 2226 &:= C(2) + F(C(2)) + C(F(F(2) + 6)) & 2230 &:= T(2) \times T(T(C(2))) + T(T(T(3))) + 0! \\
 2226 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (22 + 6!) & 2230 &:= T(C(2)) - T(2) + C(F(0! + T(3))) \\
 2226 &:= Q(Q(C(2))) - Q(Q(2)!) + 2 - Q(Q(6)) & 2230 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 0 \\
 2226 &:= T(2) \times (22 + 6!) & & \\
 2226 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (-2 + T(2) \times T(F(6))) & 2231 &:= (Q(C(2)) - 2) \times Q(3!) - 1 \\
 2226 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2) \times T(6)) & 2231 &:= -C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 3!) - 1 \\
 & & 2231 &:= -C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + T(3)) - 1 \\
 2227 &:= 2 \times F(T(T(2))) + T(T(-2 + F(7))) & 2231 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (Q(2)! + 3!!) - 1 \\
 2227 &:= 2 + Q(Q(2)) + Q(-2 + Q(7)) & 2231 &:= T(2) \times (Q(2)! + T(3)!) - 1 \\
 2227 &:= C(2) + 22 + C(F(7)) & 2231 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 1 \\
 2227 &:= C(C(2)) + (C(2) - T(2)) \times C(7) & 2231 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2) + F(T(3)))) - 1 \\
 2227 &:= C(C(2)) + (F(2) + Q(2)) \times C(7) & 2231 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(3)) - 1 \\
 2227 &:= Q(Q(2)) + T(T(2 + 2 + 7)) & & \\
 2227 &:= T(2^{T(T(2))}) + 7 \times T(T(T(2))) & & \\
 & & 2232 &:= (2 + T(Q(2) + Q(3))) \times Q(2)! \\
 & & 2232 &:= (Q(2) + F(2 + Q(3))) \times Q(2)! \\
 2228 &:= (Q(Q(2)!) - F(Q(2))) \times Q(2) - Q(8) & 2232 &:= (Q(C(2)) - 2) \times Q(3 \times 2) \\
 2228 &:= 2 \times (C(2)!/T(C(2)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) & 2232 &:= (Q(Q(2)) - Q(2) + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(2)! \\
 2228 &:= C(Q(Q(2)) - 2) - Q(2) - C(8) & 2232 &:= (T(2) + T(23)) \times C(2) \\
 2228 &:= F(2) + Q(Q(2)) + T(2 + Q(8)) & 2232 &:= (T(T(2)^{T(2)}) - T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\
 2228 &:= Q(2) \times (Q(2)! + F(C(2)) + C(8)) & 2232 &:= -C(C(2)) \times F(2) + C(3! + C(2)) \\
 2228 &:= Q(2) + Q(T(2) \times Q(2)) + T(Q(8)) & 2232 &:= C(C(2)) - C(2) + C(2 \times 3!) \\
 2228 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - F(2) + T(2) \times T(T(8)) & 2232 &:= C(C(2) + 2 \times 3) - C(C(2)) \\
 & & 2232 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 2 \\
 2229 &:= (F(Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times F(Q(2)) + Q((\sqrt{9})!) & & \\
 2229 &:= 2 \times Q(T(2)) + T(T(2 + 9)) & 2233 &:= (C(2)!/T(T(2)) - T(T(3))) \times (1/3) \\
 2229 &:= C(2) \times Q(2) + C(9 + Q(2)) & 2233 &:= (F(C(2)) - C(2)!/3!) \times (-1/3) \\
 2229 &:= \sqrt{C(C(2)) + C(C(2))} + C(F(-2 + 9)) & 2233 &:= (Q(Q(2)) - F(Q(2)))^3 + Q(3!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2233 &:= C(C(2) + 2 + 3) + Q(3!) \\
 2233 &:= C(F(2 + 2 + 3)) + Q(3!) \\
 2233 &:= F(F(2) + T(T(2)))^3 + T(F(T(3))) \\
 2233 &:= Q(2)! + Q(2 + Q(3) + Q(3!)) \\
 2233 &:= Q(2)! + Q(2 + T(3 \times 3)) \\
 2233 &:= T(C(2)) + C(C(2) + F(3) + 3) \\
 2233 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 3 \\
 2233 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 3 \times T(T(T(3))) \\
 \\
 2234 &:= (Q(C(2)) - 2) \times Q(3!) + \sqrt{4} \\
 2234 &:= 2 + (Q(2)! + 3!) \times F(4) \\
 2234 &:= 2 + F(C(2)) + T(F(3) + C(4)) \\
 2234 &:= 2 + T(2) \times (T(3)! + 4!) \\
 2234 &:= 2 + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4))) \\
 2234 &:= -C(2) - T(C(2)) + T(3 + C(4)) \\
 2234 &:= C(C(2)) + C(2 \times 3!) - F(4)! \\
 2234 &:= -C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 3!) + \sqrt{4} \\
 2234 &:= F(2) + T(2) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(F(T(4))) \\
 2234 &:= Q(Q(2)) + F(C(2)) + C(F(3 + 4)) \\
 2234 &:= T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2 + 3)) - Q(4) \\
 2234 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 4 \\
 \\
 2235 &:= (2 + 2)! + T(T(T(3) + 5)) \\
 2235 &:= (C(C(2)) + Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 5 \\
 2235 &:= (F(C(2))^2 + 3!) \times 5 \\
 2235 &:= (F(C(2))^2 + T(3)) \times 5 \\
 2235 &:= C(C(2)) + C(2 \times 3!) - 5 \\
 2235 &:= C(C(2)) + C(2 \times T(3)) - 5 \\
 2235 &:= F(Q(2)) \times ((2 \times 3)! + Q(5)) \\
 2235 &:= T(2) \times ((2 \times 3)! + Q(5)) \\
 2235 &:= T(2) \times F(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3) + 5)) \\
 2235 &:= T(2) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3) + 5)) \\
 2235 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2236 &:= (C(T(C(2))) + T(3 \times C(2)))/T(6) \\
 2236 &:= 2 \times (2 + F(T(3)))/T(F(6)) \\
 2236 &:= C(C(2)) - Q(2) + C(3! + 6) \\
 2236 &:= C(F(C(2) - F(2))) \times 3! - F(F(F(6))) \\
 2236 &:= F(F(C(2))) + C(T(2)) - C(C(3)) + F(T(6)) \\
 2236 &:= Q(2) \times (-2 + T(-3 + Q(6))) \\
 2236 &:= -Q(2) + (F(2) + F(Q(3))) \times Q(F(6)) \\
 2236 &:= Q(2) - C(C(2)) + C(3! + F(6)) \\
 2236 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)! \times Q(Q(3)) + Q(6) \\
 2236 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 6 \\
 \\
 2237 &:= -2 + T(T(T(2) + F(T(3)))) + T(7) \\
 2237 &:= -2 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(3)))) + T(7) \\
 2237 &:= -2 - 2 \times Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2237 &:= C(2) \times (2 + 3) + C(F(7)) \\
 2237 &:= Q(C(2)) - Q(2)! + C(7 + 3!) \\
 2237 &:= Q(Q(2)) - Q(2) \times T(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2237 &:= -T(2) + T(T(2)) \times T(C(3)) - T(7) \\
 2237 &:= T(22) \times Q(F(3)) + T(Q(7)) \\
 2237 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 7 \\
 \\
 2238 &:= -2 + (C(2) + C(3)) \times Q(8) \\
 2238 &:= -2 + (F(2) + F(Q(3))) \times Q(8) \\
 2238 &:= -2 + C(2 \times 3!) + C(8) \\
 2238 &:= -2 + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) - Q(8) \\
 2238 &:= C(T(2)) + T(F(2) \times T(3 + 8)) \\
 2238 &:= C(T(2)) + T(T(2) + C(3) + T(8)) \\
 2238 &:= T(2)^{T(2)} + T(T(3 + 8)) \\
 2238 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 8 \\
 2239 &:= -2 + F(Q(2)) \times 3! + Q(9) \\
 \\
 2239 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2)) + T(9) \times C(3) \\
 2239 &:= C(C(2)) - F(2) + C(3 + 9) \\
 2239 &:= Q(22) + T(3)! + T(T(9)) \\
 2239 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) - Q(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2239 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(C(2) \times 3!) - Q(9) & 2243 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 3 \\
 2239 &:= Q(Q(Q(2)) + Q(2!)) + 3! - Q(9) & 2243 &:= C(C(2)) + F(Q(2)) + C(4 \times 3) \\
 2239 &:= T(F(2) + T(T(2))) + T(T(F(3) + 9)) & 2243 &:= C(C(2)) + T(2) + C(4 \times 3) \\
 2239 &:= T(T(T(2))) + Q(2 + T(Q(3))) + 9 & 2243 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 3 \\
 2239 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2))) - T(T(3)) + T(\sqrt{9})! & 2243 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 3 \\
 2239 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))/T(2)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(9)) & 2243 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + T(F(F(F(4)))) + T(F(T(3))) \\
 & & 2243 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + T(F(\sqrt{4}) + T(F(T(3)))) \\
 2240 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 0 & 2243 &:= T(F(T(T(2)))) - F(2) + F(4!)/T(T(3)) \\
 2240 &:= F(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4) + 0!)) & 2243 &:= T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 4 + T(T(T(3))) \\
 2240 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) \times 0! & & \\
 2240 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 0 & 2244 &:= (T(C(2)) - T(2)) \times (C(4) + 4) \\
 2240 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 0 & 2244 &:= (T(T(2))^{T(2)} - 4) \times T(F(4)) \\
 2240 &:= T(T(2))! - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4))) + 0! & 2244 &:= 4 \times T(T(2)^2 + 4!) \\
 & & 2244 &:= 4 \times T(T(2) + T(2) \times T(4)) \\
 2241 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 1 & 2244 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 4 \\
 2241 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 1 & 2244 &:= C(C(2)) + Q(2) + C(Q(4) - 4) \\
 2241 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 1 & 2244 &:= F(C(2) + F(2)) \times (C(4) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 2241 &:= Q(T(2)) \times (Q(2)! + Q(T(4 + 1))) & 2244 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 4 \\
 2241 &:= T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2))! + T(F(T(4)) - 1) & 2244 &:= Q(2) \times T(T(2)^{\sqrt{4}} + 4!) \\
 2241 &:= T(F(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4) + 1)) & 2244 &:= Q(2 \times (F(2) + 4!)) - Q(Q(4)) \\
 & & 2244 &:= Q(2 + 2 \times 4!) - Q(Q(4)) \\
 & & 2244 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 4 \\
 2242 &:= 2 + (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) \times Q(Q(2)) & & \\
 2242 &:= 2 - Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) & 2245 &:= (C(C(2)) + F(2) - C(4)) \times 5 \\
 2242 &:= C(C(2)) + 2 + C(F(4) \times Q(2)) & 2245 &:= (C(C(2)) - C(2) - T(T(4))) \times 5 \\
 2242 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 2 & 2245 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times T(4) - 5 \\
 2242 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 2 & 2245 &:= C(2)!/F(C(2)) + T(T(4) + T(5)) \\
 2242 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 2 & 2245 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 5 \\
 2242 &:= T(C(2) + F(2)) + C(T(4) + T(2)) & 2245 &:= F(T(2)^2) + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \\
 2242 &:= -T(T(2)) \times T(2) + T(F(T(4))) + T(T(2))! & 2245 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 5 \\
 2242 &:= -T(T(2)) \times T(2) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))! & 2245 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 5 \\
 2242 &:= T(T(2^{T(2)})) + T(F(T(4))) + T(F(T(T(2)))) & 2245 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (T(2) + \sqrt{4})! + T(Q(5)) \\
 2242 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2)))))) + T(4) + T(T(T(2))) & 2245 &:= T(T(2))!/(-T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\
 2243 &:= 2 + F(Q(2)) \times F(Q(4)) - 3! & & \\
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2246 &:= -2^{T(T(2))} + T(4) \times T(T(6)) \\ 2246 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 6 \\ 2246 &:= C(C(2) + Q(2)) + F(4)! + C(F(6)) \\ 2246 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 6 \\ 2246 &:= -Q(2)^{T(2)} + T(4) \times T(T(6)) \\ 2246 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 6 \\ 2246 &:= T(T(2)) + C(2) \times (C(4) + C(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2247 &:= (F(Q(2)) - Q(2 + Q(4))) \times (-7) \\ 2247 &:= 2 \times (F(2) + 4!) + C(F(7)) \\ 2247 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 7 \\ 2247 &:= Q(2) \times (-2 + Q(4!)) - Q(7) \\ 2247 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 7 \\ 2247 &:= Q(2 \times T(2)) + T(T(4 + 7)) \\ 2247 &:= Q(C(2)) - Q(2) + F(4)^7 \\ 2247 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 7 \\ 2247 &:= T(2^{T(2)}) + T(T(4 + 7)) \\ 2247 &:= T(C(2)) + T(F(2) \times T(4 + 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2248 &:= (2 - T(T(T(2)))) + T(4!) \times 8 \\ 2248 &:= (T(2) + Q(2)) \times 4! + T(Q(8)) \\ 2248 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(F(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \\ 2248 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \\ 2248 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 8 \\ 2248 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times (2 + T(4!) - F(8)) \\ 2248 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(\sqrt{4}^{\sqrt{T(8)}}) \\ 2248 &:= Q(2) \times (2 + Q(4!)) - Q(8) \\ 2248 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 8 \\ 2248 &:= Q(22) + Q(\sqrt{4} \times F(8)) \\ 2248 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2249 &:= 2 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\ 2249 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2)) + T(49) \\ 2249 &:= C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2249 &:= F(2) + T(2 + F(T(4))) + T(F(9)) \\ 2249 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(Q(2)) - Q(4!)) + 9 \\ 2249 &:= Q(C(2)) \times Q(2)! - Q(4) + C(9) \\ 2249 &:= Q(C(2)) - 2 + F(4) \times C(9) \\ 2249 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(2) + T(Q(4))) + 9 \\ 2249 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2))! + F(T(4)) + F(9) \\ 2249 &:= T(Q(2)^{T(2)}) + Q(4 + 9) \\ 2249 &:= T(T(2))! - 2 + T(T(T(4))) - 9 \\ 2249 &:= -T(T(2)) + F(2 \times T(4))/\sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2250 &:= (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 0 \\ 2250 &:= (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 0 \\ 2250 &:= 250 \times Q(F(Q(2))) \\ 2250 &:= 250 \times Q(T(2)) \\ 2250 &:= 50 \times T(T(2)^2) \\ 2250 &:= T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 0 \\ 2250 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2251 &:= (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 1 \\ 2251 &:= (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 1 \\ 2251 &:= T(2 \times T(F(T(T(2)))) - F(T(5) - 1) \\ 2251 &:= T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 1 \\ 2251 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2252 &:= (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 2 \\ 2252 &:= (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 2 \\ 2252 &:= (T(T(2))! + T(T(2 + 5))) \times 2 \\ 2252 &:= F(C(2) + 2) + C(F(5 + 2)) \\ 2252 &:= -F(Q(2)) + F(5 \times Q(2))/F(Q(2)) \\ 2252 &:= -Q(2) \times (-2 - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(Q(2))) \\ 2252 &:= Q(2 \times Q(2)!) - 52 \\ 2252 &:= T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 2 \\ 2252 &:= T(T(2))! - F(T(T(2))) + T(F(5 \times 2)) \\ 2252 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$2252 := T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$2252 := T(T(2+2)) + C(T(5) - 2)$$

$$2253 := (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$2253 := (F(C(2)) - 2) \times 5! - C(3)$$

$$2253 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 3$$

$$2253 := 2 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5 + T(3)))$$

$$2253 := -2 + (1/3) \times F(5 \times Q(2))$$

$$2253 := F(Q(2)) \times (F(2) + C(5) \times 3!)$$

$$2253 := Q(Q(2)!) - Q(2) + Q(5 + Q(3!))$$

$$2253 := -Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2) \times Q(Q(5)) + Q(3)$$

$$2253 := T(2) + T(2) \times C(5) \times T(3)$$

$$2253 := T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 3$$

$$2253 := T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$2254 := (2 + F(C(2))) \times (C(5) - C(F(4)))$$

$$2254 := (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$2254 := (F(Q(2)) - F(5 \times Q(2)))/(-F(4))$$

$$2254 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 4$$

$$2254 := 2 \times (Q(Q(2)!) - Q(5) + Q(4!))$$

$$2254 := Q(2 \times Q(2)!) - Q(5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$2254 := T(2)^{T(T(2))} - T(5) + T(F(T(4)))$$

$$2254 := T(2)^{T(T(2))} - T(5) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$2254 := T(2) + T(T(2) + T(5)) + T(C(4))$$

$$2254 := T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 4$$

$$2254 := T(T(2))! + T(F(2 \times 5)) - T(F(4))$$

$$2254 := T(T(2))! - T(T(2)) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))$$

$$2254 := T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$2255 := (2 + 2)! \times 5! - Q(Q(5))$$

$$2255 := (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$2255 := (F(C(2)) - 2) \times C(5) - 5!$$

$$2255 := (F(Q(2)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 5! - Q(5)$$

$$2255 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 5$$

$$2255 := (Q(Q(2)) + T(Q(2) + Q(5))) \times 5$$

$$2255 := C(2)!/(T(2) + T(5)) + T(5)$$

$$2255 := T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 5$$

$$2255 := T(T(2))! + T(F(2 \times 5)) - 5$$

$$2255 := T(T(2))! + T(T(2 \times 5)) - 5$$

$$2255 := T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$2255 := T(T(T(2)^2)) + F(T(5)) + F(T(5))$$

$$2256 := (2^{C(2)} + 5!) \times 6$$

$$2256 := (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$2256 := (Q(2)^{Q(2)} + 5!) \times 6$$

$$2256 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 6$$

$$2256 := 2 \times T(F(2 \times 5)) - F(6)$$

$$2256 := Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(Q(2)) + \sqrt{5^6})$$

$$2256 := T(2) \times (2^5 + 6!)$$

$$2256 := T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 6$$

$$2256 := T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$2256 := T(T(2)^2) + T(T(5 + 6))$$

$$2257 := (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$2257 := (C(2) + C(C(2))) \times 5 - C(7)$$

$$2257 := (C(2) + Q(2)) \times 5 + C(F(7))$$

$$2257 := (-C(2) - C(C(2))) \times (-5) - C(7)$$

$$2257 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 7$$

$$2257 := C(2) \times T(25) - C(7)$$

$$2257 := F(C(2) + 2) + 5 + C(F(7))$$

$$2257 := -Q(2 + 2 \times 5) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$2257 := -T(2) + T(T(2) \times T(5)) + T(Q(7))$$

$$2257 := T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 7$$

$$2257 := T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$2257 := T(T(T(2))) + T(2) \times F(T(5)) + T(T(7))$$

$$2257 := -T(T(T(2))) + T(\sqrt{5 \times T(T(2))}) + 7$$

$$2258 := (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$2258 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 8$$

$$2258 := 2 + Q(Q(2)) \times (5! + F(8))$$

$$2258 := -2 + T(F(2 \times 5)) + (\sqrt{T(8)})!$$

$$2258 := -2 + T(T(2 \times 5)) + (\sqrt{T(8)})!$$

$$2258 := Q(C(2)) - F(Q(2)) + C(5 + 8)$$

$$2258 := Q(T(2)) + Q(-2 + T(5)) + T(Q(8))$$

$$2258 := T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 8$$

$$2258 := T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$2259 := (2^{C(2)} - 5) \times 9$$

$$2259 := (2 + Q(Q(2))) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$2259 := -(2 - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$2259 := (Q(2)^{Q(2)} - 5) \times 9$$

$$2259 := (Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times Q(5) + 9$$

$$2259 := -T(2) + T(T(2)) \times F(5 + 9)$$

$$2259 := T(2) + T(T(T(T(2)) + 5)) + T(9)$$

$$2259 := T(Q(2)) \times Q(T(2) \times 5) + 9$$

$$2259 := T(T(2))! + 9 \times T(T(2) + T(5))$$

$$2259 := T(T(2)) \times T(2) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$2260 := F(Q(Q(2))) - Q(2)! + Q(Q(6)) + 0!$$

$$2260 := T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 0$$

$$2260 := T(Q(2)) \times (Q(Q(2)) + T(T(6) - 0!))$$

$$2260 := T(T(2))! + T(T(T(2) + 6 + 0!))$$

$$2260 := T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 0$$

$$2261 := 6 \times F(Q(Q(2)) - 2) - 1$$

$$2261 := C(2 + 2) + C(F(6 + 1))$$

$$2261 := Q(C(2)) + C(2 \times 6 + 1)$$

$$2261 := -Q(Q(2)) + Q(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + 1)$$

$$2261 := T(C(T(2))) - C(2) + T(61)$$

$$2261 := T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 1$$

$$2261 := T(T(2)) \times F(T(T(2)) + F(6)) - 1$$

$$2261 := T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 1$$

$$2262 := (2 + C(T(2))) \times T(6 \times 2)$$

$$2262 := (C(2) - 2) \times F(6 + C(2))$$

$$2262 := (Q(Q(2)) + Q(-2 + T(6))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$2262 := 6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)}) - T(T(2))$$

$$2262 := C(C(2)) \times Q(2) + C(6) - 2$$

$$2262 := F(Q(2))! \times F(2 \times 6 + 2)$$

$$2262 := T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 2$$

$$2262 := T(T(2)) \times F(2 \times 6 + 2)$$

$$2262 := T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 2$$

$$2263 := -2 + T(Q(2)) \times T(T(6)) - T(Q(3))$$

$$2263 := C(C(2)) \times Q(2) + C(6) - F(F(3))$$

$$2263 := C(Q(2) + Q(2)!) - 6 - C(C(3))$$

$$2263 := F(2) + F(6 + C(2)) \times 3!$$

$$2263 := F(2) + F(Q(2)) \times (6! + F(Q(3)))$$

$$2263 := F(2) + T(T(2)) \times F(F(6) + T(3))$$

$$2263 := T(2) - C(2) + 6 \times T(C(3))$$

$$2263 := T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 3$$

$$2263 := T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 3$$

$$2264 := -(Q(2)! - Q(-2 + Q(6))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$2264 := (-Q(Q(2))^{F(Q(2))} + F(6)!)/Q(4)$$

$$2264 := 2 \times (Q(-2 + Q(6)) - 4!)$$

$$2264 := 6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)}) - 4$$

$$2264 := C(2) \times (T(2) + C(6) + C(4))$$

$$2264 := C(C(2)) + C(2 \times 6) + 4!$$

$$2264 := T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 4$$

$$2264 := T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 4$$

$$2265 := (2 + T(2))! + T(65)$$

$$2265 := (F(C(2)) + 2 \times C(6)) \times 5$$

$$2265 := C(C(2)) \times T(2) + C(-6 + T(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2265 &:= C(C(2)) + C(2 \times 6) + Q(5) \\
 2265 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5!) \\
 2265 &:= T(2 + T(2) \times T(6)) + T(T(5)) \\
 2265 &:= T(F(2) + 2^6) + T(T(5)) \\
 2265 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 5 \\
 2265 &:= T(T(2)) \times Q(T(2)) + T(T(6 + 5)) \\
 2265 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 5 \\
 \\
 2266 &:= -2 + F(Q(2)) \times (6! + Q(6)) \\
 2266 &:= -2 + Q(6 \times C(2)) - Q(6) \\
 2266 &:= -2 + T(2) \times T(6) \times Q(6) \\
 2266 &:= F(T(2 + 2)) + T(66) \\
 2266 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 6 \\
 2266 &:= T(T(2 + 2)) + T(66) \\
 2266 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 6 \\
 \\
 2267 &:= -(1/2) \times Q(Q(Q(2))) - 6 + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2267 &:= -2 \times (F(Q(2)) + Q(F(6))) + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2267 &:= -2 - Q(T(2)) + T(67) \\
 2267 &:= -C(2) - T(2) + T(67) \\
 2267 &:= C(2 + 2) + 6 + C(F(7)) \\
 2267 &:= C(C(2))/(-Q(2)) - 6 + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2267 &:= -F(2) + \sqrt{T(2)^{F(6)}} \times T(7) \\
 2267 &:= -T(2) - F(T(T(2))) + T(67) \\
 2267 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 7 \\
 2267 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 7 \\
 2267 &:= T(T(T(T(2))))/(-T(T(T(2)))) + T(67) \\
 \\
 2268 &:= (1/8) \times (Q(Q(2)) - 2) \times Q(Q(6)) \\
 2268 &:= (T(2)^{T(2)} + Q(6)) \times T(8) \\
 2268 &:= F(2 + 2) \times Q(6) \times F(8) \\
 2268 &:= F(C(2)) \times \sqrt{-2 + 6! + F(F(8))} \\
 2268 &:= T(2) \times F(2 + 6) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2268 &:= T(2)^2 \times (C(6) + T(8)) \\
 2268 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 8 \\
 2268 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(-2 + T(6) + 8) \\
 2268 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 8 \\
 \\
 2269 &:= -C(2) + Q(6 \times C(2)) - C(\sqrt{9}) \\
 2269 &:= C(2 + 26) - C(\sqrt{C(9)}) \\
 2269 &:= F(2) - (C(2) - Q(6)) \times Q(9) \\
 2269 &:= F(2) + F(C(2)) \times C(6)/F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 2269 &:= -F(2) - 2 \times (F(F(6)) - Q(F(9))) \\
 2269 &:= T(2)^{T(T(2))} + T(T(6) + F(9)) \\
 2269 &:= T(22) + T(T(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 2269 &:= T(C(2 + 2)) + 9 \times T(6) \\
 2269 &:= T(F(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 9 \\
 2269 &:= T(Q(2)^{T(2)}) + 9 \times T(6) \\
 2269 &:= T(T(2) + 2^6) - 9 \\
 2269 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 6! + 9 \\
 \\
 2270 &:= 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(7) - 0!) \\
 2270 &:= F(Q(2)) \times Q(2)! + C(F(7)) + 0! \\
 2270 &:= -F(Q(F(2 + 2))) + Q(Q(7) - 0!) \\
 2270 &:= -F(T(T(2))) + T(-T(2) + 70) \\
 2270 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 0 \\
 2270 &:= Q(Q(C(2))) + Q(Q(2)!) - Q(Q(7)) - 0! \\
 \\
 2271 &:= -Q(2)! - Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q(7) - 1) \\
 2271 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 1 \\
 2271 &:= Q(Q(C(2))) + Q(Q(2)!) - Q(Q(7)) \\
 2271 &:= T(2) \times (C(T(2)) \times T(7) + 1) \\
 2271 &:= T(2) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(7) - 1) \\
 2272 &:= (2^{C(2)} + T(7)) \times C(2) \\
 \\
 2272 &:= 7 \times Q(2 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2272 &:= C(2) - (C(C(2)) - 7!) \times (1/2) \\ 2272 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 2 \\ 2272 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times \sqrt{(F(2) + 7!) \times Q(2)} \\ 2272 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times \sqrt{Q(2) \times 7! + Q(2)} \\ 2272 &:= T(2)^{Q(2)} \times T(7) + Q(2) \\ 2272 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(F(2)) + T(F(7) - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2273 &:= 2 + 2 + C(T(7)) - C(C(3)) \\ 2273 &:= 2 + T(2) \times (T(F(7)) + T(T(F(T(3)))))) \\ 2273 &:= 2 + T(2) \times Q(T(7)) - Q(Q(3)) \\ 2273 &:= F(C(2) + 2) + C(F(7)) + F(C(F(3))) \\ 2273 &:= Q(2 \times Q(2)) + Q(Q(7) - F(3)) \\ 2273 &:= Q(C(2)) + (-2 + Q(7))^{F(3)} \\ 2273 &:= Q(C(2)) + Q(7 \times C(2)) - Q(3) \\ 2273 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 3 \\ 2273 &:= Q(Q(2)!) + Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(7)) - 3!! \\ 2273 &:= T(T(T(2))) + 2 \times (T(T(7)) + T(3)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2274 &:= (2 + F(2 \times 7)) \times F(4)! \\ 2274 &:= (F(2) + T(27)) \times T(F(4)) \\ 2274 &:= 2 \times (C(C(2)) + Q(Q(7) - 4!)) \\ 2274 &:= -2 + Q(2) \times (-7 + Q(4!)) \\ 2274 &:= F(2) + Q(C(2)) + Q(Q(7) - \sqrt{4}) \\ 2274 &:= -Q(2) + T(2 + Q(7)) + Q(4) \\ 2274 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 4 \\ 2274 &:= T(C(2)) + C(T(2)) + T(T(7 + 4)) \\ 2274 &:= T(T(2)) \times (F(2 \times 7) + \sqrt{4}) \\ 2274 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-T(2) + T(T(7)) - 4!) \\ 2274 &:= -T(T(2)) \times (T(T(2)) - 7 \times T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2275 &:= (2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times 5 \\ 2275 &:= (C(2) - F(2)) \times F(7) \times Q(5) \\ 2275 &:= -2 \times F(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 5! \\ 2275 &:= -2 - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) - 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2275 &:= 7 \times (Q(Q(2)) - F(Q(2))) \times Q(5) \\ 2275 &:= C(2)!/Q(Q(2)) - 5 \times Q(7) \\ 2275 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 5 \\ 2275 &:= -T(2) + T((C(2) - C(7)) \times (-1/5)) \\ 2275 &:= -T(2) + T(2 + 5 \times F(7)) \\ 2275 &:= -T(2) + T(T(2) + Q(7) + T(5)) \\ 2275 &:= T(T(2))! + T(T(T(2) + 7)) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2276 &:= (Q(2) + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(7) + Q(Q(6)) \\ 2276 &:= -2 + T(T(2) + T(7) + Q(6)) \\ 2276 &:= C(2) + 6 \times T(27) \\ 2276 &:= C(2 \times Q(2)) + Q(7 \times 6) \\ 2276 &:= C(C(2)) + F(2) \times Q(7 \times 6) \\ 2276 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 6 \\ 2276 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(27) + F(6) \\ 2276 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(2) - 6! - 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2277 &:= 2 + 7 \times T(-T(2) + T(7)) \\ 2277 &:= C(2) - C(27) + C(T(7)) \\ 2277 &:= C(C(2)) + F(2) + Q(Q(7) - 7) \\ 2277 &:= -F(2) + T(2)^7 + T(F(7)) \\ 2277 &:= -F(2) + T(T(2) \times F(7) + T(7)) \\ 2277 &:= Q(2) - 2^7 + Q(Q(7)) \\ 2277 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 7 \\ 2277 &:= Q(T(2)) + Q(2 + 7) \times T(7) \\ 2277 &:= -T(T(2)) - T(T(2))! + T(77) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2278 &:= (F(Q(2)) + Q(C(2))) \times (F(7) + F(8)) \\ 2278 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 8 \\ 2278 &:= Q(Q(Q(2)!/C(2))) + C(\sqrt{-C(7) + C(8)}) \\ 2278 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + F(Q(2)) \times (F(F(7)) + Q(F(8))) \\ 2278 &:= T((2 + 2)! + 7 + T(8)) \\ 2278 &:= T(-(2 + 2) + 7 + Q(8)) \\ 2278 &:= T(-2 + T(2 \times 7) - T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$2278 := T(C(2) + T(2) + 7 \times 8)$$

$$2278 := T(F(2 + 2) + T(7) + T(8))$$

$$2279 := -(1/2) \times Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(7)) + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$2279 := -(F(2) + Q(2))! + Q(Q(7)) - F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$2279 := 2 + 9 \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(7))$$

$$2279 := C(2) + T(2) \times (T(7) + C(9))$$

$$2279 := F(2) + C(F(2) \times F(7)) + Q(9)$$

$$2279 := F(C(2) + 2) + C(F(7)) + C(\sqrt{9})$$

$$2279 := Q(C(2)) + Q(-2 + Q(7)) + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$2279 := Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(C(2)) + C(F(7)) + 9$$

$$2279 := Q(T(2)) + 2 + T(7) \times Q(9)$$

$$2279 := T(2^{T(T(2))}) + F(F(7)) - F(9)$$

$$2280 := 2 + T(T(2) + Q(8)) + 0$$

$$2280 := 2 + T(T(T(2) + 8) + 0!)$$

$$2280 := C(C(2)) + Q(2) \times (Q(F(8)) + 0!)$$

$$2280 := -Q(2)! + Q(-(Q(Q(2)) - Q(8)) \times 0!)$$

$$2280 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2))) + 0$$

$$2280 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(Q(2)) \times \sqrt{8 + 0!})$$

$$2281 := -(F(2) + Q(2))! + Q(Q(8 - 1))$$

$$2281 := 2 + T(T(2) + Q(8)) + 1$$

$$2281 := C(C(2)) \times Q(2) + F(F(8 - 1))$$

$$2281 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2))) + 1$$

$$2281 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(-Q(2) + Q(8 - 1))$$

$$2281 := T(2) + T(T(2) + Q(8))$$

$$2281 := T(2) + T(T(T(2) + 8) + 1)$$

$$2282 := 2 + T(T(2) + Q(8)) + 2$$

$$2282 := -22 + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2)))$$

$$2282 := C(C(2)) + T(C(T(2)) + \sqrt{-1 + T(Q(5))})$$

$$2282 := -F(2) - T(T(2))! + T(T(F(8))/T(2))$$

$$2282 := F(Q(Q(2))) - F(2) + Q(Q(8 - 2))$$

$$2282 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2))) + 2$$

$$2282 := Q(2) + T(T(2) + 8^2)$$

$$2282 := Q(C(2)) + F(C(2)) + C(F(8) - C(2))$$

$$2283 := 2 \times T(C(2)) + T(T(8 + 3))$$

$$2283 := 2^{T(T(2))} \times T(8) - T(T(3))$$

$$2283 := 2 + T(2) + T(3 + Q(8))$$

$$2283 := 2 + T(T(2) + Q(8)) + 3$$

$$2283 := -F(C(2)) + C((\sqrt{2 \times 8})!)/3!$$

$$2283 := F(Q(2)) - Q(2)! + Q(8 \times 3!)$$

$$2283 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2))) + 3$$

$$2284 := 2 \times (C(C(2)) + 8!/C(4))$$

$$2284 := 2 + T(T(2) + Q(8)) + 4$$

$$2284 := C(C(2)) + C(2) + Q(F(8) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$2284 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2))) + 4$$

$$2284 := Q(2) - Q(2)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(4))$$

$$2284 := -Q(2) - Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(8) - Q(4))$$

$$2284 := T(2) + T(2 + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$2284 := T(T(2))! + T(T(2 + 8)) + 4!$$

$$2284 := T(T(2)) + T(T(2) \times F(8) + 4)$$

$$2284 := T(T(2)) + T(T(2) + \sqrt{8^4})$$

$$2285 := (C(C(2)) - F(2 + 8)) \times 5$$

$$2285 := (C(C(2)) - T(2 + 8)) \times 5$$

$$2285 := (-F(T(T(2))) + T(-T(T(2)) + T(8))) \times 5$$

$$2285 := (Q(Q(2)) + Q(F(2) \times F(8))) \times 5$$

$$2285 := 2 + T(T(2) + Q(8)) + 5$$

$$2285 := -Q(2)! + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2))) + 5$$

$$2285 := Q(2) - Q(2)! + T(Q(8)) + Q(T(5))$$

$$2285 := Q(C(2)) + Q(2)! + C(8 + 5)$$

$$2286 := 2 + T(T(2) + Q(8)) + 6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2293 &:= (-2) + (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))) - Q(3) \\
 2293 &:= -2 + (Q(2) + Q(9)) \times C(3) \\
 2293 &:= -2 + 9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) - Q(3) \\
 2293 &:= -2 + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2))) - Q(3) \\
 2293 &:= -2 + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(3)!) \\
 2293 &:= -2 - Q(T(2)) + Q(3 + T(9)) \\
 2293 &:= -F(2) + 2 \times (Q(F(9)) - Q(3)) \\
 2293 &:= -F(T(T(2))) + 2 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 2293 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) + Q(T(9)) + 3 \\
 2293 &:= T(C(2 + 2)) - \sqrt{9} + C(T(3)) \\
 \\
 2294 &:= (Q(C(2)) - 2) \times (F(9) + F(4)) \\
 2294 &:= -(Q(F(2 + 2)) - Q(F(9))) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 2294 &:= -2 \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(-\sqrt{9} + T(T(4)))) \\
 2294 &:= 2 + Q(2) \times (-\sqrt{9} + Q(4!)) \\
 2294 &:= -2 - C(2) + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(4)) \\
 2294 &:= 9 \times 2^{C(2)} - T(4) \\
 2294 &:= 9 \times Q(2)^{Q(2)} - T(4) \\
 2294 &:= -F(C(2)) + (C(F(C(2))) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times (1/4) \\
 2294 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) + Q(T(9)) + 4 \\
 2294 &:= T(2) + T(2 \times F(9)) - F(T(4)) \\
 2294 &:= -T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) + 9 \times T(4!) \\
 \\
 2295 &:= (F(2) + Q(Q(2))) \times \sqrt{C(9) \times Q(5)} \\
 2295 &:= 2 \times (Q(2) + Q(F(9))) - Q(5) \\
 2295 &:= C(2)!/F(C(2)) + \sqrt{9} \times C(5) \\
 2295 &:= C(2)!/Q(Q(2)) - 9 \times Q(5) \\
 2295 &:= C(T(2)) \times ((C(2) + 9) \times 5) \\
 2295 &:= -Q(2) + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2))) - 5 \\
 2295 &:= Q(Q(2)) + (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))) - Q(5) \\
 2295 &:= Q(Q(2)) + 9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) - Q(5) \\
 2295 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2))) - Q(5) \\
 2295 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) + Q(T(9)) + 5 \\
 \\
 2295 &:= Q(T(2)) \times (T(2) \times T(9) + 5!) \\
 2295 &:= T(2^{T(2)} + 9) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 2296 &:= (-2) + (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))) - 6 \\
 2296 &:= (T(22) + F(9)) \times F(6) \\
 2296 &:= -2 + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2))) - 6 \\
 2296 &:= 9 \times 2^{C(2)} - F(6) \\
 2296 &:= 9 \times Q(2)^{Q(2)} - F(6) \\
 2296 &:= C(2) \times (C(C(2)) - 9 - C(6)) \\
 2296 &:= -C(2) + Q(2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times Q(6) \\
 2296 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) + Q(T(9)) + 6 \\
 2296 &:= T(2^{T(T(2))}) + \sqrt{T(\sqrt{9})^6} \\
 2296 &:= T(C(2 + 2)) + C(T(9 - 6)) \\
 2296 &:= T(Q(2 + 2)) + \sqrt{9} \times 6! \\
 \\
 2297 &:= 9 \times 2^{C(2)} - 7 \\
 2297 &:= 9 \times Q(2)^{Q(2)} - 7 \\
 2297 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) + Q(T(9)) + 7 \\
 2297 &:= T(T(2)^{T(2)} + F(9)) + T(T(7)) \\
 2297 &:= T(T(T(2 + 2)) + T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) \\
 \\
 2298 &:= 2 \times (F(2) + Q(F(9)) - 8) \\
 2298 &:= 2 \times T(Q(2)) + T(\sqrt{9} + Q(8)) \\
 2298 &:= 2 + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2))) - 8 \\
 2298 &:= 2 - 8 + 9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) \\
 2298 &:= 9 \times T(22) + F(8) \\
 2298 &:= C(2)!/Q(C(2)) + Q(F(9)) + C(8) \\
 2298 &:= Q(2 \times Q(2)!) - (\sqrt{9!/8!})! \\
 2298 &:= Q(Q(C(2)) - Q(Q(2))) - (\sqrt{9!/8!})! \\
 2298 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) + Q(T(9)) + 8 \\
 2298 &:= T((2 + 2)!) + \sqrt{9} \times T(T(8)) \\
 2298 &:= T(2) + T(2) \times (C(9) + T(8)) \\
 2298 &:= -T(T(2)) + 2^{T(\sqrt{9})} \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2299 &:= (C(2) + Q(2 + Q(9)))/\sqrt{9} \\
 2299 &:= -2 + Q(\sqrt{9} \times Q(Q(2))) - \sqrt{9} \\
 2299 &:= -2 + T(2 \times F(9)) - T(9) \\
 2299 &:= -2 - T(2) + Q(\sqrt{9} + T(9)) \\
 2299 &:= C(C(2)) \times F(Q(2)) + F(9) + C(9) \\
 2299 &:= C(F(C(2) - F(2))) + F(9) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2299 &:= F(Q(2)) - Q(Q(2)) + Q(F(9)) + Q(F(9)) \\
 2299 &:= Q(2) + (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9) \\
 2299 &:= Q(2) + 9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9 \\
 2299 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(2)) + Q(T(9)) + 9 \\
 2299 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(2^{T(\sqrt{9})} + \sqrt{9}) \\
 2299 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2 + T(T(9)) + T(T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2300 &:= -Q(2) + Q(Q(3! + 0!) - 0!) \\
 2300 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) - Q(0! + 0!) \\
 2300 &:= Q(T(Q(2))) \times (T(T(3)) + 0! + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2301 &:= -F(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(1 + 0!)) \\
 2301 &:= -F(Q(2)) + Q(Q(3! + 0!) - 1) \\
 2301 &:= -T(2) + Q(T(Q(3)) + T(1 + 0!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2302 &:= -2 + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) \\
 2302 &:= -2 + Q(C(2) \times 3!) \\
 2302 &:= -2 + Q(F(3) \times Q(2)!) \\
 2302 &:= -F(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\
 2302 &:= Q(2)! + T(Q(Q(3) - 0!) + T(2)) \\
 2302 &:= T(C(2)) \times C(3 + 0!) - 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2303 &:= (2 + T(Q(3))) \times Q(0! + T(3)) \\
 2303 &:= C(2) \times T(C(3)) - 0! - T(3)! \\
 2303 &:= -F(2) + C((3 + 0!)!)/3! \\
 2303 &:= -F(2) + Q((Q(3) - 0!) \times 3!) \\
 2303 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) - (0 \times 3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2303 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) - (0 \times 3)! \\
 2304 &:= (2 \times (3 + 0!)!)^{F(F(4))} \\
 2304 &:= (2 \times (3 + 0!)!)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2304 &:= (C(2) \times 3!)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2304 &:= (C(2) + C(3) + 0!) \times C(4) \\
 2304 &:= (T(T(2)) \times F(T(3)))^{F(F(4))} \\
 2304 &:= (T(T(2)) \times F(T(3)))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2304 &:= Q(2 \times (3 \times 0 + 4)!) \\
 2304 &:= Q(2 \times 3) \times C(4) \\
 2304 &:= Q(Q(2) \times 3 \times 4) \\
 2304 &:= T(2^3) \times C(4) \\
 2304 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(4) \\
 2304 &:= -T(T(2)) - T(T(T(3))) \times (0 - T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2305 &:= (2 \times T(T(T(3))) - 0!) \times 5 \\
 2305 &:= (Q(2) - T(30)) \times (-5) \\
 2305 &:= F(2) + Q(-F(3) \times (0! - Q(5))) \\
 2305 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + (0 \times 5)! \\
 2305 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) + (0 \times 5)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2306 &:= 2 + (1/6) \times C((3 + 0!)!) \\
 2306 &:= 2 + Q((Q(3) - 0!) \times 6) \\
 2306 &:= 2 + Q(3! \times F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2307 &:= F(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times (0! + 7)) \\
 2307 &:= -Q(C(2)) - 30 + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2307 &:= T(2) + Q(T(3) \times (0! + 7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2308 &:= -2 + T(3 + 0!) \times T(F(8)) \\
 2308 &:= -2 + T(3 + 0!) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \\
 2308 &:= Q(2) + Q(8 \times 3!) \\
 2308 &:= Q(2) + Q(8 \times T(3)) \\
 2308 &:= -T(2) + T(C(3 + 0!)) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2309 &:= -2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(C(\sqrt{9} + 0!)) \\ 2309 &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times (-0! + Q(F(9))) \\ 2309 &:= -F(2) + T(T(T(3))) \times (0! + 9) \\ 2309 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) - 0! + (\sqrt{9})! \\ 2309 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) - 0! + (\sqrt{9})! \\ 2309 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + T(0! + T(3)) + Q(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2310 &:= 10 \times T(F(2^3)) \\ 2310 &:= 2 \times F(F(3!)) \times F(10) \\ 2310 &:= 2 \times T(T(3)) \times F(10) \\ 2310 &:= 2 \times T(T(3)) \times T(10) \\ 2310 &:= F(C(2)) \times F(3) \times F(10) \\ 2310 &:= F(Q(2))! + Q(Q(3! + 1) - 0!) \\ 2310 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2311 &:= (C(F(C(2))) + F(C(3)))/F(11) \\ 2311 &:= 2 \times Q(F(Q(3))) - 1 \times 1 \\ 2311 &:= Q(Q(2) + T(3)) + T(T(11)) \\ 2311 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 1 \\ 2311 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(C(3 + 1)) \\ 2311 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(-F(3) + T(11)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2312 &:= (2 + Q((3 + 1)!)) \times Q(2) \\ 2312 &:= (F(T(T(2))) \times T(F(T(3))) + 1) \times F(T(T(2))) \\ 2312 &:= 2 \times F(C(F(3)) + 1)^2 \\ 2312 &:= 2 \times F(F(3!) + 1)^2 \\ 2312 &:= 2 \times Q(31 + T(2)) \\ 2312 &:= 2 \times Q(C(3) - 1 + C(2)) \\ 2312 &:= 2 \times Q(F(3^2)) \\ 2312 &:= 2 \times Q(Q(3) + Q(1 + Q(2))) \\ 2312 &:= T(T(2)) \times T((3 + 1)!) + C(C(2)) \\ 2312 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2313 &:= 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(C(1 + 3)) \\ 2313 &:= Q(2 \times (3 + 1)!) + Q(3) \\ 2313 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(3) \\ 2313 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) + Q(3) \\ 2313 &:= Q(T(2)) + Q(3 \times Q(1 + 3)) \\ 2313 &:= T(2^{T(3)}) + F(13) \\ 2313 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2314 &:= (Q(-2 + Q(3!)) + 1) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 2314 &:= 2 + F(3!) \times Q(1 + Q(4)) \\ 2314 &:= -2 + T(3)! + T(1 + F(T(4))) \\ 2314 &:= F(C(2) + 3) \times (-1 + C(F(4))) \\ 2314 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) + 1 + Q(F(4)) \\ 2314 &:= T(C(2)) + T(3 + C(4)) \\ 2314 &:= T(Q(2)) + Q(3 \times Q(4)) \\ 2314 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2315 &:= (2 \times T(T(T(3))) + 1) \times 5 \\ 2315 &:= (C(F(C(2))) - F(F(3)))/(-1 + 5) \\ 2315 &:= -5 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 3!! + 1) \\ 2315 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + \sqrt{1 + 5!} \\ 2315 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) + \sqrt{1 + 5!} \\ 2315 &:= -Q(Q(2)) + T(T(Q(3))) + Q(Q(1 + 5)) \\ 2315 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2316 &:= (C(2) + T(C(3))) \times 6 \\ 2316 &:= (C(F(C(2))) + 3)/\sqrt{16} \\ 2316 &:= F(C(2) + Q(3)) - 1 + 6! \\ 2316 &:= -Q(2) - Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(1 + 6)) \\ 2316 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$2317 := (2 \times 3)! + F(17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2317 &:= -C(2) - T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{1+7!}) \\ 2317 &:= Q(2) + Q(3) + Q(-1 + Q(7)) \\ 2317 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(F(T(3) + 1)) + T(T(7)) \\ 2317 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2318 &:= 2 \times (3 + Q(F(1 + 8))) \\ 2318 &:= -2 - Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(-1 + 8)) \\ 2318 &:= F(T(T(2))) + T(3 + 1) \times T(F(8)) \\ 2318 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) + 1 + T(Q(8)) \\ 2318 &:= T(T(C(2)) + T(T(3))) - 1 + T(T(8)) \\ 2318 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2319 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(Q(3) + 1) - Q(9) \\ 2319 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(3 + 1)) - Q(9) \\ 2319 &:= Q(Q(Q(2) + 3)) - 1 - Q(9) \\ 2319 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(C(3)) + 1) + T(9) \\ 2319 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2320 &:= (1/3) \times T(T(2))! + T(C(0! + T(2))) \\ 2320 &:= (F(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\ 2320 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 0 \\ 2320 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times (Q(3 \times Q(2)) + 0!) \\ 2320 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 0 \\ 2320 &:= T(-2 + T(3)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 0!) \\ 2320 &:= T(Q(2)) \times (T(T(3 \times 2)) + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2321 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2))) - T(Q(3))) \times (T(Q(2)) + 1) \\ 2321 &:= C(2) \times T(C(3)) - T(T(C(2)) + 1) \\ 2321 &:= Q(2) + 3!! + F(Q(Q(2)) + 1) \\ 2321 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 1 \\ 2321 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$2322 := (C(2) + T(2 \times T(3))) \times C(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2322 &:= (Q(C(2) + C(3)) - Q(C(2))) \times 2 \\ 2322 &:= (T(T(2))! + T(T(3))^2) \times 2 \\ 2322 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(F(T(3)))) + T(2)) \times T(2) \\ 2322 &:= 2 \times (3!! + F(C(2))^2) \\ 2322 &:= 2 \times Q(3) + Q(2 \times Q(2)!) \\ 2322 &:= C(Q(2) + Q(3)) + C(F(2) + Q(2)) \\ 2322 &:= F(Q(2))! \times (3 + Q(Q(2)) \times Q(2)!) \\ 2322 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(Q(3)) + T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 2322 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 2322 \quad := Q(3 \times Q(2)) \\ 2322 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2323 &:= -C(2) + C(3) + Q(C(2) \times 3!) \\ 2323 &:= C(T(2)) + C(T(3)) + T(2^{T(3)}) \\ 2323 &:= F(C(2)) \times 3! + C(F(F(2) + 3!)) \\ 2323 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 3 \\ 2323 &:= Q(Q(2)) + 3 + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) \\ 2323 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 3 \\ 2323 &:= T(2) \times Q(Q(3)) + T(Q(2^3)) \\ 2323 &:= -T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(F(T(3)))) / (-T(T(2))) - F(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2324 &:= (2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(2) + 4!) \\ 2324 &:= (C(F(C(2))) + C(3) + C(2)) \times (1/4) \\ 2324 &:= 2 \times (-T(3^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 2324 &:= 2^{T(3)} + T(T(2))! + T(T(T(4))) \\ 2324 &:= 2 - Q(3) \times (-2 - Q(Q(4))) \\ 2324 &:= F(T(T(2))) + T(3)! + T(F(2) + F(T(4))) \\ 2324 &:= Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 4 \\ 2324 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 4 \\ 2324 &:= Q(Q(2)) + Q(F(3)) + Q(2 \times 4!) \\ 2324 &:= T(F(2) + T(3))^2 + T(F(T(4))) \\ 2324 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(3)) - C(2) + C(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$2325 := (2 + 3) \times T(2 \times T(5))$$

$$2325 := (Q(2) + F(Q(3) + 2)) \times Q(5)$$

$$2325 := (-Q(2) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(5)$$

$$2325 := 5 \times T(-(2 - 32))$$

$$2325 := C(Q(2) + Q(3)) + C(2) + 5!$$

$$2325 := F(C(2)) - C(3!) + F(C(2)) \times 5!$$

$$2325 := Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 5$$

$$2325 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 5$$

$$2326 := F(Q(2))! + 3!! + Q(Q(2) + Q(6))$$

$$2326 := F(T(T(2)))! / T(T(3)) + T(T(F(2) + 6))$$

$$2326 := Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 6$$

$$2326 := Q(Q(2)) + 3! + Q(6 \times C(2))$$

$$2326 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 6$$

$$2326 := T(T((1/3) \times T(T(T(2)))))) - C(2)! / (-T(6))$$

$$2326 := T(T(2)) + T(3)! + Q(Q(2) + Q(6))$$

$$2327 := (C(C(2)) + T(C(3))) \times T(2) - C(7)$$

$$2327 := (-Q(2) + 3!!) \times F(7) / Q(2)$$

$$2327 := -3 \times Q(2)! - 2 + Q(Q(7))$$

$$2327 := C(C(2)) \times (3 + 2) - F(F(7))$$

$$2327 := Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 7$$

$$2327 := Q(C(2)) \times (C(3) + Q(2)) + C(7)$$

$$2327 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 7$$

$$2327 := -T(2) + T(F(3) + 2) \times F(F(7))$$

$$2327 := T(Q(2^3)) + T(2) + Q(7)$$

$$2328 := (Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(2)) + 8)$$

$$2328 := C(2) \times (3 + C(2) \times T(8))$$

$$2328 := F(F(C(2)) - 3) - 2^8$$

$$2328 := F(T(2) \times T(3)) - 2^8$$

$$2328 := Q(2)! \times (-3 + Q(2 + 8))$$

$$2328 := Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 8$$

$$2328 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 8$$

$$2328 := T(2) \times T(3)! + 8 \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$2328 := -T(T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(2 \times T(8))$$

$$2329 := -2 + T(F(T(3)))^2 + T(T(9))$$

$$2329 := -F(F(C(2)) - 3) + C(C(2) + 9)$$

$$2329 := F(Q(2)) \times 3!! + Q(Q(2) + 9)$$

$$2329 := Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(Q(2)) \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$2329 := Q(2 + 3) + Q(T(2) + T(9))$$

$$2329 := Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) + 9$$

$$2329 := Q(C(2) \times 3!) + Q(C(2) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$2329 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(3! \times C(2)) + 9$$

$$2329 := T(T(2)) \times C(T(3)) - 2 + T(T(9))$$

$$2330 := (2 + F(3!)) \times F(F(3! + 0!))$$

$$2330 := (2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (Q(3) + 0!)$$

$$2330 := (2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3 + 0!)$$

$$2330 := (C(2) + F(3)) \times F(F(0! + 3!))$$

$$2330 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) + 3) \times Q(3) - 0!$$

$$2330 := F(Q(2) + Q(3)) \times (Q(3) + 0!)$$

$$2330 := Q(C(2) \times 3!) + C(3) - 0!$$

$$2330 := T(F(2) + 3) \times F(F(T(3) + 0!))$$

$$2331 := (Q(Q(Q(2))) + 3) \times Q(3)$$

$$2331 := C(C(2) + 3) + C(T(3 + 1))$$

$$2331 := F(T(2) \times T(3)) - T(T(T(3)) + 1)$$

$$2331 := Q(C(2) \times 3!) + C(3)$$

$$2331 := Q(F(Q(2))) \times (3 + Q(Q(3 + 1)))$$

$$2331 := Q(T(2)) \times (3 + Q(Q(3 + 1)))$$

$$2331 := T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(3) - 1)))$$

$$2331 := T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(3 + 1)$$

$$2332 := F(Q(Q(2))) + 3!! + Q(Q(3 + 2))$$

$$2332 := -Q(2) + Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(2))$$

$$2332 := Q(C(2)) - Q(3!) + Q(C(2) \times 3!)$$

$$2332 := T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2332 &:= T(Q(Q(2))) + Q(T(3)) \times (T(Q(3)) + Q(Q(2))) & 2336 &:= -(Q(Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(3+3)) - Q(Q(6))) \\
 2332 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(3)) + C(T(3) - 2) & 2336 &:= 2^{F(T(3))} + T(F(3)^6) \\
 2332 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3))) + T(F(3)^{T(T(2))}) & 2336 &:= C(2+3) + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(6)) \\
 & & 2336 &:= Q(2) \times F(3!) + Q(3! \times F(6)) \\
 2333 &:= -(Q(Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(3!))) - 3 & 2336 &:= -Q(2) + 3 \times T(3 + Q(6)) \\
 2333 &:= -(Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(Q(3)))) + 3 & 2336 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q(3))/6! \\
 2333 &:= F(F(C(2))) - C(F(C(F(3)))) + 3 \times C(3!) & 2336 &:= T(2^{T(3)}) + F(3)^{F(6)} \\
 2333 &:= -Q(Q(2)) + (3! + Q(Q(3))) \times C(3) & & \\
 2333 &:= Q(Q(2)) + 3!! + F(F(3!)) + Q(3) & 2337 &:= -2^{3+3} + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2333 &:= -Q(Q(2)) + T(Q(3)) + Q(3 + T(Q(3))) & 2337 &:= C(T(2)) + T(3) \times (T(C(3)) + 7) \\
 2333 &:= T(2^{T(3)}) + T(F(F(3)) + T(T(3))) & 2337 &:= F(C(2)) \times C(3!) - F(3) - C(F(7)) \\
 & & 2337 &:= Q(2)! \times F(Q(3)) + Q(3 \times F(7)) \\
 2334 &:= (C(F(C(2))) + C(F(3)!)/F(C(F(3))) - C(F(4))) & 2337 &:= -T(2) + 3 \times T(3 \times F(7)) \\
 2334 &:= -2 + Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(4) & 2337 &:= T(T(2))! + 7 \times T(T(3+3)) \\
 2334 &:= C(2)!/T(3)! + T(3 + C(4)) & & \\
 2334 &:= Q(2)! + 3! + Q(3 \times Q(4)) & 2338 &:= -2 + 3 \times T(3 + T(8)) \\
 2334 &:= Q(2)! + 3! + Q(F(3) \times 4!) & 2338 &:= -2 + Q(3!) + Q(8 \times 3!) \\
 2334 &:= Q(T(2)) + T(T(3)) + Q(3 \times Q(4)) & 2338 &:= F(F(2) \times Q(3)) + Q(8 \times 3!) \\
 2334 &:= T(2) \times (3 + T(3)! + F(T(4))) & 2338 &:= F(F(C(2)) - 3!) + 8 \times C(3!) \\
 2334 &:= T(2) \times (3 + T(3)! + T(T(4))) & 2338 &:= T((-2 + C(3)) \times 3) - C(8) \\
 2334 &:= T(2 \times T(T(3))) + T(-F(3) + F(T(4))) & 2338 &:= T(2 \times F(3 \times 3)) - 8 \\
 2334 &:= -T(T(2)) + (3 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) & 2338 &:= T(Q(2)) \times T(3) + T(3 + Q(8)) \\
 & & & \\
 2335 &:= (2^{Q(3)} - T(Q(3))) \times 5 & 2339 &:= -(Q(Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(3!))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 2335 &:= (C(C(2)) - T(3 \times 3)) \times 5 & 2339 &:= -(Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) - 3 - Q(Q(9))) \\
 2335 &:= (F(F(C(2))) + C(3 \times 3)) \times (1/5) & 2339 &:= -C(2)! - C(3!) + C(F(F(3)) + F(9)) \\
 2335 &:= -(Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(3))) \times Q(3!) - 5 & 2339 &:= C(C(2) + 3) - C(3) + T(T(9)) \\
 2335 &:= (T(2)^{T(3)} + F(T(T(3)))) \times (1/5) & 2339 &:= -F(2) + 3 \times T(39) \\
 2335 &:= (T(T(2))! - T(F(F(3)) + T(T(3)))) \times 5 & 2339 &:= F(Q(2))^3 + F(3) \times Q(F(9)) \\
 2335 &:= Q(C(2) \times 3!) + 3! + Q(5) & 2339 &:= -Q(C(2)) + C(3!) + C(3) \times Q(9) \\
 & & 2339 &:= -T(Q(2)) + T(Q(3)) + Q(3 + T(9)) \\
 2336 &:= (1/6) \times Q(C(2)) \times (3 + C(3!)) & & \\
 2336 &:= (F(F(C(2))) - F(3))/3! + C(F(6)) & 2340 &:= (Q(Q(2)) + Q(T(3))) \times T(T(4) - 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2340 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 0$$

$$2340 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q((4 + 0)!))$$

$$2340 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 0$$

$$2340 := Q(2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + 0!)$$

$$2340 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 0$$

$$2340 := T(2^3) \times (C(4) + 0!)$$

$$2341 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 1$$

$$2341 := F(2 \times 3!) + C(F(F(4)! + 1))$$

$$2341 := Q(2)! + 3!! + F(1 + Q(4))$$

$$2341 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 1$$

$$2341 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 1$$

$$2341 := T(-2 + C(3)) + T(-1 + C(4))$$

$$2342 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 2$$

$$2342 := 2 + Q(3!) + Q(2 \times 4!)$$

$$2342 := 2 + Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(2))$$

$$2342 := C(C(2)) + T(3 \times T(4) \times 2)$$

$$2342 := F(F(C(2)) - 3!) \times F(4) + C(C(2))$$

$$2342 := F(T(T(2)))^3 + T(T(4) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$2342 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 2$$

$$2342 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 2$$

$$2342 := T(2 \times 34) - Q(2)$$

$$2343 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 3$$

$$2343 := C(C(2)) \times 3! - F(4)^3!$$

$$2343 := C(C(2)) \times 3! - Q(4! + 3)$$

$$2343 := F(Q(2)) + Q(3!) + Q(3 \times Q(4))$$

$$2343 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 3$$

$$2343 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 3$$

$$2343 := T(2 \times 34) - 3$$

$$2344 := -(C(C(2)) - 4 \times 3!! + 4!)$$

$$2344 := (C(C(2)) - C(3!)) \times \sqrt{C(4)} - 4!$$

$$2344 := (C(C(2)) - C(3!) - F(4)) \times \sqrt{C(4)}$$

$$2344 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 4$$

$$2344 := 2 \times (Q(34) + Q(4))$$

$$2344 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 4$$

$$2344 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 4$$

$$2344 := T(2 \times 34) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$2345 := (C(C(2)) + F(C(F(3)))) - C(4) \times 5$$

$$2345 := (Q(2) + T(3 \times T(4))) \times 5$$

$$2345 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 5$$

$$2345 := C(C(2)) + 3 + T(4 \times T(5))$$

$$2345 := -F(2) + T(F(3) \times F(4 + 5))$$

$$2345 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 5$$

$$2345 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 5$$

$$2345 := Q(C(2) \times 3!) + Q(4) + Q(5)$$

$$2345 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5)$$

$$2345 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(F(3) \times 4!) + Q(5)$$

$$2346 := (Q(2)! + C(3)) \times 46$$

$$2346 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 6$$

$$2346 := 2 \times (F(3) \times Q(4!) + F(F(6)))$$

$$2346 := C(C(2)) \times 3! - F(4)! - 6!$$

$$2346 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 6$$

$$2346 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 6$$

$$2346 := T((2 \times 3) \times T(4) + F(6))$$

$$2346 := T(-2 + T(3) + \sqrt{4^6})$$

$$2346 := T(23 + 4! + T(6))$$

$$2346 := T(F(2) + 3 + \sqrt{4^6})$$

$$2346 := T(F(2^3)) \times T(4) + T(F(6))$$

$$2347 := (-2 + C(3)) \times F(4)! + C(F(7))$$

$$2347 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 7$$

$$2347 := 2 \times (-3 - 4!) + Q(Q(7))$$

$$2347 := 2 \times Q(Q(3) + 4!) + Q(F(7))$$

$$2347 := 2 \times T(Q(3) + 4!) + T(Q(7))$$

$$2347 := C(T(2 + 3)) - C(T(4)) - T(7)$$

$$2347 := F(2) + T(F(3) + T(4 + 7))$$

$$2347 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 7$$

$$2347 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 7$$

$$2348 := (-Q(2) + 3!!) \times Q(F(4)) - Q(Q(8))$$

$$2348 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 8$$

$$2348 := -2 \times (F(3) - T(48))$$

$$2348 := 2 \times Q(34) + T(8)$$

$$2348 := C(C(2)) + (C(3) + 4!) \times T(8)$$

$$2348 := C(C(2)) + C(3) \times (4 + Q(8))$$

$$2348 := Q(2) \times (3 + Q(4!)) + 8$$

$$2348 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 8$$

$$2348 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 8$$

$$2349 := (2 + 3 + 4!) \times Q(9)$$

$$2349 := (23 + C(4)) \times \sqrt{C(9)}$$

$$2349 := (Q(2) + Q(3) + Q(4)) \times Q(9)$$

$$2349 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 9$$

$$2349 := -F(C(2)) \times C(3) + 4 \times C(9)$$

$$2349 := Q(2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4!)) + 9$$

$$2349 := Q(2 \times C(3)) - Q(4!) + 9$$

$$2349 := T(2) + T((T(3) - 4) \times F(9))$$

$$2349 := T(2 \times 34) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$2350 := (2 + T(Q(3))) \times 50$$

$$2350 := 2 \times (Q(Q(3!)) - 5! - 0!)$$

$$2350 := 2 \times (T(T(3)!/T(5)) - 0!)$$

$$2350 := 50 \times F(Q(Q(2)))/F(F(3!))$$

$$2351 := 2 \times (Q(Q(3!)) - 5!) - 1$$

$$2351 := 2 \times T(T(3)!/T(5)) - 1$$

$$2351 := -F(C(2)) \times (C(F(3)) - 5!) - 1$$

$$2351 := F(Q(2)) \times Q(3 + Q(5)) - 1$$

$$2351 := Q(Q(2)) \times (C(3) + 5!) - 1$$

$$2351 := T(2) \times Q(3 + Q(5)) - 1$$

$$2351 := -T(T(T(2))) \times (F(T(3)) - T(T(5))) - 1$$

$$2352 := 2 \times T(3 \times T(5) + T(2))$$

$$2352 := 3 \times Q(Q(2)) \times Q(5 + 2)$$

$$2352 := C(2) \times ((C(3) + 5!) \times 2)$$

$$2352 := C(2) \times 3! \times Q(5 + 2)$$

$$2352 := F(Q(2)) \times Q(3 + 5^2)$$

$$2352 := T(2) \times Q(3 + 5^2)$$

$$2352 := T(2) \times T(F(3) + 5)^2$$

$$2353 := -C(2) - T(3)! + T(T(T(5) - 3))$$

$$2353 := F(2) + F(F(3!)) \times (5! - F(3!))$$

$$2353 := -F(C(2)) \times (C(F(3)) - 5!) + F(F(3))$$

$$2353 := F(Q(2)) \times Q(3 + Q(5)) + F(F(3))$$

$$2353 := F(T(2) \times T(3)) - T(F(5 + 3))$$

$$2353 := Q(2)! + C(Q(3)) + Q((1/3) \times 5!)$$

$$2353 := -Q(2) \times (Q(3!) - Q(Q(5))) - 3$$

$$2353 := Q(2) + (Q(T(3)) + Q(T(5))) \times Q(3)$$

$$2354 := 2 - (C(3) - C(5)) \times 4!$$

$$2354 := 2 \times T(T(3)!/T(5)) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$2354 := 2 + (C(3) + 5!) \times Q(4)$$

$$2354 := -2 + (Q(3!) - Q(Q(5))) \times (-4)$$

$$2354 := -2 + (T(T(3)) - F(T(5))) \times (-4)$$

$$2354 := 2 - F(F(3!)) \times (-5! + F(F(4)!))$$

$$2354 := -2 - T(Q(3)) + Q(Q(5) + 4!)$$

$$2354 := F(Q(2)) \times Q(3 + Q(5)) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$2354 := Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$2354 := -T(T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) + 5) \times T(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2355 &:= (C(C(2)) - Q(3!) - 5) \times 5 \\
 2355 &:= (T(T(2)) \times C(3) - 5) \times T(5) \\
 2355 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(5 \times T(3))) \times 5 \\
 2355 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(F(3) \times T(5))) \times 5 \\
 2355 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (3!! + Q(5)) + 5! \\
 2355 &:= Q(2)! \times T(Q(3)) + T(Q(5) + Q(5)) \\
 2355 &:= Q(2) \times (3!! + Q(5)) - Q(Q(5)) \\
 \\
 2356 &:= (-2 + 3!) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6)) \\
 2356 &:= (F(2) + 3) \times (F(T(5)) - T(6)) \\
 2356 &:= (Q(2) + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(5) + T(T(6)) \\
 2356 &:= 2 \times (F(3) - 5! + Q(Q(6))) \\
 2356 &:= -2 + (T(C(3)) + T(5)) \times 6 \\
 2356 &:= -Q(2) \times (3! + C(5) - 6!) \\
 2356 &:= T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(5) + F(6)) \\
 2356 &:= T(T(2 \times T(3))) - 5 - 6! \\
 \\
 2357 &:= 2 \times (3 - Q(5)) + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2357 &:= C(2) \times T(3)! - C(T(5)) - T(7) \\
 2357 &:= C(2) + C(3) + C(5) + C(F(7)) \\
 2357 &:= F(2) - 5 \times Q(3) + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2357 &:= Q(2) \times C(3) \times Q(5) - C(7) \\
 2357 &:= -Q(2) - T(3)! + T(T(5 + 7)) \\
 2357 &:= T(T(2)) + F(3 + T(5)) - F(F(7)) \\
 \\
 2358 &:= (3 \times T(2))! / 5! - T(T(8)) \\
 2358 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2))) + 3!) \times Q(- (5 - 8)) \\
 2358 &:= (T(2)^{F(3)})! / 5! - T(T(8)) \\
 2358 &:= (T(T(2)^3) + T(5)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 2358 &:= -2 \times Q(Q(3)) + 5! \times F(8) \\
 2358 &:= F(T(2) \times T(3)) + 5 - T(F(8)) \\
 2358 &:= T(2) \times (T(3) \times C(5) + T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2358 &:= T(2) \times (T(3 \times 5) + T(T(8))) \\
 2358 &:= -T(2) \times Q(Q(3)) + Q(T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 2359 &:= -(C(C(2)) - 5 \times 3!! + C(9)) \\
 2359 &:= -2 - T(3)! + T(T(T(5) - \sqrt{9})) \\
 2359 &:= -C(2)! + C(3 \times 5) + C(F(9)) \\
 2359 &:= -C(2) + C(3) + C(T(5)) - T(T(9)) \\
 2359 &:= C(2 \times 3!) + Q(Q(5)) + (\sqrt{9})! \\
 2359 &:= F(T(2) \times T(3)) - 5 \times T(9) \\
 2359 &:= -Q(2) \times (Q(3!) - Q(Q(5))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 2359 &:= Q(2) \times F(3 \times 5) - Q(9) \\
 2359 &:= Q(23) + T(T(5) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 2360 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2))) + C(3!)) \times (6 - 0!) \\
 2360 &:= -C(2) \times (C(3!) - C(F(6)) + 0!) \\
 2360 &:= F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(F(3)) + Q(Q(6) + 0!) \\
 2360 &:= T(Q(2)) \times (T(3)! - Q(0! + T(6))) \\
 2360 &:= T(T(2 \times T(3))) - 6! - 0! \\
 \\
 2361 &:= (C(F(C(2))) + C(F(3))!) / F(F(6)) \\
 2361 &:= C(C(2)) + Q(3! + Q(6) + 1) \\
 2361 &:= -Q(2) - Q(3!) + Q(Q(6 + 1)) \\
 2361 &:= -Q(2) - Q(T(3)) + Q(Q(6 + 1)) \\
 2361 &:= T(T(2 \times T(3))) - 6! \\
 \\
 2362 &:= (C(2)! + T(T(3)) + C(T(6))) / T(T(T(2))) \\
 2362 &:= (C(F(C(2))) + C(F(3))! + F(F(6))) / F(C(2)) \\
 2362 &:= F(2) - T(3)! + T(T(6 \times 2)) \\
 2362 &:= F(Q(Q(2))) + 3! + Q(Q(6) + F(2)) \\
 2362 &:= F(T(2) \times T(3)) - T(T(F(6))) / T(2) \\
 2362 &:= Q(2) + Q(3) \times (6 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \\
 2362 &:= Q(C(2)) - 3! + Q(6 \times C(2)) \\
 2362 &:= Q(Q(2)) + T(T(3) + 62)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2362 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(6!/Q(Q(2)))$$

$$2363 := (C(F(C(2))) + C(F(3)!)/F(F(6)) + F(3))$$

$$2363 := 2 - T(3)! + T(T(6 + T(3)))$$

$$2363 := F(Q(Q(2))) + 3!! - Q(F(6)) + 3!!$$

$$2363 := -Q(2) + T(Q(T(3))) + T(6) \times Q(Q(3))$$

$$2363 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + (C(C(3)) - 6!)/Q(3)$$

$$2363 := -Q(Q(Q(2))) + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q(Q(6))) \times (1/3)$$

$$2363 := T(T(2 \times T(3))) - 6! + F(3)$$

$$2364 := (2 \times F(Q(3)) + 6!) \times F(4)$$

$$2364 := (C(C(2)) - C(3!)) \times F(6) - 4$$

$$2364 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) \times F(6))) \times F(F(4))$$

$$2364 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) \times F(6))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$2364 := 2 \times T(3)! + 4 \times T(T(6))$$

$$2364 := C(C(2)) + 3 - T(T(6)) + T(C(4))$$

$$2364 := Q(2)! + Q(3!) + Q(6) \times C(4)$$

$$2364 := Q(2)! + Q(3! + Q(6)) + Q(4!)$$

$$2364 := Q(2)! + Q(T(3) + Q(6)) + Q(4!)$$

$$2364 := -T(T(2)) - (-T(3) - T(T(6))) \times T(4)$$

$$2365 := (-F(2) + C(3!)) \times (6 + 5)$$

$$2365 := -(Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(3))) \times Q(6) + Q(5)$$

$$2365 := C(C(2)) + C(3! + 6) + C(5)$$

$$2365 := C(C(2)) + C(T(3) + 6) + C(5)$$

$$2365 := Q(C(2) \times 3!) + Q(6) + Q(5)$$

$$2365 := Q(Q(2)) + T(Q(3)) + Q(6!/T(5))$$

$$2365 := T(2^{T(3)} + 6) - 5!$$

$$2365 := T(2^{T(3)} + 6) - T(T(5))$$

$$2366 := -2 + F(3 \times 6) - C(6)$$

$$2366 := C(C(2) + T(3)) - T(T(6) + 6)$$

$$2366 := -Q(C(2)) - Q(Q(3)) \times (6 - Q(6))$$

$$2366 := Q(Q(2) + Q(3)) \times (F(6) + 6)$$

$$2366 := -T(Q(2)) + 66 \times Q(T(3))$$

$$2367 := 2 - 36 + Q(Q(7))$$

$$2367 := 2 - Q(3!) + Q(Q(6)) + F(7)$$

$$2367 := 2 - Q(T(3)) + Q(T(6) + T(7))$$

$$2367 := C(C(2)) + 3! + Q(-6 + Q(7))$$

$$2367 := C(C(2) + 3!) - 6! + C(7)$$

$$2367 := C(C(2) + T(3)) - 6! + C(7)$$

$$2367 := -T(T(2))! + 7 \times T(T(3)) \times T(6)$$

$$2367 := T(T(2)) - T(3)! + T(6 \times F(7))$$

$$2367 := T(T(T(2))) + T(F(3) \times (T(6) + F(7)))$$

$$2368 := (C(2^3) - C(6)) \times 8$$

$$2368 := F(2) + T(T(3)) + T(68)$$

$$2368 := F(T(2) \times T(3)) - 6 \times T(8)$$

$$2368 := Q(2^3) + Q(6 \times 8)$$

$$2369 := 2 + F(3) \times T(T(F(6))) + T(T(9))$$

$$2369 := 2 + Q(T(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + T(T(9))$$

$$2369 := -2 - Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(F(9))$$

$$2369 := 2 - T(3)! - C(T(6))/(-\sqrt{9})$$

$$2369 := F(2) - C(3!) + F(6 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$2369 := F(T(T(2))) - T(3)! + T(T(T(6) - 9))$$

$$2369 := -Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(Q(6) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$2369 := Q(Q(C(2))) - (-C(3) + C(Q(6)))/C(\sqrt{9})$$

$$2370 := -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 0$$

$$2370 := F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 0$$

$$2370 := Q(2) - Q(3!) + Q(Q(7)) + 0!$$

$$2370 := T(2) \times (T(3)! + 70)$$

$$2370 := T(Q(3) + 2) + Q(Q(7) - 0!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2371 &:= (Q(2)! + 3! - Q(Q(7))) \times (-1) \\ 2371 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 1 \\ 2371 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 1 \\ 2371 &:= Q(2) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) \\ 2371 &:= Q(C(2)) + 3 + Q(Q(7) - 1) \\ 2371 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(-3 + Q(7)) - 1 \\ 2371 &:= T(T(2)) - Q(T(3)) + Q(Q(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2372 &:= (C(C(2)) - C(3!) - 7!) \times (-1/2) \\ 2372 &:= 2 \times (3!! + 2 \times F(F(7))) \\ 2372 &:= 2 \times F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7) - F(2)) \\ 2372 &:= -2^{F(T(3))} + T(72) \\ 2372 &:= -2^{T(3)} + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2372 &:= -2 - C(3) + Q(7^2) \\ 2372 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 2 \\ 2372 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 2 \\ 2372 &:= -Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(2) \\ 2372 &:= Q(Q(2)) - T(Q(3)) + Q(7^2) \\ 2372 &:= T(T(2)) - T(C(3)) + C(7 \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2373 &:= ((2 + 3)! - 7) \times F(F(3!)) \\ 2373 &:= ((2 + 3)! - 7) \times T(T(3)) \\ 2373 &:= (F(2) + T(T(3)) + T(F(7))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 2373 &:= (F(3) \times C(C(2)) - F(F(7))) \times 3 \\ 2373 &:= (Q(2^3) + Q(7)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 2373 &:= (Q(C(2)) + 3!! + 7) \times 3 \\ 2373 &:= (T(T(2 + 3)) - 7) \times T(T(3)) \\ 2373 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 3 \\ 2373 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 3 \\ 2373 &:= -Q(2^3) + Q(Q(7)) + Q(3!) \\ 2373 &:= -Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(7)) - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2374 &:= -2 + C(3!) \times (7 + 4) \\ 2374 &:= 2 + Q(-3 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2374 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 4 \\ 2374 &:= -F(2) \times C(3) + 7^4 \\ 2374 &:= F(2 \times Q(3)) - 7!/4! \\ 2374 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 4 \\ 2374 &:= -T(2) \times Q(3) + 7^4 \\ 2374 &:= -T(2)^3 + 7^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2375 &:= -(2 - 3 \times 7) \times C(5) \\ 2375 &:= (F(2) + Q(Q(3)) + F(7)) \times Q(5) \\ 2375 &:= (Q(2) + T(T(3) + 7)) \times Q(5) \\ 2375 &:= (Q(2 \times 3!) - Q(7)) \times Q(5) \\ 2375 &:= 2 + F(F(3!)) \times (-7 + 5!) \\ 2375 &:= 2 + T(T(3)) \times (-7 + T(T(5))) \\ 2375 &:= 2 + T(T(3)) \times (F(F(7)) - T(T(5))) \\ 2375 &:= 2 - 3 + Q(Q(7)) - Q(5) \\ 2375 &:= 2 - T(T(3)) \times (7 - 5!) \\ 2375 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 5 \\ 2375 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2376 &:= (2^3! + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\ 2376 &:= (-2 + 3! + 7) \times C(6) \\ 2376 &:= (F(2) + 3 + 7) \times C(6) \\ 2376 &:= (T(2) + 7 \times Q(3)) \times Q(6) \\ 2376 &:= (T(-2 + T(3)) - T(T(7))) \times (-6) \\ 2376 &:= (T(3) - 2 + 7) \times C(6) \\ 2376 &:= 2 + Q(3) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(6) \\ 2376 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 6 \\ 2376 &:= F(Q(2)) \times (Q(3) + F(7)) \times Q(6) \\ 2376 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 6 \\ 2376 &:= Q(2)! \times (7 \times Q(3) + Q(6)) \\ 2376 &:= T(F(2) + 3 + 7) \times T(F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2377 &:= -3 \times C(2) + 7 \times C(7) \\ 2377 &:= -3 \times C(2) + Q(7 \times 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2377 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 7 \\
 2377 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 7 \\
 2377 &:= -Q(2) \times 3! + Q(7 \times 7) \\
 2377 &:= -Q(2) \times T(3) + Q(7 \times 7) \\
 2377 &:= Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(7) \\
 2377 &:= -T(2) - (T(3) - T(F(7))) \times T(7) \\
 2377 &:= -T(2) + (-T(3) + T(F(7))) \times T(7) \\
 2377 &:= T(T(2^3)) + T((1/7) \times T(T(7))) \\
 \\
 2378 &:= (Q(2)! + F(Q(3))) \times (Q(7) - 8) \\
 2378 &:= (Q(C(2)) - 3!) \times (Q(7) - 8) \\
 2378 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3)) + T(7)) - T(8)) \\
 2378 &:= 2 + C(F(3)) \times F(F(7)) + C(8) \\
 2378 &:= 2 + T(-F(3) + F(7)) \times T(8) \\
 2378 &:= -23 + \sqrt{7^8} \\
 2378 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 8 \\
 2378 &:= C(C(2)) \times T(3) - T(7) - T(T(8)) \\
 2378 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 8 \\
 2378 &:= -Q(2)! + Q(3) + Q(Q(7)) - 8 \\
 2378 &:= T(2) \times T(3)! - F(7) + T(F(8)) \\
 2378 &:= T(Q(2)) + 37 \times Q(8) \\
 2378 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (-F(3) - T(T(7))) + F(F(8)) \\
 \\
 2379 &:= (3 \times T(2) + Q(T(7))) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2379 &:= (Q(2)! + 3!! + Q(7)) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2379 &:= C(2) \times T(3) \times T(7) + T(T(9)) \\
 2379 &:= C(2 \times 3) + C(F(7)) - F(9) \\
 2379 &:= -C(3) - Q(2) + Q(Q(7)) + 9 \\
 2379 &:= -F(2) - (3 - 7) \times T(F(9)) \\
 2379 &:= F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3)) + Q(Q(7)) + 9 \\
 2379 &:= -Q(2) - Q(3) + Q(Q(7)) - 9 \\
 2379 &:= -Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(7)) + \sqrt{9} \\
 2379 &:= T(2) \times (T(3)! + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 2379 &:= -T(2) + T(3) \times (T(T(7)) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2379 &:= T(T(2)) \times F(T(3)) \times T(7) + T(T(9)) \\
 \\
 2380 &:= (F(2) + 3) \times T(F(8 + 0!)) \\
 2380 &:= (F(Q(2))! + Q(F(3!))) \times F(8 + 0!) \\
 2380 &:= -Q(2)! + 3 + Q(Q(8 - 0!)) \\
 2380 &:= Q(2) \times T(-3 + T(8) + 0!) \\
 \\
 2381 &:= Q(Q(2)) - Q(3!) + Q(Q(8 - 1)) \\
 2381 &:= Q(Q(2)) - Q(T(3)) + Q(Q(8 - 1)) \\
 \\
 2382 &:= (C(F(C(2))) + C(F(3)!)/F(8) + F(C(2))) \\
 2382 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(Q(3)) + Q(F(8)) - F(Q(2)) \\
 2382 &:= Q(Q(2)!) + Q(Q(3!)) + C(8) - 2 \\
 2382 &:= T(2) \times T(3)! + T(T(8))/T(2) \\
 2382 &:= T(2^3) + T(Q(8) + Q(2)) \\
 2382 &:= T(C(2)) + T(T(3 + 8) + 2) \\
 2382 &:= T(T(2) \times T(3)) + T(T(8 + T(2))) \\
 \\
 2383 &:= -2 + Q(Q(3)) + Q(8 \times 3!) \\
 2383 &:= -2 + Q(Q(3)) + Q(8 \times T(3)) \\
 2383 &:= T(2) \times T(3)! + T(F(8)) - F(T(3)) \\
 2383 &:= T(2) \times T(3)! - 8 + T(T(T(3))) \\
 \\
 2384 &:= (2 - C(3!) + C(8)) \times \sqrt{C(4)} \\
 2384 &:= (Q(2) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(8)) \times Q(4) \\
 2384 &:= -2 \times F(T(3)) + 8 \times T(4!) \\
 2384 &:= 2 + Q(T(3)) + T(Q(8) + 4) \\
 2384 &:= C(2) \times (T(3 \times 8) - \sqrt{4}) \\
 2384 &:= C(2) + C(3) \times (Q(8) + 4!) \\
 2384 &:= -F(2) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(8) - Q(4)) \\
 2384 &:= -T(T(2)) + (F(T(3)) + T(F(8))) \times T(4) \\
 2384 &:= -T(T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) + 8) \times T(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2385 &:= (C(2) + C(3) - C(8)) \times (-5) \\
 2385 &:= C(2) \times T(3 \times 8) - T(5) \\
 2385 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(Q(3)) + Q(T(8) - T(5)) \\
 2385 &:= Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + Q(8 + Q(5)) \\
 2385 &:= T(2) \times (T(3 + T(8)) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 2386 &:= -C(T(2)) + C(T(3)) + C(-8 + T(6)) \\
 2386 &:= F(2) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(8 \times 6) \\
 2386 &:= Q(C(2)) + 86 \times C(3) \\
 2386 &:= T(Q(2)) + T(3 + 8) \times Q(6) \\
 \\
 2387 &:= (-2 + C(-F(F(3)) + 8)) \times 7 \\
 2387 &:= -(F(Q(2)) - F(Q(3))) \times (Q(8) + F(7)) \\
 2387 &:= (Q(T(2)) \times T(Q(3)) - Q(8)) \times 7 \\
 2387 &:= -2 \times 3 - 8 + Q(Q(7)) \\
 2387 &:= T(2) \times T(3)! - \sqrt{T(8)} + F(F(7)) \\
 2387 &:= T(2^{T(3)}) - T(8) + C(7) \\
 2387 &:= T(T(2) + T(3 + 8)) - T(7) \\
 \\
 2388 &:= 2 \times T(8 \times T(3)) + T(8) \\
 2388 &:= C(2 \times T(3)) - \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(8)) \\
 2388 &:= C(F(C(2)) - 3!) - F(8 + 8) \\
 2388 &:= Q(2) \times (Q(3 \times 8) + F(8)) \\
 2388 &:= T(2) + Q(Q(3)) + Q(8) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 2389 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8))) + T(F(9)) \\
 2389 &:= -2 + T(T(T(3))) + (\sqrt{T(8)})! \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2389 &:= -C(2) - T(C(3)) + T((1/9) \times T(T(8))) \\
 2389 &:= C(Q(2) + Q(3)) + Q(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2389 &:= F(C(2)) - C(3!) + F(F(8) - \sqrt{9}) \\
 2389 &:= Q(2) + Q(8 \times 3!) + Q(9) \\
 2389 &:= Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(8 + F(9)) \\
 2389 &:= T(2) \times T(3)! + T(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{9})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2389 &:= T(Q(2) \times T(3)) + Q(8) + Q(T(9)) \\
 \\
 2390 &:= (C(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (9 + 0!) \\
 2390 &:= (F(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (9 + 0!) \\
 2390 &:= -2 - Q(3) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9})! + 0!)) \\
 2390 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(F(Q(3))) + Q(F(9) + 0!) \\
 2390 &:= T(Q(2)) \times (T(3)!/\sqrt{9} - 0!) \\
 2390 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(3)! \times \sqrt{9} - 0! \\
 \\
 2391 &:= Q(Q(F(2) + 3!)) - (9 + 1) \\
 2391 &:= Q(Q(Q(2) + 3)) - (9 + 1) \\
 2391 &:= T(2) \times T(3)! + T(F(9 - 1)) \\
 2391 &:= -T(Q(2)) + Q(3 + T(9) + 1) \\
 2391 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(3)! \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \\
 2392 &:= (2 + C(3!) + Q(9)) \times C(2) \\
 2392 &:= (C(C(2)) - C(3!) + \sqrt{9}) \times C(2) \\
 2392 &:= (C(C(2)) - C(T(3)) + \sqrt{9}) \times C(2) \\
 2392 &:= (F(2) - C(3)) \times (-92) \\
 2392 &:= (Q(2)! + F(3)) \times 92 \\
 2392 &:= (T(Q(2)) - Q(T(3))) \times (-92) \\
 2392 &:= 2 \times ((3 + T(F(9))) \times 2) \\
 2392 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + 3!! \times \sqrt{9} - Q(2)! \\
 2392 &:= Q(Q(Q(2) + 3)) - \sqrt{9^2} \\
 \\
 2393 &:= (C(2)!/(-F(3)) + C(F(9)))/C(F(3)) \\
 2393 &:= 2 \times T(F(F(3)) + T(9)) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 2393 &:= 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(3)! \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2393 &:= C(C(2) + 3) + T(T(9)) + C(3) \\
 2393 &:= F(F(F(2) + 3!)) + 3!! \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2393 &:= F(T(T(2))) + 3 \times T(T(9)) - T(3)! \\
 2393 &:= -Q(C(2)) + C(Q(3)) + C(9 + 3) \\
 2393 &:= Q(Q(2)) \times F(Q(3)) + Q(F(9) + Q(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2409 &:= C(2)!/4! + C(9) \\
 2409 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 09 \\
 2409 &:= C(2) + Q(40 + 9) \\
 2409 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 09 \\
 2409 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 09 \\
 2409 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + 4! \times Q(0! + 9) \\
 2409 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(9) + 4!) \\
 2409 &:= T(T(2) \times (4! - 0!)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \\
 2410 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times 10 \\
 2410 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 10 \\
 2410 &:= C(2) + Q(Q(\sqrt{C(4)} - 1)) + 0! \\
 2410 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 10 \\
 2410 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 10 \\
 2410 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(Q((4 - 1)! + 0!)) \\
 2410 &:= T(Q(2)) + 4! \times Q(10) \\
 \\
 2411 &:= 2 \times Q(T(4)) + T(T(11)) \\
 2411 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 11 \\
 2411 &:= C(2) + C(F(4)) \times F(11) \\
 2411 &:= F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(4) \times F(11) \\
 2411 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 11 \\
 2411 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 11 \\
 \\
 2412 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 12 \\
 2412 &:= -F(2) + C(F(4)!) + C(F(C(2) - 1)) \\
 2412 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 12 \\
 2412 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 12 \\
 2412 &:= Q(2) \times (Q(4!) + C(1 + 2)) \\
 2412 &:= Q(F(Q(2))) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 12) \\
 2412 &:= -T(2) + T((4! - 1) \times T(2)) \\
 2412 &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(4) + 1) + T(2)) \\
 2412 &:= T(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 1 + 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2413 &:= -2 + T((4! - 1) \times 3) \\
 2413 &:= -2 + T(T(T(4) + 1) + 3) \\
 2413 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 13 \\
 2413 &:= C(2 + 4) + C(13) \\
 2413 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 13 \\
 2413 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 13 \\
 2413 &:= -Q(2) + Q(4) + Q(Q(1 + 3!)) \\
 2413 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + F(4) \times (-1 + 3!!) \\
 \\
 2414 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(Q(4))) \times (1 + Q(4)) \\
 2414 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 14 \\
 2414 &:= C(F(C(2)) - \sqrt{C(4)}) + 1 + C(F(4)!) \\
 2414 &:= -F(2) + T((4! - 1) \times F(4)) \\
 2414 &:= -F(2) + T(F(4) + T(T(4) + 1)) \\
 2414 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 14 \\
 2414 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 14 \\
 2414 &:= Q(Q(Q(2) + F(4))) + F(1 + F(4)!) \\
 2414 &:= T(-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4!)) - 1^4 \\
 \\
 2415 &:= (Q(-2 + 4!) - 1) \times 5 \\
 2415 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 15 \\
 2415 &:= F(C(2)) \times ((4! - 1) \times 5) \\
 2415 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 15 \\
 2415 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 15 \\
 2415 &:= Q(2) \times F(Q(4) - 1) - Q(5) \\
 2415 &:= T(2 \times 4! + T(1 + 5)) \\
 2415 &:= T(2^{T(4-1)} + 5) \\
 2415 &:= T(Q(2 \times 4) + 5) \\
 \\
 2416 &:= -(-2 - T(4!)) \times F(6) \\
 2416 &:= C(2)!/(-4!) + C(16) \\
 2416 &:= C(2) \times T(4!) + 16 \\
 2416 &:= -F(2) + Q(4) + Q(Q(1 + 6)) \\
 2416 &:= F(T(T(2))) \times T(4!) + 16 \\
 2416 &:= Q(2)! \times Q(T(4)) + 16
 \end{aligned}$$

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